

Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers from 0 to 10000 Using Fibonacci Sequence Values

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Abstract

*This work brings natural numbers from 0 to 10000 written in two different forms. Increasing and decreasing orders of 1 to 9 and 9 to 1. This is done using Fibonacci sequence values along with basic operations. Previously, the author worked with similar kind of work using only basic operations. For the higher values, some extra operations, such as, **square-root**, **factorial**, etc. also done by the author. The previous total work is up to number 300.000. For more details refer Taneja [7]-[27]. This kind of work is never seen before using **Fibonacci sequence values**. The results are up to number 10000.*

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1 Introduction

First we shall give some different ways of representing natural numbers using the digits 0 to 9 or 1 to 9. See the subsections below

1.1 Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers

In this section natural numbers are* represented in three different types.

1.1.1 Increasing and Decreasing

In 2014, author [7] wrote natural numbers in increasing and decreasing orders of 1 to 9 and 9 to 1. See examples below:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{100} &:= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 \times 9 = 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\ \mathbf{101} &:= 1 + 2 + 34 + 5 + 6 \times 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\ \mathbf{102} &:= 12 + 3 \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4^3 + 2 + 1 \\ \mathbf{103} &:= 1 \times 2 \times 34 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4 + 3 + 21 \\ \mathbf{104} &:= 1 + 23 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 65 + 4 \times 3 + 2 + 1 \end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{105} &:= 1 + 2 \times 3 \times 4 + 56 + 7 + 8 + 9 &= 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{106} &:= 12 + 3 + 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 \times 8 + 9 &= 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{107} &:= 1 \times 23 + 4 + 56 + 7 + 8 + 9 &= 9 + 8 + 76 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{108} &:= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 78 + 9 &= 9 + 8 + 76 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1.
 \end{aligned}$$

See more examples,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{786} &:= 1 + 23 + 4 + 56 + 78 \times 9 &= 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 \times 4 \times 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{999} &:= 12 \times 3 \times (4 + 5) + (67 + 8) \times 9 &= 9 + 8 + 7 + 654 + 321 \\
 \mathbf{2535} &:= 1 + 2345 + (6 + 7 + 8) \times 9 &= 9 + 87 \times (6 + 5 \times 4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{2607} &:= 123 \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + (7 + 8) \times 9 &= 987 + 6 \times 54 \times (3 + 2) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{10483} &:= 1 + 23 \times 456 - 7 - 8 + 9 &= (9 \times 87 \times 6 + 543) \times 2 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{10549} &:= 1^2 \times 34 \times 5 \times (6 + 7 \times 8) + 9 &= 9 + (87 \times 6 + 5) \times 4 \times (3 + 2) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{10550} &:= 1^2 + 34 \times 5 \times (6 + 7 \times 8) + 9 &= 9 + (87 \times 6 + 5) \times 4 \times (3 + 2) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{10553} &:= 1 \times 23 \times 456 + 7 \times 8 + 9 &= 9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 \times 5 \times 43 + 21) \\
 \mathbf{10554} &:= 1 + 23 \times 456 + 7 \times 8 + 9 &= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) \times 4^3 + 2 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{11807} &:= 1 \times 234 \times (5 + 6 \times 7) + 89 &= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3)^2 \times 1.
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer [7]-[27]. These works brings the representations of natural numbers from 1 to 300.000. Soon, we shall extend it to half-million, i.e., 500.000.

1.2 Fibonacci Sequence

Fibonacci sequence numbers are well known in literature [5, 6]. This sequence is defined as

$$F(0) = 0, \quad F(1) = 1, \quad F(n+1) = F(n) + F(n-1), \quad n \geq 1.$$

Initial values of Fibonacci sequence are given by

$\mathbf{F(1)} := 1$	$\mathbf{F(8)} := 21$	$\mathbf{F(15)} := 610$	$\mathbf{F(22)} := 17711$
$\mathbf{F(2)} := 1$	$\mathbf{F(9)} := 34$	$\mathbf{F(16)} := 987$	$\mathbf{F(23)} := 28657$
$\mathbf{F(3)} := 2$	$\mathbf{F(10)} := 55$	$\mathbf{F(17)} := 1597$	$\mathbf{F(24)} := 46368$
$\mathbf{F(4)} := 3$	$\mathbf{F(11)} := 89$	$\mathbf{F(18)} := 2584$	$\mathbf{F(25)} := 75025, \text{ etc,}$
$\mathbf{F(5)} := 5$	$\mathbf{F(12)} := 144$	$\mathbf{F(19)} := 4181$	
$\mathbf{F(6)} := 8$	$\mathbf{F(13)} := 233$	$\mathbf{F(20)} := 6765$	
$\mathbf{F(7)} := 13$	$\mathbf{F(14)} := 377$	$\mathbf{F(21)} := 10946$	

Based on values of $F(\cdot)$, we can write composition values, such as, $F(F(1))$, $F(F(2))$, etc. See examples below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{F(F(1))} &:= 1 \\
 \mathbf{F(F(2))} &:= 1 \\
 \mathbf{F(F(3))} &:= 1 \\
 \mathbf{F(F(4))} &:= 2 \\
 \mathbf{F(F(5))} &:= 5 \\
 \mathbf{F(F(6))} &:= 21 \\
 \mathbf{F(F(7))} &:= 233 \\
 \mathbf{F(F(8))} &:= 10946 \\
 \mathbf{F(F(9))} &:= 5702887 \\
 \mathbf{F(F(10))} &:= 139583862445 \\
 \mathbf{F(F(11))} &:= 1779979416004714189 \\
 \mathbf{F(F(12))} &:= 555565404224292694404015791808 \\
 \mathbf{F(F(13))} &:= 2211236406303914545699412969744873993387956988653, \text{etc.}
 \end{aligned}$$

1.2.1 Natural Numbers in Terms of Fibonacci Sequence

Below are few examples of natural numbers written in terms of **Fibonacci sequence** values.

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 \mathbf{0} := F(0) & \mathbf{9} := F(2) + F(6) & \mathbf{18} := F(5) + F(7) \\
 \mathbf{1} := F(1) = F(2) & \mathbf{10} := F(3) + F(6) & \mathbf{19} := F(2) + F(5) + F(7) \\
 \mathbf{2} := F(3) & \mathbf{11} := F(4) + F(6) & \mathbf{20} := F(3) + F(5) + F(7) \\
 \mathbf{3} := F(4) & \mathbf{12} := F(2) + F(4) + F(6) & \mathbf{21} := F(8) \\
 \mathbf{4} := F(2) + F(4) & \mathbf{13} := F(7) & \mathbf{22} := F(2) + F(8) \\
 \mathbf{5} := F(5) & \mathbf{14} := F(2) + F(7) & \mathbf{23} := F(3) + F(8) \text{ etc,} \\
 \mathbf{6} := F(2) + F(5) & \mathbf{15} := F(3) + F(7) & \\
 \mathbf{7} := F(3) + F(5) & \mathbf{16} := F(4) + F(7) & \\
 \mathbf{8} := F(6) & \mathbf{17} := F(2) + F(4) + F(7) &
 \end{array}$$

For more details refer author's work [35].

1.2.2 Selfie Numbers Using Fibonacci Sequence Values

Below are few examples of **selfie numbers** by using **Fibonacci sequence** values.

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \mathbf{55} := F(5 + 5) & \mathbf{23732} := (-F(2) + 3 \times F(F(7))) \times F(3^2) \\
 \mathbf{474} := (4 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(4)) & \mathbf{28882} := F(2 + F(8)) - 8 + F(F(8 - F(2))) \\
 \mathbf{484} := (F(F(F(4))) + F(8))^{F(F(4))} & \mathbf{32823} := (-3 - 2 + F(F(8))) \times (F(2) + F(3)) \\
 \mathbf{2772} := (-2 + F(F(7))) \times (F(7) - F(2)) & \mathbf{39393} := 3^9 \times F(3) + 9 \times 3 \\
 \mathbf{3773} := (-F(3) + F(7)) \times 7^3 & \mathbf{44944} := ((4 + 49) \times 4)^{F(F(4))} \\
 \mathbf{13531} := F((1 + 3) \times 5) \times F(3) + 1 & \mathbf{46264} := F(4 \times 6) - 26 \times 4 \\
 \mathbf{14641} := 1 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 - 1 & \mathbf{46364} := F(4 \times 6) - F(3) - 6 + 4 \\
 \mathbf{15251} := F(15) \times 25 + 1 & \mathbf{46464} := F(4 \times 6) + 4 \times 6 \times 4 \\
 \mathbf{21961} := 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 1 & \mathbf{46664} := 4 + 6^6 + F(6) - 4
 \end{array}$$

$$46764 := 4 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(F(7)) + F(6)^{F(4)})$$

$$47374 := (F(F(F(4)) \times 7)^{F(3)} - 7) / F(4)$$

$$47574 := F(4) \times (F(F(7)) + 5^{7-F(F(4))})$$

$$48384 := (F(4) \times 8)^{F(3)} \times 84$$

$$48384 := (F(4) \times 8)^{F(3)} \times 84$$

$$49994 := F(F(4)) \times (-F(9) + F(F(9) - 9)) / F(4)$$

$$54645 := (F(F(5 + F(4))) - F(F(6)) + 4) \times 5$$

$$54745 := 5 \times F(F(4) \times 7) + F(4) \times 5$$

$$54845 := (5^{F(F(4))} + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5$$

$$62426 := (F(6) - F(2))^4 \times 26$$

$$63936 := 6^3 \times (F(9) + 3) \times F(6)$$

$$65556 := (F(F(F(6))) - 5 \times 5 + 5) \times 6$$

$$66666 := (F(F(F(6))) + F(6 + 6) + F(F(6))) \times 6$$

$$67176 := (F(F(F(6))) + F(F(7)) + 17) \times 6$$

$$68286 := (-6 + F(8)^2 + F(F(8))) \times 6$$

$$69696 := (F(6) \times F(9) - F(6))^{F(9-6)}$$

$$73793 := (7 + F(3)^{F(7)}) \times 9 + F(3)$$

$$75257 := F(F(7)) + F(5^2) - F(-5 + 7)$$

$$75457 := 7 \times F(F(5 + F(4))) - 5 \times F(F(7))$$

$$75957 := (F(F(F(7) - 5)) - 95) \times 7$$

$$76167 := (-F(7) \times (6 - 1) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7$$

$$76367 := 7 \times F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3)) - F(F(6)) - F(F(7))$$

$$76467 := F(7) + (F(F(F(6))) - 4 \times 6) \times 7$$

$$76567 := 7 \times F(F(F(6))) - F(-5 + F(6) + 7)$$

$$76667 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 6) + F(F(6)) / 7$$

$$76867 := (-7 + F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) \times 7$$

$$78487 := 7 \times F(F(8)) + F(F(F(4))) + 8 \times F(F(7))$$

$$78987 := (F(F(7)) + 8 + 98) \times F(F(7))$$

$$84284 := F(F(8) + 4) - 2 + F(8)^{F(4)}$$

$$86368 := (F(F(8)) - 6 - F(F(3) \times 6)) \times 8$$

$$86968 := (F(F(8)) - 69 - 6) \times 8$$

$$87878 := (F(F(8)) + 7) \times 8 + F(F(7)) + F(8)$$

$$88288 := (F(F(8)) + 82 + 8) \times 8$$

$$88788 := 8 \times F(F(8)) + F(F(7)) + F(8 + 8)$$

$$98289 := (-F(9) + F(F(8)) + F(2) + 8) \times 9$$

$$98389 := -98 + (-3 + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98489 := -F(9) + (F(8/4) + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98589 := 9 + F(8) + (5 + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98789 := 9 \times F(F(8)) + F(F(7)) + 8 + F(9)$$

$$747747 := (-7 + F(4)^7) \times 7^{F(4)} + 7$$

$$777777 := F(7) \times 77 \times 777$$

$$999999 := (9 + F(9)) \times 9 \times F(9 + 9) - 9$$

The above numbers are without use of any extra operation. For more work with **factorial** and **square-root** refer author's work [36, 38].

2 Crazy Representations from 0 to 10000 Using Fibonacci Sequence Values

In this work we have written natural numbers from 0 to 10000 in terms of increasing and decreasing orders of 1 to 9 and 9 to 1 by use of **Fibonacci sequence values**. The same numbers are also written before by author [7] without use of **Fibonacci sequence**. Moreover, without use of any extra operations just with basic operations. Here we have done it by using **Fibonacci sequence values** just to have more possibilities. Still there are few numbers written without use of **Fibonacci sequence values**. Moreover, we have removed $F(5)$, because $F(5) = 5$.

$$0 := F(-1 - 2 + 3) \times (456789)$$

$$1 := (1 - F((F(2 - F(3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2 := (-1 + 2 - (F((3 \times F(4))) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$3 := ((-1 - 2) \times (F((3 \times F(4))) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$4 := ((F(-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times F(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$5 := F((-1 - 2 - ((3^{F(4)}) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))$$

$$6 := ((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F(F(4)))) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$7 := ((1 - 2 - (3^{F(4)})) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8 := (-1 - ((2 \times F(3 + 4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$0 := F(F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1 := 9 - F(8 + 7 + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$2 := 9 + F(8) - 7 - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$3 := F((-9 + F((F(8) + (7 - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$4 := -9 + F(F(8) + 7 - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$5 := 9 + 8 / (7 + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$6 := -9 \times F(8) + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7 := -9 + 8 - (F(7) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$8 := (-9 + 8) \times (F(7) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times F(3+4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
10 &:= (-1 \times ((F(2+3))^{F(4)}) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
11 &:= (((-1 - F(2+3)) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
12 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) + (F(F(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
13 &:= (-1 - (F((F(2+3) + F(4)))) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
14 &:= (-F((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
15 &:= (-1 \times ((F(2+3) \times 4) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
16 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((F(3)^4) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
17 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
18 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
19 &:= (-1 - 2 - (F(3+4) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
20 &:= (F((-1 - 2 + F(3+4))) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
21 &:= ((1 - 2 - F(3+4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
22 &:= (-1 \times (F((F(F(2+3)) + F(F(4)))) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
23 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F(3+4) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
24 &:= (-1 - ((F(F(2+3)) \times F(F(4))) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
25 &:= ((1 + 2 - F(3+4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
26 &:= (-F(-1 + F(2 \times 3)) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
27 &:= ((-1 - F(2+3)) - (F(F(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
28 &:= ((-1 \times F(2+3)) - (F(F(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
29 &:= (-F(F((-1 + F(2+3)))) - (4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
30 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
31 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
32 &:= ((1 - F(2 \times 3)) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
33 &:= (-1 - (F(2+3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
34 &:= (-1 \times (F(2+3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
35 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
36 &:= (-1 \times (F((2 + F(3))) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
37 &:= (-F(F((-1 + F(2+3)))) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
38 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F(3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
39 &:= ((1 - 2 + F(3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
40 &:= (1 - 2 + (F(3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
41 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2+3)))) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
42 &:= (1 \times (F((2 + F(3))) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
43 &:= (1 \times 2 + (F(3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
44 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3 + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
45 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3+4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
46 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
47 &:= (((-1 + F(2+3)) \times F(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
48 &:= (F((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9 &:= -9 \times 8 / (F(7) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
10 &:= -9 - (F(F(8)/7) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
11 &:= ((9 - F(((8 + 7) - F(6)))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
12 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) + 7)) / (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
13 &:= (-F(-9 + 8 + 7) + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
14 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
15 &:= -9 + (F(8)/7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
16 &:= (9 - F(8) + (7 + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
17 &:= -9 - 8 + F(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
18 &:= -9 / (F(8)/7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
19 &:= -9 + F(8 + 7 - F(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
20 &:= -9 + F(8) - (F(7) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
21 &:= F((-9 + 8) \times (F(7) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
22 &:= -9 + 8 - (F(7) - F(F(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
23 &:= 9 - 8 + (F(7) - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
24 &:= -9 \times (8 - F(7)) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
25 &:= 9 + 8 - F(7) + 6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
26 &:= (-9 + F(8) - 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
27 &:= ((9 - (F(8)/7)) + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
28 &:= (F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) - (F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
29 &:= F(-9 + 8 + 7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
30 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
31 &:= (F(-9 + 8 + 7) + (F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
32 &:= 9 + F(F(8)/7) + 6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
33 &:= -9 + 8 + F(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
34 &:= F(-9 \times 8 / (F(7) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
35 &:= -9 + 8 + F(7) + F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
36 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (F(7) + (F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
37 &:= 9 + F(8 + 7 - F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
38 &:= (9 \times 8 - (F(7) + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
39 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - F(F(6))) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
40 &:= -9 + F(8) + 7 + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
41 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (F(F(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
42 &:= F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
43 &:= -9 \times (F(8) + 7 \times 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
44 &:= (F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) + (F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
45 &:= (F((-9 + F(((8 + 7) - F(6)))))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
46 &:= -9 + (F(8) + F(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
47 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) - 7 - 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
48 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times F(F(F(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
49 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3+4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
50 &:= ((F(F((-1+2 \times 3))) \times F(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
51 &:= (((-1 + F(2+3)) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
52 &:= (F(-1 + F(2 \times 3)) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
53 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
54 &:= (F((-1 \times 2 + F(3+4))) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
55 &:= (1 \times ((F(2+3) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
56 &:= (F((-1 + (2 + (3+4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
57 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
58 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) + (4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
59 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
60 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times F(3+4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
61 &:= (-1 - (F(F((2 + F(3)))) \times (4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
62 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2+3)))^{F(4)}) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
63 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F(3) \times (4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
64 &:= ((-1 - F(2+3)) + (F(F(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
65 &:= ((-1 \times F(2+3)) + (F(F(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
66 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3+4) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
67 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F(3) \times (F(F(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
68 &:= (-1 + (F((2 + (3+4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
69 &:= (F((F((-1 + F(2+3)))^{F(F(4))})) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
70 &:= (F(F((-1 - (2 - 3 - 4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
71 &:= (1 + ((F(2+3) - F(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
72 &:= (1 - 2 + 3 + (F(F(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
73 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F(3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
74 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
75 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
76 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
77 &:= (-1 + (F(F((2 + F(3)))) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
78 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2+3)))) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
79 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
80 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4+5) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
81 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
82 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3^{F(4+5)-(6+7+8+9)})) \\
83 &:= (1 + (2 \times (F(3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
84 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3+4) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
85 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3 + F(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
86 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2+3)))) \times (F((F(F(4)) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
87 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) + (4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
88 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3^{F(4)})) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
49 &:= F(-9 + 8 + 7) \times F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
50 &:= 9 - 8 - 7 \times (F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
51 &:= (9 + 8 + (F(7) + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
52 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
53 &:= -9 \times F(8) + F(F(7)) - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
54 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
55 &:= -9 - 8 \times (F(7) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
56 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
57 &:= 9 \times (F(8) - 7 - 6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
58 &:= 9 + F(8) + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
59 &:= -9 \times F(8) + F(7 + 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
60 &:= (-9 - F(8)) \times (7 + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
61 &:= -9 - 8 + F(7) \times (F(F(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
62 &:= (9 \times 8 + (F(7) - (F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
63 &:= -9 \times (F(8) - (7 + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
64 &:= 9 \times 8 + F(7) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
65 &:= (9 + 8 - 7) \times F(6) + 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
66 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(7))) + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
67 &:= -9 - (F(8) - 7 - 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
68 &:= (-F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(F(7)) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
69 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - F(F(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
70 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
71 &:= -9 \times 8 + F(F(7)) - 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
72 &:= -9 \times (F(8 + 7) - F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
73 &:= -9 - (F(8) - F(7) - 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
74 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times F(7))) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
75 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (F((F(7) - F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
76 &:= -9 + 8 - F(7) + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
77 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (F(7) - 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
78 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - F(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
79 &:= F(-9 + 8 + 7) \times F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
80 &:= ((9 \times 8 - F(7)) + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
81 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (F(F(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
82 &:= (-F(-9 + 8 + 7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
83 &:= ((9 - 8 - F(F(7))) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
84 &:= -9 \times F(8) + F(7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
85 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 - F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
86 &:= -9 + 8 \times F(7) + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
87 &:= (-9 + 8 + F(7)) \times 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
88 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(7) \times F(6))) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
89 &:= F((((-1 - F(2+3)) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
90 &:= (F((-1 - 2 + F(3+4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
91 &:= (1 + (F((F(F(2+3)) \times F(F(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
92 &:= ((-1 + (2^{3+4})) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
93 &:= (-1 \times (F((2 + F(3))) \times (4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
94 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
95 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3+4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
96 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
97 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (F(4) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
98 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) + (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
99 &:= (((-1 + F(2+3))^{F(4)}) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
100 &:= ((-1 \times F(2+3)) + (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
101 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) - (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
102 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3/F(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
103 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
104 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2+3)) - F(F(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
105 &:= (F((-1 - (2 - 3 - 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
106 &:= (((-1 + 2)^{F(3)}) + (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
107 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2+3)))) + (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
108 &:= (1 - 2 + (F(3 \times 4) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
109 &:= ((-1 + F(2+3)) + (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
110 &:= ((-1 + 2 + F(3 \times 4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
111 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
112 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (F(F(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
113 &:= (1 - 2 + (3 \times (F(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
114 &:= (((1 + 2) \times 3) + (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
115 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (3 \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
116 &:= (-1 + (F((2 + F(3))) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
117 &:= (F((-1 + F(2+3))) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
118 &:= (1 + (F((2 + F(3))) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
119 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
120 &:= (-1 \times ((F(2+3) - (4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
121 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (F(4+5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
122 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (F(4+5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
123 &:= (-1 - ((2 + F(3)) \times (4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
124 &:= (F((-1 \times 2 + F(3+4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
125 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) + (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
126 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
127 &:= (-1 - ((2 + F(3)) \times (F(4) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
128 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) - (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
89 &:= F(-9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
90 &:= (-9 + 8 - (F(7) \times (F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
91 &:= (-9 + 8) \times F(7) \times (F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
92 &:= -9 + 8 + F(7) \times 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
93 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times 7 - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
94 &:= 9 - 8 + 6 \times F(7) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
95 &:= -9 - 8 + F(8) + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
96 &:= -9 - (8 - F(7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
97 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (7 + (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
98 &:= F(-9 + 8 + 7) + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
99 &:= (-9 - F(F(8)/7)) \times (6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
100 &:= -9 - 8 - F(7) \times (6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
101 &:= (9 + 8) \times F(7) - F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
102 &:= -9 + 8 + F(7) + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
103 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (F(7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
104 &:= -9 + 8 + (F(7) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
105 &:= F(-9 + F(8) - 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
106 &:= 9 \times 8 + F(7) + 6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
107 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (F(7) - F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
108 &:= (9 - 8 - F(7)) \times (6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
109 &:= -9 + (F(8) + 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
110 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) - F(7) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
111 &:= -9 + (F(8) - 7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
112 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
113 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
114 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (F(6) + F((5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
115 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times F(F(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
116 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) - (7 + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
117 &:= -9 - F(8) + 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
118 &:= -9 + 8 + F(7) \times F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
119 &:= -9 + 8 - (F(7) - F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
120 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (F(7) - F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
121 &:= (F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) - (F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
122 &:= 9 + (8 \times F(7) - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
123 &:= F(-9 + 8 + F(7)) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
124 &:= 9 + 8 - F(7) + F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
125 &:= (9 + 8) \times 7 + F(F(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
126 &:= ((9 - (F(8)/7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
127 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7) + F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
128 &:= (F(-9 + 8 + 7) + (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
129 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times (F(4+5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
130 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times F(4+5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
131 &:= (1 - 2 + ((3 \times F(4+5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
132 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
133 &:= ((1 - F(2 \times 3)) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
134 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
135 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 + 3) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
136 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
137 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times (F(F(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
138 &:= (-F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
139 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F(3) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
140 &:= (((1 + F(2 + 3)) - F(F(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
141 &:= (((-1 + 2)^{F(3)}) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
142 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
143 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
144 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
145 &:= (1 \times (F(2 + 3) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
146 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) + (F(F(4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
147 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
148 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (F(F(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
149 &:= (-1 - (((2 + F(3)) - (4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
150 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (4 + 5)) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
151 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times (F(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
152 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (F(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
153 &:= (F(-1 + F(2 \times 3)) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
154 &:= (-1 - (F(2 + 3) \times (4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
155 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
156 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
157 &:= (1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
158 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 + 5))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
159 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 + 3)) \times (F(4) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
160 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) \times (F(4) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
161 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3^{F(4+5)-(6+7+8+9)}))) \\
162 &:= (1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
163 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) - (F(F(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
164 &:= (-1 - (F(F(F(2 + 3))) \times (F(F(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
165 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) \times (F(F(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
166 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times F(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
167 &:= (-1 - (F(2 \times 3) \times ((4 + 5) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
168 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) \times ((4 + 5) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
129 &:= F(-9 + (8 + 7 + 6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
130 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + 7 - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
131 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times F(F(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
132 &:= -9 + 8 + F(7) + F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
133 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times F(7) - F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
134 &:= 9 + 8 \times F(7) + 6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
135 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times F(7) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
136 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (F(7) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
137 &:= (F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) + (F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
138 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
139 &:= -9 + (F(8) + 7 + F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
140 &:= -9 \times 8 + F(F(7)) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
141 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + 6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
142 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + 7 + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
143 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) - (7 - 6)^{54321} \\
144 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 - 6)^{54321} \\
145 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + (7 - 6)^{54321} \\
146 &:= ((9 \times ((F(8) - 7) \times 6)) - F((5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
147 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + F((F(7) + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
148 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(7) + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
149 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times F(7) + F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
150 &:= (9 + (8 - 7)^{F(F(6))}) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
151 &:= F(-9 + 8 + F(7)) - F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
152 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) - (F(7) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
153 &:= F(-9 + 8 + 7) \times F(F(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
154 &:= -9 \times 8 + F(F(7)) + F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
155 &:= -9 + F(8) + F(F(7)) - 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
156 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times ((7 + F(F(6)))) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
157 &:= 9 + F(8) + 7 + F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
158 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) - 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
159 &:= -9 + F(8) + 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
160 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
161 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times F(F(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
162 &:= -9 \times (F(8)/7 - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
163 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times F(7) - F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
164 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(7) - (F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
165 &:= F(-9 + 8 + F(7)) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
166 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7) - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
167 &:= F(-9 + 8 + F(7)) + F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
168 &:= F(-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
169 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) - (F(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 169 &:= -9 \times 8 + F(F(7)) + F(F(F(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
170 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 170 &:= -9 \times 8 + F(F(7)) - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
171 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F((3 + (4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 171 &:= -9 \times (F(F(8)/7) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
172 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F((3 + F(F(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 172 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + 7 + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
173 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F((3 + F(F(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 173 &:= -9 + F(8) + 7 \times (F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
174 &:= (1 - 2 + (F((3 + F(F(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 174 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
175 &:= ((1 - 2 + 3 + F(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 175 &:= 9 \times F(8) + 7 - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
176 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F((3 + F(F(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 176 &:= -9 \times 8 + F(7 + 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
177 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3 \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 177 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times F(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
178 &:= (-1 + (F(((2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 178 &:= 9 + 8 + 7 \times (F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
179 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times F(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 179 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times F(7) + F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
180 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3 \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 180 &:= ((9 \times (8 + F(7))) + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
181 &:= (1 \times 2 + (F(3 \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 181 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) - (7 + (6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
182 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F((3 \times F(4))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 182 &:= -9 \times 8 + F(F(7)) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
183 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (F(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 183 &:= 9 - F(8) + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
184 &:= (-1 + (F(F(F(2 + 3))) \times (F(F(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 184 &:= F(-9 + 8 + 7) \times (F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
185 &:= ((1 \times F(2 + 3)) \times (F(F(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 185 &:= -9 + 8 \times F(7) + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
186 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) \times (4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 186 &:= -9 + F(8 + 7 - F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
187 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times ((F(F(4)))^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 187 &:= -9 - (F(8) + 7) \times (F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
188 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F((F(4) + 5)) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) & 188 &:= -9 \times F(8) - F(7 + 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
189 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 + 3)) \times (F(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 189 &:= (-9 \times (F(8 + 7) - (F(F(6)) + F((5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
190 &:= (F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3)))) \times (F(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 190 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + (6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
191 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (F(4) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) & 191 &:= 9 \times F(8) - 7 - 6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
192 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) \times (F(4) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 192 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times (7 - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
193 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (F(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 193 &:= -9 - 8 + F(F(7)) - F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
194 &:= (-1 + (F(2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 194 &:= 9 \times F(8) + F(F(F(7) - F(F(F(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
195 &:= (F((-1 + 2 \times 3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 195 &:= ((-9 - 8 + F(F(7))) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
196 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + F(F(3 + 4))) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 196 &:= ((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) - (F(F(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
197 &:= ((-1 + F(F((F(F(2 + 3)) + F(F(4)))))) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 197 &:= -9 \times 8 + F(F(7)) + F(F(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
198 &:= (F(F((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 198 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
199 &:= ((-1 + 2 + F(F(3 + 4))) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 199 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 + F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
200 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + (F(F(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 200 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + F(F(6))) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
201 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (F(F(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 201 &:= -9 \times 8 + F(7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
202 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + (4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 202 &:= -9 - F(8) \times (F(7) + 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
203 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 203 &:= 9 \times F(8) - 7 + 6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
204 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - (F(F(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 204 &:= -9 \times (F(8) - 7 \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
205 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F(3) - (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 205 &:= -9 + 8 \times F(7) + (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
206 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 206 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + (6 + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
207 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + F(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 207 &:= -9 + F(8) + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
208 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + F(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 208 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
209 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 \times 3) - F(F(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
210 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
211 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + F(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
212 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + ((4 + 5) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
213 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
214 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3))^{F(4)} + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
215 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
216 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) + (F(4)^5)) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
217 &:= ((1 - F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
218 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
219 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) + (F(4) \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
220 &:= ((-1 + (2^{F(3+F(4))})) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
221 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3))^4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
222 &:= (-1 - 2 - (3 \times (F(4) \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
223 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times (F(4) - (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
224 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) \times (F(4) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
225 &:= (((1 + 2) \times (F(3 + 4) \times 5)) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
226 &:= ((-1 + F((2 \times (3 + 4)))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
227 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (F(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
228 &:= ((1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (F(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
229 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) - (F(4 + 5) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
230 &:= (-1 - 2 + F(F(((3 + F(4 + 5)) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
231 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) \times (F(F(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
232 &:= (-1 + F(F(((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F(F(4))) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
233 &:= F(F(F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F(F(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
234 &:= (-1 + 2 + F(F(((3 + F(4 + 5)) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
235 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + F(F((F(4 + 5) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
236 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + F((F(4 + 5) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
237 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + (F(4 + 5) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
238 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3 + 4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
239 &:= (1 + (2 \times (F((F(3) + (4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
240 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (F(3) - (4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
241 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times F(4 + 5))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
242 &:= (1 \times ((F(2 \times 3) \times F(4 + 5)) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
243 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3^{F(4+5)-(6+7+8+9)})) \\
244 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 + 3)) + F(F(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
245 &:= (((1 \times F(2 + 3)) + F(F(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
246 &:= (1 + ((F(F(2 + 3)) + F(F(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
247 &:= (-1 - (F(2 \times 3) \times (4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
248 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) \times (4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
209 &:= ((-9 + F(F(((8 + 7) - F(6)))) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
210 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
211 &:= -9 + 8 + F(F(7)) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
212 &:= -9 - F(8) + F(F(7)) - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
213 &:= -9 \times 8 + (F(7) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
214 &:= (-9 - F(8)) \times F(7) - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
215 &:= (9 + 8) \times F(7) - F(F(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
216 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (F(F(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
217 &:= -9 + 8 + F(7 + 6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
218 &:= -9 - (F(8) - F(7 + 6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
219 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(7) + F(F(6)))) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
220 &:= (-9 - F(8)) \times (7 + 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
221 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) - F(7) + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
222 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7 + F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
223 &:= -9 + 8 + F(F(7)) + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
224 &:= -9 + F(F(F(8) + 1 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
225 &:= (F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
226 &:= 9 - 8 + (7 + F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
227 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) - 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
228 &:= -9 + 7 \times F(8) + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
229 &:= -9 - (F(8) + F(7)) \times (F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
230 &:= -9 + F(8) + F(7 + 6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
231 &:= -9 - 8 + F(7 + 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
232 &:= -9 + 8 + F(7 + F(F(6))) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
233 &:= F(-9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
234 &:= -9 \times (8 - F(7) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
235 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (F(F(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
236 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + (F(F(7)) + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
237 &:= -9 - 8 + F(F(7)) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
238 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 - (F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
239 &:= -9 + F(F(8 + 7 - F(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
240 &:= (-9 - F(8)) \times (F(7) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
241 &:= -9 + 8 + F(F(7)) - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
242 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - F(6 + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
243 &:= -9 - F(8) + F(7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
244 &:= (9 + 8) \times F(7) + F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
245 &:= 9 \times (F(8) + 7) + F(6) + 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
246 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times F(7) + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
247 &:= -9 + 8 + F(7 + 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
248 &:= (9 - 8) \times (F(7 + 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
249 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) - ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
250 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^{F(4)} + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
251 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) + ((F(4)^5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
252 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times F(3 \times 4))) - 5-6-7-8-9) \\
253 &:= (F(-1 + F(2 \times 3)) + ((F(4) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
254 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) - ((4+5) - 6-7-8-9)) \\
255 &:= (-1 - (F(2 \times 3) \times (F(4) - 5-6-7-8-9))) \\
256 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) \times (F(4) - 5-6-7-8-9))) \\
257 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times F((3 + (4+5)))))) - 6-7-8-9) \\
258 &:= (F(F(((-1 + 2) \times (3+4)))) - (5-6-7-8-9)) \\
259 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
260 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + (F(F(4)) - (5-6-7-8-9))) \\
261 &:= ((1+2) + (F(F(3+4)) - (5-6-7-8-9))) \\
262 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) - ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
263 &:= (-1 - (F(2 \times 3) \times (F(F(4)) - 5-6-7-8-9))) \\
264 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) - (4-5-6-7-8-9)) \\
265 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(F(3+4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
266 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(F(3+4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
267 &:= (-1 + (F(F((F(F(2+3)) + F(F(4)))))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
268 &:= (F(F(((-1 + 2) \times (3+4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
269 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(F(3+4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
270 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + (F(F(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
271 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + (F(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
272 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
273 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
274 &:= (1 \times 2 + (F(3) + ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
275 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F(3) - (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
276 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
277 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
278 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3) \times (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
279 &:= (-1 + ((F(2+3) + F(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
280 &:= (((1 + F(2+3)) + F(F(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
281 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
282 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((3 \times F(4)) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
283 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
284 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3 + F(4)) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
285 &:= (1 + (2 \times (F(3) + (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
286 &:= (-1 \times (2 \times ((3+4) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
287 &:= (-1 + (2 \times F((3 \times (F(4+5) - 6-7-8-9)))))) \\
288 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (F(4) - 5-6-7-8-9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
249 &:= -9 + F(8) \times (7+6) - 5-4-3-2-1 \\
250 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + F(F(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1) \\
251 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (F(F(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
252 &:= (-9 + 8 + F(7)) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1) \\
253 &:= -9 + 8 + F(F(7)) + 6+5+4+3+2+1 \\
254 &:= F(-9 + 8 + F(7)) \times 6 - F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
255 &:= -9 + 8 + F(F(7)) + F(6) + 5+4+3+2+1 \\
256 &:= -9 - 8 + F(7) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1) \\
257 &:= -9 + 8 + F(7) \times F(F(6)) - 5-4-3-2-1 \\
258 &:= -9 + 7 \times F(8) + F(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1) \\
259 &:= (-9 - F(8) - 7) \times (F(6) - 5-4-3-2-1) \\
260 &:= -9 + F(8) + F(7+6) + 5+4+3+2+1 \\
261 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) - F(7) \times (6-5-4-3-2-1) \\
262 &:= -9 + F(F(8)/7)^{F(6)} + 5+4+3+2+1 \\
263 &:= -9 + 8 \times (F(7) + 6+5+4+3+2+1) \\
264 &:= F(-9 + 8 + F(7)) + F(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1) \\
265 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 \times 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
266 &:= -9 + (F(8) + F(F(7)) + 6+5+4+3+2+1) \\
267 &:= 9 \times 8 + (7+6) \times (5+4+3+2+1) \\
268 &:= 9 - 8 \times 7 + F(F(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1) \\
269 &:= -9 - F(8) + F(7) \times (F(6) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
270 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7)))/F(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
271 &:= -9 - 8 + F(7) \times F(F(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1 \\
272 &:= -9 + 8 + F(7) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1) \\
273 &:= -9 + F(8) \times F(7) - 6+5+4+3+2+1 \\
274 &:= 9 - 8 + F(7) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1) \\
275 &:= F(F(-9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6+5))) \times F(4+3+2+1) \\
276 &:= (-9 + 8 + F(7)) \times (F(6) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
277 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7) + F(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1) \\
278 &:= -9 + F(F(8) - 7) - 6 \times (5+4+3+2+1) \\
279 &:= -9 + F(8) \times (7+6) + 5+4+3+2+1 \\
280 &:= -9 \times (8-7-6) \times 5 + F(4+3+2+1) \\
281 &:= 9 + 8 \times (F(7) + 6+5+4+3+2+1) \\
282 &:= -9 - 8 + F(7) \times (F(6) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
283 &:= 9 - 8 \times 7 \times 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
284 &:= -9 + 8 + (F(7) + 6) \times (5+4+3+2+1) \\
285 &:= -9 - F(8) \times (7-6-5-4-3-2-1) \\
286 &:= 9 - 8 + (F(7) + 6) \times (5+4+3+2+1) \\
287 &:= -9 + 8 + F(7) \times F(F(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1 \\
288 &:= F(-9 + 8 + 7) \times (F(F(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
289 &:= (-1 - 2 - (F(3) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
290 &:= (-1 + ((2^{F(3+F(4))}) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
291 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3))^4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
292 &:= (1 + ((2^{F(3+F(4))}) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
293 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F(3) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
294 &:= (F(((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times F(4))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
295 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times (F(F(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
296 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (F(F(4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
297 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (F(F(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
298 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (F(F(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
299 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 + (4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
300 &:= ((1 - 2 + (F(3) + (4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
301 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 \times 3) \times F(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
302 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + (F(F(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
303 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times (F(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
304 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times (F(F(4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
305 &:= ((F((-1 - 2 + F(3 + 4))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
306 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
307 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times (F(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
308 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3))^{F(4)}) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
309 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
310 &:= F(F(F(F(-1 + 2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4))^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
311 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
312 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
313 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
314 &:= (1 - 2 + (3 \times (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
315 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
316 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
317 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times F((3 + (4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
318 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3))^{F(4)}) + (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
319 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 + 3)) \times (F(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
320 &:= (F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3))) \times (F(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
321 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3))^4) + (F((5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
322 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times F(3 \times 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
323 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3 + 4) \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
324 &:= (-1 - (F(F(F(F(2 + 3))) + F(F(4)))) \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
325 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3 + 4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
326 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F(3 + 4) \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
327 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3) + (4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
328 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3) + (4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
289 &:= -9 + F(8) + F(F(7)) - 6 - 5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
290 &:= 9 + 8 + F(7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
291 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
292 &:= -9 - (F(8) - 7 - F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
293 &:= -9 - (F(8) - F(F(7)) - 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
294 &:= (9 - 8 + F(7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
295 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - F(F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
296 &:= 9 \times 8 + F(F(7)) + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
297 &:= -9 - (F(8) + F(7)) \times (6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
298 &:= -9 + 8 + F(7) \times (F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
299 &:= -9 \times 8 - F(F(7)) - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
300 &:= (-9 + 8 + F(7) + F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
301 &:= -9 + 8 - F(7) + F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
302 &:= 9 + 8 + (F(7) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
303 &:= 9 - F(8) \times (7 - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
304 &:= -9 \times (F(8) + 7 + 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
305 &:= -9 \times 8 - F(7 + 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
306 &:= (9 \times F(((8 + 7) - (F(F(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
307 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
308 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
309 &:= -9 + F(8)/7 + F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
310 &:= -9 \times (F(8) + F(7)) + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
311 &:= (9 + 8) \times F(7) + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
312 &:= (9 \times 8 + (F(F(7)) - (F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
313 &:= -9 \times 8 - (F(F(7)) - F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
314 &:= -9 + 8 + (F(7) + F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
315 &:= 9 \times (F(8) - (7 - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
316 &:= 9 - 8 + (F(7) + F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
317 &:= -9 \times F(8) - F(7) \times F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
318 &:= (9 \times 8) \times F(7) - F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
319 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
320 &:= 9 \times 8 + F(7 + 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
321 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
322 &:= -9 + 8 + F(F(7)) + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
323 &:= F(-9 + 8 + 7) + F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
324 &:= -9 \times (F(8) - 7 \times 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
325 &:= 9 + 8 - 7 + F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
326 &:= 9 \times 8 + F(F(7)) + 6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
327 &:= -9 + 8 + F(7) + F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
328 &:= -9 - F(8) \times (7 + 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
329 &:= (-1 + ((F(F((2 + F(3)))) + (4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
330 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + (4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
331 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3) + (4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
332 &:= (((-1 - (2 - 3 - 4)) \times F((5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
333 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) - (4 \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
334 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + ((4 \times F((5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
335 &:= (1 + (2 \times ((F(3 + 4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
336 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (F(3) - (4 + (5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
337 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3 \times 4) - (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
338 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
339 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
340 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
341 &:= ((-1 + F((2 \times (3 + 4)))) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
342 &:= (F((-1 + 2 + F(3 + 4))) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
343 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3))^{F(F(4+5)-6-7-8-9)}) \\
344 &:= ((-1 - 2 + F(((3 \times F(4)) + 5))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
345 &:= (((-1 + (F(2 \times 3))^{F(F(4))}) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
346 &:= ((-1 + F((2 + (3 + (4 + 5)))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
347 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F((3 + (4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
348 &:= ((-1 + 2 + F(((3 \times F(4)) + 5))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
349 &:= (-1 + (F(F(F(2 + 3))) \times (F(F(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
350 &:= ((-1 - 2 + F(3 + 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
351 &:= (-1 + (F((2 \times (3 + 4))) + (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
352 &:= (F((-1 + 2 + F(3 + 4))) + (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
353 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3^{F(4)}) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
354 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) + ((4 + (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
355 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
356 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F((F(F(4)) + 5)) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
357 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3 \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
358 &:= ((1 \times 2) \times (F(3 \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
359 &:= (1 + (2 \times (F(3 \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
360 &:= (1 \times ((F(F(2 \times 3)) - (4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
361 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + (4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
362 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + ((4 + (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
363 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) + ((4 + (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
364 &:= (F(-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4) - (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
365 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))^{F(F(4))}) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
366 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) \times (4 - (F((5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
367 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F((3 \times F(4))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
368 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3))^{F(4)}) - (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
329 &:= -9 - 8 \times (F(7) + F(F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
330 &:= -9 \times (F(8) - 7 \times F(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
331 &:= -9 + 8 + F(F(7)) + F(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
332 &:= 9 + 8 + (F(7) + F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
333 &:= (-9 - F(8) - 7) \times (6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
334 &:= -9 - (F(8) \times F(7) - 6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
335 &:= -9 + F(8) + F(F(7)) + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
336 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
337 &:= 9 + 8 \times (7 \times F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
338 &:= -9 + F(F(8) - 7) + 6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
339 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
340 &:= -9 + F(8) + F(7) + F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
341 &:= (9 + 8) \times F(7) + F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
342 &:= (9 \times ((8 + 7) + (F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
343 &:= -9 \times F(8) - F(7) \times 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
344 &:= -9 + F(8) + F(F(7)) + F(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
345 &:= 9 \times 8 + F(7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
346 &:= 9 - F(8) \times (7 + 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
347 &:= -9 + F(F(8) - 7) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
348 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
349 &:= 9 + 8 + F(F(7)) + (F(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
350 &:= -9 \times (F(8) + 7) - F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
351 &:= -9 \times F(8) \times F(7) / (F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
352 &:= -9 + 8 + F(F(7)) + F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
353 &:= -9 - F(8) - (F(F(7)) - 6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
354 &:= 9 + (8 + 7) \times (F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
355 &:= 9 \times 8 + F(7 + 6) + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
356 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + F(F(7)) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
357 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (F(7) - F(6 + 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
358 &:= (-9 - F(8) / 7) \times F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
359 &:= -9 + (F(F(8) - 7) + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
360 &:= -9 - 8 - F(7 + 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
361 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
362 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7 + 6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
363 &:= -9 + F(8) \times F(7) + F(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
364 &:= -9 \times (F(8) + 7) + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
365 &:= -9 \times F(8) - 7 \times F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
366 &:= -9 - 8 - (F(F(7)) - 6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
367 &:= -9 \times (8 + (F(7) + 6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
368 &:= -9 - F(F(8 + 7 - F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
369 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3^{F(4)} - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
370 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (4 \times 5)) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
371 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times ((F(F(4))^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
372 &:= ((1 + F(2 + 3)) \times ((F(F(4))^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
373 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
374 &:= (-1 - ((2 + F(3 + 4)) \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
375 &:= (-F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3)))) \times (F(4) \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
376 &:= (-1 + F((2 \times ((3 + F(4 + 5)) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
377 &:= F(((((-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
378 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3))^{F(4)} + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
379 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) - (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
380 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(F(3 + 4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
381 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(F(3 + 4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
382 &:= -1 + F(F(F(F(F(2 + 3))) + F(F(4)))) + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
383 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (F(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
384 &:= (-1 - ((2 - F(3 + 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
385 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + F(3 + 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
386 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + (F(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
387 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(F(3 + F(4))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
388 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (F((F(F(4)) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
389 &:= (-1 - ((F(F(2 \times 3)) - F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
390 &:= ((-1 + (2 + (3 + (4 + 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
391 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(((3 \times 4) - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
392 &:= F(F(-1 + F(2 + 3))) + F(F(F(4)) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
393 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) + (F((F(F(4)) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
394 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + (F((F(F(4)) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
395 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3 + 4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
396 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (4 + F((5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
397 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((F(3)^4) \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
398 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((F(3)^4) \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
399 &:= (-1 - ((2 + F(3)) \times (4 \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
400 &:= (-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))^{F(F(F(4+5)-6-7-8-9))} \\
401 &:= ((-1 + F((2 \times (3 + 4)))) - (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
402 &:= (F((-1 + 2 + F(3 + 4))) - (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
403 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
404 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(((3 \times F(4)) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
405 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3))^{F(F(4))})) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
406 &:= (-1 + (F((2 + (3 + (4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
407 &:= (F((-1 + (2 \times 3 + (4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
408 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(((3 \times F(4)) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
369 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (F(F(7)) + F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
370 &:= -9 + 8 - F(F(7)) - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
371 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (F(F(7)) + 6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
372 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (F(F(7)) - (6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
373 &:= -9 - 8 - F(7) \times (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
374 &:= (9 + 8) \times (F(7) - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
375 &:= (-9 + F(8) + 7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
376 &:= -9 + 8 - F(7 + 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
377 &:= F((-9 + 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
378 &:= -9 \times F(8) \times (7 + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
379 &:= -9 \times F(8) - 7 \times 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
380 &:= (F(-9 + 8 + 7) + 6 \times 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
381 &:= (-9 - 8) \times F(7) - F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
382 &:= -9 + 8 - (F(F(7)) - 6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
383 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (F(F(7)) - 6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
384 &:= 9 \times F(8) + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
385 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (F(F(7)) - F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
386 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + F(F(7)) - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
387 &:= (-9 - F(8) - F(7)) \times (6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
388 &:= (-9 - F(8) - 7) \times 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
389 &:= -9 + (F(F(8) - 7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
390 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 - F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
391 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (F(7) - F(F(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
392 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7 + 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
393 &:= -9 \times F(8) - 7 - F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
394 &:= (-9 - F(8)) \times 7 - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
395 &:= (-9 - 8) \times F(7) + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
396 &:= -9 \times 8 + F(7) \times (F(F(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
397 &:= (9 + F(8)) \times F(7) - F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
398 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + F(F(7)) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
399 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + 7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
400 &:= (-9 - (8 - 7)) \times F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
401 &:= 9 \times F(8) + (F(F(7)) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
402 &:= -9 \times F(8) - F(7) - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
403 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
404 &:= -9 + F(F(8) - 7) + F(F(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
405 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
406 &:= (-9 - F(8)) \times 7 + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
407 &:= 9 + F(F(8) - 7) + 6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
408 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
409 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times F((F(F(4)) \times 5)))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 409 &:= -9 \times F(8) - 7 + (6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
410 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F((F(4) + 5)))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 410 &:= (-9 - 8) \times F(7) + F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
411 &:= (-1 + (F((2 \times (3 + 4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 411 &:= -9 + F(8) \times (F(7) - F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
412 &:= (F((-1 + 2 + F(3 + 4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 412 &:= -9 \times (F(8) + 7 - 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
413 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - ((F(F(4)) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 413 &:= (-9 \times 8 + F(7)) \times (F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
414 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 414 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) - (F(7) - (6 + F((5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
415 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3 + 4)) + (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) & 415 &:= -9 \times (8 + F(7)) - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
416 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - ((F(F(4)) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 416 &:= -9 \times F(8) - (F(7) - F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
417 &:= (1 + (2 \times (F(F(3 + 4)) + (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) & 417 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
418 &:= ((1 - 2 + 3) \times (F((F(F(4)) + (5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 418 &:= (-9 - (8 + 7)) \times F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
419 &:= (-1 + (F((2 + F(3))) \times (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 419 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
420 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 420 &:= (-9 - F(8)) \times (7 - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
421 &:= (1 + (F((2 + F(3))) \times (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 421 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
422 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - ((F(4)^5) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) & 422 &:= -9 \times F(8) + 7 - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
423 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 \times F(4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 423 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) + F(F(6)))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
424 &:= (-1 + (F(2 + 3) \times (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 424 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7) \times F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
425 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3 + 4)) - 5))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 425 &:= -9 - 8 + F(7) \times (F(6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
426 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times ((F(4)^5) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 426 &:= F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) \times F(F(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
427 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times ((F(4)^5) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) & 427 &:= -9 \times (8 + F(7)) + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
428 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) - (F(4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 428 &:= -9 \times F(8) + F(7) - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
429 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + 4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 429 &:= -9 \times (8 + F(7)) + F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
430 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times F(F(3 + 4)))) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 430 &:= -9 \times (F(8) - 7 + 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
431 &:= ((F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times F(F(4))) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 431 &:= -9 + F(8 - (F(7) - 6 - 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
432 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) + (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 432 &:= -9 + (8 + F(7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
433 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 433 &:= -9 - 7 \times F(8) - F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
434 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times ((F(F(4))^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 434 &:= -9 \times F(8) + 7 + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
435 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))^{F(F(4))}) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 435 &:= (F(-9 + 8 + 7) + F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
436 &:= F(F(-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times F(F(F(F(4)) + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 436 &:= -9 \times F(8) + 7 + F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
437 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 437 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + 7)) \times (F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
438 &:= (-1 - 2 - (3 \times (F(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 438 &:= -9 \times 8 + (F(7) + F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
439 &:= (1 + 2 + ((F(3) \times F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 439 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times F(F(F(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
440 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times ((4 + 5) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) & 440 &:= -9 \times F(8) + F(7) + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
441 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times ((4 + 5) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) & 441 &:= F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
442 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (F(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 442 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
443 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) + (F(4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 443 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7) \times (F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
444 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) + (F(4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 444 &:= -9 \times F(8) + 7 \times F(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
445 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3 + 4)) + 5))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 445 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
446 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) - (F(4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 446 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
447 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3/F(4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 447 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 7 - F(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
448 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 448 &:= -9 - 7 \times F(8) - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
449 &:= ((-(-1+2)^{F(3)} + (F(4) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
450 &:= ((-1-2 + (F(3) \times (4+5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
451 &:= (((-1+2)^{F(3)} + (F(4) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
452 &:= (-1-2 + (F(3+4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
453 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3+4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
454 &:= (-1 + (F((F(F(2+3)) + F(F(4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
455 &:= (F(((-1+2) \times (3+4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
456 &:= (-1+2 + (F(3+4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
457 &:= (-1+2 + (3 \times (F(F(4)) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
458 &:= (-1 + (F((2+F(3))) \times (F(4) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
459 &:= ((-1 + F((2+F(3+4)))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
460 &:= (-1+2 + (3 \times (F(4) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
461 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4) + (5-6-7-8-9))) \\
462 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times ((4+5) - 6-7-8-9)) \\
463 &:= (1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4) + (5-6-7-8-9))) \\
464 &:= ((-1 + F(2+3)) \times (F(4) + (F((5+6)) + 7+8+9))) \\
465 &:= (-1 + (2 \times F(F(((3+F(4+5)) - 6-7-8-9)))) \\
466 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times F(F((F(4+5) - 6-7-8-9))) \\
467 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (F(F(3+4)) - (5+6))) + 7+8+9)) \\
468 &:= (-1 - (((2-3-4) \times F((5+6))) - 7-8-9)) \\
469 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 \times 3) \times F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
470 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) + (F(4) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
471 &:= (((-1+2)^{F(3)} - (F(4+5) - (F(F(6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
472 &:= ((F(-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times F(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9) \\
473 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + ((F(4) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
474 &:= ((-1 + (F(2+3)^4)) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
475 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3))^{F(F(4))} + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
476 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 \times 3)^{F(4)})) - 5-6-7-8-9) \\
477 &:= (-1-2 + (F(3) \times ((F(4) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
478 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3) \times ((F(4) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
479 &:= ((-1-2 + (F(3)^{4+5})) - 6-7-8-9) \\
480 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 \times 3) + (4+5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
481 &:= (F(-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
482 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2+3))))^{4+5} - 6-7-8-9) \\
483 &:= ((-1+2 + (F(3)^{4+5})) - 6-7-8-9) \\
484 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4) + (5-6-7-8-9))) \\
485 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (F(F(3+4)) - 5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
486 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 \times 3)^{F(4)} + (5-6-7-8-9))) \\
487 &:= (-1+2 + (F(3) \times ((F(4) \times F((5+6))) - 7-8-9))) \\
488 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2+3)) \times (4 + F((5+6)))) + 7+8+9)) \\
449 &:= 9 \times 8 - F(7+6) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
450 &:= F(-9 + F(8) - 7) \times 6 \times (5+4+3+2+1) \\
451 &:= -9 - 8 + F(7) \times (F(F(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
452 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) - 7 + F(F(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1) \\
453 &:= -9 + F(8) \times (F(7) - 6+5+4+3+2+1) \\
454 &:= -9 \times (8+7) - F(F(6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
455 &:= (-9-8 \times 7) \times (F(6) - 5-4-3-2-1) \\
456 &:= F(F(-9+8+7)) \times F(F(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1 \\
457 &:= -9 - F(F(F(8)/7) \times 6) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
458 &:= -9 + F(F(8) - 7) + 6 \times (5+4+3+2+1) \\
459 &:= 9 \times (8+7 + F(F(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
460 &:= -9 \times 8 - F(7) \times 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
461 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6+5 + F(4+3+2+1)) \\
462 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times F(F(6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
463 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 \times (6+5 + F(4+3+2+1)) \\
464 &:= 9 - 8 - 7 \times F(F(6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
465 &:= (-9 + 8 \times F(F(7) - F(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1) \\
466 &:= (-9-8-7) \times 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
467 &:= -9 \times (8+7) - F(6) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
468 &:= -9 \times (F(8) - (7 + (6+5))) - F(4+3+2+1) \\
469 &:= -9 \times (8+7) - 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
470 &:= (-9-8) \times 7 - F(F(6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
471 &:= 9 + F(8) \times (F(7) - 6+5+4+3+2+1) \\
472 &:= (-9 - F(8) + 7) \times 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
473 &:= -F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(7) - 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
474 &:= (-9 - F(8) + F(7)) \times F(6) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
475 &:= -9 - (7 \times F(8) - F(F(6)) - F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
476 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (F(F(7)) + (F(F(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
477 &:= -9 \times F(8) + 7 \times F(6) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
478 &:= -9 \times (F(8) - 7) - 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
479 &:= (-9+8+7) \times F(6+5) - F(4+3+2+1) \\
480 &:= (-9 \times 8 + F(7) \times F(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1) \\
481 &:= -9 \times (8+7) + 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
482 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 \times F(6) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
483 &:= (F(F(-9+8+7)) \times (F(6) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
484 &:= (-9 + F(8)/7) \times F(F(6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
485 &:= (-9-8) \times 7 - 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
486 &:= -F(-9 + F(8)) + 7 \times (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
487 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + F(F(7)) + (6+5) \times (4+3+2+1) \\
488 &:= -9 + F(F(8) - 7) + F(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
489 &:= ((1+2) \times (F(3+4) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
490 &:= ((-1+2 + F(3+4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
491 &:= ((F(F(-1+F(2 \times 3))) \times F(F(4))) - (5-6-7-8-9)) \\
492 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - F(F((F(F(4))+5)))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
493 &:= (-1-2 + ((F(3) \times F(F((F(F(4))+5)))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
494 &:= (F(-1+F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4)+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
495 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times F(F(((3 \times 4) - 5)))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
496 &:= F(F(-1+F(2+3))) \times F(F(F(F(4)+5)) + 6+7+8+9) \\
497 &:= (-1+2 + ((F(3) \times F(F((F(F(4))+5)))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
498 &:= (-1+2 + (F(F(3+4)) + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
499 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2+3)) \times (4 \times (5-6-7-8-9)))) \\
500 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times F(F(3+4))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
501 &:= ((F(F(-1+F(2 \times 3))) \times F(F(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
502 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3+4) - ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
503 &:= (F(F(-1+F(2 \times 3))) + ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
504 &:= (F(F(((((-1-2) \times 3) + (4+(5+6)))))) \times (7+8+9)) \\
505 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (F(F(3+4)) + 5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
506 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) + (5-6-7-8-9))) \\
507 &:= (F(-1+F(2 \times 3)) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
508 &:= ((1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) + (F(F(4)) \times ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
509 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 \times 3) + (4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
510 &:= ((-1 + (F(F((2+F(3)))) \times (4+5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
511 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times (F(4+5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
512 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - (F(4)^5))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
513 &:= (-1-2 + ((F(3) \times (F(4)^5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
514 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3) \times (F(4)^5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
515 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3+4)) - (5-6-7-8-9)))) \\
516 &:= ((F(F((-1+F(2+3)))) \times (F(4)^5)) + 6+7+8+9) \\
517 &:= (-1+2 + ((F(3) \times (F(4)^5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
518 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) \times (4 - ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
519 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (F(F((F(F(4))+5)))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
520 &:= (F(-1+F(2 \times 3)) \times ((F(F(4)) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
521 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F(3) - (F(F((F(F(4))+5)))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
522 &:= (-1-2 - (F(F(3+F(4))) \times (5-6-7-8-9)) \\
523 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(F(3+F(4))) \times (5-6-7-8-9)) \\
524 &:= (-1 + ((2+F(3+4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
525 &:= (F(F(F((-1+2 \times 3)))) \times (F(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
526 &:= (-1 + (F((2 \times (3+4)) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
527 &:= (F((-1+2+F(3+4))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
528 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 \times 3) + (4 + (5+6)))) \times (7+8+9)) \\
489 &:= -9 - 8 - F(7) \times F(6) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
490 &:= -9 \times (F(8) - 7) + 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
491 &:= (-9-8) \times (F(7) - 6) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
492 &:= -9 \times (F(8) - 7) + F(6) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
493 &:= -9 \times F(8+7 - F(6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
494 &:= -9 \times (F(8) - 7 \times (6+5)) - (4+3+2+1) \\
495 &:= (-9+8 + F(7) + F(F(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1) \\
496 &:= -9 \times (8+7) + F(F(6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
497 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7+6) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
498 &:= (-9+8 - F(7)) \times F(6) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
499 &:= 7 \times (-9-8) + F(6) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
500 &:= F(-9+F(8)) - F(F(7)) - F(F(6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
501 &:= -9 + (F(8) + 7+6) \times (5+4+3+2+1) \\
502 &:= -9 - F(8) - F(7) \times 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
503 &:= -9 + 8^{F(F(7)+6-5-4-3-2-1)} \\
504 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) + (F(7) - (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
505 &:= (9+8 \times 7) \times F(6) - 5-4-3-2-1 \\
506 &:= (-9+8) \times (F(7) \times F(6) - F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
507 &:= ((9-8 - (F(7) \times F(6))) + F((5+4+3+2+1))) \\
508 &:= (-9 - F(8) + F(7)) \times 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
509 &:= 9 - (8 \times F(7) + 6 - F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
510 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 - F(F(6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
511 &:= -9 + F(8+7) - 6 \times (5+4+3+2+1) \\
512 &:= (-9-8) \times 7 + F(F(6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
513 &:= (F(-9+F(8)) - (F(F(7)) + (F(6) - F((5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
514 &:= (9-8 - F(7)) \times F(6) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
515 &:= -9 - 8 - F(7) \times 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
516 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 - F(F(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1) \\
517 &:= -9 \times 8 - F(7) - F(6) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
518 &:= -9 - (8 \times F(7) - F(F(6)) - F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
519 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times 7 \times 6 + 5+4+3+2+1 \\
520 &:= -9 \times (F(F(8)/7) + F(6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
521 &:= F(-9+F(8)) - F(7+6) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
522 &:= (-9 - F(F(8)/7)) \times F(6) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
523 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 - F(6) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
524 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 - F(F(6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
525 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) + F(7))) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
526 &:= (-9+8 - F(7)) \times 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
527 &:= 9+8 + (F(7) + F(F(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1) \\
528 &:= -9 \times (F(8) - F(7) \times 6) + 5+4+3+2+1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
529 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
530 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times F(F(3+4))) + (F((5+6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
531 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
532 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2+3)))) \times (F(F(4)) + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
533 &:= (1 + (2 \times (3 + (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
534 &:= ((1 + F(2+3)) + (F(F(4)) \times ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
535 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3+4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
536 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
537 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
538 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3) \times ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
539 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3))^{4+5} + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
540 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2+3)))) \times ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
541 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
542 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2+3))))^{4+5} + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
543 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3))^{4+5} + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
544 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3) \times ((F(4))^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
545 &:= (1 + 2 + ((F(3))^{4+5} + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
546 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 \times 3))^{F(4)} + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
547 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times ((F(4))^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
548 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) + (F(F(4)) \times ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
549 &:= ((F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times F(4)) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
550 &:= ((-1 - F((F(F(2+3)) + F(4)))) \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
551 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + ((F(4))^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
552 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (F((3 \times F(4))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
553 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3+4) + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
554 &:= (-1 - (F(2+3) \times (F(F(4)) - (F((5+6)) + 7+8+9)))) \\
555 &:= ((-1 \times F(2+3)) \times (F(F(4)) - (F((5+6)) + 7+8+9))) \\
556 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((3 + F(4)) \times F((5+6))) + 7+8+9)) \\
557 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3))^4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
558 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3))^4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
559 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
560 &:= ((-1 + F(2+3)) \times (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
561 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3))^4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
562 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F((3 + F(F(4)))) \times (F((5+6)) + 7+8+9))) \\
563 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3))^{F(F(4))} \times (5+6)) + 7+8+9) \\
564 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) - (F((4 + (5+6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
565 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) - (F((4 + (5+6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
566 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) - (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
567 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((F(3) - F((F(4) + 5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
529 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
530 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
531 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (F(F(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
532 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (F(7) \times 6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
533 &:= -9 \times 8 - (F(7) - F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
534 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times F(6 - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
535 &:= -9 + F(8 + 7) - 6 - 5 - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
536 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (F(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
537 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
538 &:= -9 \times (F(8) - 7 - 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
539 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
540 &:= ((9 + 8 + (F(7) + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
541 &:= -9 - (8 - (7 + (6 + 5))) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
542 &:= 9 - 8 \times 7 - F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
543 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + F(7)) - (F(6) - F((5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
544 &:= -9 \times (F(8) - F(7)) + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
545 &:= -9 \times 8 + F(7) - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
546 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
547 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
548 &:= (9 - 8) \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
549 &:= 9 + (8 + 7) \times (F(F(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
550 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
551 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
552 &:= (9 + 8 + 7) \times (F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
553 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
554 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
555 &:= (-9 \times (8 - F(7)) - F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
556 &:= -9 \times ((8 - 7) \times 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
557 &:= -9 \times 8 + F(7) + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
558 &:= -9 \times (F(8) + 7 - 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
559 &:= 9 \times (8 - F(7)) - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
560 &:= -9 + F(8) + F(F(7)) + F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
561 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 7 + F(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
562 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
563 &:= (-9 - F(8) \times F(7)) / 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
564 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + (7 + F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
565 &:= 9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
566 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
567 &:= -9 - F(8) - 7 - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$568 := (-1 \times 2 - ((F(3) - F((F(4) + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$569 := (1 - 2 - ((F(3) - F((F(4) + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$570 := ((-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times (4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$571 := (-1 + 2 - ((F(3) - F((F(4) + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$572 := (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) - (F((F(4) \times 5)) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))$$

$$573 := (((-1 - 2 \times 3) + F((F(4) \times 5))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$574 := ((-1 + F((2 + F(3 + 4)))) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$575 := (F((F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3))) \times F(4))) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$576 := (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) - (F((F(4) \times 5)) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))$$

$$577 := ((-1 - 2 + F((F(3) + F((F(F(4) + 5)))))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$578 := (((-1 + 2 - 3) + F((F(4) \times 5))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$579 := ((-1 + F((2 \times 3 + (4 + 5)))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$580 := (F((-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times (4 + 5)))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$581 := (((-1 + 2)^{F(3)}) + (F((F(4) \times 5)) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$582 := (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + (F((F(4) \times 5)) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$583 := (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) + (F((F(4) \times 5)) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$584 := (-1 + (F((2 + F(3 + 4))) + (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))$$

$$585 := (F((F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3))) \times F(4))) + (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$586 := (F((-1 - (2 - (3 + (4 + (5 + 6)))))) - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$587 := (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4) - (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))))$$

$$588 := ((-1 \times 2 - F(3)) \times (F(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$589 := (1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4) - (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))))$$

$$590 := (((-1 + 2 \times 3)^4) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$591 := (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$592 := (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$593 := ((1 - F(2 \times 3)) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$594 := (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$595 := ((-1 + 2 + (F(3)^4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$596 := (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$597 := (-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times (F(F(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$598 := (-F(F(-1 + F(2 + 3))) + 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$599 := (-1 + ((2 + (F(3) \times (4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$600 := ((-1 + F((2 - (3 - (4 + 5)))))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$601 := (((-1 + 2)^{F(3)}) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$602 := (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$603 := (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$604 := ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$605 := (1 \times (F(F(2 + 3)) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$606 := (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (F(F(F(4) + 5))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))$$

$$607 := (-1 - 2 + F(((3 \times (F(4) \times 5)) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))$$

$$568 := (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$569 := -9 + (F(8) + 7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + F(3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$570 := (-9 + 8 \times F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$571 := (-9 + 8 - F(F(7)))/6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$572 := -9 - 8 - F(7) - F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$573 := (-9 - (F(8) + (F(7) - (6 + F((5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$574 := -9 - 8 - F(7) - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$575 := -9 + 8 - F(7) - F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$576 := -9 \times 8 \times (F(7) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$577 := (-9 \times F(8))/7 - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$578 := -9 - 8 - 7 - F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$579 := -9 + F(8) \times (7 + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$580 := -9 + F(8 + 7) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$581 := -9 + 8 - 7 - F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$582 := 9 \times (F(8) + 7 \times 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$583 := -9 + F(8)/7 - F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$584 := -9 \times F(F(8)/7) - F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$585 := (9 - (F(8) + ((7 + 6) - F((5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$586 := -9 - 8 - (F(7) - 6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$587 := -9 - F(8) + F(7) - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$588 := -9 - F(8 + 7 - F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$589 := (-9 + 8) \times (F(7) + F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$590 := -9 + 8 - F(7) - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$591 := (-9 + 8) \times (F(7) + 6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$592 := -9 + (F(8 + 7) + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$593 := -9 - (F(8) - 7 - 6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$594 := -9 - (8 + 7) + F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$595 := -9 + 8 + 7 - F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$596 := -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$597 := (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$598 := 9 + (F(8 + 7) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$599 := -9 - (F(8) - F(7) - 6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$600 := -9 - (8 - 7)^6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$601 := -9 + 8 + F(7) - F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$602 := -9 + 8 - (F(7) - 6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$603 := (-9 + 8) \times (F(7) - 6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$604 := -9 + 8 - (F(7) - F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$605 := (-9 + 8) \times (F(7) - F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$606 := -9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$607 := -(9 + 8 + 7)/F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
608 &:= ((-1 + F(2+3)) \times (F(F(4)) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 608 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 - F(6) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
609 &:= (-1 + F(((F(2+3) \times (4+5)) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) & 609 &:= -9 + F(8) - 7 - 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
610 &:= F((-1 \times ((F(2+3) \times 4) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) & 610 &:= F(-9 + (F(8)/7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
611 &:= (-1 + 2 + F(((3 \times (F(4) \times 5)) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) & 611 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)/6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
612 &:= ((-1 + F(2+3)) \times (F(4) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 612 &:= F(-9 + 8 + 7) - 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
613 &:= (F(-1 + F(2 \times 3)) + (4 \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 613 &:= (9 + 8 + 7)/F(6) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
614 &:= ((-1 + F(2+3)) + F((F(F(4)) - ((5+6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) & 614 &:= -9 + F(8+7 - F(6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
615 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times F(F(3+4))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 615 &:= ((9-8) \times (F(7) - (F(6) - F((5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
616 &:= ((-1 + F(2+3)) \times (4 + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 616 &:= -9 + 8 + F(7) - 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
617 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) + F((F(F(4)) - ((5+6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))))) & 617 &:= (9-8) \times (F(7) - 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
618 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) - (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 618 &:= 9 - 8 + (F(7) - 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
619 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) - (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 619 &:= -9 \times 8 / (F(7) - F(F(6))) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
620 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) + (4 \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))))) & 620 &:= 9 + (8-7)^{F(F(6))} + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
621 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) + (F((F(4) + 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 621 &:= -9 + F(8) - 7 + 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
622 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) - (F((F(4) + 5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 622 &:= -9 + (F(8+7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
623 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) + (F((F(4) + 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 623 &:= (9-8) \times (7+6) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
624 &:= (-1 + (F(2+3)^{F(4+5)-(6+7+8+9)})) & 624 &:= F(-9 + 8 + 7) + 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
625 &:= (F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3)))^{F(4+5)-(6+7+8+9)}) & 625 &:= F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) - 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
626 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) - (F((F(4) + 5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 626 &:= F(-9 + 8 + 7) + F(6) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
627 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F((F(3+4) - 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 627 &:= (-9-8) \times (7 - F(6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
628 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F((F(3+4) - 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 628 &:= -9 + 8 + F(7) + 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
629 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (F(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 629 &:= ((9-8) \times (F(7) + (6 + F((5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
630 &:= ((-1 - 2 + F(F(3+F(4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) & 630 &:= (9+8+F(7)) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1) \\
631 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F((F(3+4) - 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 631 &:= (F(((9-8) \times (F(7) - F(F(6)))))) + F((5+4+3+2+1))) \\
632 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2+3)))) + (F((F(4) + 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 632 &:= F(-9 + 8 + 7) \times (F(6+5) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
633 &:= (F((-1 + F(2+3))) + (F((F(4) + 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 633 &:= 9 + F(8) - F(7) + 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
634 &:= ((-1 + F((2 + F(3+4)))) - (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 634 &:= F(-9 + 8 + F(7))/6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
635 &:= ((-1 \times F(2+3)) + (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 635 &:= -9 + F(8) + 7 + 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
636 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times ((F(4)^5) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) & 636 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 - F(F(6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
637 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F((F(3) + F((F(4) + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 637 &:= F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) + 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
638 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 638 &:= -9 \times (F(8) + 7) + F(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1) \\
639 &:= (-1 + (F((2 \times 3 + (4+5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 639 &:= F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) + F(6) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
640 &:= (F((-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times (4+5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 640 &:= 9 + F(8+7) + 6 + (5+4+3+2+1) \\
641 &:= (((-1+2)^{F(3)}) + (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 641 &:= -9 + (F(8) + F(7) + 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
642 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2+3)))) + (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 642 &:= -9 + F(8) + 7 \times (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
643 &:= (F((-1 + F(2+3))) + (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 643 &:= 9 \times F(8)/7 + 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
644 &:= (-1 + (F((2 + F(3+4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 644 &:= F(-9 \times 8 / (F(7) - F(F(6)))) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
645 &:= (F((F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3))) \times F(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 645 &:= -9 \times (8 - F(7) \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
646 &:= (-1 + (((F(F(F(2+3))) + F(F(4))) \times F((5+6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 646 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
647 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) + (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 647 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(7))) - (F(6) - F((5+4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
648 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times (4 + (5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
649 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F(3 + 4) \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
650 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
651 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
652 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times F(F(3 + 4)))) - (5 - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
653 &:= (F(-1 + F(2 \times 3)) + (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
654 &:= (-1 + (((F(2 + 3))^{F(4)} \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
655 &:= (((F((-1 + 2 \times 3))^{F(4)} \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
656 &:= (-1 \times ((F(2 \times 3) \times (4 - F((5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
657 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3) + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
658 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3) + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
659 &:= (1 - 2 + ((F(3) + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
660 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times 3)^4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
661 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3) + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
662 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3) \times ((4 \times F((5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
663 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
664 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) - F(F(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
665 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 + 3) \times 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
666 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (3 \times F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
667 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
668 &:= -1 + F(2 + F(3)) \times F(F(F(F(4)) + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
669 &:= (((1 + 2) \times F(F(((3 \times 4) - 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
670 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3 \times F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
671 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
672 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
673 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3^{F(4)}) \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
674 &:= ((F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times F(4)) + (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
675 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times F(3 + 4))) \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
676 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3^{F(4)}) \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
677 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 \times 3) - F(F(4))) \times (F((5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
678 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times (F(4) \times (F((5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
679 &:= (-1 - (((2 - F(3 \times 4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
680 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + F(3 \times 4)) \times 5) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
681 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + (F(4) \times (F((5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
682 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
683 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F(4 + 5))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
684 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4) \times (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
685 &:= ((F(-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
686 &:= ((F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times F(4)) + ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
687 &:= (1 - 2 + ((F(3) \times (4 \times F((5 + 6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
648 &:= -9 \times (F(8) - F(7)) \times (6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
649 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
650 &:= 9 + 8 + (7 \times F(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
651 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
652 &:= (9 - 8) \times 7 \times 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
653 &:= 9 + F(8) + 7 + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
654 &:= -9 \times F(8) + F(7 + 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
655 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
656 &:= 9 \times (8 \times F(7) - 6 \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
657 &:= -9 + 8 \times (F(7) - 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
658 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
659 &:= -9 + F(8 + 7) + F(6) + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
660 &:= (-9 \times F(8) + F(7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
661 &:= -9 \times (8 - F(7)) + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
662 &:= -9 \times F(8) + F(F(7)) + F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
663 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
664 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - F(F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
665 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
666 &:= -9 \times (8 + F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
667 &:= -9 + (F(8 + 7) + 6 + 5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
668 &:= -9 + F(F(8) - 7) + 6 \times 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
669 &:= 9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
670 &:= (9 + 8 - 7) \times 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
671 &:= -9 - 8 + F(7) \times 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
672 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times 7 \times F(F(F(6))) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
673 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
674 &:= F(-9 + 8 + 7) \times F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
675 &:= (((9 + 8 + 7) + F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
676 &:= -9 \times (8 - F(7)) + F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
677 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times F(6 + 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
678 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
679 &:= -9 - 8 \times (F(7) - (F(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
680 &:= -9 + F(8 + 7) + F(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
681 &:= ((9 \times 8 - (7 - 6)) + F((5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
682 &:= (-9 + 8 + F(7)) \times 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
683 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
684 &:= -9 \times (F(8) - 7 - 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
685 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
686 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times 7 - F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
687 &:= -9 + 8 + F(7) \times 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
688 &:= (((1 + F(2 + 3)) + F(F(4))) \times F((5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
689 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F((F(3 + 4) - 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
690 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (F(3) + (4 + 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
691 &:= (1 + ((2 + F((F(3 + 4) - 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
692 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
693 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
694 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + (F(4 + 5) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
695 &:= (((-1 + 2 + F(3 \times 4)) \times 5) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
696 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (3 \times (F(4)^5))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
697 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (F(4)^5))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
698 &:= ((-1 + (F((2 + F(3))) \times (F(4)^5))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
699 &:= (-1 + (F(2 + 3) \times (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
700 &:= ((-1 + F((F(2 + 3) + F(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
701 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4))^5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
702 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((3^{F(4)}) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
703 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times (F((F(4) + (5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
704 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
705 &:= (-1 + (F(F((2 + F(3)))) \times (F((F(4) + (5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
706 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times (F((F(4) + (5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
707 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times (F((F(4) + (5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
708 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F(3 + 4) - (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
709 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + (F((F(4) + (5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
710 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times F(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
711 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - ((F(4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
712 &:= ((F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times F(4)) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
713 &:= (1 + ((F(2 \times 3) \times (F(4) + F((5 + 6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
714 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - ((F(4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
715 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F(3) - ((4 + (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
716 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - ((4 + (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
717 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times ((F(4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
718 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times ((F(4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
719 &:= (1 - 2 + (3 \times ((F(4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
720 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (3 \times (4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
721 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times ((F(4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
722 &:= (-1 + (F((2 + F(3 + 4))) + (F((5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
723 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - F(F(F(4) + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
724 &:= ((F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times F(4)) - (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
725 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - (3^{F(4)})) \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
726 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
727 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times F(F(F(4) + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
688 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times 7 - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
689 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
690 &:= (9 + (8 - 7)) \times F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
691 &:= -9 + F(8 + 7) + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
692 &:= (9 - 8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(6) - 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
693 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times 7) - (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
694 &:= (9 - 8 + F(7)) \times 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
695 &:= -9 + 8 \times (F(7) \times (6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
696 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7) \times (F(F(6)) - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
697 &:= -9 - 8 + F(7) \times F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
698 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) - 7 \times F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
699 &:= F(-9 + F(8) - 7 + 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
700 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times 7 + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
701 &:= -9 \times F(8) \times (7 - 6 - 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
702 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times 7) + (F(6) + F((5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
703 &:= -9 + 8 \times (F(7) \times F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
704 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + F(6 + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
705 &:= -9 + F(8) \times (F(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
706 &:= (-9 + 8 + F(7)) \times F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
707 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (F(6) + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
708 &:= -9 \times F(8) + 7 + F(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
709 &:= 9 + F(8 + 7) + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
710 &:= (-9 \times 8 + F(7) \times (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
711 &:= (9 \times ((8 \times 7) + (F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
712 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) - 7 \times 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
713 &:= -9 + 8 + F(7) \times F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
714 &:= F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) \times (F(6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
715 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times 7 + F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
716 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) - F(7) \times (6 + 5 - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
717 &:= -9 - (8 \times (F(7) - F(F(6)) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
718 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times F(F(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
719 &:= -9 - 8 \times F(7) \times (F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
720 &:= F(-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
721 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
722 &:= F(-9 + 8 + 7) \times F(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
723 &:= 9 + F(8) \times (F(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
724 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + 7)) \times 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
725 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
726 &:= -9 + 8 \times F(7) + F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
727 &:= 9 \times F(8 + 7 - F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
728 &:= (-1 + ((F((2 + F(3))) \times F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 728 &:= 9 \times (F(8) - 7) - F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
729 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 729 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((F(7) \times F(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
730 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 + 3)) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 730 &:= 9 \times (F(8) - 7) - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
731 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times F((F(4) + (5 + 6)))))) - 7 - 8 - 9) & 731 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
732 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 732 &:= -9 \times (F(8) - F(7) \times F(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
733 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 733 &:= F(-9 + 8 + F(7)) - F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
734 &:= (-1 + (F((F(2 + 3) + F(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 734 &:= -9 - 7 \times F(8) + F(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
735 &:= (F((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 735 &:= 7 \times (9 + 8) + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
736 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 736 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
737 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 + 3)^4) + (F((5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 737 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - F(6 + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
738 &:= ((F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3)))^4) + (F((5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 738 &:= -9 \times (F(8) - F(7) - 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
739 &:= (-1 - (F(F(F(F(2 + 3)))) \times (F(F(4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 739 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
740 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 740 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
741 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (4 - F((5 + 6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) & 741 &:= 9 \times (F(8) - 7) \times 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
742 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((F(3) - (F(4) \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 742 &:= -9 + F(8) \times 7 - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
743 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 743 &:= -9 - 8 - (F(7) - F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
744 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times (4 + (5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) & 744 &:= 9 \times (F(8) - 7) + F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
745 &:= ((F(-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 745 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times F(7) - F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
746 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + ((4 + 5) + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 746 &:= F(-9 + 8 + F(7)) - F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
747 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F((3 + F(F(4))) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 747 &:= 9 \times (8 \times F(7) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
748 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F((3 + F(F(4))) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 748 &:= F(-9 + 8 + F(7)) - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
749 &:= (1 - 2 + (F((3 + F(F(4))) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 749 &:= 9 - (8 + 7 - F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
750 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 750 &:= -9 \times 8 + F(F(7)) - F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
751 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F((3 + F(F(4))) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 751 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
752 &:= ((-1 + ((F((2 + F(3))) + F(4 + 5)) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) & 752 &:= -9 + 8 \times (F(7) + F(6 + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
753 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - (F(4)^5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 753 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) - 7 + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
754 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - ((4 \times F((5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 754 &:= F(-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
755 &:= (((-1 + 2 + F(3 \times 4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 755 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + 7 - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
756 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 \times (F(4)^5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 756 &:= (9 - F(8)) \times 7 \times (6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
757 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times (F(4)^5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 757 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + 7 \times F(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
758 &:= (-1 + ((F((2 + F(3))) \times (F(4)^5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 758 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times F(7) - F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
759 &:= (-1 + (F((2 + F(3 + 4))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 759 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(7) - (F(6) - F((5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
760 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 760 &:= F(-9 + 8 + F(7)) + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
761 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times ((4 \times F((5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 761 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7) - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
762 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (F((F(F(4)) + (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 762 &:= F(-9 + 8 + F(7)) + F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
763 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) \times (4 - (F((5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 763 &:= -9 \times 8 + F(F(7)) - F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
764 &:= (-1 + (F(F(F(2 + 3))) \times (F(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 764 &:= -9 \times (F(8) - 7) + F(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
765 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3 + 4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 765 &:= (-9 \times 8 - F(7)) \times (6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
766 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(F(3 + F(4))) + (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 766 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
767 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (F(3) \times (4 + (5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 767 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + 7 + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
768 &:= ((F((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4)))) + (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
769 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 + 3)) \times (4 + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
770 &:= ((-1 + 2 + F(F(3 + F(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
771 &:= (1 + (F(F(2 + 3)) \times (4 + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
772 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (F((F(F(4)) + (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
773 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (F((F(F(4)) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
774 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 + 3))^4 + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
775 &:= (1 \times ((F(2 + 3))^4 + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
776 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
777 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(F(3 + F(4))) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
778 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(F(3 + F(4))) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
779 &:= (-1 - ((F(2 \times 3) - F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
780 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
781 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(F(3 + F(4))) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
782 &:= ((F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times 4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
783 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
784 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (F(4) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
785 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (F((F(F(4)) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
786 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
787 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
788 &:= (-1 + (F((2 + F(3))) \times (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
789 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
790 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
791 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) \times (F((5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
792 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + (4 + (5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
793 &:= (((-1 + 2)^{F(3)} + (F(4) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
794 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + (F(4) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
795 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) + (F(4) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
796 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + (F(4) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
797 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
798 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times (F(F(4)) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
799 &:= (-1 - (F(2 \times 3) \times (4 \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
800 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) \times (4 \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
801 &:= (1 - (F(2 \times 3) \times (4 \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
802 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times (F((F(4) + (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
803 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times (F((F(4) + (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
804 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) + F(F(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
805 &:= (1 \times ((F(F(2 \times 3)) + F(F(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
806 &:= (F(-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times ((F(F(4))^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
807 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
768 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
769 &:= 9 - 8 \times (F(7) + 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
770 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) + (F(7) - (6 + 5)))) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
771 &:= -9 \times 8 + F(7 + 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
772 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times F(7) + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
773 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7) + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
774 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + 7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
775 &:= (F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) + (F(F(6)) + F((5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
776 &:= (-9 - 8) \times F(7) + F(F(F(6)) - 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
777 &:= -9 \times 8 + F(F(7)) + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
778 &:= F(-9 + 8 + 7) \times F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
779 &:= -9 \times 8 + F(F(7)) + F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
780 &:= (-9 \times F(8) + F(F(7)) + F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
781 &:= -9 \times (F(F(8)/7) - F(F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
782 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + 7 + F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
783 &:= -9 \times (F(8)/7 - 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
784 &:= 9 \times F(8) - 7 - F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
785 &:= ((F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) \times (F(6) \times 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
786 &:= 9 \times F(8) - 7 - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
787 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times F(7) + F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
788 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7) + F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
789 &:= 9 \times (8 + 6 \times F(7)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
790 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - F(F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
791 &:= (-9 - 8 \times F(7)) \times (F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
792 &:= -9 \times (F(F(8)/7) - 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
793 &:= -9 \times (F(F(8)/7) - F(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
794 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + (7 + 6) \times 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
795 &:= (-9 + (8 \times 7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
796 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + 7 \times 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
797 &:= -9 + 8 \times (F(7) + F(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
798 &:= -9 \times F(8) + F(7 - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
799 &:= -9 \times (F(8) - 7 \times 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
800 &:= (-9 + F((8 - 7) \times (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
801 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - F(F(7))) \times (6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
802 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - F(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
803 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
804 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times (6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
805 &:= 9 \times (8 + F(7)) + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
806 &:= 9 \times F(8) + (F(7) - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
807 &:= -9 - F(8) + F(F(7)) - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
808 &:= ((1 \times 2 + F(3)) \times ((F(F(4)) \times F((5+6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
809 &:= (-1 + (F((2 + F(3))) \times ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
810 &:= (F((-1 + F(2+3))) \times ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
811 &:= (1 + (F((2 + F(3))) \times ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
812 &:= ((-1 + F(2+3)) \times (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
813 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - ((F(4)^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
814 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F((F(3) - (4 - (5+6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
815 &:= (((F(-1 + F(2 \times 3)))^{F(F(4))}) \times 5) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
816 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times ((F(4)^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
817 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times ((F(4)^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
818 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
819 &:= (F((-1 + F(2+3))) \times ((F(4)^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
820 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times ((F(4)^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
821 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (((4+5) + F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
822 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 \times (F(4) \times F((5+6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
823 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times (F(4) \times F((5+6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
824 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (3+4)) \times F((5+6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
825 &:= ((-1 + 2 - F((3 \times F(4)))) \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
826 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times (F(4) \times F((5+6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
827 &:= (-1 - (((2 - F((3 + (4+5)))) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
828 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + F((3 + (4+5)))) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
829 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F((F(3) + (4+5))) - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
830 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F((F(3) + (4+5))) - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
831 &:= (-1 - ((F(2 \times 3))^{F(F(4))}) \times ((5+6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
832 &:= (F(-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4+5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
833 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
834 &:= ((-1 - 2 + F((F(3)^4))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
835 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + F((F(3)^4))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
836 &:= ((-1 + F((F(2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
837 &:= (F(((-1 + F(2+3)) \times 4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
838 &:= ((-1 + 2 + F((F(3)^4))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
839 &:= (1 \times 2 + (F((F(3)^4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
840 &:= ((-1 + (F(2+3))^{F(F(4))}) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
841 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3) + (F(4) \times (5+6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
842 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3+4) \times (F((5+6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
843 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3+4) \times (F((5+6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
844 &:= -1 + F(F(F(F(F(2+3)))) + F(F(4))) \times (F(5+6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
845 &:= (F(((-1 + 2) \times (3+4))) \times (F((5+6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
846 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3+4) \times (F((5+6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
808 &:= -9 + 8 \times F(7) \times F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
809 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)/7) + F(6+5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
810 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
811 &:= -9 \times 8 + F(7) \times F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
812 &:= 9 \times F(8) + 7 + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
813 &:= -9 - (F(8) - F(7+6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
814 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + F(6+5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
815 &:= -9 + 8 \times (F(7) + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
816 &:= 9 \times 8 \times F(7) - F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
817 &:= -9 + 8 \times (F(7) + F(6+5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
818 &:= -9 - 8 + F(F(7)) - F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
819 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + (6 + F((5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
820 &:= -9 - 8 + F(F(7)) - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
821 &:= 9 - 8 - (7 - F(6+5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
822 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) - 7) \times (F(F(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
823 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
824 &:= 9 \times (8 + 6 \times F(7)) + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
825 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 \times F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
826 &:= -9 - 8 + F(7+6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
827 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) - 7) \times 6 - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
828 &:= -9 \times (F(8) + 7 - F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
829 &:= -9 \times (F(8)/7 - F(6+5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
830 &:= (-9 + F(8)/7 + F(6+5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
831 &:= -9 + 8 \times (F(7) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
832 &:= -9 - 8 + F(F(7)) + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
833 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 \times (F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
834 &:= -9 + F(F(8 + 7 - F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
835 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + 6) \times 5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
836 &:= -9 + 8 + F(F(7)) - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
837 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) - 7) \times 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
838 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) + 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
839 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
840 &:= (-9 + 8 \times F(7) - 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
841 &:= -9 - 8 + F(7) \times (6 + 5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
842 &:= -9 + 8 + F(7+6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
843 &:= (9 - 8) \times (F(7+6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
844 &:= 9 - 8 + F(7+6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
845 &:= 9 \times (8 - F(7)) + F(6+5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
846 &:= -9 - (F(8) - F(7) \times 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
847 &:= (-1 - 2 - (F((3 \times F(4))) \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
848 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F((3 \times F(4))) \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
849 &:= (-1 - (F((2 + (3 + 4))) \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
850 &:= (-1 \times (F((2 + (3 + 4))) \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
851 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F((3 \times F(4))) \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
852 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times ((F(4)^5) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
853 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
854 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(F(3 + 4)) + ((5 + F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
855 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 \times (F(F(4)) - F((5 + 6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
856 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (4 \times (5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
857 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F(4 + 5)) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
858 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
859 &:= ((-1 + (F((2 + (3 + 4))) \times (5 + F(F(6)))))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
860 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F((F(F(4)) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
861 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + (F(4) \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
862 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + (F(4) \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
863 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + (F((F(4) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
864 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - (4 + (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
865 &:= -1 + F(F(F(F(2 + 3)))) \times F(F(4)) \times F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
866 &:= (((-1 + F((F(F(2 \times 3)) - F(F(4)))))/5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
867 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F((3 \times F(4))) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
868 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F((3 \times F(4))) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
869 &:= (-1 - ((F(2 + 3) - F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
870 &:= (((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) + F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
871 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F((3 \times F(4))) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
872 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) \times (4 - (F((5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
873 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
874 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 + 3))^{F(F(4))}) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
875 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times F(3 + 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
876 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
877 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((F(3 + 4) \times 5) - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
878 &:= (((1 + (F((2 + F(3)))^4)) \times (5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
879 &:= (-1 - (F(2 \times 3) \times (F(4) - (F((5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
880 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) \times (F(4) - (F((5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
881 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (F(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
882 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) \times (F(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
883 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F((3 \times F(4))) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
884 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F((3 \times F(4))) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
885 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F((3 + (4 + 5))) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
886 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F((3 + (4 + 5))) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
847 &:= 9 \times (F(8) - F(7)) \times (6 + 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
848 &:= -9 + 8 + F(F(7)) + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
849 &:= F(-9 + 8 + F(7)) \times 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
850 &:= -9 + 8 + F(F(7)) + F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
851 &:= -9 - (F(8)/7 - F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
852 &:= -9 + F(8) + 7 \times F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
853 &:= 9 \times (8 + (F(7) + 6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
854 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 - 6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
855 &:= (9 - 8 + 7 \times F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
856 &:= -9 \times (8 - F(7) - F(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
857 &:= 9 + 8 + 7 \times F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
858 &:= -9 + F(8) \times 7 \times 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
859 &:= 9 - 8 + F(7) \times (6 + 5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
860 &:= -9 - 8 - F(7) + F(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
861 &:= -9 + (F(8) + F(F(7)) + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
862 &:= (-9 + 8 + F(7)) \times F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
863 &:= -9 + 8 + F(F(7)) + F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
864 &:= (9 + 8 + 7) \times (F(F(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
865 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - F(F(6)) \times 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
866 &:= -9 - 8 + F(7) \times F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
867 &:= -9 - (F(8) - 7 - F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
868 &:= -9 + F(8) \times F(7) - 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
869 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times (6 + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
870 &:= (-9 - F(8)) \times (7 - F(F(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
871 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
872 &:= 9 \times (F(8) + 7 \times (6 + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
873 &:= -9 + 8 \times (F(7) + F(F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
874 &:= -9 + F(8) \times (7 + 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
875 &:= -9 + (F(8) + F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
876 &:= 9 + F(8) \times 7 \times 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
877 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (F(7) - F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
878 &:= -9 - F(8)/7 + F(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
879 &:= 6 \times F(-9 + 8 + F(7)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
880 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(7)) + (6 + F((5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
881 &:= -9 + F((8 - 7) \times (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
882 &:= 9 \times (F(8) - (F(7) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
883 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + F(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
884 &:= -9 + F(8)/7 + F(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
885 &:= (F((F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) - 6)) + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
886 &:= -9 - 8 + F(7) + F(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
887 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (F(F(4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
888 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) \times (F(F(4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
889 &:= (1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (F(F(4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
890 &:= (F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3)))) \times (F(4 + 5) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
891 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (F(F(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
892 &:= (((1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times F(4 + 5)) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
893 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (F(4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
894 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - (F(F(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
895 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F(3) - (F(4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
896 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - (F(4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
897 &:= ((F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times 4) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
898 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + F(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
899 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) + (4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
900 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - (F(3) - F(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
901 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + F(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
902 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
903 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + (F(4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
904 &:= ((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4))) \times (F((5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
905 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (F(4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
906 &:= (F(((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times 4)) - ((5 \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
907 &:= ((F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times 4) + (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
908 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times F((F(F(4)) + (5 + 6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
909 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3 + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
910 &:= (F(-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
911 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (F(F(4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
912 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3+4})) - F((5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
913 &:= -1 + (F(F(F(F(2 + 3)))) \times F(F(4)) \times F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
914 &:= (((-1 - 2 + F(3 + 4)) \times F((5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
915 &:= (((F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))^4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
916 &:= (1 + (((F((2 + F(3)))^4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
917 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (F(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
918 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (F(4 + 5) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
919 &:= ((F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times 4) + ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
920 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times ((F(F(4)) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
921 &:= ((-1 + F((F(2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) - (F((5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
922 &:= (F(((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times 4)) - (F((5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
923 &:= (1 + (F((F(2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) - (F((5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
924 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (4 + F((5 + F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
925 &:= ((-1 - 2 - F((3 \times F(4)))) \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
926 &:= (((1 + (F((2 + F(3)))^4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
927 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 - F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
928 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3 - F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
929 &:= (-1 - ((F((2 + F(3))) - F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
930 &:= (-1 \times ((F((2 + F(3))) - F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
931 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 - F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
932 &:= (F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4 + 5) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
933 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times ((F(F(4)) + (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
934 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times ((F(F(4)) + (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
935 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3+4}) - F((5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
936 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((F(3) - (4 + (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
937 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times ((F(F(4)) + (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
938 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) + ((F(F(4))^5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
939 &:= ((-1 \times F(F(2 \times 3))) + ((F(F(4))^5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
940 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (F(4 + 5) - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
941 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times (F(4)^5)) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
942 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3^{F(4)}) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
943 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3^{F(4)}) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
944 &:= (-1 + ((F((2 + F(3)))^{F(4)}) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
945 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))^{F(4)}) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
946 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3^{F(4)}) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
947 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 \times (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
948 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) \times (F(4 + 5) - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
949 &:= ((-1 - 2 + F((F(3)^4))) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
950 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + F((F(3)^4))) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
951 &:= ((-1 + F((F(2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
952 &:= (F(((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times 4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
953 &:= ((-1 + 2 + F((F(3)^4))) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
954 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) + ((F(F(4))^5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
955 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) + ((F(F(4))^5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
956 &:= ((-1 + F((2 \times (F(3 + 4) - 5)))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
957 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((F(3) - F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
958 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((F(3) - F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
959 &:= (-1 - ((F(F((2 + F(3)))) - F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
960 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) + F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
961 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((F(3) - F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
962 &:= (F(((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times 4)) + (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
963 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3)^{4+5}) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
964 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + ((F(F(4))^5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
965 &:= F(F(F(F(-1 + 2 \times 3))) + F(F(4))^5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
927 &:= -9 - 8 \times F(7) \times (6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
928 &:= (-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(6) \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
929 &:= 9 \times 8 \times F(7) + F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
930 &:= -9 \times (8 - F(7)) \times F(F(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
931 &:= -9 - (8 - F(7) - F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
932 &:= F(-9 + F(8) - 7 + 6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
933 &:= -9 - 8 + (F(7) + 6) \times 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
934 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
935 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7 + (6 + 5))) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
936 &:= -9 + (F(8) + 7 \times 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
937 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
938 &:= 9 \times 8 \times F(7) + F(F(6) + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
939 &:= (((-9 \times F(8)) + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
940 &:= ((-9 + F(8) - (7 - F((6 + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
941 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times 6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
942 &:= 9 \times 8 \times F(7) + F(F(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
943 &:= -9 + 8 \times (F(7) \times F(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
944 &:= 9 \times 8 \times F(7) + F(F(F(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
945 &:= -9 \times (8 - F(7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
946 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
947 &:= 9 \times 8 \times F(7) + (6 - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
948 &:= (-9 + 8 + F(7)) \times (F(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
949 &:= -9 + 8 + (F(7) + 6) \times 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
950 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
951 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
952 &:= (9 + 8) \times 7 \times F(F(F(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
953 &:= 9 + 8 \times (F(7) - F(F(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
954 &:= -9 \times (F(8) - 7 - F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
955 &:= 9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
956 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + 7) \times 6 + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
957 &:= -9 - F(8) + F(7 - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
958 &:= -9 + F(8 + 7) + F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
959 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
960 &:= F(-9 + 8 + 7) \times F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
961 &:= -9 + (F(8) - F(7) + F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
962 &:= (-9 \times F(8) + F(F(7))) \times F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
963 &:= -9 + F(8 - F(7) + F(F(6))) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
964 &:= (9 \times 8 - F(7)) \times 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
965 &:= 9 - 8 - F(7) + F(F(F(6)) - 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
966 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) - F((F(4) - ((5+6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))))) \\
967 &:= ((F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
968 &:= (-1 + (((F(2 + 3) \times (4 + 5)) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
969 &:= (F((-1 + (F(2 \times 3) + (4 + 5)))) + (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
970 &:= (1 + (((F(2 + 3) \times (4 + 5)) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
971 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F((F(3)^4)) + ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
972 &:= (((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) + (4^5)) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
973 &:= (F(-1 + F(2 \times 3)) + ((F(F(4))^5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
974 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(3 + 4)) \times (F((5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
975 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3 + 4) \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
976 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times F(3 + 4))) \times (5 \times F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
977 &:= ((-1 - (2 + (3 + 4))) + F(((5 \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
978 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + F((F(4) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
979 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) - F((F(4) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))))) \\
980 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3^{F(4)})) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
981 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) + F((F(4) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
982 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) + F((F(4) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
983 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) - F((F(4) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))))) \\
984 &:= (-1 - 2 + F((F(3)^{F(4+5)-(6+7+8+9)}))) \\
985 &:= (-1 \times 2 + F((F(3)^{F(4+5)-(6+7+8+9)}))) \\
986 &:= (-1 + F((2 - (F(F(3 + F(4)))) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
987 &:= F((-1 - 2 - ((F(3)^4) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
988 &:= (-1 + 2 + F((F(3)^{F(4+5)-(6+7+8+9)}))) \\
989 &:= (-1 + (((2 - 3) + F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
990 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (F(3) - F(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
991 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (F(3)^{F(F(4) \times 5)})) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
992 &:= (-F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + (4^5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
993 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (F(3)^{4+5}))) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
994 &:= (((1 \times 2) \times (F(3)^{4+5})) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
995 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F(3)^{F(F(4) \times 5)})) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
996 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + (4^5)) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
997 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) + (4^5)) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
998 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) - (F(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
999 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) - (F(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1000 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times ((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1001 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) + (4^5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1002 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (F(4)^5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1003 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + F(3 + 4)) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
966 &:= (9 - 7 \times F(8)) \times (F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
967 &:= (9 + 8) \times 7 \times F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
968 &:= -9 + F(8 \times (F(7) - 6 - 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
969 &:= (((-9 + F(((8 + 7) - F(6))))^5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
970 &:= -9 - 8 + F(7 - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
971 &:= -9 + (F(8) + 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
972 &:= F(F(-9 + 8 + 7) + F(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
973 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
974 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times 7 + F(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
975 &:= 9 - F(8) + F(7 - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
976 &:= -9 + 8 + F(F(7) + F(6) - 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
977 &:= F(-9 + F(8) - 7 + 6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
978 &:= -9 + F(8 - (F(7) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
979 &:= F(-9 + F(8)) + F(F(7)) - F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
980 &:= (9 + F((8 - 7) \times (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
981 &:= -9 \times (8 + F(7) \times (6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
982 &:= 9 \times (F(8) - 7 + F(6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
983 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + F(F(F(6)) - 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
984 &:= -9 + (F(F(8) - 7) + 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
985 &:= -9 + 8 \times F(7) + F(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
986 &:= -9 + 8 + F(7 - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
987 &:= ((9 - 8) \times F((7 - (6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
988 &:= -9 + F(8 \times (F(7) - 6 - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
989 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + (6 + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
990 &:= (-9 \times (8 - F(7)) + F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
991 &:= -9 + (F(8) - 7 + 6) \times 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
992 &:= F(F(-9 + 8 + 7) + F(6)) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
993 &:= 9 + 8 \times (F(7) + (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
994 &:= -9 / (F(8) / 7) + F(F(F(6)) - 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
995 &:= (9 + F(8)) \times F(7) + (6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
996 &:= -9 + 8 + F(F(7) + F(6) - 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
997 &:= F(-9 + F(8) - 7 + 6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
998 &:= 9 - 8 + (F(F(7) + F(6) - 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
999 &:= -9 + F(8) + F(7 - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1000 &:= -9 + F(8) \times (F(7) + 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1001 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times 7) + (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1002 &:= (F((-9 + 8 + 7) + F(6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1003 &:= (-9 - 8) \times ((7 - (6 + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1004 &:= -1 + F(F(2+3)) \times (4+5 + F(6) \times (7+8+9)) \\
1005 &:= (-1-2 - ((F(3) - (4 \times (5+6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
1006 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((F(3) - (4 \times (5+6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
1007 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + (4^5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
1008 &:= ((-F(F((-1 + F(2+3)))) + 4 \times (5+6)) \times (7+8+9)) \\
1009 &:= ((-1-2 + F(F(3)^4)) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
1010 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + F(F(3)^4)) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
1011 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) + (F(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1012 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) - (F(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1013 &:= ((-1-2 \times 3) + (F(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1014 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3^{F(4)})) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1015 &:= ((-1 \times F(2+3)) + (F(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1016 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) - (F(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1017 &:= (F((-1 + (F(2 \times 3) + 4+5))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
1018 &:= ((-1+2-3) + (F(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1019 &:= (-1-2 + (F(F(3)^4) + (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1020 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(F(3)^4) + (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1021 &:= (-1 + (F((F(2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) + (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1022 &:= (F(((-1 + F(2+3)) \times 4)) + (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1023 &:= (-1+2 + (F(F(3)^4) + (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1024 &:= ((-1 + F(2+3)) + (F(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1025 &:= (F(F(F((-1+2 \times 3)))) + (F(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1026 &:= ((1 + F(2+3)) + (F(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1027 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) + (F(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1028 &:= ((-1 + F(2+3)) \times (F((F(F(4)) + 5+6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
1029 &:= ((-1-2 \times 3) \times (F(4) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1030 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + (F(4+5) + 6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
1031 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3) \times (F(4)^5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
1032 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) + ((4^5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
1033 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + (F(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1034 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) - (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
1035 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3 - (4 \times F(5+6)))) - 7-8-9) \\
1036 &:= ((-1-2 \times 3) \times (F(F(4)) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1037 &:= (-1-2 + ((F(3)^4) \times (F(5+6) - 7-8-9))) \\
1038 &:= (((-1-2) \times (F(3) - (4 \times F(5+6)))) - 7-8-9) \\
1039 &:= (-1 - ((2 + F(3)) \times (4 - ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
1040 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) + (F(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1041 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3)^4) \times (F(5+6) - 7-8-9))) \\
1042 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times 4) \times F(5+6))) - 7-8-9) \\
1043 &:= (-1 - ((2 + F(3)) \times (F(4) - ((5+6) \times (7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1004 &:= (9+8 + F((7 - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1005 &:= (((-9 - (F(8) - F(7+6))) \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1006 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times 7) - F((F(6) + (5-4-3-2-1)))) \\
1007 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + (F(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1008 &:= (-F((-9+8 + F(7))) \times (F(6) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1009 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) + 7)) \times F(F(6))) + F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1010 &:= ((-9+8 + (F(7) + F(6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
1011 &:= (-9 + ((8+7) \times (F(6) + (5+F(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1012 &:= (((-9 \times F(8)) + F(F(7))) \times (F(6) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1013 &:= (((-9+8 + F(7)) \times F(6+5)) - F(4+3+2+1)) \\
1014 &:= (((-9 - (F(8) - F(F(7)))) \times F(6)) - F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1015 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times 7) - (F(6) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1016 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times 7) + F((F(F(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1017 &:= ((-9 - 8 \times F(7)) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1018 &:= (9 + ((F(8) \times (F(7) + 6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1019 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7) \times 6))) - F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1020 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + F(F(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1021 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) - (7 - F(6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1022 &:= (-9 + (((F(8+7) \times F(6))/5) + F(4+3+2+1))) \\
1023 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (7 - F(F(6)))) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1024 &:= (F((-9+8 - (7 - (6+5))))^{4+3+2+1}) \\
1025 &:= (9 + (8 \times (7 + (F(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1026 &:= (-9+8 + (F(7) \times (F(6+5) - 4-3-2-1))) \\
1027 &:= ((9-8) \times (F(7) \times (F(6+5) - 4-3-2-1))) \\
1028 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times 7 + (F(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1029 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times 7) + (6 + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1030 &:= (((-9 - F(8)) \times (7 - F(F(6)))) + F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1031 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + (F((7 + F(6))) + F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1032 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times ((7 + F(6+5)) - 4-3-2-1)) \\
1033 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) - F(7)) \times F(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1034 &:= (F((-9+8 + F(7))) + (F(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1035 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - F(7)) \times (F(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1036 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) - (F(7) - (6+5))) \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\
1037 &:= (F((F(-9+8+7) + F(6))) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1038 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (F(7+6) \times 5)) - F(4+3+2+1)) \\
1039 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (F(7) - (F(6+5) + F(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1040 &:= (F(-9+8+7) \times ((F(6) + 5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1041 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (F(7) \times 6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1042 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times F(6)))) + F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1043 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7) \times (6+5)))) - F(4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1044 &:= ((F(-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times (4 \times F(5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1045 &:= ((1 \times F(2 + 3)) \times (F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1046 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 \times 3)) + ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1047 &:= ((1 - F(2 \times 3)) + ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1048 &:= ((1 - F(2 + 3)) \times (F(F(4)) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1049 &:= (-1 - (((2 - 3) - F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1050 &:= (((-1 + 2)^{F(3)} + F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1051 &:= (1 - ((2 - 3 - F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1052 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1053 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (F(3)^{4+5})) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1054 &:= (((1 \times 2) \times (F(3)^{4+5})) + (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1055 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3)^{F(F(4)) \times 5}) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1056 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1057 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) + ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1058 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1059 &:= (F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3))) + ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1060 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1061 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) + ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1062 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times ((F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1063 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) + (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1064 &:= (-1 + (F(2 + 3) \times ((F(4)^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1065 &:= (F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3)))) \times ((F(4)^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1066 &:= ((-1 - (F(2 + F(3))^4)) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1067 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1068 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (F(4) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1069 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1070 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F((F(4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1071 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1072 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (4 + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1073 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times (F(4 + 5) + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1074 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) + ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1075 &:= ((-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F(F(4)))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1076 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) + (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1077 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3) + F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1078 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3) + F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1079 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1080 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1081 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3) + F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1082 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) \times 4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1044 &:= (9 + 8 + (F(7) \times (F(6 + 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1045 &:= ((F(-9 + 8 + 7) + 6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1046 &:= (9 \times 8 \times F(7) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1047 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 \times F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1048 &:= ((9 + 8 + 7) + (F((F(6) - 5))^{4+3+2+1})) \\
1049 &:= (-9 + (8 \times 7 \times F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1050 &:= (9 + (F(8) + ((F(7) + F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1051 &:= ((F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) \times F(F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1052 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times 7) - ((6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1053 &:= (-9 \times ((F(8)/7) - (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1054 &:= (9 + ((F(8) - (F(7) - (6 + 5))) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1055 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(7) + (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1056 &:= ((-9 - 8 - 7) \times ((6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1057 &:= (-F(-9 + F(8)) + 7) \times (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1058 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(7)) \times F(6 + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1059 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1060 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times F(7)) + 6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1061 &:= (-9 - (((8 - F(7 + 6)) \times 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1062 &:= (-9 \times (F(F(8)/7) - (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1063 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) - F(7)) \times F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1064 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) + 7)) \times ((6 - 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1065 &:= (((9 \times (8 + 7)) \times F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1066 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times 7) + (F(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1067 &:= (9 + (8 \times 7 \times F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1068 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times ((F(7) \times F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1069 &:= (9 + ((F(8) - F(7 + 6)) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1070 &:= (((-9 - 8 + F(7 + 6)) \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1071 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1072 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - ((F(7) \times F(6 + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1073 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((F(7) \times F(6)) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1074 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times 7) + ((6 + 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1075 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (F(7) \times F(6 + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1076 &:= ((((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7)))/6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1077 &:= (((9 \times F(8)) - 7) \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1078 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(7)) \times F(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1079 &:= ((9 \times (8 + F(7))) + (F(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1080 &:= ((-9 + 8 + F(7)) \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1081 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1082 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times F(7)) + F((F(F(6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1083 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3)^{4+5}) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1084 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) - (F(4 + 5) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1085 &:= ((-1 - 2 + F(3 \times F(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1086 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - (4 \times F(5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1087 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F(3) - (F(4 + 5) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1088 &:= (F((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4 + 5)))) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1089 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((3 \times 4) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1090 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((3 \times 4) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1091 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times ((F(4)^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1092 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times ((F(4)^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1093 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((3 \times 4) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1094 &:= ((-1 + 2 + F(3 \times 4 + 5)) - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1095 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) + (F(4 + 5) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1096 &:= (-1 + (F((2 \times (3 + 4))) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
1097 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(F(3)^4) + (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1098 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - F((F(4) + 5 + 6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1099 &:= (-1 + (F((F(2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) + (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1100 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1101 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(F(3)^4) + (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1102 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3) + 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1103 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 + F(3)))) + 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1104 &:= ((1 + (F(2 + F(3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1105 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1106 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 + F(3)) \times F((F(4) + 5 + 6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1107 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1108 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1109 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 + F(3)) + F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1110 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) + F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1111 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1112 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + F(3 + 4 + 5)) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1113 &:= (-1 + (F(((2 \times 3) + 4 + 5)) + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1114 &:= (F((-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times (4 + 5)))) + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1115 &:= (((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) - 4) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1116 &:= (-1 \times ((F((2 \times (3 + 4))) - 5) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1117 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((3 + 4) \times 5) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1118 &:= (((-1 - 2 + F(F(3 + 4))) \times 5) - (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1119 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1120 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + F(3 \times F(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1121 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((3 + 4) \times 5) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1122 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (3 + 4)) \times (5 - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1083 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (F((7 + 6 - 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1084 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (7 \times F(F(6)))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1085 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (F(7) \times F(6 + 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1086 &:= (-9 + ((8 - (F(F(7)) - 6)) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1087 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (F(6 + 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1088 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) - F(6 + 5)))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1089 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1090 &:= (((-9 - 8 + F(7 + 6)) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1091 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (F(7) + F(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1092 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) \times 7)) \times (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1093 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + (F(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1094 &:= (9 + ((8 - (F(F(7)) - F(6))) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1095 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(7) \times F(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1096 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - 7) \times F((F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1097 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6 + 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1098 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (F(7) \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1099 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 + (F(6) + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1100 &:= ((F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) + F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1101 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(7) \times F(6 + 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1102 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times F(6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1103 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(7 + 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1104 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times F((F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1105 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(7 + 6)) \times 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1106 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F(F(7)) + (F(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1107 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - F((F(7) - ((6 + 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
1108 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7) \times (6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1109 &:= ((9 \times (8 \times 7)) + ((6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1110 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times F(7))) - F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1111 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) - 7) \times F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1112 &:= ((9 \times (8 + 7)) + (F((F(F(6)) - 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1113 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times 7) - (F(F(6)) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1114 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times 6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1115 &:= (((-9 \times F(8)) - (F(7) + F(F(6)))) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1116 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (7 \times F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1117 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - ((F(7) \times F(6 + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1118 &:= (((-9 - 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1119 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (7 \times F(F(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1120 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) - 6) \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1121 &:= (F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) + (F((F(F(6)) - 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1122 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) + (F(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1123 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + F(F(3+4))) \times 5) - (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1124 &:= (-1 - (((2 - F(F(3+4))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1125 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + F(F(3+4))) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1126 &:= (1 - (((2 - F(F(3+4))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1127 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3 \times (4 + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1128 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (F(3+4) + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1129 &:= (-1 + (F(F(F(F(2+3)))) \times (F(F(4)) \times (F(5+6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1130 &:= (((1 - 2 + F(F(3+4))) \times 5) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1131 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (F(3+4) \times F(5+6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1132 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (F(F(3+4)) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1133 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (F(F(3+4)) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1134 &:= (1 - 2 + ((F(F(3+4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1135 &:= ((F(F((-1+2) \times (3+4)))) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1136 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F(F(3+4)) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1137 &:= (F((-1 + F(2+3)) \times 4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1138 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(F(3)^4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1139 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (F(3) + F(4+5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1140 &:= (((-1 + F(2+3)) + F(4+5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1141 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times ((4 \times F(5+6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1142 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + F(F(3+4))) \times 5)) - (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1143 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + F(3+4+5)) \times F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1144 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + F(F(3+4))) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1145 &:= (((1 \times 2 + F(F(3+4))) \times 5) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1146 &:= (-1 - 2 - (F(F(3)^4) - (F(5+6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1147 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(F(3)^4) - (F(5+6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1148 &:= (-1 - (F((F(2 \times 3)) \times F(F(4)))) - (F(5+6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1149 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - F((F(4) + 5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1150 &:= (((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + F(4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1151 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3+4) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1152 &:= (((-1 + F(2+3)) + 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1153 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (F((F(4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1154 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (F((F(4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1155 &:= ((-1 + F((2 + (3 + 4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1156 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - (F((F(4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1157 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1158 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1159 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 + F(3))) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1160 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2+3)))) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1161 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1162 &:= ((F(F((-1+2) \times (3+4)))) \times 5) + (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1123 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7) \times 6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1124 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((F(F(7)) - F(6)) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1125 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times F(F(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1126 &:= (-9 - (((8 - F(7+6)) \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1127 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (F(7) \times F((6 - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))))) \\
1128 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times 7) + (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1129 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (7 \times F(F(6)))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1130 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (F(7) \times F(6+5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1131 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + F((7 - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1132 &:= (9 + (F(8) + ((F(7) \times F(6+5)) - F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1133 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) - F(6+5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1134 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (7 \times (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1135 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1136 &:= (9 - 8 - ((F(F(7)) - 6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1137 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1138 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F((7 + 6 - 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1139 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(7) + 6) \times (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1140 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (F(7) \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1141 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times F(7)) + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1142 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6+5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1143 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - F(F(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1144 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((F(F(7)) - 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1145 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (F(7) \times (6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1146 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7 + F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1147 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) + F(7)) \times (F(6+5) - F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1148 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (F((7 + F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1149 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (7 \times F(F(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1150 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(7) \times F(6+5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1151 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (F(F(7)) - F(6+5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1152 &:= (-F(-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) - (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1153 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F(7) \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1154 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times F(F(6)))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1155 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(7) \times 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1156 &:= (-9 - (F(F((8+7) - F(6)))) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1157 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times F(6)) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1158 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(7+6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1159 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + ((F(7) \times F(6+5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1160 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(7) \times (6 + 5)))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1161 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (F(6+5) + F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1162 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) + (F(7) + F(6+5)))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1163 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + (F((F(4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1164 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - (F((F(F(4)) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1165 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + F((F(4) \times 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1166 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (F((4 + 5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1167 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3 \times F(4)) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1168 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1169 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 + 3)) + F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1170 &:= ((F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3))) + F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1171 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3 \times F(4)) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1172 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times (F((4 + 5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1173 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times (F((4 + 5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1174 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3 + 4 + 5) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1175 &:= (-1 - (F(2 \times 3) \times (F(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1176 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) \times (F(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1177 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + F((4 + 5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1178 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3 + 4) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1179 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3 + 4) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1180 &:= (((-1 - 2 + F(F(3 + 4))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1181 &:= ((F((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1182 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3 + 4) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1183 &:= (-1 - (F(2 \times 3) \times (F(F(4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1184 &:= (-1 - (((2 - F(F(3 + 4))) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1185 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + F(F(3 + 4))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1186 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - F((F(4) \times 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1187 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3 \times F(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1188 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3 \times F(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1189 &:= (-1 + (F((2 + (3 + 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1190 &:= (F((F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))^{F(F(4))})) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1191 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3 \times F(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1192 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(F(3 + 4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1193 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(F(3 + 4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1194 &:= (1 - 2 + ((F(F(3 + 4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1195 &:= ((F(F((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1196 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(F(3 + 4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1197 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1198 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3) \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1199 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) + F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1200 &:= ((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4))) \times (F(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1201 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1202 &:= (-1 + (F(2 + F(3)) \times (F((F(4) + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1163 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (F(7) \times (6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1164 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1165 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (F(7 + 6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1166 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(7) \times F(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1167 &:= ((-F(-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) - F(F(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1168 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + ((F(7) - (6 + 5))⁴⁺³⁺²⁺¹)) \\
1169 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F(7) \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1170 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times 7) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1171 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(7) \times (F(6 + 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1172 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7 \times F(F(6)))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1173 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (F(7) + ((6 - 5) + F((4 + (3 + (2 + 1))))))) \\
1174 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(7 + 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1175 &:= (((9 \times 8 + F(7)) \times F(F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1176 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (F(6 + 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1177 &:= (-9 + F(8) - (F(7 + 6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1178 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((F(F(7)) + 6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1179 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + ((F(7) \times F(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1180 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times F(7))) \times 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1181 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) - F(6)))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1182 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + (F(7) \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1183 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 \times F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
1184 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) + 6) \times 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1185 &:= (9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1186 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (F(7) - F(F(6)))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1187 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + ((F(7 + 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1188 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (7 \times 6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1189 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (7 + F(F(6)))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1190 &:= ((-9 + F(8 + 7)) - (F(F(6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1191 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) + (F(F(6)) \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1192 &:= (((-9 + F(8 + 7)) \times F((F(6) - 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1193 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + 7) \times F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1194 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1195 &:= (-9 - (F((F(8)/7)) \times (F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1196 &:= (-9 - ((8 + F(7 + 6)) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1197 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) - 6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1198 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (F(F(7)) - F(6 + 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1199 &:= (-9 - (F((F(8)/7)) \times (6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1200 &:= ((-9 + F(((F(8)/7) + F(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1201 &:= (-9 + (F((F(8)/7)) \times ((6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1202 &:= ((-9 + F(8 + 7)) \times F((F(6) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1203 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1204 &:= (-1 + (((2 + F(F(3 + 4))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1205 &:= (((1 \times 2 + F(F(3 + 4))) \times 5) + (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1206 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (F(3) \times F(4 + 5))) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1207 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) + F(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1208 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(F(3 + 4)) \times 5) + (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1209 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - ((4 + 5) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1210 &:= (((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + F(4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1211 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times ((F(F(4)) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1212 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 \times (4 + 5)) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1213 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - F((F(F(4)) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))))) \\
1214 &:= (-1 + (F(F(F(2 + 3))) \times ((F(4) \times F(5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1215 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times (F(F(4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1216 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - F((F(F(4)) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))))) \\
1217 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1218 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3) \times F((F(F(4)) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))))) \\
1219 &:= (-1 + (2 \times F(((3 \times (F(4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1220 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times F((F(F(4)) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))))) \\
1221 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times (3 + 4)) \times F(5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1222 &:= (((-1 + 2 + F(3 + 4)) \times F(5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1223 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times (F(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1224 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 \times 3) + 4 \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1225 &:= ((-1 + 2 + F(3 \times F(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1226 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
1227 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + (4^5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1228 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1229 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1230 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 \times 3) + F(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1231 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times (4 + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1232 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1233 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (4 + F(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1234 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) - F(F(4))) \times (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1235 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 + 3) \times 4)) \times (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1236 &:= (((F((-1 - 2 + F(3 + 4))) + 5) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1237 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - F((4 + 5 + 6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1238 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3 - F((4 + 5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1239 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (F(3) - F((4 + 5 + 6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1240 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times ((F(F(4))^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1241 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3) \times F((4 + 5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1242 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3) \times F((4 + 5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1203 &:= ((-9 + F(8 + 7)) - (F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1204 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((F(F(7)) + F(6)) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1205 &:= ((-9 + F(8 + 7)) - (6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1206 &:= (-9 + (F(8 + 7) + ((6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1207 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6 + 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1208 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + 7) \times F((F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1209 &:= ((9 \times F(8)) + ((F(7) + F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1210 &:= ((F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) + (6 - 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1211 &:= (-9 + (F((8 - F((F(7) - F(6)))) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1212 &:= (((-9 + F(8 + 7)) \times F((F(6) - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1213 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + 7) \times F(6)) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1214 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) + F(6 + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1215 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1216 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (7 \times (F((F(6) + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1217 &:= (-9 + (F(8 + 7) + (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1218 &:= (((-9 - (F(8) - F(F(7)))) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1219 &:= (-9 + (F(8 + 7) + (F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1220 &:= ((F(-9 + 8 + 7) - 6) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1221 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) + (F(7) + F(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1222 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1223 &:= (-9 + (F((F(8)/7)) \times (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1224 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times F(F(7)))) - (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1225 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (F(7) \times 6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1226 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) - F(F(6)))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1227 &:= (-9 + (F((F(8)/7)) \times (F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1228 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) - (F(F(7)) - ((6 \times 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1229 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) + (F((F(F(6)) - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1230 &:= (-9 - (F(8) \times ((7 - (6 + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1231 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) + (F(F(7)) - 6)) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1232 &:= (-9 + (F(8 + 7) + (F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1233 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) \times F(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1234 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) + F(6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1235 &:= (9 + (F(8 + 7) + (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1236 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1237 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (F(F(7)) \times F(6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1238 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1239 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times F(F(7)))) - (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1240 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(7) \times 6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1241 &:= (9 + (F((F(8)/7)) \times (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1242 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) - 7)) \times ((6 - 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1243 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - F((F(4) \times 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1244 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2+3)) \times (F(4)^5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1245 &:= ((F(F((-1+2 \times 3))) \times (F(4)^5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1246 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - F((F(4) \times 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1247 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3) \times F((F(4) \times 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1248 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3) \times F((F(4) \times 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1249 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{F(3+F(4))} \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1250 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2+3)))) \times F((F(4) \times 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1251 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3) \times F((F(4) \times 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1252 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(F(3)^4) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1253 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + (F(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1254 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (F((F(4) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1255 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F(3) - (F((F(4) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1256 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - (F((F(4) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1257 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times (F((F(4) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1258 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3) \times (F((F(4) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1259 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^{F(4)}) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1260 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1261 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times (F((F(4) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1262 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (F((4 + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1263 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + (F((F(4) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1264 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - (F((4 + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1265 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (F((F(4) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1266 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3) \times (F((4 + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1267 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 + F(3))) \times (F((4 + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1268 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times (F((4 + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1269 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times (F((4 + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1270 &:= (1 \times 2 + (F(3) \times (F((4 + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1271 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + (F((4 + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1272 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3))^{F(4)}) - (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
1273 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1274 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1275 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F(3) - (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1276 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1277 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1278 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1279 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 + F(3))) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1280 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1281 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1282 &:= (1 \times 2 + (F(3) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1243 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) \times F(6))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1244 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) - 6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1245 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times F(7 + 6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1246 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1247 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(7) + (F(6 + 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1248 &:= ((9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1249 &:= ((9 \times F(8)) - ((F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1250 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times F(F(7)))) - ((6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1251 &:= (9 \times 8 \times F(7) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1252 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1253 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) \times F(6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1254 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) - (F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1255 &:= (9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times F(6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1256 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) - (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1257 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (F(7) \times (F(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1258 &:= (-9 + (F((F(8) - 7)) + (F(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1259 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(7) + F(6)) \times (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1260 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (7 \times (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1261 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) + F(7 + 6)) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1262 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + 6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1263 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1264 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 - (6 \times 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1265 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(7) + 6 + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1266 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times F(F(7))) + (F(F(6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1267 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) - ((6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1268 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) + (6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1269 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (7 \times F(F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1270 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) + (F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1271 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7)) \times F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1272 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + (F(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1273 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1274 &:= (((-9 \times F(8)) + 7) \times (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1275 &:= ((-9 \times F(8 + 7)) + F(((6 \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1276 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (F(F(7)) \times 6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1277 &:= (9 \times 8 - ((F(F(7)) + F(6)) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1278 &:= (-9 - (((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1279 &:= (-9 + (8 \times 7 \times (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1280 &:= (((9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) + (F(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1281 &:= (((-9 - 8 + F(F(7))) \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1282 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1283 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1284 &:= (-1 + (F(F(F(F(2+3)))) \times (F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1285 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1286 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2+3)))) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) + F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1287 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1288 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) - ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1289 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 \times (F(4) \times 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1290 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times F((F(4) + 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1291 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 + 3) - ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1292 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) - ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1293 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3 + 4) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1294 &:= (1 \times 2 \times (((3 + 4) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1295 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3)^{F(4+5)-6-7-8-9})) \\
1296 &:= ((-1 - (F((2 + (3 + 4))) - F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1297 &:= (((-1 + 2)^{F(3)}) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1298 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1299 &:= (-1 - (F(2 + 3) \times (4 - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1300 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 + 3) \times (4 - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1301 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times ((F(F(4))^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1302 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4) - (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1303 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1304 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 + 3)) \times (F(4) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1305 &:= (((-1 + (2^{F(3+F(4))}) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1306 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(F(3 + 4)) \times 5) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1307 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(F(3 + 4)) \times 5) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1308 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((F(3) \times F(F((F(4) + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1309 &:= (-1 + (((2^{F(3+F(4))}) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1310 &:= ((((-1 + F(2 + 3))^4) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1311 &:= ((F(F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3)))) \times (F(4) \times F(5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1312 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 \times 3) + F(4 + 5))) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1313 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) + ((F(4 + 5) + F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1314 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 + F(4 + 5)))) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1315 &:= (1 \times F(2 + 3) \times (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1316 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1317 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F((3 - (4 - (5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1318 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F((3 - (4 - (5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1319 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3) + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1320 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 + 3) \times (4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1321 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F((3 - (4 - (5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1322 &:= ((-1 + (F((F(2 + 3) \times 4)/5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1283 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) + (F(F(6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1284 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + ((F(7) + 6) \times (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1285 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) + (F(F(7)) - 6))) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1286 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F(7) \times (F(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1287 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 \times F(F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1288 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) \times F((F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1289 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) \times F(6 + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1290 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) - (F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1291 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + ((F(7) \times F(6 + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1292 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) - (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1293 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) + 6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1294 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) \times 7)) + (F(F(6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1295 &:= ((9 \times (8 \times 7 + F(6 + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1296 &:= ((-9 - 8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1297 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + (7 - 6)) \times (5 + 4)) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1298 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(7 + 6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1299 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + (F(7) \times (F(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1300 &:= (((-9 \times (F(8) + 7)) - F(6)) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1301 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1302 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (F(7) - F(6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1303 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1304 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) + (6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1305 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (F(7) \times F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1306 &:= ((9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1307 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) \times 7)) - (F(F(6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1308 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times ((F(7) \times F(6)) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1309 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (F(7) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1310 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times (7 + 6))) \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1311 &:= (((-9 - 8 + F(F(7))) \times 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1312 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) - (6 - 5 - 4)) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1313 &:= (-9 - (((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times 6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1314 &:= (-9 - (F(8) \times (7 \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1315 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) \times 7)) - F((F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1316 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times F(6 + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1317 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) \times 7)) - (F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1318 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - ((F(F(7)) \times 6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1319 &:= (9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1320 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - (7 \times F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1321 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times 6) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1322 &:= (F((-9 - 8) \times (7 - F(6))) - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1323 &:= ((F((-1 + F((F(F(2+3)) + F(4)))))/5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
1324 &:= ((-1 + F(2+3)) + ((F(4+5) + F(F(6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
1325 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3^{F(4)}))) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
1326 &:= ((-1-2) \times (F(3 \times F(4)) \times ((5+6) - 7-8-9))) \\
1327 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times ((4 \times F(5+6)) - 7-8-9))) \\
1328 &:= ((-1 + F(2+3)) \times ((4 \times F(5+6)) - 7-8-9)) \\
1329 &:= (-1 + (F(F(F(2+3))) \times (F(F(4)) + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
1330 &:= ((1 \times F(F(2+3))) \times (F(F(4)) + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
1331 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 + F(4+5)) \times (6-7-8-9)))) \\
1332 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) \times (F(F(4)) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1333 &:= (F((-1+2 + (F(3)^4))) - ((5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
1334 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2+3)) \times (F(4) + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
1335 &:= (F(F(F((-1+2 \times 3)))) \times (F(4) + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
1336 &:= ((F(F(F(F((-1+2 \times 3)))))) \times (F(4+5) \times F(6))) - 7-8-9) \\
1337 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1338 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - ((F(4+5) - 6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
1339 &:= (-1 + (F(2+3) \times (4 + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
1340 &:= (((-1 + (F(2+3)^{F(4)})) \times (5+6)) - 7-8-9) \\
1341 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3 - (F(4) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
1342 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (4 - (F(5+6) - 7-8-9))) \\
1343 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4+5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
1344 &:= ((-1-2) \times (F(3) - (F(4) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
1345 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3) + ((4+5) \times 6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
1346 &:= (-1 - (((2 - F(F(3+4))) \times 5) - (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
1347 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (F(4) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
1348 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (F(4) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
1349 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2+3)) \times ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1350 &:= (F((-1+2 \times 3)) \times ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1351 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (F(4) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
1352 &:= (1 \times 2 + (3 \times (F(4) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
1353 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 \times 4) \times (F(5+6) + 7+8+9))) \\
1354 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times 4) \times (F(5+6) + 7+8+9))) \\
1355 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (F(F(4)) \times (F(5+6) + 7+8+9)))) \\
1356 &:= (F((-1 + F(2+3))) \times (4 \times (F(5+6) + 7+8+9))) \\
1357 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times 4) \times (F(5+6) + 7+8+9))) \\
1358 &:= (-1 + (((2 + F(3+4)) \times F(5+6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
1359 &:= ((F(F(F(F((-1+2 \times 3)))))) \times (F(4) \times F(5+6))) + 7+8+9) \\
1360 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times ((4 \times (5+6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
1361 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (F(3) \times F(4+5))) \times F(F(6))) + 7+8+9)) \\
1362 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4))) \times (F(5+6) - 7-8-9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1323 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + F(7)) \times (F(6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1324 &:= ((9+8) \times (7 \times 6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
1325 &:= ((-9 - (F((F(8)/7))^{F(6)})) \times (5-4-3-2-1)) \\
1326 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1327 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) - ((6+5) + F(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1328 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 + F(F(6))) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1329 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + (((F(F(7)) + 6) \times 5) - 4-3-2-1)) \\
1330 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) \times 7)) - (F(6) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1331 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (F(F(7)) \times 6)) - (5-4-3-2-1)) \\
1332 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + ((F(7) + 6 + 5) \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1333 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (F(7) \times (F(6) + 5)))) - 4-3-2-1) \\
1334 &:= ((-9 + (F((F(8) - (7-6)))/5)) - 4-3-2-1) \\
1335 &:= (F((-9 + F(8) - (7-6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1336 &:= (-9 + (((8+7) \times F(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
1337 &:= (9+8 + ((F(7) + 6 + 5) \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\
1338 &:= ((-9+8+7) \times (F((F(6) + 5)) - 4-3-2-1)) \\
1339 &:= ((-9-8) \times (7 - F(6+5))) - F(4+3+2+1) \\
1340 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - F(7))) + F(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
1341 &:= ((9+8) \times (F(7) \times 6)) + (5+4+3+2+1) \\
1342 &:= (((-9+8 + F(F(7))) \times 6) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1343 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) - F(6)))) - F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1344 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) + (F(6+5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1345 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) + (F(F(7)) + 6))) \times (5-4-3-2-1)) \\
1346 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times ((7+6) \times 5))) - 4-3-2-1) \\
1347 &:= ((-9-8) \times (F(7) - F(6+5))) + F(4+3+2+1) \\
1348 &:= (-9-8 - (F(7) \times (F(F(6)) \times (5-4-3-2-1)))) \\
1349 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) - ((F(F(7)) + F(6)) \times (5-4-3-2-1))) \\
1350 &:= (((9+8 \times 7) \times F(F(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1351 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (F(F(7)) - F(6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1352 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + 6))) - F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1353 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - ((F(F(7)) \times 6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1354 &:= ((-9+8 + (F(7) \times (F(F(6)) \times 5))) - 4-3-2-1) \\
1355 &:= ((-9-8 - (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) \times (5-4-3-2-1)) \\
1356 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - (F(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1357 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7) \times F(6)))) + F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1358 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (F(7) \times ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1359 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((F(7) \times F(6)) - (5 \times F(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1360 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + F(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
1361 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) - 6))) - F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1362 &:= (((-9 - F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - 6))/5 - 4-3-2-1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1363 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4)))) \times (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1364 &:= (-1 + (F(2 + 3) \times ((F(4)^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1365 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1366 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4)))) \times (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1367 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1368 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - (F(F(4)) \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1369 &:= (1 + (((2 \times 3) \times F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1370 &:= ((-1 + (F((F(F(2 + 3)) \times 4))/5)) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1371 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (F(F(3 + 4)) - 5))) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1372 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) + (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1373 &:= (1 - 2 + ((F(F(3 \times 4 - 5)) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1374 &:= (-1 - (F((F(F(2 + 3)) \times F(F(4)))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1375 &:= (-1 \times (F((F(F(2 + 3)) \times F(F(4)))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1376 &:= (((-1 + (F(2 + 3) \times F(4 + 5))) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1377 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times ((F(4 + 5) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1378 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3) \times ((F(4 + 5) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1379 &:= (1 - 2 + (F(3) \times ((F(4 + 5) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1380 &:= (((-1 - 2 + F(F(3 + 4)))/5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1381 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times ((F(4 + 5) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1382 &:= (-1 + ((F((F(2 + 3) \times 4))/5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1383 &:= ((F((-1 + F((F(F(2 + 3)) + F(4))))/5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1384 &:= ((F(F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3)))))) \times (F(4 + 5) \times F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1385 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4 + 5) + (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1386 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) - (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1387 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3 + 4) \times (5 \times F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1388 &:= (((-1 + (F(2 + 3)^{F(4)})) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1389 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + (F(4 + 5) + F(F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1390 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + (F(4 + 5) + F(F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1391 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (F(3) + ((4 + 5) \times 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1392 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + ((4 + 5) \times 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1393 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + (F(4 + 5) + F(F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1394 &:= (-1 - ((F(2 + F(3)) - F(4 + 5)) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1395 &:= (-1 \times ((F(2 + F(3)) - F(4 + 5)) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1396 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 - F(4 + 5)) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1397 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times (F(4)^5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1398 &:= (-1 + (((F(2 + 3)^{F(4)}) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1399 &:= (((F((-1 + 2 \times 3))^{F(4)}) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1400 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1401 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((F(3)^4) \times F(5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1402 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (F(3) \times (F(4 + 5) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1363 &:= (((9 \times 8) \times (F(7) + 6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1364 &:= (((9 + 8) \times (7 \times (6 + 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1365 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (F(7) \times (F(F(6)) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
1366 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (F(F(7)) \times 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1367 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + ((F(6) - 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1368 &:= (9 \times 8 \times (F(7) + (F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1369 &:= (-9 + 8 - (F(F(7)) - (6 + F(((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1370 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times F(7))) \times F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1371 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + (F(7) \times (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1372 &:= (((-9 \times F(8)) - 7) \times (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1374 &:= ((9 - ((8 - F(F(7))) \times 6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1375 &:= ((9 - 8 + (F(7) + 6 + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1376 &:= ((9 \times ((F(8) - 7) \times (6 + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1376 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times 6) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1377 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1378 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (7 - (F(F(6)) + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1379 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) \times 7)) + ((6 - 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1380 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times 7) + F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1381 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1382 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) \times 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1383 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - ((F(F(7)) \times 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1384 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - F(6 + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1385 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times F(7))) \times F(F(6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1386 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (7 \times F(F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1387 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times 6) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1388 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (F(F(6) + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1389 &:= (-9 + (F((F(8) + (7 - (6 + (5 + 4)))))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1390 &:= ((F((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6)))) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1391 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) - (F(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1392 &:= ((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1393 &:= (-9 - (F(8) + (7 - ((F(F(6)) + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1394 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (F(F(7)) - (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1395 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + ((F(F(7)) \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1396 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1397 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1398 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1399 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 + F(F(6))) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1400 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + (7 - (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1401 &:= (-9 - (((8 - F(F(7))) \times 6) - (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1402 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) \times 6)) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1403 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 + F(3)))) \times (F(4 + 5) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1404 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times (F(4 + 5) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1405 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times F(3 \times 4))) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1406 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) + (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
1407 &:= (-1 - 2 - (3 \times (F(4 + 5) - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1408 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1409 &:= (-1 + (((2 + F(F(3 + 4)))/5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1410 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1411 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times (F((F(4) + 5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1412 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (F((F(4) + 5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1413 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((F(3 + 4) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1414 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times ((F(F(4)) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1415 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 + 3)) + ((4 + 5) \times 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1416 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1417 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((F(3 + 4) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1418 &:= (-1 - ((2 - F(3 + 4)) \times ((5 \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1419 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + F(3 + 4)) \times ((5 \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1420 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + ((F(F(F(4) + 5))) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1421 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(F(4) + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1422 &:= ((F((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4 + 5)))) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1423 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times (F(4 + 5) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1424 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(F(2 + F(3))) + 4 + 5)) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1425 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F((F(3) + 4 + 5)) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1426 &:= (1 \times 2 - (F((F(3) + 4 + 5)) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1427 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) \times F(F(F(4) + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1428 &:= (((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + 4 + 5) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1429 &:= (((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) + ((F(4)^5) \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1430 &:= ((-1 + 2 + F(F(3 + F(4)))) \times (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1431 &:= (((1 - 2 + (F(3) \times F(4 + 5))) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1432 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1433 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4 + 5 + F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1434 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - ((4 + 5 + F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1435 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F(F(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1436 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - ((4 + 5 + F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1437 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times F(F(3 + 4))) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1438 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((F(3) - F(4 + 5)) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1439 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times ((F(4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1440 &:= (((-1 - 2 \times 3) + F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1441 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((F(3) - F(4 + 5)) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1442 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + (F(F(4)) \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1403 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((F(F(7)) \times 6) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1404 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) \times 7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1405 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (F(7) + F(F(6)))) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1406 &:= ((9 \times 8 \times (7 + F(F(6)))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1407 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1408 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times F((F(6) + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1409 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) - (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1410 &:= ((9 \times (8 + (7 \times F(F(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1410 &:= ((9 \times (8 + (7 \times F(F(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1412 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1413 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((F(F(7)) \times 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1414 &:= (((-9 \times F(8)) - F(7)) \times (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1415 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(7 + 6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1416 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((F(6) \times 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1417 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (F(F(7)) - ((6 \times 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1418 &:= (9 - F(8) + (F(7) \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1419 &:= (((9 - 8 + F(F(7))) \times 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1420 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(7) \times (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1421 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) + (6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1422 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + F(F(7))) \times 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1423 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) + (F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1424 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times F(F(7))))/6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1425 &:= ((9 + 8 + (F(7) \times 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1426 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((F(F(7)) \times 6) + (F(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1427 &:= (((9 + (F(8) \times F(F(7))))/6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1428 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times ((F(7) \times F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1429 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F(7) \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1430 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) - F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1431 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (F(7) \times F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1432 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) - 7) \times 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1433 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (F(7) \times F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1434 &:= (((-9 - F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + 6))/(5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1435 &:= (-9 + F(8) - (7 - ((F(F(6)) + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1436 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) + (F(F(6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1437 &:= (-9 + ((8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1438 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1439 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) - F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1440 &:= ((-9 + 8 + F(7)) \times (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1441 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7 + F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1442 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) - (F(F(7)) \times (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1443 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + ((4 + 5 + F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1444 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times (F(F(4)) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1445 &:= (1 + (2 \times (F(3) + ((4 + 5 + F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1446 &:= ((-1 + F((F(F(2 \times 3)) - 4))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1447 &:= (F((-1 + 2 + (F(3)^4))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1448 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times 4) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1449 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((F(3)^4) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1450 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3) \times (F(4 + 5) \times F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1451 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 + F(3))) \times (F(4 + 5) \times F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1452 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times (F(4 + 5) \times F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1453 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3) \times (F(4 + 5) \times F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1454 &:= (-1 + (F(F(F(2 + 3))) \times ((F(4) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1455 &:= (F(F(F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3)))))) \times ((F(4) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1456 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - F((F(3) + 4 + 5))) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1457 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1458 &:= (1 \times 2 \times ((3 \times F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1459 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3) \times F((F(4) + 5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1460 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + 4) \times (F((5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1461 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(F(3 + 4)) - (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1462 &:= (1 - 2 + ((3 + 4) \times (F((5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1463 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times (F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1464 &:= (((-1 - 2 \times 3) \times 4) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
1465 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times F((3 \times 4)))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1466 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3 + 4) \times (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1467 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3 + 4) \times (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1468 &:= (-1 + (F((F(F(F(2 + 3))) + F(F(4)))) \times (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1469 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1470 &:= (((-1 - F(2 + 3)) + F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1471 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3) \times (4 \times F(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1472 &:= ((-1 - 2 - F((F(3) + 4 + 5))) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1473 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times F(4 + 5))) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1474 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3) \times ((F(4 + 5) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1475 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 + F(3))) \times ((F(4 + 5) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1476 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + 4 + 5) - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1477 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times ((F(4 + 5) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1478 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - F(3)) + (((F(4)^5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1479 &:= (-1 + (F(F(F(2 + 3))) \times ((F(4 + 5) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1480 &:= (F(F(F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3)))))) \times ((F(4 + 5) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1481 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + ((F(4 + 5) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1482 &:= (-1 - 2 - (3 \times (4 + 5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1443 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) + 7)) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1444 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) - F(F(6)))) - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1445 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + (7 \times F(F(6)))) \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1446 &:= (((-9 - F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + F(6))) / (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1447 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times 6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1448 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) - (F(7) - ((6 \times 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1449 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - F(6 + 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1450 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) - (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1451 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) - F(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1452 &:= (-9 + (((8 + F(F(7))) \times 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1453 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times F((F(6) + 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1454 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) - (7 - ((6 \times 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1455 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) + F(F(7)))) \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1456 &:= (((-9 \times F(8)) + 7) \times (F((F(6) - 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1457 &:= (9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) - F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1458 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times 7 \times F(6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1459 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(7) \times (F(6) + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1460 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(7) - (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1461 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times F(7)) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1462 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (F(7) - (F(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1463 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times (6 + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1464 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + ((F(7) + 6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1465 &:= (((-9 \times F(8)) - (F(7) \times F(6))) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1466 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) + (F(7) \times (6 + 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1467 &:= (9 \times ((F(8) \times F(7)) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1468 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((F(7) - (F(6) \times 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1469 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + 6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1470 &:= ((-9 - F(8)) \times (7 \times (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1471 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times 7 + (6 - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1472 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) - (F(6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1473 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) + F(F(7)))) \times 6) + ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1474 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1475 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1476 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) + (F(7) \times 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1477 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) \times 7 + 6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1478 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F(7) \times ((F(F(6)) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1479 &:= (((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) + F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1480 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - (7 - (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1481 &:= (-9 + (F(8 + 7) + ((F(F(6)) - 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1482 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times ((7 \times F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1483 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3) - 4)) - (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 1484 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times F((F(4) + 5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 1485 &:= (-1 - 2 - (((3^{F(4)}) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1486 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (((3^{F(4)}) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1487 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) \times (F(4)^5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 1488 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times F(3 + 4)) - F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 1489 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((3^{F(4)}) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1490 &:= ((-1 - 2 + F(3 + 4)) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1491 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times ((F(4)^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1492 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) - (F(4) \times (5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
 1493 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (F(3) \times F(4 + 5))) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 1494 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) + F(F(4))) \times (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
 1495 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 1496 &:= (F(((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times 4)) + (5 + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1497 &:= (((-1 - F(2 + 3)) + F(4)) \times (5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1498 &:= (((-1 + 2)^{F(3)} - (F(4) \times (5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
 1499 &:= (-1 + (F(F(F(2 + 3))) \times (F(F(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
 1500 &:= ((-1 - 2 + F(3 + 4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1501 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) - (F(4) \times (5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
 1502 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (F((F(4) \times 5)) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
 1503 &:= (-1 + (((2 + F(F(3 + 4)))/5) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1504 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + F(4 + 5)) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 1505 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3 + F(4 + 5)) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
 1506 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((3 + 4) - 5) - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1507 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F(F(3 + 4)) - F(((5 \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
 1508 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4) + (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1509 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) - (F(4 + 5) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1510 &:= (-1 - ((F(F(2 + 3))^4 - (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1511 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times F(3 + 4)) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1512 &:= (((-1 \times 2 \times F(3 + 4)) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 1513 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F((3 - (4 - 5))) \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1514 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) - ((F(F(4)) - 5) \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1515 &:= (((-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times (4 + 5))) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 1516 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) - ((F(F(4)) - 5) \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1517 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times (F(4)^5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1518 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) \times (4 - (F((5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1519 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times ((4 \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1520 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times ((4 \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1483 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (7 \times 6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1484 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((F(7) - (F(6) \times 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1485 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - (F(7) + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1486 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (F(6) + F(((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1487 &:= ((-9 \times F((F(8) - 7))) + (F(6) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1488 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (F(7) \times (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1489 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (F((F(6) + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
 1490 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times 7 + 6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1491 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + F(F(7)))) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1492 &:= ((9 \times ((8 \times F(7)) - 6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1493 &:= (((-9 - (F(8) - F(F(7)))) \times 6) + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1494 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F(7) \times ((F(F(6)) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1495 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - (F(F(7)) - 6)) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
 1496 &:= (9 + 8) \times ((F(7) \times (6 + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1497 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) \times (F(7) - F(F(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1498 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times 6)) + F(((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1499 &:= (-9 + (F((F(8) - 7)) \times ((F(6) \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1500 &:= ((-9 + ((F(8) + F(F(7))) \times 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1501 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) + 7)) \times (F(6 + 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
 1502 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times F(6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1503 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) + ((6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1504 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times F((F(6) + 5)))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1505 &:= ((9 \times ((8 + F(F(7))) - 6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1506 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) \times (7 - (6 + (5 + 4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1507 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - 7) \times (6 - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
 1508 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times (6 + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 1509 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) - (F(7) \times (F(F(6)) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
 1510 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + 6)) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 1511 &:= (-9 + (((8 + F(F(7))) - F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1512 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) \times (F(7) - (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 1513 &:= (9 + 8) \times ((F(7) \times F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1514 &:= (((9 + (8 \times F(7))) \times F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1515 &:= (((9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1516 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + 7) \times 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1517 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) - 7) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 1518 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times (6 - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
 1519 &:= (9 + ((8 + (F(7) \times (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1520 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + (7 + 6 - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1521 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (4 + (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1522 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) - (F(4 + 5) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1523 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) + (F(4 + 5) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1524 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) + (F(4 + 5) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1525 &:= (-1 - (F((2 + F(3 + 4))) - (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1526 &:= (-1 \times (F((2 + F(3 + 4))) - (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1527 &:= (((-1 - 2 + F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1528 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (F(4 + 5) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1529 &:= (-1 - (((2 + F(3)) - F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1530 &:= (((1 - F(2 + 3)) + F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1531 &:= ((-1 + F((F(F(2 \times 3)) - 4))) - (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1532 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times F((F(4) + 5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1533 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) + (F(4 + 5) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1534 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + (F(4 + 5) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1535 &:= (-1 - (((F(2 + 3))^{F(F(4))} - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1536 &:= (-1 \times (((F(2 + 3))^{F(F(4))} - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1537 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (F(3)^4)) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1538 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1539 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times (4 + 5 + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1540 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (4 + 5 + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1541 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1542 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - (F(3)^{4+5})) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1543 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + (F(4 + 5) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1544 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (F(F(4)) - ((5 - F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1545 &:= ((-1 - 2 - (F(3)^{4+5})) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1546 &:= (1 + (((F((F(2 + 3) \times 4)) / 5) + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1547 &:= (F((-1 + 2 + (F(3)^4))) - (5 + (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1548 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times ((F(4)^5) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1549 &:= (((-1 + F(((2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) \times (5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1550 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) + (F(4 + 5) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1551 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) - (F((4 + 5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1552 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) - (F((4 + 5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1553 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times (F(4) \times F(5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1554 &:= (((-1 + (2^{F(3+4)-5})) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1555 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3) \times F((F(4) + 5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1556 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) + ((F(4) + 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1557 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 - F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1558 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3 - F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1559 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(F(3 + F(4))) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1560 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (F((F(F(4)) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1521 &:= (-9 \times (((8 + F(7)) \times F(F(6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1522 &:= ((9 \times 8 \times F((7 + 6 - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1523 &:= (((9 + (F(8) - F(7))) \times F(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1524 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1525 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - F(7 + 6)) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1526 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times F(F(6)))) + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1527 &:= ((9 \times 8 \times (F(7) + F(6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1528 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1529 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times (6 + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1530 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - (7 \times 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1531 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) - 7) \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1532 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) \times (F(7) - F(6 + 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1533 &:= ((-9 + F((F(8) + (7 - (6 + 5)))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1534 &:= ((9 \times 8 - F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1535 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) + (F(6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
1536 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
1537 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) \times 6) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1538 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7 - F((F(6) + 5)))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1539 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 + 6)) - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1540 &:= ((9 \times 8 \times F(7)) - (6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1541 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times F(6)) + F(((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1542 &:= (9 + (F(8) \times ((7 + 6 + 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1543 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F(7) \times (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1544 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (F((F(6) + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1545 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(7) \times F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1546 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) \times 6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1547 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (F(7) \times (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1548 &:= (9 - F(8) + (F(7) \times (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1549 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times F((F(6) + 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1550 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1551 &:= ((9 \times (8 + F(F(7)))) - (F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1552 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7)) \times 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1553 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (7 \times (6 + 5)))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1554 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (F(7) - (F(F(6)) \times 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1555 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - F(7)) \times F(F(6)))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1556 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (F(F(6)) \times 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1557 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) - (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1558 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) - (F(6) \times 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1559 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F(7) \times (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1560 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (F(7) \times (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1561 &:= ((-1 + F((F(F(2 \times 3)) - 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1562 &:= (F((-1 + 2 + (F(3)^4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1563 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3 \times F(4)) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
1564 &:= ((-1 - 2 + F(3 \times 4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1565 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + F(3 \times 4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1566 &:= ((-1 + F((F(2 \times 3) + 4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1567 &:= (F((-1 + (F(F(2 + F(3))) \times (4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1568 &:= ((-1 + 2 + F(3 \times 4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1569 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) - (F((4 + 5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1570 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))^{F(4)})/5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1571 &:= (-1 + (F((F(F(2 \times 3)) - 4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1572 &:= (F((-1 + 2 + (F(3)^4))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1573 &:= (F((F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + (4 + 5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1574 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1575 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(F(3 + F(4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1576 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) - F((4 - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
1577 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1578 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - (F(F(4)) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1579 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F(3) - (F(4) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1580 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - (F(4) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1581 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 + 4)) \times (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1582 &:= ((-1 + 2 + F(3 + 4)) \times (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1583 &:= (-1 + ((F((F(2 + 3) \times F(F(4)))) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1584 &:= ((F((-1 - 2 + F(3 + 4))) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1585 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + F(4)) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1586 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1587 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((F(3) - F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1588 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((F(3) - F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1589 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) + (F(F(4))^5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1590 &:= ((-F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1591 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((F(3) - F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1592 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) + F((4 - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
1593 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) - F((4 - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
1594 &:= (-1 - 2 + F((F(3) - ((F(4) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1595 &:= (-1 \times 2 + F((F(3) - ((F(4) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1596 &:= (-1 + F((F(F(2 \times 3)) - (F(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1597 &:= F((-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) - (4 + (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1598 &:= (-1 + 2 + F((F(3) - ((F(4) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1599 &:= (-1 - ((F(2 \times 3))^{F(F(4))}) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1600 &:= (-1 \times ((F(2 \times 3))^{F(F(4))}) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1561 &:= (9 - 8 + (F(7) \times (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1562 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) - 7) \times (6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1563 &:= (((9 + (F(8) + F(F(7)))) \times 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1564 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (F(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1565 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1566 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - ((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1567 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) - (F(F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1568 &:= (((9 \times F(8)) + 7) \times F((F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1569 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1570 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) + (F(6) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1571 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times 7 + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1572 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + (F(7) \times (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1573 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times (6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1574 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times (6 + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1575 &:= (F((-9 + F(8) - 7) \times (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1576 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) \times 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1577 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) \times (F(7) - F(6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1578 &:= ((-9 + F((F(8) + (7 - (6 + 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1579 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times 6) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1580 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times F(7 + 6))) - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1581 &:= (-9 - (F(8 + 7) - (F(6) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1582 &:= (F((-9 - 8) \times (7 - F(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1583 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) - (F(6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1584 &:= (((-9 \times F(8)) + F(7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1585 &:= (9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) - (F(F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1586 &:= (-9 + ((8 + F((7 + 6 - 5))) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1587 &:= (F((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6 + 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1588 &:= (-9 + F((F(8) - (F(7) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1589 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times 6) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1590 &:= ((-9 - F(8)) \times (F(7) - ((6 + 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1591 &:= (9 + (F(8) + (7 \times (F((F(6) + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1592 &:= (F((-9 - 8) \times (7 - F(6)))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1593 &:= (((9 + (F(8) + F(F(7)))) \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1594 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1595 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8)/7)) + 6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1596 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) + (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1597 &:= F((-9 - 8 + (F(7) + (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1598 &:= (((-9 + F((F(8) - 7))) \times 6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1599 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1600 &:= ((9 \times ((8 \times F(7)) + 6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1601 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1602 &:= (F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3))) + F((4 - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
1603 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times (F((F(4) + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1604 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (F((F(4) + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1605 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F((3 \times 4)) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1606 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F((3 \times 4)) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1607 &:= (1 - 2 + ((F((3 \times 4)) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1608 &:= ((F(((F(-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times F(4))) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1609 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F((3 \times 4)) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1610 &:= (F((-1 + 2 + (F(3)^4))) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1611 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (F(4 + 5) + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1612 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (F((4 + 5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1613 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) - (F((4 + 5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1614 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times (F(4 + 5) + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1615 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times ((F(F(4)) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1616 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) + (F((4 + 5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1617 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) + F((4 - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))))) \\
1618 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F((F(3) + (4 + 5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1619 &:= (1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) + F((4 - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))))) \\
1620 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) + F(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1621 &:= ((-1 + F((F(F(2 \times 3)) - 4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1622 &:= (F((-1 + 2 + (F(3)^4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1623 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1624 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3 \times 4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1625 &:= ((-1 - (F(2 \times 3)^{F(F(4))})) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1626 &:= (-1 + (F((F(2 \times 3) + 4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1627 &:= (F((-1 + (F(F(2 + F(3))) \times (4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1628 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3 \times 4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1629 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) - (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1630 &:= ((((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))^{F(4)})/5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1631 &:= (-1 + (F((F(F(2 \times 3)) - 4) + (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1632 &:= (F((-1 + 2 + (F(3)^4))) + (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1633 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((F(F(3 + F(4))) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1634 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + (F((4 + 5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1635 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (3 \times F((F(4) \times 5)))) - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1636 &:= (((-1 + (F(2 + 3)^{F(4)})) \times (5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1637 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times ((F(4)^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1638 &:= ((-1 - (F(F(2 + 3))^{F(4)})) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1639 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + F(3 + 4)) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1640 &:= ((((-1 + F(2 + 3))^{F(4)}) \times (5 + F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1601 &:= (-9 - (F(8) + (F(F(7)) \times (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1602 &:= ((9 \times F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) \times 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1603 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7 - F((F(6) + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1604 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1605 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) - (6 \times 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1606 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + 7) \times (6 + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1607 &:= (F((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1608 &:= (-9 - (F(8) \times (F(7) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1609 &:= (((-9 - (F(8) - F(F(7)))) \times F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1610 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times 7) - (F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1611 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (F(F(6)) \times 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1612 &:= (F((-9 - 8) \times (7 - F(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1613 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times 7) + ((6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1614 &:= (-9 - 8 - (F(F(7)) \times (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1615 &:= (-9 - 8) \times ((F(7) + 6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1616 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1617 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times F(6))) - F(5 + 4)) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1618 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (7 - F(F(6)))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1619 &:= (((-9 - (F(8) - F(F(7)))) \times F(6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1620 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1621 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (F(F(6)) \times 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1622 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7)))/F(6) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
1623 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) \times 7)) + (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1624 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times 7) + (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1625 &:= ((9 + 8) \times ((F(7) + 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1626 &:= (9 - (F(8) \times (F(7) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1627 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (7 + ((6 \times 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1628 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) + 7)) \times ((6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1629 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1630 &:= (-9 + 8 - (F(F(7)) \times (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1631 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (F(F(7)) \times (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1632 &:= ((-9 \times F(F(8)/7)) + ((6 \times 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1633 &:= (9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) + (6 \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))))) \\
1634 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7) \times 6))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1635 &:= (((-9 \times (F(8) + F(7))) - F(F(6))) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1636 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) + 7)) \times F(6 + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1637 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (F(7) - ((6 \times 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1638 &:= ((-9 + 8 - F(F(7))) \times (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1639 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times 7) + (F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1640 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 \times F((F(6) + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1641 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) + (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1642 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) - (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1643 &:= ((-1-2 \times 3) + (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1644 &:= ((-1 - F(2+3)) + (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1645 &:= ((-1 \times F(2+3)) + (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1646 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) - (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1647 &:= (-1-2 + (F((F(3) + (F(4) + 5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1648 &:= ((-1+2-3) + (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1649 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) + F(4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1650 &:= (F((-1 \times (2 - (3+4+5)))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
1651 &:= (-1+2 + (F((F(3) + (F(4) + 5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1652 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2+3)))) + (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1653 &:= (F((-1 + F(2+3))) + (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1654 &:= ((-1 + F(2+3)) + (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1655 &:= (1 \times F(2+3) + (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1656 &:= (((-1 \times (F(2+3) \times 4)) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9)) \\
1657 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) + (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1658 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4+5) + (F(F(6)) + 7+8+9)))) \\
1659 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2+3)) \times ((4 \times F(5+6)) - 7-8-9)) \\
1660 &:= (F(F(F(F((-1+2 \times 3)))) \times ((4 \times F(5+6)) - 7-8-9)) \\
1661 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
1662 &:= (F((-1+2 + (F(3)^4))) + (F(5+6) - 7-8-9)) \\
1663 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1664 &:= (1-2 + ((3 + F(4+5)) \times (F(F(6)) + 7+8+9))) \\
1665 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2+3))) + F(4+5)) \times (F(F(6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
1666 &:= ((-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) - F(F(4))) \times F(5+6))) - 7-8-9) \\
1667 &:= (((-1 + (F(2+3) \times 4)) \times F(5+6)) - 7-8-9) \\
1668 &:= ((-1+2 - F(3+4)) \times (5 - (6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
1669 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times F(F(3+4))) - (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
1670 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) + (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1671 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4)^5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
1672 &:= ((-1 + (2 + (3+4))) \times (F((5 + F(6))) - 7-8-9)) \\
1673 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3)^4) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1674 &:= (((-1+2 + F(F(3+4))) \times 5) + (F(F(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
1675 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3+4) \times ((5 \times F(F(6))) + 7+8+9))) \\
1676 &:= (1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (4 - F(5+6)) - 7-8-9 \\
1677 &:= (((1+2) \times (3 \times (4+5))) \times F(F(6))) - 7-8-9 \\
1678 &:= 1 + F(F(2+3) + F(F(4))) \times (5 \times F(F(6)) + 7+8+9) \\
1679 &:= (-1 - (((2-3) - F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1680 &:= ((-1+2 + F((F(3) + (F(4) + 5)))) \times (6+7+8+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1641 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times F(7)) + 6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1642 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) \times (F(7) - F(6+5))) - F(4+3+2+1))) \\
1643 &:= ((-9 + (F((F(8) - 7)) \times 6)) - F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1644 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (F(7) \times 6)) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1645 &:= (9 - F(8) + (7 + ((6 \times 5) \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1646 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F(7) + ((6 \times 5) \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1647 &:= (-9 \times ((F(8) \times (F(7) - F(F(6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1648 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) - (6 \times 5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
1649 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (F(7) - ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1650 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - (F(7) + F(F(6)))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1651 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + 7) \times (6+5)) - 4-3-2-1) \\
1652 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(F(7))) \times 6) - F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1653 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + ((7 \times F((F(6) + 5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1654 &:= (((9 \times 8 + 7) \times F(F(6))) + (5-4-3-2-1)) \\
1655 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(7) \times (F(F(6)) + (5-4-3-2-1)))) \\
1656 &:= (-9 \times 8 \times (F(7) - (F(F(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1657 &:= (F((-9 - 8) \times (7 - F(6)))) + (5 + F(4+3+2+1)) \\
1658 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) - F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1659 &:= (F(F(-9+8+7)) \times (F(6+5) - 4-3-2-1)) \\
1660 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) \times F(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1661 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) \times (6+5))) - F(4+3+2+1)) \\
1662 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F(7) + ((6 \times 5) \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1663 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (7 \times (6+5))) + F(4+3+2+1))) \\
1664 &:= (9 - 8 + (F(7) + ((6 \times 5) \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1665 &:= ((-9 + ((8+7) \times F(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1666 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + (F(F(6)) \times (5-4-3-2-1))) \\
1667 &:= (9 + (F(8) - (F(7) - ((6 \times 5) \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1668 &:= (((-9 - 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(6)) - (5 + F(4+3+2+1))) \\
1669 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 \times F((F(6) + 5))) + F(4+3+2+1))) \\
1670 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) + 6+5) \times (4+3+2+1) \\
1671 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) - (F(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1672 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1673 &:= ((9 \times 8 \times (F(7) + 6+5)) + F(4+3+2+1)) \\
1674 &:= (((9 \times 8 + 7) \times F(F(6))) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1675 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + (F(F(7)) \times F((F(F(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1676 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (F(F(6)) \times 5))) + 4+3+2+1 \\
1677 &:= (((9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times 6) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1678 &:= (-9 - ((8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1679 &:= ((9+8) \times (F(7) + F(6+5))) - F(4+3+2+1) \\
1680 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(7) + 6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1681 &:= (1 - (((2-3) - F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1682 &:= (-1 - ((2 + (3+4)) \times (5 - (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
1683 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + (3+4))) \times (5 - (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
1684 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (F(4) \times (5 - (F(6) \times (7+8+9))))) \\
1685 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3))^{F(4)} \times 5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
1686 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2+3))) \times F((F(4) \times 5))) - (6 \times (7+8+9))) \\
1687 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3+4}) \times (5 + F(6))) + 7+8+9)) \\
1688 &:= (((-1 + F((2 \times (3+4)))) \times 5) - (F(6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
1689 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3+4) \times (F(5+6) - 7-8-9))) \\
1690 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) \times (F(5+6) - 7-8-9))) \\
1691 &:= (-1 - ((F((F(2 \times 3) + F(4))) + 5) \times (6-7-8-9))) \\
1692 &:= ((-1 + (F((2 \times (3+4))) \times 5)) - (F(6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
1693 &:= ((F((-1 + 2 + F(3+4))) \times 5) - (F(6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
1694 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(3+4)) \times (F(5+6) + 7+8+9))) \\
1695 &:= (F(F(F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3))))) \times (F(4) \times (F(5+6) + 7+8+9))) \\
1696 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4+5)))) \times (F(6) + 7+8+9)) \\
1697 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((F(3) - F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \times (F(6) + 7+8+9))) \\
1698 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times F(3+4+5))) \times 6) - 7-8-9) \\
1699 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F(3 \times F(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1700 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3 \times F(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1701 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times ((F(4) \times F(5+6)) - 7-8-9)) \\
1702 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((F(3+4) \times 5) + 6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
1703 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times ((F(4)^5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1704 &:= (((-1 - F(2+3)) \times F(4)) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9) \\
1705 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((F(3+4) \times 5) + 6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
1706 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) - ((4+5) \times (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
1707 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3) + F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1708 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3) + F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1709 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F((F(3) + (F(4) + 5)))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1710 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2+3)))) + F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
1711 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3) + F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1712 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times F(3 \times F(4))) - 5) \times (F(6) - 7-8-9) \\
1713 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3+4)) + ((5 + F(F(6))) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
1714 &:= (-1 + (((F(F(2 \times 3)) - F(F(4))) \times F(5+6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
1715 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3))^{F(F(4))} \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1716 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times F((3 \times 4)))) - 5) \times 6) + 7+8+9) \\
1717 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4)^5)) - (F(6) - 7-8-9)) \\
1718 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(F(2+3))) \times (F(4)^5)) + (F(F(6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
1719 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + ((4+5) \times (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
1720 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) - ((4+5) \times (F(6) \times (7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1681 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) + 7)) \times F(6+5)) - 4-3-2-1) \\
1682 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6)))) + (5-4-3-2-1))) \\
1683 &:= ((9 + (F(8) - F(7))) \times (F(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1) \\
1684 &:= (-9-8 + (7 \times (F((F(6)+5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1685 &:= (-9+8 + ((7 \times F((F(6)+5))) + F(4+3+2+1))) \\
1686 &:= ((-9+8+7) \times (6 + (5 \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1687 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) - (6 + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1688 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) + (F(7+6) - F(5+4)))) \times F(3+2+1)) \\
1689 &:= (-9+8 + (F(7) \times ((F(6)+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1690 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) \times F(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1691 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) + (7+6)) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1692 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (F(F(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1693 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) - (6 \times 5)))) + F(4+3+2+1)) \\
1694 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + (F(F(7)) + ((6 \times 5) \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1695 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) - ((6 \times 5) - 4-3-2-1))) \\
1696 &:= (9 - ((8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1697 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + ((6 \times 5) \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\
1698 &:= ((9 - (F(8)/7)) \times (F(6) + (5 \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1699 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
1700 &:= ((-9+8) \times ((F(7) + F(F(6))) \times (5 - F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1701 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + F(7)) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1702 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6)))) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1703 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) \times (7 - F(6+5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
1704 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(7) \times (F(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1705 &:= (9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) - (6 + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1706 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) - 7) \times F(6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1707 &:= (((9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times 6) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1708 &:= (-9 + (((8+7) \times F(6)) + F((5+4) + F(3+2+1)))) \\
1709 &:= (9 + ((F(8) + (7+6)) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1710 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) + 7)) \times (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1711 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times F(F(7)))) - (F(6+5) + F(4+3+2+1))) \\
1712 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) - (6+5)))) - F(4+3+2+1)) \\
1713 &:= (((-9-8 + F(F(7))) \times F(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1714 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times F(6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1715 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) + F(F(7)))) \times ((6 + (5+4)) - F(3+2+1))) \\
1716 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1717 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7)) \times (6+5)) - 4-3-2-1) \\
1718 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - F(6+5))) - 4-3-2-1) \\
1719 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) - (6 + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1720 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (F(F(7)) + 6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1721 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) + ((4 + 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1722 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) + ((4 + 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1723 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) + ((4 + 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1724 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) - ((4 + 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1725 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times F(3 \times F(4)))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1726 &:= (-F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + ((4 + 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1727 &:= (-1 - ((F(F(2 \times 3)) - (4 + F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1728 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times ((F(4) - (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1729 &:= (1 - ((F(F(2 \times 3)) - (4 + F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1730 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + ((4 + 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1731 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (F((F(4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1732 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + ((4 + 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1733 &:= ((1 \times F(2 + 3)) + ((4 + 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1734 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - (F((F(4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1735 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) + ((4 + 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1736 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times ((F(4 + 5) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1737 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1738 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1739 &:= (1 - 2 + (3 \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1740 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1741 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1742 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3 \times 4 + 5) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1743 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1744 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (F(3) \times F((F(4) \times 5)))) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1745 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3))^{F(4)} \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1746 &:= (-1 + (F((F(F(2 \times 3)) - 4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1747 &:= (F((-1 + 2 + (F(3)^4))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1748 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) + ((4 + 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1749 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (F((4 + 5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1750 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (((F(3)^4) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1751 &:= (-1 - (((F(2 \times 3) \times F(F(4))) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1752 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - (F((4 + 5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1753 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((F(3)^4) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1754 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 + F(3))^{F(4)} \times (F(5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1755 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (F((4 + 5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1756 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (F((4 + 5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1757 &:= (-1 + (F(2 + F(3)) \times (F((4 + 5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1758 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times (F((4 + 5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1759 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (F((4 + 5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1760 &:= (-1 - ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 - F(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1721 &:= (9 - ((F(8) \times (7 - F(6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1722 &:= (((-9 + F(8))^{F(7+6-5-4)} - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1723 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) \times (7 - F(6 + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1724 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (F(7) + F(6 + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1725 &:= (-F(-9 + F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) \times F(6)) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1726 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) \times (6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1727 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7)) \times (6 - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1728 &:= (-9 + F(8))^{F(F(7)+6-(5+4+3+2+1))} \\
1729 &:= (9 + ((8 \times F(F(7))) - (F(6 + 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1730 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times 7) + F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1731 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) - (F(7) - F(F(6)))) \times (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1732 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (F(F(7)) - (6 + (5 + 4)))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1733 &:= (((-9 - 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(6)) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1734 &:= (-9 - (F(8) \times (7 - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1735 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(7 + 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1736 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + ((F(7) - 6) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1737 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1738 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - F(6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1739 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times (F(6) + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1740 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - (7 + F(F(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1741 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + F((7 + ((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1742 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (F(F(7)) \times F(6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1743 &:= (((-9 - 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1744 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (7 \times F(F(6)))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1745 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times F(F(7)))) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1746 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) + 7)) \times F(6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1747 &:= ((9 \times ((8 \times F(7)) + F(6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1748 &:= (((-9 + F(8 + 7)) \times (F(6) - 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1749 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times F(F(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1750 &:= ((-9 - 8 - F(F(7))) \times (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1751 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 + 5))) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1752 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) - (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1753 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + F(((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1754 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) - (6 + 5)))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1755 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) - (7 \times F(F(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1756 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times F(F(7)))) - (F(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1757 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) - (6 + 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1758 &:= (-9 - ((F(8)/7) \times (F(F(6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1759 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times F(F(6)))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1760 &:= ((F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) + 6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1761 &:= (-1 \times ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 - F(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1762 &:= (1 - ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 - F((5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1763 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + (F(4 + 5) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1764 &:= (-1 + (F(F(F(2 + 3))) \times (F((F(4) + 5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1765 &:= (F(F(F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3)))))) \times (F((F(4) + 5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1766 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) - F((F(4) \times 5))) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1767 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (F((F(4) \times 5)) + (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
1768 &:= (((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) - (4 + 5)) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1769 &:= (-1 + (((F(2 \times 3)^{F(F(4))}) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1770 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1771 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3)^4) - F(5 + 6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1772 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3 + 4)) \times (5 + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
1773 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3) + ((4 + 5) \times F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1774 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3) + ((4 + 5) \times F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1775 &:= (-1 - (((2 + F(3 + 4)) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1776 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1777 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3) + ((4 + 5) \times F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1778 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) \times (F(4) - (F((5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1779 &:= (-F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + (4 \times (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1780 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1781 &:= (-1 - ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4) - F(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1782 &:= (-1 \times ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4) - F(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1783 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (F(F(3 + 4)) - 5)) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1784 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1785 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times F((F(4) \times 5))) - (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1786 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3 \times F((F(4) \times 5)))) - (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1787 &:= (-1 + (F(2 + F(3)) \times (4 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1788 &:= (-1 + (F((F(2 \times 3) + 4 + 5)) + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1789 &:= (F((-1 + (F(F(2 + F(3))) \times (4 + 5)))) + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1790 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3 \times 4 + 5) + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1791 &:= (-F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + ((F(F(4))^{5+6}) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1792 &:= ((((-1 - F(2 + 3)) + F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1793 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3)^4) + (5 \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))))) \\
1794 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
1795 &:= (1 + (2 \times (F(F(3)^4) + (5 \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))))) \\
1796 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) + F(5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1797 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 + 4) \times F(5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1798 &:= (1 - 2 + ((3 + 4) \times (F((5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1799 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(F(2 + 3))) + F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1800 &:= ((F((-1 - 2 + F(3 + 4))) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1761 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) \times (6 + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1762 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1763 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1764 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1765 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times F(F(7)))) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1766 &:= ((-9 + (F(8 + 7) \times (F(6) - 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1767 &:= ((-9 / (F(8) / 7)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1768 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) \times (7 - F(6 + 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1769 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) + F(F(7))) \times (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1770 &:= ((-9 - F(8)) \times ((7 - (6 + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1771 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) \times (6 + 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1772 &:= (9 \times 8 + ((F(7) + F(F(6))) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1773 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7 + 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1774 &:= (9 + ((8 \times F(F(7))) - (F(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1775 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1776 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) - F(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1777 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7 \times F(F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1778 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (F(7 + 6) - 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1779 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times F(F(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1780 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + F((7 + F((F(6) - 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1781 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1782 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1783 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1784 &:= (F(-9 + 8 + 7) \times (F((F(6) + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1785 &:= (F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1786 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (F(F(7)) - F(6))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1787 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times F(F(7))) - (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1788 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) - (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1789 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times F(F(7)))) - ((6 + 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1790 &:= (-9 + F(8) - (7 \times (F(F(6)) - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1791 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1792 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (F(F(7)) \times F((F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1793 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) - (F(6 + 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1794 &:= (F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) + ((6 \times 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1795 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times F(7 + 6))) - (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1796 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (F(7) \times F(6))) + (F(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1797 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) / 7) \times (F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1798 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1799 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) + (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1800 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (F(7) \times (F(6 + 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1801 &:= 1 + (F(2+3) + F(F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9) \\
1802 &:= (-1 - ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) - F(5+6))) + 7+8+9)) \\
1803 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (3 \times F((4+5+6)))) - 7-8-9) \\
1804 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times F((4+5+6)))) - 7-8-9) \\
1805 &:= ((-1 + (F(2+F(3)) \times F((4+5+6)))) - 7-8-9) \\
1806 &:= ((F((-1+F(2+3))) \times F((4+5+6))) - 7-8-9) \\
1807 &:= ((-1+2+(3 \times F((4+5+6)))) - 7-8-9) \\
1808 &:= (((-1+F(2+3)) \times 4) \times (F(5+6)+7+8+9)) \\
1809 &:= (-1+2+((F(3)^4) \times (F(5+6)+7+8+9))) \\
1810 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times F((F(4) \times 5))) + (6-7-8-9))) \\
1811 &:= (-1 + ((F(2+F(3)) \times F((F(4) \times 5))) + (6-7-8-9))) \\
1812 &:= ((F((-1+F(2+3))) \times F((F(4) \times 5))) + (6-7-8-9)) \\
1813 &:= (-1+2+((3 \times F((F(4) \times 5))) + (6-7-8-9))) \\
1814 &:= (-1 - ((F((2+F(3+4))) - 5) \times (F(F(6)) - 7-8-9))) \\
1815 &:= (-1 \times ((F((2+F(3+4))) - 5) \times (F(F(6)) - 7-8-9))) \\
1816 &:= (((-1+F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4)+F(5+6))) - 7-8-9) \\
1817 &:= (-1+2+(F(3) \times ((4 \times F((5+F(6)))) - 7-8-9))) \\
1818 &:= ((-1+2-(3 \times F(4+5))) \times (6-7-8-9)) \\
1819 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (F(F(3)^4) - F(5+6))) + 7+8+9)) \\
1820 &:= (F((-1+F(2 \times 3))) \times (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1821 &:= (-1-2-((F(3+4) - F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
1822 &:= (((-1+(F(F(2 \times 3))^{F(4)})) / 5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
1823 &:= ((-1+(2 \times F(F(3)^4))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1824 &:= (((-1+F((F(2+3) \times 4))) / F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9)) \\
1825 &:= (-1+2-((F(3+4) - F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
1826 &:= (1 \times 2 - ((F(3+4) - F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
1827 &:= (-1-2+(3 \times F((F(F(4)) - ((5+6) - 7-8-9)))) \\
1828 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times F((F(F(4)) - ((5+6) - 7-8-9)))) \\
1829 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) + F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1830 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 - F(4+5)))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
1831 &:= (-1+2+(3 \times F((F(F(4)) - ((5+6) - 7-8-9)))) \\
1832 &:= (((-1+F((2+(F(3)+4+5)))) \times F(6)) - 7-8-9) \\
1833 &:= ((-1+(F(2 \times 3) \times F(F((F(4)+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
1834 &:= ((F(F((-1+F(2 \times 3)))) \times (F(4)+5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
1835 &:= (((F((-1+F(2 \times 3)))^{F(F(4))}) \times (5+6)) - 7-8-9) \\
1836 &:= (((-1+F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (4+F(5+6))) - 7-8-9) \\
1837 &:= (-1+2-(3 \times (F(4+5) \times (6-7-8-9)))) \\
1838 &:= (((-1+2-3) + (F(F((F(F(4)+5))) \times F(6))) - 7-8-9) \\
1839 &:= ((-1+(F(2 \times 3) \times F((F(F(4))+5+6)))) - 7-8-9) \\
1840 &:= ((F((-1+(2+(3+4+5)))) \times F(6)) - 7-8-9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1801 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times F(F(7))) + ((6-5) - F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1802 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (F(F(7)) - 6)) + (5-4-3-2-1))) \\
1803 &:= (-9 - ((F(8)/7) \times (6 - F(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1804 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) - 6))) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1805 &:= ((-9 + ((8+F(7)) \times F(6+5))) - F(4+3+2+1)) \\
1806 &:= ((-9/(F(8)/7)) \times (F(6) - F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1807 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times F(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1808 &:= ((9 + (8 \times F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) + (5-4-3-2-1))) \\
1809 &:= (9 + ((8+7) \times (F(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1810 &:= ((-9+8+(7 \times (F(F(6))+5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
1811 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times F(F(7))) + ((6+5) - F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1812 &:= ((-9/(F(8)/7)) \times (6 - F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1813 &:= (((-9+F(8+7)) \times (F(6)-5)) + 4+3+2+1) \\
1814 &:= ((F(F(-9+8+7)) \times F(6+5)) - F(4+3+2+1)) \\
1815 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7) - (6+5)))) \times F(4+3+2+1)) \\
1816 &:= ((F(-9+F(8)) \times F(7)) - ((6-5) + F(4+3+2+1))) \\
1817 &:= ((9 \times 8 + 7) \times (F(6) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1818 &:= (((-9 \times F(8)) - F(7)) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1819 &:= (-9-8) \times (F(7) - (F(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1820 &:= ((9 \times F(8)) - (F(F(7)) \times (F(6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1821 &:= (-9 + ((8 - F((F(7) - F(6)))) \times F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1822 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (F(F(7)) - 6)) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1823 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) - ((6 \times 5) + F(4+3+2+1))) \\
1824 &:= ((-9+F(8)) \times (7 \times F(F(6)) - (5-4-3-2-1))) \\
1825 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (F(7+6) - 5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
1826 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) \times (6+5)) + F(4+3+2+1)) \\
1827 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1828 &:= (((-9 - (F(8) - F(F(7)))) \times 6) + F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1829 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) - (F(6+5) - 4-3-2-1)) \\
1830 &:= (F((-9 + F(((8+7) - F(6)))) \times F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1831 &:= (-9 + (((F(8) \times F(7)) - F(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1832 &:= ((-9-8 + (F(F(7)) \times F(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1833 &:= (9 + (8 \times (F(7+6) + (5-4-3-2-1)))) \\
1834 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times F(F(7)))) - (6 + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1835 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times F(F(7)))) - ((6 \times 5) - 4-3-2-1)) \\
1836 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) - (6 + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1837 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) - (6-5)))) - 4-3-2-1) \\
1838 &:= ((F(-9+F(8)) \times F(7)) - (F(6+5) - F(4+3+2+1))) \\
1839 &:= (-9 + ((F(8)/7) \times (6 + F(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1840 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times F(7+6))) - (5+4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1841 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1842 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4))) \times F(5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1843 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4))) \times F(5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1844 &:= ((-1 + (F((F(2 + 3) + F(4))) \times F(5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1845 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - F((4 + 5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1846 &:= (1 + ((F((F(2 + 3) + F(4))) \times F(5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1847 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 + 3)) + F(F(4))) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1848 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - F((4 + 5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1849 &:= (1 + ((F(F(2 + 3)) + F(F(4))) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1850 &:= (((-1 + F((2 \times (3 + 4)))) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1851 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - F((F(4) \times 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1852 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times F((4 + 5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1853 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 + F(3)) \times F((4 + 5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1854 &:= ((-1 + (F((2 \times (3 + 4))) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1855 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3^{F(4)}))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1856 &:= ((((-1 + 2 + F(F(3 + 4))) - 5) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1857 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 \times F((F(4) \times 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1858 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times F((F(4) \times 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1859 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 - F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1860 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((3 - F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1861 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times F((F(4) \times 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1862 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1863 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - ((F(4 + 5) - F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1864 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4) + F(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1865 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(F(3 + 4)) \times F((5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
1866 &:= (((-1 + 2 + F((F(3) + 4 + 5))) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1867 &:= ((F((-1 + 2 + F(3 + 4))) \times 5) + (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1868 &:= (((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4) - F(5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1869 &:= (-1 - 2 - (F((3 \times 4)) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1870 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F((3 \times 4)) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1871 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (F(3 + 4) - F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1872 &:= (((1 \times 2 - F(3 + 4)) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1873 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F((3 \times 4)) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1874 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + (F((F(F(4)) + 5)) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1875 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) + (F((F(F(4)) + 5)) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1876 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1877 &:= ((-1 - 2 + ((F(F(3 + 4)) + 5) \times F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1878 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + ((F(F(3 + 4)) + 5) \times F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1879 &:= (-1 - ((2^{F(3+F(4))}) - (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1880 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{F(3+F(4))}) - (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1841 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1842 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) - ((6 + 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1843 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (F(7 + 6) - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1844 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times F(F(7)))) - (6 - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1845 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) - F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1846 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times F(F(7))) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1847 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) \times (7 + 6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1848 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) \times F(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1849 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) - (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1850 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + F(7)) \times F(6 + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1851 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) - (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1852 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (F(F(7)) \times F(6))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1853 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7 + 6) - 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1854 &:= ((9 / (F(8) / 7)) \times (F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1855 &:= (-9 + (8 \times F(((7 + F(F(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1856 &:= ((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times F((F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1857 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1858 &:= (9 + ((8 \times F(7 + 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1859 &:= ((F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) \times F(6 + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1860 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times ((F(7) \times F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1861 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times F(F(6)))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1862 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1863 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) \times F((F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1864 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times F(F(7)))) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1865 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) + (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1866 &:= (9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1867 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1868 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) \times F(6))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1869 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) - 6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1870 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times F(7 + 6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1871 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1872 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) - (F(F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1873 &:= (-9 - (((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times 6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1874 &:= (9 + ((8 \times F(F(7))) + ((6 + 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1875 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - (F(7) + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1876 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times F(F(7))) + (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1877 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + 6)) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1878 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1879 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) - (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1880 &:= (9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1881 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3 - (F((F(4)+5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1882 &:= (((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3))^{F(4)})) / 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1883 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1884 &:= ((-1-2) \times (F(3) - (F((F(4)+5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1885 &:= ((-1 - F(((2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))))) \times ((5+6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1886 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) + F(5+6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1887 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (F((F(4)+5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1888 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (F((F(4)+5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1889 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3^{F(4)}) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1890 &:= ((-1 + F((F(2+3) \times F(F(4)))))) \times (5+6+7+8+9) \\
1891 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (F((F(4)+5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1892 &:= (-1 + ((F((F(2+3) + F(4))) \times F(5+6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1893 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 \times 3) \times F(F((F(4)+5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1894 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) \times (F(4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1895 &:= (1 + ((F(2 \times 3) \times F(F((F(4)+5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1896 &:= ((-1-2) \times (F(3) - (F((4+5+6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1897 &:= (-1 - ((2 + F((3 \times 4))) \times ((5+6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1898 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - F((3 \times 4))) \times ((5+6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1899 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (F((4+5+6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1900 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (F((4+5+6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1901 &:= (-1 + (F(2 + F(3)) \times (F((4+5+6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1902 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (F((4+5+6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1903 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3)^4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1904 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F(F(3+4)) - (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
1905 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) \times (4+5)) - (F(6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
1906 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((3+4) - (5 \times (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
1907 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4) + F(5+6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1908 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F((F(4) + 5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1909 &:= ((F(F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3)))))) \times F((F(4) + 5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1910 &:= (((-1 + F((2 \times (3 + 4)))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1911 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3 - (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1912 &:= (((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + 4 + 5) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1913 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times (F(4)^5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1914 &:= (-1 + ((F((2 \times (3 + 4))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1915 &:= ((F((-1 + 2 + F(3 + 4))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1916 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - ((F(F(4))^5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1917 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1918 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1919 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((F(3) - F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1920 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((F(3) - F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1881 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1882 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) + ((6 \times 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1883 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (6 - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1884 &:= (-9 + ((F(8)/7) \times (F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1885 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) - (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1886 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) - F(F(6)))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1887 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) - (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1888 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1889 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times F(F(7))) + (F(6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1890 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (F(7 + 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1891 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times F(F(7))) + (F(F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1892 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) + F(7))) \times ((6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1893 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) + (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1894 &:= (9 + ((8 \times F(F(7))) + (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1895 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) + (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1896 &:= (9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1897 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) - (6 - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1898 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1899 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1900 &:= (((9 \times (8 + F(7))) + (6 - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1901 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) + (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1902 &:= (-9 - (F(8) \times (F(7) \times (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1903 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) + (F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1904 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) + F(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1905 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) - (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1906 &:= (((-9 - 8 + F(F(7))) \times 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1907 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) - ((6 + 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1908 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) - (F(F(7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1909 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) + ((6 + 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1910 &:= (((9 \times F(8)) + (F(7) - (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1911 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) - (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1912 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) - (F(6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1913 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(7 + 6))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1914 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) + (F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1915 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) - (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1916 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (F(F(7)) + 6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1917 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1918 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (F(F(7)) + 6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1919 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) + F((F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1920 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) - (F(F(7)) - (6 + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1921 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1922 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + (F(F(4)) \times (5 \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1923 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3)^4) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1924 &:= (-1 + (F((F(2 + 3) \times F(F(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1925 &:= (F((-1 - 2 + F(3 + 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1926 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((F(F(3 + 4)) + 5) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1927 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3)^4) - (5 + 6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1928 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 + F(5 + 6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1929 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - F(4 + 5)) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1930 &:= ((F((-1 + 2 + F(3 + 4))) \times 5) + (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1931 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
1932 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(F(3 + F(4))) - F(((5 \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1933 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3)^4) - 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1934 &:= (((-1 + 2 + F(F(3 + F(4)))) \times F(5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1935 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3 + 4) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1936 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (F(F(3 + 4)) + 5)) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1937 &:= (F(((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1938 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times F(F(3)^4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1939 &:= 1 \times 2 \times F(F(3)^4) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1940 &:= (1 + ((2 \times F(F(3)^4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1941 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((F(3 + F(4)) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1942 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((F(3 + F(4)) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1943 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times F((F(3) \times (F(4) + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1944 &:= (((-1 - F(2 + 3)) - (F(F(4)) - F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1945 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((F(3 + F(4)) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1946 &:= (1 \times 2 - ((F(3 + F(4)) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1947 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1948 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1949 &:= (1 - 2 + (F(3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1950 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times F(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1951 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1952 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 - F(4 + 5)))) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1953 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3)^4) + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1954 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - ((4^5) - (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1955 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4) + F(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1956 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (F((F(4) \times 5)) + (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1957 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3)^4) - F((5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
1958 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times ((4^5) - (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1959 &:= ((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1960 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times F(F(3)^4)) + ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1921 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1922 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1923 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(7 + 6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1924 &:= ((F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) \times F(6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1925 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) - ((7 + 6) \times 5))) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1926 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) - (F(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1927 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1928 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) + ((6 - 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1929 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) + (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1930 &:= ((-9 - F((F(8) - (F(7) - 6)))) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1931 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) + (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1932 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1933 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) + 6 + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1934 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) - F(6)) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1935 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1936 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1937 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) - (F(F(6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1938 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) - F(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1939 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) \times 7)) + (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1940 &:= (((9 \times (8 + (7 + 6))) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1941 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((F(6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1942 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (F(F(7)) + F(6))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1943 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7 + 6) + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1944 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1945 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times F(F(7))) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1946 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) - (F(6 + 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1947 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1948 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) - (F(6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1949 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (F(7) + F((F(6) + 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1950 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times F(F(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1951 &:= (-9 - (((8 - F(F(7))) \times 6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1952 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) - ((6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1953 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((7 + F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1954 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times F(F(7))) + (F(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1955 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) + F(F(7)))) \times F(6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1956 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) - 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1957 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + 6))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1958 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(7 + 6))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1959 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) - ((6 + 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1960 &:= (((9 + F(8)) \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1961 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + ((4 + 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1962 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) + (((F(4)^5) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1963 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) + (((F(4)^5) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1964 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - ((4 \times 5 + F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1965 &:= (-1 - 2 - (((3 + 4) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1966 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (((3 + 4) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1967 &:= (-1 - (((F(F(2 + 3)) + F(F(4))) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1968 &:= (((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) - (F(F(4)) - F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1969 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((3 + 4) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1970 &:= ((((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))^{F(F(4))}) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1971 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times F((F(4) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
1972 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3) \times F((F(4) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
1973 &:= (-1 + (2 \times F((F(3))^{F(4+5)-6-7-8-9}))) \\
1974 &:= (1 \times 2 \times F((F(3))^{F(4+5)-6-7-8-9})) \\
1975 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times F((F(4) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
1976 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1977 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + F((F(4) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
1978 &:= (1 \times 2 \times (F(3) + F((F(4) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
1979 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (F(3) \times F(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1980 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (F(3) \times F(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1981 &:= (1 - ((2 - (F(3) \times F(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1982 &:= (((1 + F((F(2 + 3) + F(4)))) \times F(5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1983 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F(3) - ((4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1984 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - ((4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1985 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times ((4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1986 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3) \times ((4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1987 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3))^{F(F(4)) \times 5}) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1988 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times ((4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1989 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times ((4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1990 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F((3 \times 4)) - (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1991 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3) + (4^5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1992 &:= (((-1 + 2 - (3 + 4)) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1993 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (F(F(3)^4) - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1994 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) - (4 \times (5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1995 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))^{F(F(4))+5}) - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1996 &:= (((-1 - F(2 + 3)) + F(F(4))) \times (5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1997 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times F((F(3) + (F(4) + 5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1998 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times F(F(3)^4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1999 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3)^4) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1961 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) + F((6 - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
1962 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1963 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7 + 6) + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1964 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) + ((6 - 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1965 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - (7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1966 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (6 + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1967 &:= (((9 - 8) \times 7) \times (6 + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1968 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) - F(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1969 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) - ((6 - 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1970 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(7 + 6) - 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1971 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) - (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1972 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - F((F(6) + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1973 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1974 &:= (F((F((-9 + 8 + F(7)))/F(6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1975 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(7 + 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1976 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) - 6))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1977 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + 6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1978 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - ((F(F(7)) \times 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1979 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + (6 - 5)))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1980 &:= (9 \times ((8 + F(F(7))) - (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1981 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) + ((6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1982 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1983 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) + (F(F(6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
1984 &:= ((-9 + (F((F(8)/7)^{6+5})) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1985 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) + (F(6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
1986 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) - 6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1987 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) + (F(6 + 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1988 &:= (9 + ((8 \times F(F(7))) + ((F(F(6)) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1989 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (F(7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1990 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(7 + 6) - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1991 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1992 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) + (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1993 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) \times F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1994 &:= (9 + ((F(8) \times ((F(7) + 6) \times 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1995 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times F(7))) \times (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1996 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) + (F(F(6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1997 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (7 + F(6 + 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1998 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1999 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times F(F(7))) + (F(6 + 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2037 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times (F(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2038 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3) \times (F(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2039 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2+F(3))) \times (F(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2040 &:= (F(F((-1+F(2+3)))) \times (F(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2041 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times (F(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2042 &:= (F(F((-1+F(2+3)))) - ((4-F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2043 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3)^4) + (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2044 &:= ((-1+F(2+3)) - ((4-F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2045 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (F(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2046 &:= (-1 - (F((F(2 \times 3) + F(4))) - (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2047 &:= ((F((-1+F(2 \times 3)))^{F(4)}) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2048 &:= (((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times 4) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2049 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3)^{F(4)+F(5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)})) \\
2050 &:= ((-1 - (F(2+F(3))^4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2051 &:= (-1 - ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times 4) - (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2052 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3^4) - (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2053 &:= (F((-1+F(2 \times 3))) - ((4-F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2054 &:= (-1 - ((F(2+F(3))^4) - (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2055 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) - ((F(4) - F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2056 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3^4) - (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2057 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) - ((F(4) - F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2058 &:= ((-1 - F(2+3)) - ((F(4) - F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2059 &:= ((-1 \times F(2+3)) - ((F(4) - F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2060 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) - ((4-F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2061 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((F((F(3) + F(F(4)))) - F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2062 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) - ((F(4) - F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2063 &:= (-1 - ((F(F(F(2+3))) - (F(F(4)) + F(5+6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2064 &:= (((-1 - F(2+3)) + (F(4) + F(5+6))) \times (7+8+9)) \\
2065 &:= (((-1+2)^{F(3)}) - ((F(4) - F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2066 &:= (F(F((-1+F(2+3)))) - ((F(4) - F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2067 &:= ((F(F((-1+F(2 \times 3)))) \times (4+5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2068 &:= ((-1 + F(2+3)) - ((F(4) - F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2069 &:= (-1 + (((F(2 \times 3)^{F(F(4))}) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2070 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times F(4+5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
2071 &:= (1 + (((F(2 \times 3)^{F(F(4))}) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2072 &:= (((1 - F(2+3))^{F(4)}) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2073 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (F(3) - (4^5))) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2074 &:= (1 - 2 + 3 + ((F(F(4))^{5+6}) + 7+8+9)) \\
2075 &:= ((1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times 4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2037 &:= (((9 + (F(8) - 7)) \times F(6+5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2038 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2039 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) + (F(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2040 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(7+6))) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2041 &:= ((F(-9+F(8)) + F(7)) \times (F(6) - (5-4-3-2-1))) \\
2042 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + ((F(F(7)) - (6 \times 5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2043 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7+6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2044 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + (6-5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2045 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2046 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) + (6 + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2047 &:= (-9 + (((8 + F(F(7))) \times 6) + F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2048 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) + (F(6) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2049 &:= (-9 + ((F((F(8)/7))^{6+5}) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
2050 &:= (((-9 - 8 + F(F(7))) - (6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
2051 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) + (F(F(6)) - (5-4-3-2-1))) \\
2052 &:= (-9 \times (F((F(8) - 7)) - ((6+5) \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2053 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) - (F(F(6)) + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2054 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) - (F(F(6)) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2055 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((F(7) \times F(F(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2056 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + (6 \times (5+4)))) \times F(3+2+1)) \\
2057 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (F(6) \times (F(5+4) \times F(3+2+1))) \\
2058 &:= ((F(-9+F(8)) \times 7) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2059 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) + (F(6+5) - F(4+3+2+1))) \\
2060 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(7+6) + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2061 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) + (F(F(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2062 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (7 + F(6+5))) + F(4+3+2+1))) \\
2063 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) + (F(F(6)) - (5-4-3-2-1)))) \\
2064 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + 6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2065 &:= (9 + (((8 + F(F(7))) \times 6) + F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2066 &:= (((9 \times F(8)) - 7) \times F(6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1) \\
2067 &:= (-9 - (F(8) + (F(F(7)) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2068 &:= ((9 \times F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) \times F(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2069 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) - ((6+5) - F(4+3+2+1))) \\
2070 &:= ((F((-9+8+F(7))) - 6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2071 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (F(F(6)) + (5 \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2072 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (F(7+6) \times (5+4))) - F(3+2+1)) \\
2073 &:= (9 + (8 \times ((F(7) \times F(F(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2074 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (F((7 + F(6)) / (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
2075 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(7+6))) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2076 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3) \times (4^5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2077 &:= (-1 + ((2^{F(3)+4+5}) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2078 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times (4^5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2079 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3) \times (4^5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2080 &:= (1 \times 2 + ((F(3) \times (4^5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2081 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (F(3) + (4^5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2082 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) - ((F(F(4)) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2083 &:= (1 + ((2 \times (F(3) + (4^5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2084 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))^{F(4)}) - (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2085 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3) - (4 - F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2086 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) - ((F(F(4)) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2087 &:= (-1 - ((F(F(2 + 3)) - (F(4) + F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2088 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) - (4 - F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2089 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3) - (4 - F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2090 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) - ((F(F(4)) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2091 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) - ((F(F(4)) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2092 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) - ((F(F(4)) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2093 &:= (1 \times F(2 + 3) - ((F(F(4)) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2094 &:= (-1 \times ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F(F(4))) - (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2095 &:= (-1 - (F(2 \times 3) \times (F(F(4)) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2096 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) \times (F(F(4)) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2097 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times F(3 + 4)) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2098 &:= (1 - ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 - (5 \times F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2099 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (F(3) \times F(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2100 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2101 &:= (1 + ((2 + (F(3) \times F(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2102 &:= (-F((F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))^{F(F(4))})) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2103 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times (F(F((F(4) + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2104 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2105 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2106 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3) \times ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2107 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3))^{F(F(4)) \times 5}) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2108 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2109 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2110 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times F(3 + 4)) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2111 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2112 &:= (1 \times 2 \times (F(3) + ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2113 &:= (1 + (2 \times (F(3) + ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2114 &:= (-1 - (F((F(F(2 + 3)) + F(4))) - (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2076 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times F(F(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2077 &:= ((9 - (F(8) \times (7 - (F(F(6)) \times 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2078 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7) + F(6 + 5)))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2079 &:= ((9 \times (8 + F(F(7)))) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2080 &:= (-9 - 8 - (F(F(7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2081 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) + ((6 - 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2082 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2083 &:= ((9 \times (8 + (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2084 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + 6))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2085 &:= (9 - (F(8) + (F(F(7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2086 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) + (F((F(6) + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2087 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6 - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2088 &:= (-9 \times 8 \times (7 - (F(F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2089 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + (6 - 5)))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2090 &:= (((9 \times F(8))/7) + 6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2091 &:= (9 + 8) \times (F(7) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2092 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2093 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(6) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
2094 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + 6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2095 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) - (6 \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))))) \\
2096 &:= (-9 + 8 - (F(F(7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2097 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2098 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - F((F(6) + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2099 &:= (((9 - F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + (F((6 + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2100 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) - F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2101 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) - (F(F(7)) - (6 - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2102 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2103 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(6) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2104 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) + (F(6 + 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2105 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) + F((F(6) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
2106 &:= ((-9 + 8 - F(F(7))) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2107 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times F(6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2108 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (F(F(7)) - (F(F(6)) \times ((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2109 &:= (-9 + F(8) - (F(F(7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2110 &:= (((-9 \times F(8)) - F(7 + 6)) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2111 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times ((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2112 &:= ((9 \times F(F((8 + 7) - F(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2113 &:= (-9 + (F(8 + 7) + (F(F(6)) \times ((5 + 4) \times F(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2114 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - 6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2115 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3+4)) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2116 &:= ((-1 \times (F(2+3) \times 4)) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2117 &:= (-1-2-((F(3)^4) - (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2118 &:= (((-1-F(2+3)) \times F(4)) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2119 &:= ((1-2-(F(3)^4)) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2120 &:= (-1-2-(F(3+4) - (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2121 &:= ((-1-(2 \times (3+4))) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2122 &:= ((-1 \times (2 \times (3+4))) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2123 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times F(F(3)^4)) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2124 &:= (-1+2-(F(3+4) - (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2125 &:= ((-1-(F(F(2 \times 3)) \times 4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2126 &:= ((-1-(2+(3+4))) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2127 &:= ((F(F((-1+F(2 \times 3)))) \times (4+5)) + 6+7+8+9) \\
2128 &:= ((-1-F(2+3)) - (F(F(4)) - (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2129 &:= ((-1 \times F(2+3)) - (F(F(4)) - (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2130 &:= ((-1+(F(2 \times 3) \times (4+5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
2131 &:= ((-1+2-3) - (F(4) - (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2132 &:= ((-1-F(2+3)) + (F(F(4)) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2133 &:= ((-1-F(2+3)) + (F(4) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2134 &:= (F(F((-1+F(2+3)))) - (4 - (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2135 &:= (F((-1+F(2+3))) - (4 - (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2136 &:= ((-F(F((-1+F(2+3)) - 4)) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9)) \\
2137 &:= (((-1+2)^{F(F(3+4))}) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2138 &:= (F(F((-1-(2-3-4)))) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2139 &:= (F((-1-(2-3-4))) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2140 &:= ((-1-(2-3-4)) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2141 &:= (F(F(F((-1 \times (2-3-4)))) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2142 &:= (F(F((-1+F(2+3)))) + (4 + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2143 &:= (((-1+2) \times (3+4)) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2144 &:= ((-1+(2+(3+4))) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2145 &:= ((-1+F((2+(3+4)))) \times (F(5+6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2146 &:= (-1-2+(F(3+4) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2147 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3+4) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2148 &:= (((-1+F(2+3)) \times F(4)) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2149 &:= (F((-1+2) \times (3+4)) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2150 &:= (-1+2+(F(3+4) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2151 &:= ((F(F(F((-1+2 \times 3)))) \times F(4)) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2152 &:= (((-1+F(2+3)) \times 4) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2153 &:= (-1+2+((F(3)^4) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2154 &:= ((-1-2+(3^{F(F(4)+5})) - (6+7+8+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2115 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2116 &:= ((9 \times ((8-7) + F((F(6)+5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2117 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times F(6)) - (5-4-3-2-1)) \\
2118 &:= ((9 \times F((F(8) + (7 - (6 + (5 + 4)))))) + F(F(3+2+1))) \\
2119 &:= (-9-8+((F(7+6) + F(5+4)) \times F(3+2+1))) \\
2120 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) + ((F(6) \times 5) + F(4+3+2+1))) \\
2121 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) - (F(F(7)) + (6 - 5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2122 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) \times (F(7) - F(F(6)))) + F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2123 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7) + F(6+5)))) - 4-3-2-1) \\
2124 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) + (F(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
2125 &:= (-9 + (((F(8) + F(F(7))) \times 6) + F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2126 &:= ((F(-9+F(8)) \times (F(7)+6)) - F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2127 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times F(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2128 &:= (-9-8+(F(7) \times ((F(6)-5) \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2129 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + 6))) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2130 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times F(7+6)) + (5 \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2131 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (F(F(7)) - (6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2132 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(7) + F((F(6)+5)))) - 4-3-2-1) \\
2133 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (F(F(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2134 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + 6+5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2135 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - F(F(7))) \times (F(6) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2136 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) + (7+6+5)) \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\
2137 &:= (9-8+((F(7+6) + F(5+4)) \times F(3+2+1))) \\
2138 &:= (-9+8+((F(F(7)) \times F(6)) + (5 \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2139 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + 6))) + (5 + F(4+3+2+1))) \\
2140 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + 6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
2141 &:= (((F(-9+F(8)) - F(7)) \times F(F(6))) - F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2142 &:= (-9 \times ((F(8) + F(7)) \times (F(6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2143 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) + (F(F(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2144 &:= (-9+8+(F(7) \times ((F(6)-5) \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2145 &:= ((F(-9+F(8)) - (7-6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2146 &:= (-9-8-(F(7) - (F(6) \times (F(5+4) \times F(3+2+1)))) \\
2147 &:= ((F(-9+F(8)) \times (7+6)) + (5 \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\
2148 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) - (6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2149 &:= (9 - ((8 - (F(F(7)) - (6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2150 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) + (7+6))) \times (5 - F(4+3+2+1))) \\
2151 &:= (-9 \times (F((F(8) - 7)) - (6 + F(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2152 &:= (F(-9+F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) \times 6) + F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2153 &:= (-9-8+((F(F(7)) - (F(F(6)) - 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2154 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7) + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2155 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (3^{F(F(4)+5)}) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2156 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 + F(3))^{F(F(4)+5)}) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2157 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))^{F(F(4)+5)}) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2158 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3^{F(F(4)+5)}) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2159 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2160 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times F(3 \times F(4))) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2161 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times F(3 + 4)) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2162 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))^{F(4)}) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2163 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))^{F(4)}) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2164 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3^{F(4)}) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2165 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 + F(3)) \times (F(4 + 5) \times F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2166 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times (F(4 + 5) \times F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2167 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3 \times F(4)) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2168 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3 \times F(4)) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2169 &:= (-1 + (F((2 + (3 + 4))) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2170 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2171 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3 \times F(4)) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2172 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))^{F(4)}) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2173 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))^{4+5-6}) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2174 &:= ((-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3))^{F(F(4))}) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2175 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + ((F(F(4)) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2176 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times F(F(4))) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2177 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) + ((F(F(4)) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2178 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) + ((F(F(4)) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2179 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) + ((F(F(4)) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2180 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) - ((F(F(4)) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2181 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((F(3) - (4 + F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2182 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + ((F(F(4)) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2183 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times ((F(4)^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2184 &:= ((F(F((-1 - (2 - 3 - 4)))) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2185 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((F(3) - (4 + F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2186 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + ((F(F(4)) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2187 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) + ((F(F(4)) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2188 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + ((F(F(4)) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2189 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times F(3 \times F(4))) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2190 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + F(4 + 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2191 &:= (F((-1 - 2 + F(3 + 4))) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2192 &:= (((-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times F(4 + 5))) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2193 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3) \times (4^5)) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2155 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2156 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(7) \times 6)) \times (F(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2157 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))))) + (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2158 &:= (((-9 + F((F(8) - 7))) \times 6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2159 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (F(F(7)) - (6 \times (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2160 &:= (F((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2161 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) - (F(7 + 6) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2162 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times F(6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2163 &:= (-9 - (F(8) + (7 - (F(6) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2164 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2165 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) - (F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2166 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times (6 + (5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2167 &:= ((-9 - F(8)) + (F(7)^{F(6)+5-4-3-2-1})) \\
2168 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + (6 \times 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2169 &:= (-9 \times (F((F(8) - 7)) - (F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2170 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times F(F(7))) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2171 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) - F((F(6) + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2172 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) + (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2173 &:= (((-9 \times F(8))/7) + (F(6) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2174 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) - (6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2175 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(7) \times (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2176 &:= ((9 \times (8 + F(F(7)))) - (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2177 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) - (6 - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2178 &:= (9 - ((8 + F(F(7))) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2179 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + 6 + 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2180 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) - (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2181 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) - (7 + F((F(6) + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2182 &:= ((-9 \times F(F(8)/7)) + (F(6) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2183 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (F(F(7)) + (F(6) \times 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2184 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times (F(F(6)) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
2185 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times F(7))) \times (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2186 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(7 + 6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2187 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2188 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2189 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) - F((F(6) + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2190 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times F(F(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2191 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) - ((6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2192 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + (6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2193 &:= (((-9 + F((F(8) - 7))) \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2194 &:= (F((-1-2+(F(3)\times(4+5)))) - ((6+7)-F(8+9))) \\
2195 &:= (-1 - ((F((2+F(3+4)))/5) \times (6-7-8-9))) \\
2196 &:= (((-1+F(F(2\times 3))) \times F(4)) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2197 &:= F(-1+F(2\times 3))^{F(F(4+5)-(6+7+8+9))} \\
2198 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2\times 3)) \times F(4)) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2199 &:= (((-1-2)\times 3) + ((F(4)+F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2200 &:= ((-1-F(F(2\times 3))) \times (4 \times (5-(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2201 &:= (((-1+(2\times F(3+4))) \times F(5+6)) - 7-8-9) \\
2202 &:= ((-1-F(2+3)) + ((F(4)+F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2203 &:= ((-1\times F(2+3)) + ((F(4)+F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2204 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2\times 3)) \times (F(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2205 &:= ((-1 + (F(2\times 3)^{F(F(4))})) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2206 &:= ((-1+2-3) + ((F(4)+F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2207 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(F(2+3))) - (F(F(4)) - F(5+6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2208 &:= ((F((-1-(2-3-4))) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9)) \\
2209 &:= (-1 + (F((2+(3+4))) \times (F(5+6) - 7-8-9))) \\
2210 &:= (F((F((-1+F(2+3)))^{F(F(4))})) \times (F(5+6) - 7-8-9)) \\
2211 &:= (F((-1+F(2+3))) + ((F(4)+F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2212 &:= ((-1+F(2+3)) + ((F(4)+F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2213 &:= (F(F(F(F(F((-1+2\times 3)))))) + ((F(4)+F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2214 &:= (-1-2 + ((3^{F(F(4))+5}) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
2215 &:= (-1\times 2 + ((3^{F(F(4))+5}) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
2216 &:= (-1 + ((F(2+F(3))^{F(F(4))+5}) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
2217 &:= ((F((-1+F(2+3)))^{F(F(4))+5}) + 6+7+8+9) \\
2218 &:= (-1+2 + ((3^{F(F(4))+5}) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
2219 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3+F(4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2220 &:= ((F((-1+F(F(2\times 3))))/F(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2221 &:= (F((-1+F(2\times 3))) + ((F(4)+F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2222 &:= ((F((-1+F(2\times 3)))^{F(4)}) - (5-(6+7+8+9))) \\
2223 &:= (((-1-2)\times 3) + ((4+F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2224 &:= (-1 - (F((F(2\times 3)+F(4))) \times (5-(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2225 &:= (-1 \times (F((F(2\times 3)+F(4))) \times (5-(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2226 &:= ((-1-F(2+3)) + ((4+F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2227 &:= ((-1\times F(2+3)) + ((4+F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2228 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2\times 3)) + ((F(4)+F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2229 &:= (-1-2 + ((F(3)+F(F(4))+F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2230 &:= ((F((-1+F(F(2\times 3))))/F(4)) + (5-(6+7+8+9))) \\
2231 &:= (-1+2 - (F(3) - ((4+F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2232 &:= ((F((-1+F(2\times 3)))^{F(4)}) + (5+6+7+8+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2194 &:= (((-9+F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + (F(6) - F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2195 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7 \times F(6))) \times (5-4-3-2-1)) \\
2196 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (F(F(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2197 &:= ((-9/(F(8)/7)) + (F(6) \times (5 \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2198 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times (F(F(6)) - 5)) - 4-3-2-1) \\
2199 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2200 &:= ((F(-9+F(8)) - (F(7) - F(6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
2201 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) - (F(5+4) - F(F(3+2+1)))) \\
2202 &:= ((9 \times ((8+F(F(7))) - (6-5-4)) + (3+2+1)) \\
2203 &:= (-9-8 + ((F(F(7)) - (6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2204 &:= (-9+8 + (7 \times (F(F(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2205 &:= (-9 \times ((8+7) - ((F(F(6)) + 5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2206 &:= (9-8 + (7 \times (F(F(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2207 &:= (F((-9-8) \times (7-F(6))) + F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2208 &:= ((-9+F((F(8)-7))) \times (F(F(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2209 &:= (-9+8 \times 7)^{F(F(6)+5-4-3-2-1)} \\
2210 &:= (((-9+8+F(F(7))) - (6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
2211 &:= (((9 \times F(8)) + 7) \times (6+5)) + F(4+3+2+1) \\
2212 &:= (((9 \times F(8)) + F(7)) \times (6+5)) - 4-3-2-1 \\
2213 &:= (((-9+F((F(8)-7))) \times 6) - (5-4-3-2-1)) \\
2214 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + (6+(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2215 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) + F(7))) \times F(6+5)) - 4-3-2-1) \\
2216 &:= (F(-9+F(8)) + (7 \times (F(F(6)) + (5 \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2217 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + (7 \times (F(F(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2218 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2219 &:= (-9+8 + ((F(F(7)) - (6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2220 &:= ((((-9+F(8)) \times F(7)) - F(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2221 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) - (F(F(7)) + 6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2222 &:= (9+8 + (7 \times (F(F(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2223 &:= (9 \times (F(8) + (F(F(7)) + (F(6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2224 &:= ((9 \times (8 + (F(7+6) + 5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2225 &:= (((-9-F(8)) \times (F(7) - F(6+5))) - F(4+3+2+1)) \\
2226 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + F((6+(5+4)))) \times F(F(3+2+1))) \\
2227 &:= (-9-8) \times (F(7) - (F(6+5) + F(4+3+2+1))) \\
2228 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) - (F(6) - 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2229 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2230 &:= (((-9 - (8-7)) + F((F(6)+5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
2231 &:= (((-9 \times F(8+7)) + (6^5)) - F(4+3+2+1)) \\
2232 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + (F(6) + (5+4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2233 &:= (((-1+2)^{F(3)}) + ((4+F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2234 &:= (-1 + (((F(F(2 \times 3))^{F(F(4))}) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2235 &:= (F((-1+F(2+3))) + ((4+F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2236 &:= ((-1+F(2+3)) + ((4+F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2237 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times F(F(3)^4)) + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2238 &:= ((F((-1 + ((2 \times 3) + 4 + 5))) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2239 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 \times 3)^{F(F(4))}) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2240 &:= (((-1+F(2+3))^{F(4)}) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2241 &:= ((F(F((-1+F(2 \times 3)))) \times (4+5)) + (6 \times (7+8+9))) \\
2242 &:= ((F((-1+F(F(2 \times 3))))/F(4)) + ((5+6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2243 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (F(F(4)) \times (5 - (F(6) \times (7+8+9))))) \\
2244 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4+5) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2245 &:= (F((-1+F(2 \times 3))) + ((4+F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2246 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) - (F((4 \times 5))/F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2247 &:= ((F((-1+F(F(2 \times 3))))/F(4)) - F((5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2248 &:= (-1 + (((F(2+3))^{F(F(4))}) \times F(5+6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2249 &:= (-1 + ((2+F(3+4)) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2250 &:= ((-1 - F((F(2 \times 3) + F(4)))) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2251 &:= (((-1+F(2 \times 3))^4) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2252 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) + ((4+F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2253 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3) + (F(4) + F(5+6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2254 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3) + (F(4) + F(5+6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2255 &:= (F((-1+F(F(2 \times 3))))/F((F(4+5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2256 &:= ((F(F((-1 \times (2-3-4)))) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9)) \\
2257 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3) + (F(4) + F(5+6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2258 &:= (F((-1+F(2+3))) - (F((4 \times 5))/F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2259 &:= (-1 + ((F(2+3) \times 4) \times (F(5+6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2260 &:= ((-1 + F((F(F(2 \times 3)) + F(4)))) \times (F(5+6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2261 &:= ((F(F(F((-1+2 \times 3))))^{F(4)}) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2262 &:= ((F((-1+F(2 \times 3)))^{F(4)}) + (F(5+6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2263 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3+4}) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2264 &:= (((-1+2 - F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 - F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2265 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3+4) \times F(5+6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2266 &:= ((F((-1+F(F(2 \times 3))))/F(4)) - ((5+F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2267 &:= ((-1 + ((F((2 \times (3+4))) + 5) \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2268 &:= ((F((-1+F(F(2 \times 3))))/F(4)) - ((5+6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2269 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(F(3+4)) \times 5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2270 &:= ((F((-1+F(F(2 \times 3))))/F(4)) - (5 \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2271 &:= (-1 + ((2 - F(3+4+5)) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2272 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times F(3+4+5))) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2233 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) - F(F(7)))) \times (6 - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
2234 &:= (((-9 - (F(8) - F(F(7)))) \times F(6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2235 &:= (9 + (F(8) + (7 \times (F(F(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2236 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) + F(7))) \times (F(6) - (5 + F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2237 &:= (9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) - (6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2238 &:= (-9 - (F(8) \times (F(7) - (F(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2239 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (F(7) \times 6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2240 &:= ((-9 + F((F(F(8)/7) + 6 + 5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
2241 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) - (F(F(7)) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2242 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) + F(F(7)))) + ((6+5) - F(4+3+2+1))) \\
2243 &:= (((-9 - (F(8) - F(F(7)))) \times (6+5)) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2244 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2245 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (F(7) - (F((F(6)+5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2246 &:= (-9 + (((8+7) + (F(F(6)) + 5)) \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\
2247 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(F(7))) \times 6) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2248 &:= (F(-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + (5 \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2249 &:= (9 - (8 \times 7 \times (F(6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
2250 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) + 6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2251 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) + 6 + 5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2252 &:= ((-9 + F((F(8) - (7 - 6))))/((5+4) - (3+2+1))) \\
2253 &:= (-9 + (F((F(8) - 7)) \times (F(F(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2254 &:= (-9 + ((F((F(8) - 7)) \times 6) + ((5+4) - F(3+2+1)))) \\
2255 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(7+6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2256 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) \times F(7))) \times (F((F(6) - 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2257 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(F(7))) \times 6) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2258 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + 6)) - F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2259 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 - F((F(6) + 5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2260 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - (7 - F(6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
2261 &:= (9 + 8) \times (F(7) + (F(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2262 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2263 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(7+6) - 5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2264 &:= (F(-9 + 8 + 7) \times (F(6) + (5 \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2265 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(7) - 6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2266 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) - F(5+4-3-2-1)) \\
2267 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) - 7) \times F(F(6))) - F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2268 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7) \times (6 + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2269 &:= (((9 \times 8 + 7) \times F(F(6))) + F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2270 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (F(F(7)) + 6 + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
2271 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((F(7) + 6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2272 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) + (F(6) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2273 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3)^4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2274 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (((F(3) - F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2275 &:= ((-1 + 2 + F(3 \times F(4))) \times (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2276 &:= ((F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))))/F(4) + F(F((5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
2277 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 \times (F(4)^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2278 &:= (((-F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - F(4))/(5 - F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2279 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) + F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2280 &:= (((F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))^4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2281 &:= (1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) + F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2282 &:= ((F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))))/F(4) - (5 - (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2283 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2284 &:= (-1 - 2 - (F(F(3 + 4)) - (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2285 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) \times F((F(4) + 5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2286 &:= ((F((-1 + ((2 \times 3) + 4 + 5))) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2287 &:= (1 + (((2 \times 3) \times F((F(4) + (5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2288 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 - (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2289 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (F(3 + 4) \times F(5 + 6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2290 &:= ((F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))))/F(4) + (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2291 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (F(F(4)) + ((5 - F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2292 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) \times (F(F(4)) + ((5 - F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2293 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(F(3 + 4)) \times 5) + (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2294 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F(4))) \times (5 + (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2295 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times F(F(3 + 4)))) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2296 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times F((F(4) \times 5))) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2297 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) - ((F(4) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2298 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(F(3)^4) - (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2299 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3 + 4)) \times 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2300 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) \times (F(F(4)) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2301 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((3 + 4) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2302 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((3 + 4) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2303 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(F(2 + 3))) + (F(F(4)) + F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2304 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2305 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((3 + 4) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2306 &:= (((-1 - 2 + F(3 + 4)) \times F((5 + F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2307 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times F(F(3 + 4)))) \times 5) + (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2308 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) \times ((F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7)) - F(8 + 9))) \\
2309 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4) - (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2310 &:= ((1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2311 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (F(F(3 + 4)) \times 5)) + (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2312 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3 + 4)) \times (F((5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2273 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7) \times F(F(6)))))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2274 &:= ((9 \times (8 + F(F(7)))) - (F(F(6)) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
2275 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) + F(F(7)))) - (6 - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
2276 &:= (((-9 \times F(8 + 7)) + (6^5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2277 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) + F(F(7))) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2278 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) + F((F(6) - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2279 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(7 + 6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2280 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) + F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2281 &:= (9 - 8 + ((F(7 + 6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2282 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) + (F(F(7)) - 6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2283 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7) \times F(F(6)))))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2284 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times 7) + (F(6) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2285 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) + F(F(7)))) - ((6 + 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2286 &:= ((9 \times F(8)) - (F(F(7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2287 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) - ((6 - 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2288 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times F(F(6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2289 &:= ((9 \times (8 + F(F(7)))) + (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2290 &:= (((-9 - F(8)) \times (F(7) - F(6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2291 &:= (-9 + (((8 + F(F(7))) - (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2292 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + ((F(7 + 6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2293 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) - F((F(6) - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2294 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) - 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2295 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) - F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2296 &:= ((-9 \times F(8 + 7)) + ((6^5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2297 &:= (9 + 8 + ((F(7 + 6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2298 &:= (9 + (F(8) \times ((F(7) \times F(6)) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
2299 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) - (F(6) - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2300 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(7 + 6))) + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2301 &:= (-9 + ((8 + F(7)) \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2302 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) \times F(7)) - F((6 \times ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2303 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) - (6 - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2304 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2305 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + (6 \times 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2306 &:= ((-9 - 8 - 7) + (F((F(6) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2307 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (7 + (F((F(6) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2308 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(7 + 6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2309 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) + F(F(7)))) + (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2310 &:= ((-9 - F(8)) \times (F(7) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2311 &:= (-9 - ((8 - 7 - F((F(6) + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2312 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(F(7))) \times 6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2313 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (F(F(3+4)) \times 5)) + (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2314 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4+5) + (6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2315 &:= (-1 + (((F((2 \times (3+4))) + 5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2316 &:= (((F((-1 + 2 + F(3+4))) + 5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2317 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times ((F(F(3+4)) \times 5) + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2318 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) \times (4+5)) + ((6+7) \times (8+9))) \\
2319 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2320 &:= ((-1 + F(2+3)) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2321 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) - ((F(F(4)) - F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2322 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times F(F(3+4)))) \times 5) + (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2323 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(F(3+4)) \times 5) + (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2324 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times ((4 \times F(5+6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2325 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3+F(4)) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2326 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3+F(4)) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2327 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2+3)) + (F(4) + F(5+6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2328 &:= (((-1 + (2 + (3+4))) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9)) \\
2329 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3+F(4)) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2330 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) - (F(5+6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2331 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) - (F(5+6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2332 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3+4)) \times 5)) - (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2333 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times ((4^5) + (6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2334 &:= ((1+2) \times ((F(3) \times F((F(4) + (5+6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2335 &:= (-1 - ((2 + F(3+4+5)) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2336 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3))^4) - (F(5+6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2337 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (F(3+4) \times F(5+6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2338 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) \times F(5+6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2339 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (F((F(F(4)) + 5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2340 &:= (((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times 4) - 5) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
2341 &:= (((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^{F(4)})) \times (5+6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2342 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))))^{4+5}) + (F((6+7) + F(8+9)))) \\
2343 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times (F((4+5+6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2344 &:= ((-1 + F(2+3)) \times (F((4+5+6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2345 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times F(3 \times F(4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2346 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))^{F(4)} + (5 + (6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2347 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))^{F(4)} + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2348 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) \times (F(F(4)) \times 5)) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2349 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (F(4) - ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2350 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((3 \times F(4)) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2351 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (3+4)) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2352 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3 + 4 + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2313 &:= (-9 - (((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times (6+5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2314 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2315 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times F(7)) - F(F(6))) \times (F(5+4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
2316 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (7 \times F(F(6)))) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2317 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (F(7) - (F((F(6) + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2318 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2319 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) \times (6+5)) - F(4+3+2+1))) \\
2320 &:= ((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times ((6-5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2321 &:= (((-9 - 8 + F(F(7))) \times (6+5)) - F(4+3+2+1)) \\
2322 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7) + (F((F(6) + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2323 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (F((F(6) + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2324 &:= (-9 + ((F(8)/7) + (F((F(6) + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2325 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) - 6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2326 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F(7) + (F((F(6) + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2327 &:= ((-9/(F(8)/7) + (F((F(6) + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2328 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 + F((F(6) + 5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2329 &:= (9 - ((8 - 7 - F((F(6) + 5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2330 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) + F(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
2331 &:= (-9 \times (8 \times 7 - (F(F(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2332 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + ((F(F(7)) - (6-5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2333 &:= (-9 - (((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times (6+5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2334 &:= (((-9 + F((F(8) - 7))) \times F(6)) - F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2335 &:= (((-9 - F(8)) \times (F(7) - F(6+5))) + F(4+3+2+1)) \\
2336 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + (F((F(6) + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2337 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) \times 7)) + (6 \times F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2338 &:= (((-9 - 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2339 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) + (6-5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2340 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times ((7+6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2341 &:= ((-9 \times F(8+7)) + ((6^5) + F(4+3+2+1))) \\
2342 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F(7) + (F((F(6) + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2343 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7) + (F(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
2344 &:= (9 - 8 + (F(7) + (F((F(6) + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2345 &:= (((9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) \times 6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2346 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) \times (6 + (5+4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2347 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7)) \times (6 + (5+4))) - F(3+2+1)) \\
2348 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(7) + (6 \times 5)) \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\
2349 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + (F(F(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2350 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - ((F(7+6) + 5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2351 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times 7 + F(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2352 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + ((F(F(7)) + (6-5)) \times (4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2353 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((3 \times F(4)) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2354 &:= (((-1 - 2 + F(3 + 4)) \times F((5 + F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2355 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times F(F(3 + 4)))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2356 &:= (((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3))^{F(4)})) / 5) + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2357 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times F(F(3 + 4)))) \times 5) + (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2358 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (F(F(4)) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2359 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (F(F(3 + 4)) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2360 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) \times (F(F(4)) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2361 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3 + 4) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2362 &:= (-1 - ((F(F(2 \times 3)) - 4) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2363 &:= ((-1 - (F(2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2364 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times (4 \times (5 + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2365 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) - (4 - (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2366 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3))^4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2367 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(F(3 + 4)) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2368 &:= (1 - 2 + (F(F(3 + 4)) + (F((5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2369 &:= (-1 + (((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times 4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2370 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times (4 \times 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2371 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + (F(F(4)) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2372 &:= (-1 + (F((F(F(2 + 3)) + F(4))) \times (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2373 &:= (F((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4)))) \times (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2374 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4))) \times (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2375 &:= (1 - 2 + (3 \times (F(4) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2376 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3))^4) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2377 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (F(4) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2378 &:= ((-1 + ((F(2 + F(3))^{F(4)} \times F(5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2379 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3 \times F(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2380 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((3^{F(4)} \times F(5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2381 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3)^4) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2382 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (F(3) + (F(4) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2383 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times (4 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2384 &:= (((-1 + F((2 \times (3 + 4)))) \times 5) + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2385 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 + 5)))) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2386 &:= (1 \times 2 \times (F(F(3 + 4)) + (5 \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2387 &:= (1 + (2 \times (F(F(3 + 4)) + (5 \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2388 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3))^4) + ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2389 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(F(3 + 4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2390 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + F((F(3) \times (4 + 5)))) - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2391 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3) \times F((4 + 5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2392 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3))^4) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2353 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (7 \times (F(F(6)) - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2354 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + 6))) + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2355 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + (7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2356 &:= ((-9 - 8 + F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2357 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(7) + (F(6) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2358 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7 + 6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2359 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) - 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2360 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + F(7)) \times (F(6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
2361 &:= (9 + (F(8) \times (F(7) + (F(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2362 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + ((F(F(7)) + F((F(6) - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2363 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(7 + 6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2364 &:= (-9 - (F(8) \times (7 - (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2365 &:= (((9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times (6 + 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2366 &:= (((-9 - 8 + F(F(7))) \times (6 + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2367 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) + F(F(7)))) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2368 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2369 &:= (9 + ((F(8) \times 7 + F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2370 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - (7 - F(F(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2371 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) + F(F(7)))) + ((6 \times 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2372 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2373 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + (6 \times (5 + 4)))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2374 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times F(F(6)))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2375 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) + (F(F(7)) + 6 + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2376 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - ((F(7) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2377 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + ((F(7) + (6 \times 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2378 &:= (-9 - (((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times (6 + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2379 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(7 + 6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2380 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((F(7 + 6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2381 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - (6 \times 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2382 &:= (9 - (F(8) \times (7 - (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2383 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(7) \times (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2384 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2385 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (F(7) \times (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2386 &:= (((-9 - 8 + F(F(7))) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2387 &:= 9 \times (F(8) \times F(7) - F(6)) + F(5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2388 &:= (((9 + (8 \times F(7))) \times F(F(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2389 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) \times F(6)) + (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2390 &:= ((9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) - (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2391 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) \times F(7))) - ((6 + 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2392 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + ((F(7 + 6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2393 &:= ((-1 + 2 + F((F(3) \times (4 + 5)))) - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2394 &:= (((1 + 2) \times 3) \times (F(F(4)) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2395 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((F(F(3 + 4)) \times 5) + F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2396 &:= (-1 + (F(((2 \times 3) \times F(4))) + (5 - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2397 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3)^4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2398 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3)^4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2399 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2400 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2401 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3))^{F(4+5)-6-7-8-9}) \\
2402 &:= (-1 - (F((F(2 \times 3) + F(4))) \times (5 - (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2403 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3) \times F((F(4) \times 5))) + (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
2404 &:= ((F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))))/F(4)) + (5 + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2405 &:= ((F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))))/F(4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2406 &:= (((F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2407 &:= (1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (F((F(4) + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2408 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times F((F(4) \times 5))) - (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2409 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times F((F(4) \times 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2410 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times F((F(4) \times 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2411 &:= (((-1 + (F(2 \times 3)^{F(4)})) \times 5) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2412 &:= ((-1 - ((2^{3+4}) + 5)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2413 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (F(3) \times (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7)))) \times (8 + 9))) \\
2414 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3))^4) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2415 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times F((4 + 5 + 6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2416 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times F((4 + 5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2417 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + ((F(F(4)) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2418 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) - ((4 - (5 \times F(F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2419 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(F(3 + 4)) \times 5) + (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2420 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4) - (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2421 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 \times 4 + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2422 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times 4 + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2423 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times F((3 \times 4))) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2424 &:= ((((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times F(4)) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2425 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times 4 + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2426 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3))^4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2427 &:= (((F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))^{F(4)})) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2428 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((3^{F(4)}) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2429 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 \times (4 + 5))) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2430 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((F(3)^4) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2431 &:= (1 + ((2 \times (3 \times (4 + 5))) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2393 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (F(6) \times 5)))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2394 &:= (-9 \times (((8 + 7) - 6) - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2395 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + F((7 + 6 - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
2396 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) - (F(6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2397 &:= ((-9 + (F((F(8) - 7)) \times F(6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2398 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (7 \times (F(F(6)) - 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2399 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 + F((F(6) + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2400 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(7) \times F(F(6)))))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2401 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (F(F(7)) - F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2402 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2403 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - ((F(7) \times F(F(6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2404 &:= ((-9 + F(8 + 7)) \times ((F(6) \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2405 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + (F((7 + 6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2406 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) + F(F(7)))) + (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2407 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (F(7) - (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2408 &:= ((-9 - 8 + F(7)) \times (F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2409 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) \times (6 + (5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2410 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - ((F(F(7)) + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2411 &:= (-9 - (((8 - F(F(7))) \times (6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2412 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (F(6) + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2413 &:= -9 + F(8) + 7^{5 \times F(6) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)} \\
2414 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times F(F(6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2415 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + F(7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2416 &:= ((-9 - 8 + F(7)) \times (6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2417 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (F(F(7)) - 6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2418 &:= ((9 \times ((F(8) \times F(7)) - 6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2419 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (F(7) \times (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4)))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2420 &:= (9 + 8 - F(7)) \times (6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2421 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) - ((6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2422 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - F(7)) \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2423 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) \times F(7))) + (F(6) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2424 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + ((F(7 + 6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2425 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) + (F(6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2426 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - (6 \times 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2427 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times ((7 \times F(6)) + (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2428 &:= ((-9 + ((F(8) + 7) \times F(6 + 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2429 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2430 &:= (-9 \times (((F(8)/7) - F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2431 &:= (-9 - ((F(F(8)/7) - 6) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2432 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F(3+4) \times (5 - (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2433 &:= ((-1 + F(((2 \times 3) \times F(4)))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2434 &:= (F((-1 - 2 + F(F(3+F(4)))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2435 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4) + (F(5+6) + 7+8+9)))) \\
2436 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3))^4) + (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2437 &:= ((-1 - 2 + F((F(3) \times (4+5)))) - (6 \times (7+8+9))) \\
2438 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + F((F(3) \times (4+5)))) - (6 \times (7+8+9))) \\
2439 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times F((F(F(4)) - ((5+6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
2440 &:= ((-1 + F(2+3)) \times F((F(F(4)) - ((5+6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2441 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + ((F(4) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2442 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) - (F(5+6) + 7+8+9))) \\
2443 &:= (((-1 + F(2+3)) \times F((F(4) \times 5))) - (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2444 &:= ((1 - F(2+3)) - ((F(4) - (5 \times F(F(6)))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2445 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3+4) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2446 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3+4) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2447 &:= (1 - 2 + ((F(3+4) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2448 &:= ((F((-1+2) \times (3+4))) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9) \\
2449 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3+4) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2450 &:= (1 \times 2 + ((F(3+4) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2451 &:= (1 + 2 + ((F(3+4) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2452 &:= ((-1 + F(2+3)) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2453 &:= (-1 + (((F(2+F(3)))^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7+8+9) \\
2454 &:= (((F((-1 + F(2+3)))^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7+8+9) \\
2455 &:= (1 + (((F(2+F(3)))^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7+8+9) \\
2456 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 + (F(5+6) + 7+8+9)))) \\
2457 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times F((F(4) \times 5)))) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2458 &:= (((-1 + F(2+3)) \times F((F(4) \times 5))) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2459 &:= (-1 + ((2 + ((F(3)^4) \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2460 &:= ((1 \times 2 + ((F(3)^4) \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
2461 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))^{F(4)}) + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2462 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) + F((6+7)))) + F(8+9))) \\
2463 &:= (-1 + (((2 + F(3)) \times F((4+5+6))) + 7+8+9) \\
2464 &:= (((-1 + F(2+3)) \times F((4+5+6))) + 7+8+9) \\
2465 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + ((4 + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2466 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3))^4) + (F(5+6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2467 &:= ((-1 \times F(2+3)) - ((F(F(4)) - (5 \times F(F(6)))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2468 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (3^{F(4)})) \times F(5+6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2469 &:= (-1 + (((2 + F(3)) \times F((F(4) \times 5))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
2470 &:= (((-1 + F(2+3)) \times F((F(4) \times 5))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
2471 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times (3+4)) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2432 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) \times F(7))) + ((6 \times 5) - F(4+3+2+1))) \\
2433 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - (F(6) \times F(5+4)))) - (3+2+1)) \\
2434 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (F(7) \times (F(F(6)) \times (5+4)))) - (3+2+1)) \\
2435 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2436 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (F(F(7)) \times (6+5))) - F(4+3+2+1)) \\
2437 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (F(F(7)) + (F(6) \times (5+4)))) + 3+2+1)) \\
2438 &:= (9+8) \times (F(F(7)) - F(6+5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2439 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) + 6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2440 &:= ((-9 + F(((8+7) - F(6)))) \times F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2441 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) + (7 + F(F(6)))) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2442 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times F(F(7)))) / F((F(6) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
2443 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(7) + F((F(6) + 5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2444 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times F(F(7)))) - (F(F(6)) - F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2445 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(7) + 6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2446 &:= ((9 \times ((F(8) + F(7)) \times 6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2447 &:= ((9 \times ((F(8) \times (7+6)) + 5)) - F(4+3+2+1)) \\
2448 &:= (-9 - (F(8) \times (F(7) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2449 &:= (9 - ((F(F(8)/7) - 6) \times F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2450 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + (F((7+6+5)) + F(4+3+2+1))) \\
2451 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (F(7+6) + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2452 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + ((F(F(7)) + 6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2453 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times ((F(7) \times F(F(6))) + F(5+4))) + 3+2+1)) \\
2454 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) \times F(7))) - (F(6) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
2455 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (F(F(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2456 &:= (-9 - (((8 - F(F(7))) \times (6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
2457 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times F(6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2458 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) \times F(7))) + ((6+5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2459 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times F(F(7)))) - (6 - F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2460 &:= ((9+8 + (7 \times F(F(6)))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2461 &:= (9 - 8 + ((F(7) + F((F(6) + 5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2462 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(7) \times (F(F(6)) \times (5+4))) + 3+2+1)) \\
2463 &:= ((9 \times 8 \times (F(7) + F(F(6)))) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2464 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) - 6))) + F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2465 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times F(7+6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2466 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2467 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) - (7 - (F((F(6) + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2468 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (7 \times F(F(6)))) - F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2469 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7) - (F(F(6)) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
2470 &:= (((-9 - F(8)) \times (7 - F(6+5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2471 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times F(F(7))) + (6 + F(5+4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2472 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F(3 + 4) + F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2473 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (F(F(3 + 4)) \times 5)) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2474 &:= (-1 - (F(F(F(2 + 3))) \times (4 + 5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2475 &:= (F((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4 + 5)))) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2476 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) - ((F(F(4)) - (5 \times F(F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2477 &:= (1 \times F(2 + 3) - ((F(F(4)) - (5 \times F(F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2478 &:= (1 + F(2 + 3) - ((F(F(4)) - (5 \times F(F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2479 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3))^{F(4)} + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2480 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) \times (F(4) + (5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2481 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times ((4 + 5) \times F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2482 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) + (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2483 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (4 - 5 + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2484 &:= ((1 - F(2 + 3)) \times (F(4) - ((5 + F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2485 &:= (-1 - (F((2 + (3 + 4)) - (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2486 &:= ((-1 + 2 + F(F(3 + F(4)))) \times (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2487 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3) \times F((4 + 5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2488 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2489 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) + (F((F(F(4)) + 5)) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2490 &:= ((1 + 2 + ((F(3)^4) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2491 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) + (F((F(F(4)) + 5)) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2492 &:= (-1 - 2 - (F((3 + F(F(4)))) \times (5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2493 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(F(4)) \times (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2494 &:= (-1 + ((2 - 3 - 4) \times (5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2495 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (F(3 + 4) + F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2496 &:= (((F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3)))) \times F(4)) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2497 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((3 - 4) + (5 \times F(F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2498 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + (F((F(F(4)) + 5)) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2499 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3) \times F((F(4) \times 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2500 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + (F((F(F(4)) + 5)) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2501 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3)^4) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2502 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) \times (F(4) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2503 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((F((3 \times 4)) - 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2504 &:= (-1 - 2 - (F(3 + 4) - (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2505 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 + 4))) + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2506 &:= (((-1 - 2 + F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2507 &:= -F((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) + 5 \times F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2508 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F(3 + 4) - (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2509 &:= ((1 \times 2 - F(3 + 4)) + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2510 &:= ((-1 - (2 + (3 + 4))) + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2472 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) \times (7 + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2473 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2474 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) - (F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2475 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) + F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2476 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) - (6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2477 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) + ((6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2478 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - ((F(F(7)) \times (6 + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2479 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (F(7) + (F(F(6)) \times 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2480 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) \times F(7))) + (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2481 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) - (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2482 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2483 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) + 7) \times F((6 - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
2484 &:= (((9 + 8) \times 7) \times F(F(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2485 &:= 9 \times (F(8) \times F(7) - F(6) + 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2486 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times F(F(7))) + (F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2487 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) + (F(6 + 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
2488 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) + (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2489 &:= (9 + ((8 \times F(F(7))) + (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2490 &:= ((-9 - F(8)) \times (7 - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2491 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (F(F(7)) \times (6 + 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2492 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (F(F(7)) \times 6)) / 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2493 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((F(7) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2494 &:= ((9 - ((8 - F(F(7))) \times (6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2495 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(7) + (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2496 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) \times (F(F(6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
2497 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) \times F(7))) - (F(6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
2498 &:= ((9 \times 8 \times (F(7) + F(F(6)))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2499 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (F((7 + 6 + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2500 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (F(F(7)) + F(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2501 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2502 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7) \times (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2503 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (F(F(7)) - F(6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2504 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) + (F(6) - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2505 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (F(F(7)) + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2506 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + ((7^{F(F(6)-5)}) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2507 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) \times (6 + 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2508 &:= (9 + (F(8) \times ((F(7) \times F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2509 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + ((F(7) + (6 \times 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2510 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) - (F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2511 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + (3 + 4))) + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2512 &:= (-1 + (F((2 \times (3 + 4))) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2513 &:= (F((-1 + 2 + F(3 + 4))) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2514 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3))^4) + (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2515 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) - (F(4) - (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2516 &:= (-1 - (((2 - F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2517 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2518 &:= ((-1 + F(((2 \times 3) \times F(4)))) - (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2519 &:= (-1 + ((F((F(2 \times 3) + F(4))) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2520 &:= ((F((-1 \times 2 + F(3 + 4))) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2521 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((F(3)^4) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2522 &:= (F(F((-1 - (2 - 3 - 4)))) + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2523 &:= (F((-1 - (2 - 3 - 4))) + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2524 &:= ((-1 - (2 - 3 - 4)) + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2525 &:= (((-1 + (F(2 \times 3)^{F(4)})) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2526 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + (4 + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2527 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2528 &:= (((-1 + F(F((F(2 + 3) + F(F(4)))))) \times (5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2529 &:= ((-1 + ((F(2 \times 3)^{F(4)} \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2530 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3 + 4) + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2531 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3 + 4) + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2532 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times F(4)) + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2533 &:= (F(((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2534 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3 + 4) + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2535 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times (F((4 + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2536 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (F((4 + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2537 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (F(F(3 + 4)) \times (5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2538 &:= ((-1 + (F(F((F(2 + 3) + F(F(4)))))) \times (5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2539 &:= ((F(F((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) \times (5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2540 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F(F(3 + 4)) \times (5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2541 &:= (F((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4)))) + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2542 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4))) + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2543 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) - (4 - F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2544 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((F(3)^4) + F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2545 &:= (F(F(F(F(F((-1 \times (2 - 3 - 4)))))) \times (5 + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2546 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F((3 + F(F(4)))) \times (5 + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2547 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))^{F(4)} + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2548 &:= ((-1 + F(((2 \times 3) \times F(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2549 &:= (F((-1 - 2 + F(F(3 + F(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2550 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F(3)^4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2511 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) + 7) \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2512 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) - (6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2513 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (F(F(7)) + 6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2514 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (7 - (F(6) + F(5 + 4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2515 &:= (((-9 - F(8)) \times (7 - F(6 + 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2516 &:= (-9 - 8) \times ((F(7) \times (F(F(6)) - F(5 + 4))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2517 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) - ((7 + 6) \times F(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2518 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(7 + 6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2519 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 \times 6) \times (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2520 &:= (F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) \times (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2521 &:= (-9 - (((8 - F(F(7))) \times (6 + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2522 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (F((7 + 6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2523 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - ((F(F(7)) \times (6 + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
2524 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) + (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2525 &:= ((-9 + F(((F(8)/7) \times 6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2526 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) + (F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2527 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6 + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2528 &:= ((-9 + 8 + F((7 + 6 + 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2529 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (F(F(7)) + F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2530 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) + (F(7) - F(6 + 5)))) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2531 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) + F(F(7))) \times ((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2532 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2533 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (F(F(7)) \times (6 - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
2534 &:= (F((F((-9 + 8 + F(7)))/F(6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2535 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (F(F(7)) + F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2536 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (F(F(7)) \times (6 + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2537 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + 6 + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2538 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) \times F(7))) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2539 &:= ((9 - ((8 - F(F(7))) \times (6 + 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2540 &:= (((9 \times F(8)) + ((7 + 6) \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2541 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + (F((7 + 6 + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2542 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times (6 + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2543 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - ((F(F(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2544 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2545 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + (7^{F(6) \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)})) \\
2546 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2547 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + (F(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2548 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (F(7) \times (F(6) - (F(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2549 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6)))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2550 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - F(7)) \times (6 \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2551 &:= ((-1 - 2 + F((F(3) \times (4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2552 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + F((F(3) \times (4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2553 &:= ((-1 + F((F(F(2 + F(3))) \times (4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2554 &:= (F((F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times (4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2555 &:= ((-1 + 2 + F((F(3) \times (4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2556 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + (3^{F(4)})) \times F(5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2557 &:= ((-1 - 2 + F((3 + (4 + 5 + 6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2558 &:= (-1 + (F(((2 \times 3) \times F(4))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2559 &:= (F((-1 - 2 + F(F(3 + F(4)))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2560 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2561 &:= ((-1 + 2 + F((3 + (4 + 5 + 6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2562 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) - F((F(4 + 5) + (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
2563 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F((F(3) \times (4 + 5))) + (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2564 &:= (-1 - (((2 - F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2565 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2566 &:= (F((F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times (4 + 5))) + (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2567 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) - (F(4) - F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2568 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4))) + F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2569 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F((F(3) \times (4 + 5))) + (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2570 &:= (-1 + (F(((2 \times 3) \times F(4))) + ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2571 &:= (F((-1 - 2 + F(F(3 + F(4)))) + ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2572 &:= (((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + F(4)) \times (5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2573 &:= (((-1 + (F(2 \times 3)^{F(4)})) \times 5) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2574 &:= ((-1 + 2 - F(3 + 4 + 5)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2575 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + F((F(4 + 5) + (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
2576 &:= (((-1 + F(F((F(2 + 3) + F(F(4)))))) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2577 &:= (1 \times ((F(F(2 \times 3))^{F(F(4))}) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2578 &:= (1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3))^{F(F(4))}) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2579 &:= (-1 + (((F(2 + F(3))^4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2580 &:= ((-1 - 2 + F((F(3) + 4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2581 &:= (1 + (((F(2 + F(3))^4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2582 &:= (-1 \times 2 + F((3 - ((F(4) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2583 &:= (-1 + F(((2 \times (3 - (4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2584 &:= F((-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) - (4 + (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2585 &:= (-1 + 2 + F((3 - ((F(4) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2586 &:= (-1 + ((F(F((F(2 + 3) + F(F(4)))))) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2587 &:= ((F(F((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)))) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2588 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(F(3 + 4)) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2589 &:= (-1 + (((F(2 \times 3)^{F(4)} \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2590 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3 + 4 + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2551 &:= (9 - F(8) + (F(F(7)) \times (6 - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
2552 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) \times (6 + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2553 &:= (-9 - (F(8) \times (F((7 + F(6)) / (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
2554 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - F((7 + 6 - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
2555 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - ((7 \times 6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2556 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2557 &:= ((-9 - 8 + F((7 + 6 + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2558 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) + (6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2559 &:= (9 + (F(8) + (F((7 + 6 + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2560 &:= ((-9 + F(((F(8) / 7) \times 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2561 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + 7) \times F(F(6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2562 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2563 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) - F(6)))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2564 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (F((7 + 6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2565 &:= (-9 \times ((F(F(8) / 7) - F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2566 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) - 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2567 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2568 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 \times 6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2569 &:= (F((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) / F(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2570 &:= (9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times (6 + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2571 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (F(7) - F((6 \times ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2572 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + 6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2573 &:= ((-9 + 8 + F((7 + 6 + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2574 &:= (F((-9 \times 8 / (7 - (6 + 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2575 &:= (-9 + F((F(8) - F((F(7) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2576 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
2577 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F((7 + 6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2578 &:= (F((F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) + (6 - 5 - 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2579 &:= (F((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) / F(6))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2580 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + (7 + F(F(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2581 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) - 6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2582 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + 6 + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2583 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) + (7 - (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2584 &:= F(((9 / (F(8) / 7)) + (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2585 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) - (7 \times (6 + 5)))) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2586 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + (F((7 + 6 + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
2587 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + F(F(7))) \times (6 + 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2588 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - ((F(F(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2589 &:= (F((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) / F(6))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2590 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + F(6)))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2591 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) - (F(F(4)) - F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\2592 &:= (((-1 + (F(2 + 3) \times 4)) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\2593 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F(3 + 4 + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\2594 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + ((F(4) + (5 \times F(F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\2595 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\2596 &:= ((-1 + F(((2 \times 3) \times F(4)))) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\2597 &:= (F((-1 - 2 + F(F(3 + F(4)))) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\2598 &:= (((-1 + 2 + F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\2599 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\2600 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) \times (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\2601 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times F(F(3 + 4))) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\2602 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) \times F(F(4))) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\2603 &:= ((-1 + 2 + F((F(3) \times (4 + 5)))) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\2604 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (3^{F(4)})) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\2605 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F((3 + (4 + 5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\2606 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F((3 + (4 + 5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\2607 &:= (-1 + (F((F(2 + F(3)) + (4 + 5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\2608 &:= ((-1 + F(((2 \times 3) \times F(4)))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\2609 &:= (-1 - ((2 - F((F(3) + 4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\2610 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + F((F(3) + 4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\2611 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F((F(3) \times (4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\2612 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F((F(3) \times (4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\2613 &:= (-1 + (F((F(F(2 + F(3))) \times (4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\2614 &:= (F((F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times (4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\2615 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F((F(3) \times (4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\2616 &:= ((-1 + (F((F(2 + 3) + F(4)) + F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\2617 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F((F(3) \times (4 + 5))) + (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\2618 &:= (-1 + (F(((2 \times 3) \times F(4))) + (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\2619 &:= (F((-1 - 2 + F(F(3 + F(4)))) + (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\2620 &:= (((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + F(4)) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\2621 &:= ((F(F(F((-1 \times (2 - 3 - 4))))^5) - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\2622 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((3 + F(F(4)))^5) - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\2623 &:= ((-1 + F(((2 \times 3) \times F(4)))) - (5 - (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\2624 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(F(2 + 3)))^{F(4)}) \times F(F((5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\2625 &:= ((F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3)))^{F(4)}) \times F(F((5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\2626 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times ((F(F(4)) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\2627 &:= (-1 - ((2 + F(3 + 4 + 5)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\2628 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - F(3 + 4 + 5)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\2629 &:= (F((F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times (4 + 5))) + (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\2630 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F((F(3) \times (4 + 5))) + (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \end{aligned}$$
$$\begin{aligned}2591 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (F(7) \times ((6 \times 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\2592 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + 6 - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\2593 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F((7 + 6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\2594 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) + F(F(7)))) + (F(6) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\2595 &:= (9 - 8 + (F((7 + 6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\2596 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + F(7)) \times ((6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\2597 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + ((7 \times 6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\2598 &:= ((-9 + (F(((8 + 7) - F(6))) \times F(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\2599 &:= (F((F((-9 + 8 + F(7)))/F(6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\2600 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (F(6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\2601 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\2602 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + 6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\2603 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + (7 + F((6 \times ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\2604 &:= (9 + (F(8) + (F((7 + 6 + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\2605 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\2606 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + (F((7 + 6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\2607 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times (6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\2608 &:= (9 + (F(((F(8)/7) \times 6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\2609 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (F((7 + 6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\2610 &:= (((9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\2611 &:= (-9 + (((F(8) \times F(7)) - (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\2612 &:= (F((F((-9 + 8 + F(7)))/F(6))) + (F(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\2613 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) + (6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\2614 &:= (9 + (F(8) + F((7 + 6 - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))))) \\2615 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(7) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\2616 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7 + 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\2617 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\2618 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((F(F(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\2619 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (F(7) \times (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\2620 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) + (6 \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\2621 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) + (6 \times F(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\2622 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F((7 + 6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\2623 &:= (9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) + (6 \times F(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\2624 &:= (9 + (F(8) + (F((7 + 6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\2625 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - F(F(6))) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\2626 &:= ((9 \times 8 \times (7 + F(F(6)))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\2627 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) - (F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\2628 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7) + (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\2629 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) - (6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\2630 &:= (-9 - (F((F(8) - 7)) \times (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2631 &:= (((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + 4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2632 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times F((F(4) \times 5))) + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2633 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - ((F(4 + 5) + F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2634 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - ((F(4 + 5) + F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2635 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F(3) - ((F(4 + 5) + F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2636 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - ((F(4 + 5) + F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2637 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(F(3 + F(4))) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2638 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(F(3 + F(4))) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2639 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2640 &:= ((-1 + F((F(F(2 + F(3))) + 4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2641 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(F(3 + F(4))) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2642 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F(F(4))) + (F(5 + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9))) \\
2643 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + ((F(4 + 5) + F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2644 &:= (1 \times 2 \times (F(3) + ((F(4 + 5) + F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2645 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + ((F(4 + 5) + F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2646 &:= ((-1 - 2 - F(3 + 4 + 5)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2647 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 \times 3)^{F(4)}) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2648 &:= (-1 + (F(((2 \times 3) \times F(4))) + (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2649 &:= (F((-1 - 2 + F(F(3 + F(4)))) + (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2650 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3^{F(4)}))) \times (5 + (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2651 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times ((F(F(4)) \times F((5 + F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2652 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((F(3) - (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \\
2653 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times 4) + (F(5 + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9)) \\
2654 &:= (-1 + (((F(2 \times 3)^{F(F(4))}) - 5) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2655 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times ((4 \times F(5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2656 &:= ((-1 - 2 + ((3^4) + 5)) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2657 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) - ((4 - (5 \times F(F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2658 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) + ((F(4) - (5 \times F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2659 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 + F(3))) \times (F(4 + 5) + (F((6 + 7)) - F(8 + 9)))) \\
2660 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times ((4 \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2661 &:= (1 - (F(F(2 + F(3))) \times (F(4 + 5) + (F((6 + 7)) - F((8 + 9)))))) \\
2662 &:= (1 \times 2 - (F(3) \times (F(4 + 5) + (F((6 + 7)) - F((8 + 9)))))) \\
2663 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times F((F(4) + 5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2664 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4))) + F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2665 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3))^4) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2666 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) - ((5 \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2667 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F((F(3) + 4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2668 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F((F(3) + 4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2669 &:= (-1 + (F((F(F(2 + F(3))) + 4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2670 &:= (F((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + 4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2631 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) \times (7 - F(F(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2632 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + F(F(7))) \times (6 + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2633 &:= (9 + (8 \times (F(7) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2634 &:= (F((F((-9 + 8 + F(7)))/F(6))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2635 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(7 + 6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2636 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) \times (F(7) + (6 - 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2637 &:= (9 \times (8 + ((F(7) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2638 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F((7 + 6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2639 &:= (F((-9 \times 8 / (7 - (6 + 5)))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2640 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - (7 + F(6 + 5))) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2641 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) + (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2642 &:= (-9 + ((8 + F(F(7))) \times (6 - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
2643 &:= (9 + (F(((F(8)/7) \times 6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2644 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((F(7) \times (6 \times F(5 + 4))) - F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2645 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 - F(F(6))) \times ((5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2646 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) \times (7 - (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2647 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + 6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2648 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) \times (7 - F(F(6)))) + F(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2649 &:= (((-9 - (F(8) - F(F(7)))) \times (F(6) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2650 &:= ((-9 + ((F(8) \times F(7)) + (6 - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2651 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + (F((7 + 6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2652 &:= (-F(-9 + F(8)) \times 7) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2653 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (F((6 + 5)) \times F(F(4)))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2654 &:= ((9 \times (8 \times (7 + (6 \times 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2655 &:= (-9 \times (((8 + 7) \times F(F(6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2656 &:= (9 + 8 + (F((7 + 6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2657 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(7) \times (6 \times F(5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2658 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (7 + (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2659 &:= (9 + ((F(8) + (F(F(7)) + 6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2660 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (F(7) \times (F(F(6)) + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2661 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) \times (7 - F(F(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2662 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - (6 + 5))) + (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2663 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((F(7) \times F(F(6))) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2664 &:= (-9 \times 8 \times ((7 + 6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2665 &:= ((-9 - F(8)) + ((7^{F(F(6)-5)}) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2666 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2667 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + F(7 + 6)) - F(5 + 4)) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2668 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times 7) + F((6 \times ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2669 &:= (((-9 + F((F(8) - 7))) \times F(6)) - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2670 &:= ((9 + F(8)) \times ((F(7) \times F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2671 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F((F(3) + 4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2672 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - (3 \times F((F(F(4)) \times 5)))) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2673 &:= ((-1 + F((2 + (3 + 4)))) \times ((5 \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2674 &:= (F((-1 - 2 + F(F(3 + F(4)))))) - (5 \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2675 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3 + 4)) + (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
2676 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4 + 5) \times 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2677 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7))) + F(8 + 9)) \\
2678 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3^4) - ((5 \times F((6 + 7))) + F(8 + 9)))) \\
2679 &:= (1 + (2 \times (F(3) - ((4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7))) - F(8 + 9)))))) \\
2680 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((F((3 \times 4)) + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2681 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3 + 4) \times (5 \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2682 &:= (-1 \times ((F(((2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2683 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((F((3 \times 4)) + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2684 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - ((F(F(4)) + 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2685 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 + 4) \times ((5 - F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2686 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3 + 4) \times ((5 - F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2687 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) + (F(F(4)) + F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2688 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2689 &:= (1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) + (F(F(4)) + F((5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2690 &:= ((1 \times F(2 + 3)) \times (F(4 + 5) + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2691 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))^{F(F(4)+5)} + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2692 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3^{F(F(4)+5)} + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2693 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times F(F(3)^4)) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2694 &:= ((F((-1 \times 2 + F(3 + 4))) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2695 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (F(3 \times F(4)) \times (5 \times F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2696 &:= (-1 + (F(((2 \times 3) \times F(4))) + (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2697 &:= (F((-1 - 2 + F(F(3 + F(4)))))) + (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2698 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times (4 \times 5)) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2699 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (F(4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2700 &:= ((-1 + 2 + F((F(3) + 4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2701 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times (4 \times 5)) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2702 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) - ((5 - F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2703 &:= (-1 + (((F(2 \times 3)^{F(4)}) \times 5) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2704 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (F(3 \times F(4)) \times 5)) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2705 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (F(3 + 4) \times (5 \times F(F(6)))))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2706 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3 + 4)) - 5))) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2707 &:= (((-1 - (2^{F(3+4)})) / (5 - F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2708 &:= (1 - 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4))) \times ((5 \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2709 &:= (F((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4)))) \times ((5 \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2710 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4))) \times ((5 \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2671 &:= (-9 + (((F(8) \times (7 + 6)) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2672 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(7) \times (6 \times F(5 + 4))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2673 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + (F((7 + 6 + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2674 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - (6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2675 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7)) \times (F(6) + (5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2676 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) - (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2677 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) + F(7)) \times (F(6 + 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
2678 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7^{F(F(6)-5)}) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2679 &:= (9 + ((F(8)/7) \times (F(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2680 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + F((7 + F(6)))) \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2681 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7 + 6) - 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2682 &:= (-9 \times (F(F(8)/7) - (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2683 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((F(F(7)) - F(6)) \times ((5 + 4) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2684 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times F(F(7)))) - (F(6) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2685 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - F(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2686 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2687 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((F(7) \times F(F(6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2688 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2689 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + 6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2690 &:= ((-9 + ((F(8) \times (7 + 6)) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2691 &:= (-9 \times ((F(8) \times (7 - F(F(6)))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
2692 &:= (((9 - 8 + (F(7) \times 6)) \times F(5 + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2693 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) - 7) \times F(6)) + F(((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2694 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7^{F(F(6)-5)}) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2695 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) - F(6 + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2696 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) \times (7 - F(F(6)))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2697 &:= (-9 + (((8 + F(F(7))) \times (6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2698 &:= (-9 + (F((F(8) - 7)) + (F((F(6) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2699 &:= (((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + F(6 + 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2700 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2701 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) \times (F(7) + (6 - 5)))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2702 &:= (((-9 - F((F(8) - 7))) \times (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2703 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F(7) \times (F(6) \times (F(5 + 4) - F(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2704 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (F(7) \times ((F(6) - F(5 + 4)) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2705 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) + F(F(7)))) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2706 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2707 &:= ((9 \times F(F(((8 + 7) - F(6)))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2708 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (((F(7) \times F(F(6))) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2709 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (7 + (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2710 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7^{F(F(6)-5)}) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2711 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 \times 4)) \times (F(5+6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2712 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2+3))^{F(F(4))})) \times (F(5+6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2713 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(F(3+4)) \times 5) + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2714 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3+4) \times (F((5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2715 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3+4) \times (F((5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2716 &:= (1 - 2 + (F(3+4) \times (F((5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2717 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2718 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3+4) \times (F((5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2719 &:= (-1 - (F(F(F(2+3))) \times (F(4+5) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2720 &:= ((-1 \times F(2+3)) \times (F(4+5) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2721 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F(3 \times F(4)) \times (5 \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2722 &:= ((-1 + F(((2 \times 3) \times F(4)))) - (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2723 &:= (F((-1 - 2 + F(F(3 + F(4)))) - (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2724 &:= (F((-1 + F(2+3))) \times ((4 \times F((5 + F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2725 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F((F(3) \times (4 + 5))) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2726 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F((F(3) \times (4 + 5))) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2727 &:= (-1 + (F((F(F(2 + F(3))) \times (4 + 5))) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2728 &:= (F((F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times (4 + 5))) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2729 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F((F(3) + 4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2730 &:= ((1 \times 2 + F((F(3) + 4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2731 &:= ((-1 - (2^{F(3 \times 4 - 5)})) / (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2732 &:= (-1 + (F(((2 \times 3) \times F(4))) + (5 + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2733 &:= (-1 + (F(((2 \times 3) \times F(4))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2734 &:= (F((-1 - 2 + F(F(3 + F(4)))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2735 &:= (-1 + (((F(2+3))^{F(F(4))}) + F(5+6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2736 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times F(3+4)) + F(5+6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2737 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((F(3) - F((F(4) + 5))) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2738 &:= (F(F((-1 - (2 - 3 - 4))) \times (5 - (F((6 + 7)) - F(8 + 9)))) \\
2739 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (((3 - (4 + 5)) + F((6 + 7))) - F(8 + 9))) \\
2740 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (((3 - (4 + 5)) + F((6 + 7))) - F(8 + 9)) \\
2741 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times F(F(3 + 4))) - 5) \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2742 &:= (((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times F(F(4))) - 5) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2743 &:= (-1 + (F(((2 \times 3) \times F(4))) + (5 \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2744 &:= (F((-1 - 2 + F(F(3 + F(4)))) + (5 \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2745 &:= (-1 + (F((2 + F(3 + 4))) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2746 &:= (F((F(F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3)))) \times F(4))) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2747 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(F(3 \times 4 - 5)) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2748 &:= (((-1 + ((2^{3+4}) + 5)) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2749 &:= (1 + (2 \times ((F(F(3 \times 4 - 5)) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2750 &:= (F((-1 - 2 + F(3 + 4))) \times (5 + (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2711 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + F(F(7)))) + (F(6) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2712 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2713 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) + (F(6) \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2714 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + F(7)) \times (F(6) - ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2715 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - F(6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2716 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(6) + (5 + 4))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2717 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) - (F(6 + 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2718 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2719 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - (6 + 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2720 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) + (F(6) \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2721 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) + 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2722 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2723 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((F(F(7)) - 6) \times ((5 + 4) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2724 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times F(7)) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2725 &:= ((9 \times ((8 + F(F(7))) - 6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2726 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + F(F(7)))) + (F(6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2727 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - 6)) + ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2728 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + F((7 + 6 - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
2729 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) + (F(6) \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2730 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2731 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) + 6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2732 &:= ((-9 + (F((F(8) - 7)) \times F(6))) - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2733 &:= ((9 \times ((F(8) + (7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2734 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (F(7) \times (F(6) - F(5 + 4)))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2735 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2736 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) + (F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2737 &:= (-9 - (((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times (F(6) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2738 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + (F((7 + 6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2739 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - 6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2740 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) - ((6 - 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2741 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(7)) \times F((F(6) + 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2742 &:= (-9 - (F(8) \times (F(7) - (F(6 + 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2743 &:= (9 + (((F(8) - 7)^{F(6) - 5}) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2744 &:= ((9 - 8 + F(7)) \times ((6 \times F(5 + 4)) - F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2745 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - F(F(7))) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2746 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(7 + 6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2747 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times (F(6) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
2748 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - ((F(6) \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2749 &:= (9 + (((F(8) \times F(7)) + (6 - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2750 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) + F(7))) \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2751 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(F(3+4)) + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
2752 &:= ((-1 - 2 + F((F(3)+4+5))) \times (F(6)+7+8+9)) \\
2753 &:= (-1 + (F((2+(3+4))) \times ((5 \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2754 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(F(3+4)) + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
2755 &:= (((-1 - (2^{F(3+4)})) / (5 - F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2756 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (4 \times 5 + (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2757 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3+4)) \times (5 + (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
2758 &:= ((-1 + 2 + F(3+4)) \times (5 + (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2759 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times F(3+4)) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2760 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2+3))^4 + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
2761 &:= ((F(F((-1+2 \times 3)))^4 + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2762 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((3 \times (4 \times (5+6+7))) - F(8+9))) \\
2763 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3 - (4 \times F((5+F(6)))))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2764 &:= (((1+2) \times F(F(3^4))) - (5 + (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2765 &:= (1 - (2 \times (F(F(3+4)) - ((5 + (6+7)) + F((8+9)))))) \\
2766 &:= (((-1-2) \times (F(3) - (4 \times F((5+F(6)))))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2767 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3 \times F(4)) \times (5 \times F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2768 &:= ((-1 + (((2^{3+4}) + 5) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2769 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times ((F(4)^5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2770 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times 4) \times F((5+F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2771 &:= (F((-1 - 2 + F(F(3+F(4)))) - (5 - (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2772 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2+3))) \times (4 \times F((5+F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2773 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F((F(3) \times (4+5))) + (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2774 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F((F(3) \times (4+5))) + (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2775 &:= (-1 + (F((F(F(2+F(3))) \times (4+5))) + (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2776 &:= (F((F(F((-1+F(2+3))) \times (4+5))) + (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2777 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F((F(3) \times (4+5))) + (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2778 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times F(F(F(4)+5)))) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2779 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2+3)) \times (4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
2780 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2+3)) \times (4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
2781 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((3^{F(4)}) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2782 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((3^{F(4)}) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2783 &:= (((-1 - 2 + F(3 \times F(4))) \times F(5+6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2784 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times F(3+4)) + F(5+6))) \times (7+8+9)) \\
2785 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((3^{F(4)}) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2786 &:= (-1 - (((2 - 3 - 4) \times (5 + F((6+7)))) - F(8+9))) \\
2787 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (F((3 \times 4)) + (5+6+7))) \times (8+9))) \\
2788 &:= ((-1 - ((F(F(2+F(3))) \times F(4+5)) - F((6+7)))) \times (8+9)) \\
2789 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 - F(4+5)) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2790 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - F(4+5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2751 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - F(7)) \times (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2752 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + ((6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2753 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + (6 - 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2754 &:= (-9 \times ((F(8) + F(7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2755 &:= (((9 \times F(8 + 7)) / F((F(6) - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2756 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + (F(6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
2757 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) \times F(7))) + (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2758 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) - 5 - 4))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2759 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((F(7) \times (F(6) - F(5 + 4))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2760 &:= ((9 + (F(8) - 7)) \times (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2761 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (F(7) + F(F(6)))) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2762 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) - (F(6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2763 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2764 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + F(6 + 5)))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2765 &:= (9 - ((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times (F(6) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
2766 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) - F(7)) \times F(F(6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2767 &:= (9 \times 8 + ((7^{F(F(6)-5)}) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2768 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(7 + 6)) - (F(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2769 &:= (-9 - (((F(8) \times 7) - F((6 + (5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2770 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2771 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2772 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - F((F(6) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))))) \\
2773 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) - (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2774 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - (6 - 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2775 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) - (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2776 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) - ((6 \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2777 &:= ((9 \times F((F(8) - 7))) - (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2778 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) - 5 - 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2779 &:= ((9 \times (8 + F(7 + 6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2780 &:= (((9 \times (8 + F(7))) + F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2781 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(7 + 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2782 &:= ((9 \times ((F(8) + 7) \times (6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2783 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + (F((7 + 6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2784 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7) + (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2785 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2786 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(7)) \times F((F(6) + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2787 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2788 &:= ((9 \times F((F(8) - 7))) - ((6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2789 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2790 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2791 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{F(3+F(4))}) \times (5+6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2792 &:= (((-1 + F(2+3))^4) \times (5+6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2793 &:= (F((-1-2 + F(F(3+F(4)))))) + (F((5+F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2794 &:= (1 + (F(((2 \times 3) \times F(4)))) + (F((5+F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2795 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3+4)) \times (5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
2796 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) \times (4 + 5 - (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2797 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(F(3+4)) + (F(5+6+7) - (8+9)))) \\
2798 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(F(3+4)) + (F(5+6+7) - (8+9)))) \\
2799 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((F(3)^4) \times F(5+6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2800 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2801 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times F(F(3+4))) + 5) \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2802 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - (F(4) \times ((5+F(6)) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
2803 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + (F(4) + (F(5+6+7) - (8+9)))) \\
2804 &:= (-1 - ((2 + F(3+4)) \times (5 - (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
2805 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3+4))) \times (5 - (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2806 &:= (1 - ((2 + F(3+4)) \times (5 - (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
2807 &:= ((1 + 2 \times 3) \times (F((F(4) + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2808 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((3^{F(4)}) + F(5+6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2809 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 - (4 \times (5 \times 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2810 &:= ((-1 + ((F(2 + F(3))^{F(4)}) \times (5 \times F(F(6)))))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2811 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times F(4+5))) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2812 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((3^{F(4)}) \times (5 \times F(F(6)))))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2813 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times ((F(F(4)) \times 5) - (6 \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
2814 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - (4 \times F((5+F(6)))))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2815 &:= (-1 + ((2 + ((3^4) + 5)) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2816 &:= ((-1 + F((F(F(2 + F(3))) + 4 + 5))) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2817 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + F((F(4+5) + (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
2818 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((3 \times 4) \times F((5+F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2819 &:= (-1 + ((F((F(2 \times 3) + F(4))) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2820 &:= ((F((-1 \times 2 + F(3+4))) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2821 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times 3)^{F(4)})) \times ((5+6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2822 &:= (-1 + ((2^{F(3+F(4))}) + (F(5+6+7) - (8+9)))) \\
2823 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times (4 \times F(5+6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2824 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2+3))^{F(F(4))}) \times (F(5+6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2825 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times F(3+4))) \times (F(5+6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2826 &:= (-1 - ((2 - F(3+4)) \times (F((5+F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2827 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + F(3+4)) \times (F((5+F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2828 &:= ((-1 + (F((2 + F(3+4))) \times 5)) - ((6+7) \times (8+9))) \\
2829 &:= (((-1 + (2^{F(3+F(4))})) \times (5+6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2830 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3+4) + (5 \times F(F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2791 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(7+6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2792 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) - ((F(6) \times 5)/(4+3+2+1))) \\
2793 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) - (F(6) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
2794 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) - F((F(6) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
2795 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) - ((6+5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2796 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times F(((7 + F(F(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2797 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + ((6+5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2798 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) + (F(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2799 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + (F(6+5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2800 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) \times (F(6) \times (5 - F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2801 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(7+6)) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2802 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + (F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2803 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) - (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2804 &:= ((9 \times F((F(8) - 7))) + (F(F(6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2805 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2806 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(7)) \times F((F(6) + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2807 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + (6 - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
2808 &:= (-9 \times ((F(8)/7) - (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2809 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + (F(6) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
2810 &:= ((9 - 8 + (7 \times (F(6) \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2811 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(7+6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2812 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + (F(F(6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
2813 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(7+6)) + ((5+4) + F(3+2+1))) \\
2814 &:= (9 + ((8 + (F(7) + (6 \times 5))) \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\
2815 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) + (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2816 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + F(6+5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2817 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2818 &:= (((-9 + F((F(8) - 7))) \times 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2819 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2820 &:= (((9 \times (8 + 7)) \times F(F(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2821 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) - ((6 \times 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2822 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + (F(F(6)) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
2823 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) - 7) \times F(F(6))) - ((5+4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
2824 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2825 &:= (((9 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6+5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2826 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 - (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2827 &:= ((9 \times ((F(8) + 7) \times (6 + 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2828 &:= ((9 \times F(8)) + (F((7 + 6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2829 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + (F(F(7)) + F((6 \times ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
2830 &:= (((9 \times (8 + 7)) \times F(F(6))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

2831 := $(-1 + ((2 + ((3^{F(4)} + F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
2832 := $(-1 - 2 + ((3^4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
2833 := $(1 + ((2 + ((3^{F(4)} + F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
2834 := $(-1 + ((F(2 + F(3))^4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
2835 := $((F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))^4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
2836 := $(1 + ((F(2 + F(3))^4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
2837 := $((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times F((F(F(4)) + 5))) - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
2838 := $((-1 + 2 + F(F(3 + F(4)))) \times ((5 \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))$
2839 := $(-1 + (((2^{F(3+F(4))}) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))$
2840 := $((((-1 + F(2 + 3))^4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)$
2841 := $((-1 - 2) \times (F(3 + 4) - (5 \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
2842 := $(-1 \times 2 + (F(3) \times ((F(F(F(4)) + 5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))$
2843 := $(-1 + (2 \times ((F(F(3 \times 4 - 5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))$
2844 := $(((-1 + ((2 \times F(F(3 + 4))) + 5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)$
2845 := $(-1 - 2 + (F((F(3) + 4 + 5)) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
2846 := $(-1 \times 2 + (F((F(3) + 4 + 5)) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
2847 := $(-1 + (F(((2 \times 3) \times F(4))) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
2848 := $(F((-1 - 2 + F(F(3 + F(4)))) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
2849 := $(-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) - F(F(4))) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
2850 := $((-1 + (F(F(2 + 3)) \times 4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
2851 := $(F((-1 \times 2 + F(3 + 4))) + ((5 \times F((6 + 7))) + F(8 + 9)))$
2852 := $((-1 + (F(2 + 3)^{F(4)})) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))$
2853 := $(((-1 + F((2 + F(3 + 4)))) \times 5) - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
2854 := $(-1 + ((2 \times F((3 \times 4))) + (F(5 + 6 + 7) - (8 + 9))))$
2855 := $(-1 + (((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F(4 + 5))/6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
2856 := $((-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times (4 + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$
2857 := $((-1 + (F((2 + F(3 + 4))) \times 5)) - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
2858 := $(-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))$
2859 := $(((-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times F(4 + 5))) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)$
2860 := $(-1 + 2 + (((3^{F(4)}) \times (5 \times F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9))$
2861 := $(-1 - (2 \times (3 - (((F(4)^5) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))))$
2862 := $((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - ((4 \times F((5 + F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
2863 := $(-1 - ((2 + F(3)) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))$
2864 := $((-1 - (2 \times F((F(3) + 4 + 5)))) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))$
2865 := $(-1 - 2 + (3 \times ((4 \times F((5 + F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
2866 := $(-1 \times 2 + (3 \times ((4 \times F((5 + F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
2867 := $(-1 - ((2 + F(3)) \times (F(4) - (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))$
2868 := $(F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times ((4 \times F((5 + F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9))$
2869 := $(-1 + 2 + (3 \times ((4 \times F((5 + F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
2870 := $((1 + (F(2 + F(3))^4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$

2831 := $(-9 + (((F(8) \times F(7)) + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
2832 := $((9 - F(8)) \times (7 - (F((F(6) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
2833 := $(((-9 + ((F(8) - F(7)) \times F((6 + 5)))) \times 4) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))$
2834 := $(-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4))) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))$
2835 := $(-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
2836 := $((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + F(6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$
2837 := $((9 \times (F((F(8) - 7)) + 6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
2838 := $(((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) - (F(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
2839 := $(-9 - (8 \times (F(F(7)) + (F(F(6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
2840 := $(((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) - ((6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
2841 := $(-9 - ((F(8) - (F(7) \times 6)) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
2842 := $(-9 + ((8 \times F(F(7))) + F((F(F(6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))))$
2843 := $(-9 \times 8 + ((F(7) + (F(6) \times 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
2844 := $(-9 \times ((F(8) \times F(7)) + (F(F(6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
2845 := $((9 \times ((8 + 7) \times F(F(6))) + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
2846 := $(((-9 + F(8)) \times F(7 + 6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
2847 := $(-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))$
2848 := $(((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times F(F(6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
2849 := $(((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times (6 + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
2850 := $((-9 + 8 - (7 \times F(6))) \times (5 - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
2851 := $((9 \times (8 + (F(F(7)) + F(6)))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
2852 := $(((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + ((6 - 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
2853 := $(((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
2854 := $(((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + (F(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
2855 := $(-9 + 8 - ((7 - F(F(6))) \times (F(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))$
2856 := $(-9 - ((F(8) - (F(F(7)) - F(F(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
2857 := $9 - 8 \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
2858 := $((-9 \times (F(8) \times 7)) + F((F(F(6)) - F(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))))$
2859 := $(9 - ((F(8) - (F(7) \times 6)) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
2860 := $((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
2861 := $((9 \times (8 + 7)) \times F(F(6)) + (F(5 + 4) - F(3 + 2 + 1)))$
2862 := $((F(-9 + F(8)) - 7) \times F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
2863 := $(-9 + ((F((F(8) - 7)) \times 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
2864 := $((9 \times ((8 + 7) + F(F(6)))) + F(5 + 4)) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)$
2865 := $(((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + 6)) - ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))$
2866 := $(((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7 + 6) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$
2867 := $(((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + (F(F(6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
2868 := $((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + (F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
2869 := $(-9 - (F(8) - (F(7) \times (F((F(6) + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))))$
2870 := $((F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(7) \times (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$

$$\begin{aligned}
2871 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3 - ((F(F(4))^5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2872 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + F(3 \times F(4))) \times F(5+6)) + 7+8+9) \\
2873 &:= (1 + ((F(2 \times 3) \times (4 \times F(5+6))) + 7+8+9)) \\
2874 &:= ((-1-2) \times (F(3) - ((F(F(4))^5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2875 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2+3)) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7+8+9))))) \\
2876 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) + (5 - (6 \times (7+8+9))))) \\
2877 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times ((F(F(4))^5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2878 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times ((F(F(4))^5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2879 &:= (-1 + (F(2 + F(3)) \times ((F(F(4))^5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2880 &:= ((-1-2) \times ((F(3) - F(4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2881 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times ((F(F(4))^5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2882 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2+3)))) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7+8+9))))) \\
2883 &:= (F((-1 + F(2+3))) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7+8+9))))) \\
2884 &:= ((-1 + F(2+3)) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7+8+9))))) \\
2885 &:= (1 \times (F(F(2+3)) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7+8+9))))) \\
2886 &:= (F((-1 + F(2+3))) \times (F(F(4)) + (5 \times (F(6) \times (7+8+9))))) \\
2887 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (F(F(4)) + (5 \times (F(6) \times (7+8+9))))) \\
2888 &:= ((-1 + F(2+3)) \times (F(F(4)) + (5 \times (6 \times (7+8+9))))) \\
2889 &:= (F((-1 + F(2+3))) \times (F((F(4) + (5 + F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2890 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (F((F(4) + (5 + F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2891 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times (F(4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7+8+9))))) \\
2892 &:= ((-1 + F(2+3)) \times (F(4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7+8+9))))) \\
2893 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (4 + (5 \times (F(6) \times (7+8+9))))) \\
2894 &:= ((-1 + ((F(((2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) - 5) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2895 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((F(3)^4) \times F(5+6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
2896 &:= (-1 + (F((2 \times (3+4))) + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7+8+9))))) \\
2897 &:= (F((-1 + 2 + F(3+4))) + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2898 &:= ((-1 - (F(F(2+3)) \times (F(F(4))^5))) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2899 &:= (-1 + (F(F(F(2+3))) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2900 &:= (F(F(F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3))))) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2901 &:= (((-1 + F((2 + F(3+4)))) \times 5) - (6 \times (7+8+9))) \\
2902 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((3^4) + (5 \times F(6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2903 &:= (-1 - ((2 - F(3+4)) \times ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2904 &:= ((1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times (4+5+6))) \times (7+8+9)) \\
2905 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times 4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2906 &:= ((F(F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3)))) \times F((F(4) \times 5))) - (6 \times (7+8+9))) \\
2907 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (((F(3) + 4 + 5) \times (6+7)) - F(8+9)))) \\
2908 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (((F(3) + 4 + 5) \times (6+7)) - F(8+9))) \\
2909 &:= ((F(F((-1 \times (2 - 3 - 4))))^5) - (F((6+7)) - (8+9))) \\
2910 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3 \times (F(F(4))^5))) \times (6+7+8+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2871 &:= (-9 + ((F((F(8) - 7)) - F(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2872 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(F(7))) \times 6) + F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2873 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + 6+5)) - F(4+3+2+1)) \\
2874 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) + (F(6) \times 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2875 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + (F(6+5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2876 &:= (9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) - 5 - 4)) + F(3+2+1))) \\
2877 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - 7) \times (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2878 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) + F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2879 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times F(F(7)))) + (F((F(6) - 5))^{4+3+2+1})) \\
2880 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) - (F(6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2881 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + F(6+5)))) + F(4+3+2+1)) \\
2882 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) - 7) \times F(F(6))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2883 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times F(F(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2884 &:= (((-9 + F((F(8) - 7))) \times F(6)) - (5 + F(4+3+2+1))) \\
2885 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + F((6 - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
2886 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2887 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + F(6))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2888 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (7^{F(6)-5}))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2889 &:= (9 \times ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2890 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) + F(F(7)))) - (6 - F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2891 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) + F(F(7)))) + ((6+5) \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\
2892 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + F((F(F(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
2893 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times F(F(6))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2894 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times (6+5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2895 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + (F(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
2896 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) + F(7+6))) + F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2897 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + F(6))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2898 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2899 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times F(F(6))) + ((5+4) - F(3+2+1))) \\
2900 &:= (9 - F(8+7) + F(F(6))) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2901 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) - (F(F(6)) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
2902 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) + F(F(7)))) + (6 + F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2903 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times F(F(6))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2904 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2905 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times F(F(7))) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1))))) \\
2906 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2907 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + F(6))) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2908 &:= ((9 \times (((8+7) + F(F(6))) \times (5+4))) - F(3+2+1)) \\
2909 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + F(6))) + ((5+4) + F(3+2+1))) \\
2910 &:= ((-9 - F(8)) \times (F(7) - ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2911 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F((F(3) + 4 + 5))) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2912 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times ((F(F(4)) + 5) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2913 &:= (((-1 + F((2 + (3 + 4)))) \times F(5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2914 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (F(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7)))) + F(8 + 9)) \\
2915 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3^{F(4)}) \times (5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2916 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (F(4)^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9})) \\
2917 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(F(3 + F(4))) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2918 &:= (-1 - (F((F(F(2 + 3)) + F(4))) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2919 &:= (-F((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4)))) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2920 &:= ((1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2921 &:= (((1 \times F(2 + 3)) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2922 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3 + 4) - F(((5 \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
2923 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3 + 4) \times (5 \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2924 &:= (1 - 2 + (F(3 + 4) \times (5 \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2925 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times F(4 + 5))) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2926 &:= ((-1 + 2 + F(3 + 4)) \times (F((5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2927 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3 \times (F(4 + 5) + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2928 &:= ((-1 + (F((2 + (3 + 4))) + F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2929 &:= (-1 + (F(2 + 3) \times (F((4 + 5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2930 &:= (F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3)))) \times (F((4 + 5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2931 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - F((F(4) + (5 + F(6)))))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2932 &:= ((-1 + ((F(F(2 + 3))^4 \times 5)) - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2933 &:= ((F(F((-1 \times (2 - 3 - 4))))^5) - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2934 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) \times ((F(4) \times 5) - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2935 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times F((F(4) + (5 + F(6)))))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2936 &:= ((-1 + (((2 + F((3 \times 4))) - 5) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2937 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3 + 4) \times (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2938 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) \times (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2939 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2940 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + 4) - F(((5 \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
2941 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3) \times ((F(4)^5 \times 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2942 &:= (-1 + (((F(((2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) - 5) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2943 &:= (((1 + 2) \times F((F(3) \times (F(4) + 5)))) + (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2944 &:= (((-1 + F((2 \times (3 + 4)))) - 5) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2945 &:= (-1 - ((F((F(2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) - 5) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2946 &:= (((1 + 2) \times (F(F(3)^4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2947 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((F(F(3)^4) - 5) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2948 &:= (((1 + 2) \times F(F(3)^4)) + ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2949 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3 \times F(4)) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2950 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3 \times F(4)) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2911 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7 + 6) + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2912 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7 + 6) + (5 + 4))) + F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2913 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times F(F(6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2914 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2915 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) + (F(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2916 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2917 &:= (((-9 - 8 \times F(7)) \times (F(6) - F(5 + 4))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2918 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + 6 + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2919 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (F(7) \times (F(F(6)) - 5 - 4))) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2920 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + F(6 + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2921 &:= (9 - (8 \times 7 \times (F(6) - (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2922 &:= (((9 \times F(8)) - 7) \times (F(F(6)) - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2923 &:= ((9 + (F(8) + 7)) \times (F(6 + 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2924 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 + ((F(6) - 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2925 &:= (((-9 - 8 + F(F(7))) - F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2926 &:= ((-9 + ((F(8 + 7) - F(F(6))) \times 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2927 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F((F(7) + (6 - 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
2928 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + (6 - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
2929 &:= (((-9 + F((F(8) - 7))) \times F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2930 &:= (((-9 - F(8)) \times (7 - (F(F(6)) \times 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2931 &:= ((9 / (F(8) / 7)) \times (F((F(F(6)) - 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2932 &:= (9 + 8 + ((F(7) + (F(6) \times 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2933 &:= (((9 \times F(8)) + F(F(7))) \times ((6 + 5) - 4) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2934 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) + (F(7) - (6 \times (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2935 &:= (((9 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6 + 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2936 &:= (-9 + ((8 - F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2937 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) - 7) \times F(F(6))) + (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2938 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + 6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2939 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7) \times (6 + 5)))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2940 &:= (((9 \times F(8)) + (F(7) - 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2941 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times ((7 + F(F(6))) \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2942 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + F(6))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2943 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (F(F(7)) + (F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2944 &:= ((-9 + F((F(8) - 7))) \times F((F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2945 &:= (F((-9 + F(8) - 7)) \times (F((6 + (5 + 4))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2946 &:= (((9 \times F(8)) + 7) \times (6 + (5 + 4))) + (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2947 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (F(7) \times F((F(6) + 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2948 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times F(F(6))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2949 &:= (((-9 + F((F(8) - 7))) \times F(6)) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2950 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7 + 6)) \times (5 - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

2951 := $(-1 + ((F((2 + (3 + 4))) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
2952 := $((F((F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))^{F(F(4))})) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$
2953 := $(-1 + 2 + ((F(3 \times F(4)) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
2954 := $(-1 + ((2 + F(3 + 4)) \times (5 + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
2955 := $((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - F((F(4) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))))$
2956 := $((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) + (F(4) \times F(((5 \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)))$
2957 := $(-1 - (((2 - F(3 + 4 + 5)) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))$
2958 := $(-1 - 2 + (3 \times F((F(4) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))))$
2959 := $(-1 \times 2 + (3 \times F((F(4) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))))$
2960 := $(-1 + (F(2 + F(3)) \times F((F(4) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))))$
2961 := $(((-1 + F((2 + (3 + 4)))) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)$
2962 := $(-1 + 2 + (3 \times F((F(4) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))))$
2963 := $(F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + (F(4) \times F(((5 \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)))$
2964 := $(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times ((F(4 + 5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))$
2965 := $((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + (F(4) \times F(((5 \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)))$
2966 := $(((-1 - 2 + F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)$
2967 := $(F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times (F(F(4)) + F(((5 \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))))$
2968 := $(1 + 2 \times 3 + (F(4) \times F(((5 \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)))$
2969 := $(-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (4 + 5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
2970 := $((-1 - 2 + (3 \times F(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
2971 := $(-1 + 2 - (3 \times (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))))$
2972 := $(-1 + (F(2 + F(3)) \times (4 + F(((5 \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))))$
2973 := $(1 + 2 - (3 \times (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))))$
2974 := $(-1 + 2 + (3 \times (4 + F(((5 \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))))$
2975 := $(-1 - (2 \times (((3^{F(4)}) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
2976 := $((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - ((4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
2977 := $(-1 + 2 + (3 \times ((4^5) - (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
2978 := $(-1 - (((2 - F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))$
2979 := $((1 - 2 + F(3 + 4 + 5)) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9$
2980 := $(1 - (((2 - F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))$
2981 := $(-1 + (F(2 + F(3)) \times ((4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
2982 := $(F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times ((4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
2983 := $(1 + (F(2 + F(3)) \times ((4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
2984 := $(((-1 + F((2 + (3 + 4 + 5)))) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)$
2985 := $(((-1 - 2 + F(3 + 4 + 5)) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)$
2986 := $(-1 + 2 + ((3 \times F((F(4) + (5 + F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9))$
2987 := $(-1 - (2 \times (3 + (F(4) \times (5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))))$
2988 := $((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times ((F(4)^5) + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
2989 := $(-1 - 2 - ((F(3)^4) \times (5 - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
2990 := $(1 + 2 - F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$

2951 := $((9 / (F(8) / 7)) \times F((F(F(6)) - 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$
2952 := $((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) + F((F(6) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))))$
2953 := $(9 + ((F((F(8) - 7)) \times F(6)) - ((5 + 4) \times F(3 + 2 + 1))))$
2954 := $(((-9 \times F(8)) - F(F(7))) \times (F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
2955 := $((-9 - (F(8) - (F(F(7)) - 6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
2956 := $((-9 + ((F(8 + 7) - 6) \times 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
2957 := $(-9 \times 8 + (F(7) \times F((F(6) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))))$
2958 := $(9 + 8) \times ((F(7) \times (6 + (5 + 4))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))$
2959 := $(-9 - (8 \times (F(F(7)) + (6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
2960 := $((-9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) - F(6 + 5)))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
2961 := $(-9 \times ((F(8) \times F(7)) + (F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
2962 := $((-9 + ((F(8) + F(7)) \times F(6 + 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
2963 := $((-9 + (F(8) \times (7 \times F(F(6)) - 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$
2964 := $((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times F(F(6))) - (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
2965 := $(((-9 + F(8 + 7)) - 6) \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$
2966 := $((9 \times 8 + 7) + F(6)) \times F(5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)$
2967 := $(-9 - (8 \times (F(F(7)) - ((6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
2968 := $((-9 \times 8 + (F((7 + F(6))) \times 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$
2969 := $((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F((7 + 6 - 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
2970 := $(-9 \times ((8 \times 7 - F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
2971 := $(9 \times 8 + (F(7) \times (F((F(6) + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))$
2972 := $(((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - F(6))) + (F(5 + 4) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)))$
2973 := $((9 \times (F(8) \times 7)) + ((6 \times 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
2974 := $((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times F(F(6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
2975 := $(9 - F(8 + 7) + 6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$
2976 := $((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7 + 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
2977 := $((-9 + (F((F(8) - 7)) \times F(6))) - ((5 + 4) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))$
2978 := $(-9 \times 8 + (F((F(7) - F(6))) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
2979 := $(-9 \times ((F(8) \times F(7)) + (6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
2980 := $(9 + (((F(8) + F(7)) \times F(6 + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
2981 := $((9 \times (F(8) \times (F(7) + 6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
2982 := $(-9 + ((F(8) / 7) \times (F((F(F(6)) - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
2983 := $(((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + 6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
2984 := $((-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7) \times (6 + 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$
2985 := $(((-9 + F(8 + 7)) - 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$
2986 := $(9 + F(F(8) / 7)) \times F(6) \times F(5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1$
2987 := $(-9 - (F(8) + (7 - (F((F(F(6)) - 5 - 4)) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))))$
2988 := $(-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
2989 := $(-9 - (F(8) - ((F(7) \times F((F(6) + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))$
2990 := $((-9 + ((F(8) + 7) \times (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$

$$\begin{aligned}
2991 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times F((F(4) + 5 + 6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2992 &:= ((F((-1 + ((2 \times 3) + 4 + 5))) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2993 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((F(3)^4) \times (5 - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2994 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (3 + 4)) \times (5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2995 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(F(2 + 3)))) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2996 &:= (((1 + 2) \times F(F(3)^4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2997 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (F(3 + 4 + 5) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2998 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (F(3 + 4 + 5) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2999 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 \times F(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3000 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times F(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3001 &:= ((-1 + (F((2 + (3 + 4))) \times F(5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3002 &:= (-1 + ((2 - F(F(3 + 4))) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
3003 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F(3 \times F(4)) \times F(5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3004 &:= ((-1 + (F((2 + F(3 + 4))) \times 5)) - (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3005 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3006 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + F(3 + 4 + 5)) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3007 &:= (-1 + ((F((F(2 \times 3) + F(4))) + 5) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3008 &:= ((-1 + F((2 \times (3 + 4)))) \times F((5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
3009 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (F((F(3) \times (F(4) + 5))) - (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
3010 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{F(3+F(4))}) \times (5 + 6 + 7))) - F(8 + 9)) \\
3011 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) + (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3012 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - ((4^5) + (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
3013 &:= (((-1 + F((2 + F(3 + 4)))) \times 5) - (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3014 &:= (((-1 - 2 + F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3015 &:= (((-1 + F((2 + F(3 + 4)))) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3016 &:= ((-1 + 2 - F(F(3 + 4))) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3017 &:= ((-1 + (F((2 + F(3 + 4))) \times 5)) - (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3018 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - ((F(4 + 5) + F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3019 &:= ((-1 + (F((2 + F(3 + 4))) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3020 &:= (1 \times ((F((2 + F(3 + 4))) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3021 &:= (((-1 + 2 + F(3 + 4 + 5)) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3022 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3 - (4 + 5)) \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3023 &:= (-1 + (F((2 - (3 - (4 + 5)))) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3024 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((F(3) - (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3025 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 + 3)) \times F((4 + 5 + 6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3026 &:= ((F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3))) \times F((4 + 5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3027 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(F(3 + 4)) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
3028 &:= (1 - 2 - (F(F(3 + 4)) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
3029 &:= (-F(F((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2991 &:= (9 + (F(8) \times (7 \times F(F(6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
2992 &:= ((-9 + (F((F(8) - 7)) \times F(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2993 &:= ((9 \times F((F(8) - 7))) - (F(6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2994 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2995 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2996 &:= (((-9 + F(8 + 7)) \times 6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2997 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times F((F(7) + (6 - 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2998 &:= (((9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - F(5 + 4)) + F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2999 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (F(7) \times F((F(6) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))))) \\
3000 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) + F(7))) \times (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3001 &:= (-9 + ((8 - F(7)) \times (F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3002 &:= (-9 + ((F((F(8) - 7)) \times F(6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
3003 &:= ((F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) \times F((F(F(6)) - 5 - 4))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3004 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (F(7) \times (6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3005 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) - F(6 + 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3006 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(6) + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3007 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (F(7 + 6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3008 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F(((7 + F(6)) - 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3009 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times F(F(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3010 &:= (F((9 - F(8) + 7)) \times (-F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3011 &:= (-9 + ((8 - F(7)) \times (6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3012 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F(7) \times F((F(6) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
3013 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - F(7)) \times (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3014 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F((7 + 6 - 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3015 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3016 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(F(7))) \times F((F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3017 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) + F(7)) \times F((6 - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
3018 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(7) \times F((F(6) + 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3019 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
3020 &:= (F((9 - F(8) + 7)) \times (-6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3021 &:= (-9 + (((F(8 + 7) - 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3022 &:= (-9 + ((F((F(8) - 7)) \times F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3023 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (F((7 + F(6))) \times 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3024 &:= (F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3025 &:= (F((F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) - (6 + 5))) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3026 &:= ((-9 + ((F(8 + 7) + F(6)) \times 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3027 &:= (-9 + (((F(8) + F(7)) \times F(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3028 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F(7) \times F((F(6) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
3029 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times F(F(6))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3030 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 + F(3)) \times F(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3031 &:= (-1 + ((F((2 + F(3 + 4))) \times 5) + (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
3032 &:= (((-1 + F((2 + (3 + 4 + 5)))) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3033 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (F((F(3) + (F(4) + 5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3034 &:= (1 \times ((F((2 + F(3 + 4))) \times 5) + (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
3035 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (F(3)^{4+5})) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3036 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - (4^5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3037 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (3 \times (4^5))) - (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3038 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (4^5))) - (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3039 &:= (((1 + F((2 + F(3 + 4)))) \times 5) + (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3040 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3041 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 + F(3)) \times (4^5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3042 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times (4^5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3043 &:= (1 + ((F(2 + F(3)) \times (4^5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3044 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 - 5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3045 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3 + 4 + 5) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3046 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3 + 4 + 5) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3047 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3 \times F(4)) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3048 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3^{F(4)}) \times (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3049 &:= (-1 + ((F((2 + (3 + 4))) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3050 &:= ((F((F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))^{F(F(4))})) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3051 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (F(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3052 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3^{F(4)}) \times (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3053 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3054 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - (F(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3055 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - F(F(3 + 4))) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3056 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - (F(4 + 5) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3057 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (F(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3058 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (F(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3059 &:= (-1 + (F(2 + F(3)) \times (F(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3060 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times (F(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3061 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (F(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3062 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (F((3 \times 4)) + 5)) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3063 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + (F(4 + 5) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3064 &:= (1 \times 2 \times (F(3) + (F(4 + 5) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3065 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3066 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3067 &:= ((-1 + (F((2 + F(3 + 4))) \times 5)) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3068 &:= ((-1 - 2 - F(F(3 + 4))) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3069 &:= (((-1 + 2 + F(3 + 4 + 5)) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3030 &:= (((9 \times F(8)) + (7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3031 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(F(7))) \times F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3032 &:= (F(-9 + 8 + 7) + (F((F(F(6)) - 5 - 4)) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3033 &:= (-9 \times ((F(8) \times (7 + 6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3034 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F((7 + 6 - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3035 &:= (((-9 + (F(8 + 7) + F(6))) \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3036 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + ((6 \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
3037 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + (F(((7 + F(6)) - 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3038 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(7) \times F((F(6) + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3039 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3040 &:= ((F((F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) - 6)) \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3041 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 + 6)) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3042 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (F(7) + F(F(6)))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3043 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
3044 &:= ((F((-9 + F(8) - 7)) \times F((6 + (5 + 4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3045 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) - F(7 + 6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3046 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) - F(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
3047 &:= (-9 - ((8 - F(7)) \times F((6 + (5 + 4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3048 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3049 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F((F(7) - F(6))) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3050 &:= (F(((9 / (F(8) / 7)) + F(6))) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3051 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) + F(7)) \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3052 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + ((F((7 + F(6))) \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
3053 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
3054 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - ((F(7) \times F((F(6) + 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3055 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (F(F(7)) - (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3056 &:= (-9 + (((F(8 + 7) - F(6)) \times 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3057 &:= (-9 + ((F((F(8) - 7)) \times F(6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3058 &:= ((F((-9 + F(8) - 7)) \times F((6 + (5 + 4)))) + F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3059 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F((7 + F(6))) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3060 &:= ((F((F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) - 6)) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3061 &:= ((-9 + ((F(8 + 7) + 6) \times 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3062 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) \times F(7))) + ((6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3063 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (7 \times F(F(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3064 &:= ((-9 + (F((F(8) - 7)) + (6 + (5 + 4)))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3065 &:= ((-9 - (F(8 + 7) - 6)) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
3066 &:= (-9 + (((F(8 + 7) - 6) \times 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3067 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) \times (7 + 6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3068 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8) - 7) - 6 \times 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3069 &:= (9 + ((F(8) + F(7)) \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3109 &:= ((F(F((-1 \times (2-3-4))))^5) + (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 3109 &:= (9 + 8) \times 7 \times F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\ 3110 &:= ((-1 \times F(2+3)) \times (F(F(4)) - ((5 + F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3110 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + 7) \times F(F(6))) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3111 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2+3))) \times ((4^5) + F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) & 3111 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3112 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3 \times ((4^5) + F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) & 3112 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times F(7)) + F((6 + (5 + 4)))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1) \\ 3113 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(F(F(2+3)))) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3113 &:= ((9 \times (F((F(8) - 7)) - (6 \times 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\ 3114 &:= (-1 + (F((F(2 \times 3) + F(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3114 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((F(7) - F(6))^5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\ 3115 &:= (F((-1 \times 2 + F(3 + 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3115 &:= (((9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) + F(6 + 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3116 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 + F(3)) \times (4^5)) + (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3116 &:= (9 - 8 + (((F(7) - F(6))^5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\ 3117 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2+3))) \times (4^5)) + (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3117 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times 7)^{F(F(6)-5)})) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\ 3118 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times (4^5)) + (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3118 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((F(7) - F(6))^5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3119 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3 \times F(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3119 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (F(7) \times (6 \times 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\ 3120 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2+3)) \times F((F(4) + 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3120 &:= (((-9 - 8 + F(F(7))) - F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3121 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(F(3)^4) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3121 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + 7) \times F(F(6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3122 &:= (-1 + (F((F(2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3122 &:= ((((-9 + F(8)) \times 7) + F(6)) \times F(5 + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1) \\ 3123 &:= (F(((F(2+3)) \times 4) + (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3123 &:= (-9 \times ((F(8) \times (F(7) - (6 \times 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3124 &:= (-1 - ((F(F(2+3))^{F(4)}) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3124 &:= (-9 + ((8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(6) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\ 3125 &:= (-1 \times ((F(F(2+3))^{F(4)}) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3125 &:= ((-9 - (F(8 + 7) + 6)) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\ 3126 &:= (F((-1 + F(2+3))) \times ((4^5) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) & 3126 &:= (-9 - ((8 - ((7 + 6) \times 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3127 &:= ((-1 + ((F(2+3)^4) \times 5)) - (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 3127 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7)^{F(F(6)+5-4-3-2-1)})) \\ 3128 &:= ((F(F(F((-1 \times (2-3-4))))^5) - (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 3128 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (7 \times F(F(6)))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 3129 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2+3))) \times (F(4)^5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3129 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (F(7) \times (F((F(6) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 3130 &:= (1 \times (F((2 + F(3 + 4))) + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3130 &:= (9 + (((F(8) + F(F(7))) \times 6) + F(((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 3131 &:= (1 + (F((2 + F(3 + 4))) + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3131 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (F(F(7)) + F(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3132 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) & 3132 &:= (9 + 8 + (((F(7) - F(6))^5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\ 3133 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3 \times 4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3133 &:= ((9 \times (F((F(8) - 7)) - (6 \times 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\ 3134 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(3 + 4)) \times (F((5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) & 3134 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((F(7) - F(6))^5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3135 &:= ((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - (5 \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3135 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + 6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3136 &:= (((-1 + (F(F(2+3))^4) \times 5) - (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 3136 &:= (9 - 8 + (((F(7) - F(6))^5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3137 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3) \times (4 - 5 - 6 - 7)) + F(8 + 9)))) & 3137 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7)^{F(F(6)-5)})) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\ 3138 &:= (((-1 + (F(2+3)^4) \times 5) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 3138 &:= (((9 + F((F(8) - 7))) \times F(6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3139 &:= (((-1 + 2 + F(3 \times F(4))) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) & 3139 &:= ((9 \times (8 + (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3140 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (F((4 + 5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) & 3140 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7)) \times ((6 \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\ 3141 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F(3) - (F((4 + 5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) & 3141 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 3142 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - (F((4 + 5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) & 3142 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F(7) \times (F((F(6) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3143 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (F((3 \times 4)) - (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 3143 &:= (9 + 8) \times 7 + (F((F(F(6)) - 5 - 4)) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3144 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 + F(3)) \times (4 \times (5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) & 3144 &:= (9 - ((8 - ((7 + 6) \times 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3145 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F((F(3) + (4 + 5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) & 3145 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (F(7) + (6 - (F(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 3146 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2+3)))) \times (F((4 + 5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 3146 &:= (-9 - ((8 - F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 3147 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4))) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3147 &:= (-9 + F(8) + ((F((F(7) - F(6)))^5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3148 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4)))) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 3149 &:= (-1 + (F((F(2 + 3) + F(4)))) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 3150 &:= (F((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4)))) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 3151 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4)))) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 3152 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((3 + F(F(4)))^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 3153 &:= (1 + 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4)))) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 3154 &:= (1 - 2 + (((3 + F(F(4)))^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 3155 &:= (((-1 \times (2 - 3 - 4))^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 3156 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((3 + F(F(4)))^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 3157 &:= ((F(F((-1 \times (2 - 3 - 4))))^5) + (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 3158 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((3 + F(F(4)))^5) + (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 3159 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (F(3 + 4) \times ((5 \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\ 3160 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 3161 &:= (-1 + (F(2 + F(3)) \times ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 3162 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 3163 &:= (1 + (F(2 + F(3)) \times ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 3164 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3^{F(4)})) \times (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 3165 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 3166 &:= ((1 - 2 + 3) \times (4 - 5 - 6 - 7 + F((8 + 9)))) \\ 3167 &:= (-1 + (F(2 + F(3)) \times (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 3168 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 3169 &:= (-1 + (F(2 + 3) \times (F((4 + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 3170 &:= (F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3)))) \times (F((4 + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 3171 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times F((4 + 5 + F(6))))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 3172 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + ((F(4) - 5) \times ((6 + 7) - F(8 + 9)))) \\ 3173 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + F((4 + 5 + F(6))))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 3174 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (F((3 \times 4) + 5)) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 3175 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + F((4 + 5 + F(6))))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 3176 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times ((4 \times 5) \times F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 3177 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4^5))) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\ 3178 &:= ((1 \times 2 \times F(3 \times 4 + 5)) - (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\ 3179 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((F(3) - F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 3180 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4))) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 3181 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times F(3 \times 4))) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 3182 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - ((4 + 5 - (6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9))) \\ 3183 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\ 3184 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))^{F(4)}) + F(((5 \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\ 3185 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3))^{F(F(4))}) \times (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\ 3186 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times ((4 + 5 - (6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3148 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) + F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3149 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F((F(7) + (6 - 5)))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3150 &:= (((-9 - 8 + F(F(7))) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3151 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - 7) \times (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3152 &:= (9 + 8 + (((F(7) - F(6))^5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3153 &:= (9 - (8 \times (7 - (F(6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\ 3154 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6)))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3155 &:= (F((-9 + F(8) - 7)) \times (F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3156 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3157 &:= (F((-9 + (F(8) + 7))) - (F((F(6) - 5))^{4+3+2+1})) \\ 3158 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F(7) \times (F((F(6) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3159 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) + (F(F(7)) - ((6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 3160 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (F(6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\ 3161 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times ((F(7) \times F(F(6))) - 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3162 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (7 + (F(6 + 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\ 3163 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3164 &:= (9 - ((8 - F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 3165 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) - F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3166 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + 7) \times F(F(6))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\ 3167 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) \times 7 + (6 \times F(5 + 4)))) + F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3168 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 3169 &:= ((9 \times (8 + (F(7) \times (F(F(6)) + 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3170 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times 7) + F((F(6) + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3171 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + 7) \times (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3172 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + 7) \times F(F(6))) + ((5 + 4) - F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3173 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(7) \times (F((F(6) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))))) \\ 3174 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3175 &:= (((9 + (8 \times (F(7) \times 6))) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\ 3176 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + 7) \times F(F(6))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\ 3177 &:= (-9 - (((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times (6 + (5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3178 &:= ((-9 + 8 - F(7)) \times (6 - F((F(5 + 4) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\ 3179 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3180 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3181 &:= (-9 + (((F(8) \times 7) - F(6 + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3182 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7)^{F(F(6)-5)}) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3183 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (7 \times F(F(6)) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\ 3184 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + ((F((7 + F(6))) \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\ 3185 &:= (-9 + (F(((F(8)/7) \times 6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3186 &:= (-9 \times ((F((F(8)/7))^{F(6)}) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3187 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - F((4 - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))))) \\
3188 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - F((4 - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
3189 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4)^5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3190 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - F((4 - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
3191 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3192 &:= ((F(((1 - F(2 + 3)) \times F(4))) - (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3193 &:= (-1 + (2 \times F((F(3) - ((F(4) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3194 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times F((4 - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
3195 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times F((4 - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
3196 &:= (-1 - ((F(F(2 \times 3)) + F(F(4))) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3197 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + F((4 - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))))) \\
3198 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - ((4^5) + (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3199 &:= (1 + (2 \times (F(3) + F((4 - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))))) \\
3200 &:= ((1 \times F(2 + 3)) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3201 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - ((4^5) + (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3202 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times ((4 + 5 - (6 + 7)) - F(8 + 9))) \\
3203 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F((F(3) + 4 + 5)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
3204 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F((F(3) + 4 + 5)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
3205 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (F(3 \times 4 + 5) - 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3206 &:= (-1 + (F(2 + F(3)) \times ((4^5) + (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3207 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times (F((F(4) + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3208 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3209 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (F(F(3 + F(4))) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3210 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times F((F(4) \times 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3211 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - F((4 + 5 + F(6)))))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3212 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3213 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (F(3) - F((4 + 5 + F(6)))))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3214 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - F((4 + 5 + F(6)))))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3215 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (F(3) - F((4 + 5 + F(6)))))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3216 &:= (((-1 + 2 + F((3 \times 4))) - (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3217 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times F((F(3) + (4 + 5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3218 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times F((4 + 5 + F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3219 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3) \times F((4 + 5 + F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3220 &:= ((-1 + F((F(F(2 \times 3)) - F(F(4)))) - (5 \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3221 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (F(3) + F((4 + 5 + F(6)))))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3222 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times F((F(3) + 4 + 5)))) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3223 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times F(3 \times 4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3224 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times ((F(4 + 5) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3225 &:= (1 + ((2 \times F(3 \times 4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3226 &:= (((F(F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3))))))^{F(4)}) \times (5 + F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3187 &:= (9 \times 8 + (((F(7) - F(6))^5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
3188 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + 7) \times F(F(6))) + ((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3189 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3190 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7 + 6 + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3191 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times F(F(6))) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3192 &:= (((9 + F(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + (5 + 4)) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3193 &:= (((-9 - (F(8) - F(F(7)))) \times (F(F(6)) - 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3194 &:= (F((F((-9 + 8 + F(7)))/F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3195 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3196 &:= (((9 \times F(8)) - (7 - 6)) \times ((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3197 &:= (-9 + (F((F(8)/7)) \times (6 + F(((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3198 &:= (((9 \times (F(8) + (7 \times 6))) + F(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3199 &:= (9 + (((F(8) \times 7) - F(6 + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3200 &:= (F(-9 + 8 + 7) \times (F(6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3201 &:= (9 + (F(8) \times (7 \times F(F(6)) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
3202 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (F(F(7)) + 6)) \times (F(5 + 4) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3203 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) + F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3204 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) + (F(7 + 6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3205 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (F(7) \times 6)) \times 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3206 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times ((F(7) \times F(F(6))) - 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3207 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3208 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times 7) + (F(6) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3209 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times F(5 + 4)) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3210 &:= ((-9 - F(8)) \times (F(7) - (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3211 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + (6 \times 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3212 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) + (F(F(7)) - F((6 + (5 + 4)))))) + F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3213 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) \times (F(7) + (6 \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
3214 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F((F(7) + (6 - 5)))))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3215 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (F(F(7)) - F(6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3216 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3217 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 \times (6 + 5)) \times (F(F(4)) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3218 &:= ((9 \times F(8)) + (F(7) \times F((F(6) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
3219 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) + F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3220 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) \times ((6 \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
3221 &:= (9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) + F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3222 &:= (-9 \times ((F(8) \times F(7)) - (F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3223 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) \times (F(7) - (6 \times 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3224 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times F(5 + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3225 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + F(F(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3226 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3227 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^{F(F(4))}) \times F(5+6)) + 7+8+9)) \\ 3228 &:= ((-1+2-3) + (F(F(4)) \times ((5+6+7) + F(8+9)))) \\ 3229 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3 \times 4+5) - (6-7-8-9)))) \\ 3230 &:= (F(F((-1-(2-3-4)))) \times ((5+6+7) + F(8+9))) \\ 3231 &:= (((-1-2+F(3 \times F(4))) \times (5 \times F(F(6)))) - 7-8-9) \\ 3232 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 + F(3)) \times F(4+5))) \times (F(6) + 7+8+9)) \\ 3233 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\ 3234 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\ 3235 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (F((4+5+F(6))) + 7+8+9)))) \\ 3236 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (F((4+5+F(6))) + 7+8+9))) \\ 3237 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F(3) - (F((4+5+F(6))) + 7+8+9)))) \\ 3238 &:= ((F(F((-1+F(2 \times 3)))) \times (F(4) + 5+6)) - 7-8-9) \\ 3239 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (F(3) \times F((F(F(4)) \times 5)))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\ 3240 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (F(3) \times F((F(F(4)) \times 5)))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\ 3241 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F((F(3) + (4+5+6))) + 7+8+9))) \\ 3242 &:= (F(F((-1+F(2 \times 3)))) \times (F((4+5+F(6))) + 7+8+9)) \\ 3243 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times (F((4+5+F(6))) + 7+8+9))) \\ 3244 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + (3+4+5)) \times F((6+7)))) - (8+9)) \\ 3245 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + (F((4+5+F(6))) + 7+8+9)))) \\ 3246 &:= (-1 - ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F(4+5)) - (F((6+7)) \times (8+9)))) \\ 3247 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (F((4+5+F(6))) + 7+8+9)))) \\ 3248 &:= (((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3))^{F(4)}) \times (5 + F(F(6)))) + 7+8+9) \\ 3249 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((F(3) \times (4-5-6-7)) - F(8+9)))) \\ 3250 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((F(3) \times (4-5-6-7)) - F(8+9))) \\ 3251 &:= (-1 \times ((F(2 \times 3)^4) + ((5 - F((6+7))) \times (8+9)))) \\ 3252 &:= (((-1-2) \times ((3 - F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \times F(F(6)))) - 7-8-9) \\ 3253 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3 \times 4+5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\ 3254 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4) + (F(5+6+7)/(8+9)))) \\ 3255 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3 - (F(4+5) \times (F(6) + 7+8+9)))) \\ 3256 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\ 3257 &:= (F(F((-1+F(2 \times 3)))) + (F((F(4) + 5)) \times (6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\ 3258 &:= ((-1-2) \times (F(3) - (F(4+5) \times (F(6) + 7+8+9)))) \\ 3259 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (F(3 \times 4+5) + F(F(6)))) + 7+8+9)) \\ 3260 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4) + (5 \times (F(6) + 7+8+9)))) \\ 3261 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3+4+5) - F(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\ 3262 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3+4+5) - F(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\ 3263 &:= (-1 + (((F(2 \times 3)^{F(4)}) + 5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\ 3264 &:= (((F((-1+2 \times 3))^{F(4)}) + 5+6) \times (7+8+9)) \\ 3265 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3+4+5) - F(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\ 3266 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 - (6-7-8-9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3227 &:= (((9 \times F(8)) + (7 \times F((6+5)))) \times 4) - F(F(3+2+1))) \\ 3228 &:= ((9-8-F(7)) \times (6 - (5 \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\ 3229 &:= ((9 \times F(8)) + ((F((7+F(6))) \times 5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\ 3230 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times F(7))) \times (F(6+5) - F(4+3+2+1))) \\ 3231 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (F((F(7) + (6-5))) - 4-3-2-1))) \\ 3232 &:= (((9 \times F(8)) + F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + (5-4-3-2-1))) \\ 3233 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (F(7) \times ((F(6) \times F(5+4)) - F(F(3+2+1)))))) \\ 3234 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times F(F(7)))) - ((6 \times 5) \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\ 3235 &:= (9-8 + ((7 \times (6+5)) \times (F(F(4)) \times F(F(3+2+1)))) \\ 3236 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7 + F(6)) - 5) \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\ 3237 &:= (9+8 + ((F(F(7)) + F(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\ 3238 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) - (F(F(7)) - (6 \times F(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\ 3239 &:= (-9 + (8 \times 7 \times (F(6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\ 3240 &:= ((-9-8+F(7+6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\ 3241 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + ((7^{F(6)-5}) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\ 3242 &:= (((-9-8-F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) - F(5+4))) - F(3+2+1)) \\ 3243 &:= ((-9 + ((F(8)-7) \times F((F(6)+5)))) - 4-3-2-1) \\ 3244 &:= (((-9-8-F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) - F(5+4))) - (3+2+1)) \\ 3245 &:= ((-9-8 - (F(7) - F(6+5))) \times F(4+3+2+1)) \\ 3246 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (F(F(7)) - F(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\ 3247 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + (F(6) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\ 3248 &:= (((-9 - (F(8) - F(F(7)))) \times (F(F(6)) + (5-4-3-2-1))) \\ 3249 &:= (-9 \times (8 + (F(F(7)) + (F(6) - F(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\ 3250 &:= (9 + (F(8) + ((F(F(7)) + F(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\ 3251 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7+6))) \times F(5+4)) + F(F(3+2+1))) \\ 3252 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times ((F(7) \times F(F(6))) - F(5+4-3-2-1))) \\ 3253 &:= (-9 + ((F(8)-7) \times F((F(6) - (5-4-3-2-1)))) \\ 3254 &:= (((-9+8+F(F(7))) \times ((6+5) + F(4))) + 3+2+1) \\ 3255 &:= ((-9+8 + (F(7) \times (F(F(6)) - 5-4)) \times F(F(3+2+1))) \\ 3256 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) \times (7 - F(F(6)))) + F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\ 3257 &:= (9 + (8 \times 7 \times (F(6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\ 3258 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) + (F(F(7)) - (6 + F(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\ 3259 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F((F(7) + (6-5)))) + F(4+3+2+1)) \\ 3260 &:= ((-9-8 + (7^{F(6)-5}) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\ 3261 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\ 3262 &:= (((-9+8+7) + F(6)) \times (F(5+4) - F(F(3+2+1)))) \\ 3263 &:= (-9 + (((F(8)-7) \times F((F(6)+5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\ 3264 &:= (9 - ((8 - (F(F(7)) - F(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\ 3265 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) + (7 \times F((6+5)))) \times (F(4) - F(3+2+1))) \\ 3266 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F((F(7) + (6-5)))) - F(4+3+2+1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3267 &:= (1 + 2 + ((F(3 + (4 + 5))) - F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3268 &:= (-1 + (((F(2 + 3)^4) \times 5) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3269 &:= (((1 + 2) + F(3 \times F(4))) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3270 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times F((F(3) + (F(4) + 5)))))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3271 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3 + F(4))) + ((5 + 6 + 7) + F(8 + 9)))))) \\
3272 &:= (((-1 + 2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3273 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 + (F(4 + 5) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3274 &:= (((1 + (F(2 + 3)^4) \times 5) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3275 &:= (1 \times F(2 + 3) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) + (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3276 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3^{F(4)})) \times (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3277 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 \times (4 - 5 - 6 - 7)) - F(8 + 9)))) \\
3278 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3+4})) \times (5 + F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3279 &:= (((-1 - 2 + F(3 \times F(4))) \times (5 \times F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3280 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times F(4 + 5))) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3281 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3) \times (4 + (5 + 6 + 7))) + F(8 + 9)))) \\
3282 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (F((3 \times 4)) - F(5 + 6 + 7))) + F(8 + 9))) \\
3283 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3 \times 4 + 5) + (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3284 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times F(3 \times F(4))) + 5) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3285 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + F(4 + 5)))) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3286 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) \times (F(4) + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3287 &:= (-1 + (((F(2 \times 3) \times 4) + (5 \times F(F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3288 &:= (((-1 + 2 + F(3 + 4 + 5)) - F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3289 &:= ((-1 + F(((2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))))) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3290 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) \times (F(4 + 5) - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3291 &:= (((-1 + (2^{F(3+F(4))})) \times (5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3292 &:= (-1 + (F((F(2 \times 3) + F(4))) \times (5 + (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3293 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3294 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3295 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F(3) - (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3296 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3297 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3298 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3) \times (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3299 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F((F(3) + (F(4) + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3300 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3301 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3302 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times ((F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9))) \\
3303 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3304 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3))^4) \times (5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3305 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3306 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (((3 + 4) \times (5 - (6 + 7))) - F(8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3267 &:= (-9 \times (8 + (F(F(7)) + (6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3268 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) \times (F(7) - (6 \times 5)))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3269 &:= ((9 \times F(8)) + (7 \times (F(6) \times (F(5 + 4) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3270 &:= (((-9 - F(8)) \times F(7)) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3271 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
3272 &:= (((9 - 8 + F(7)) \times F((F(6) + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3273 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) - ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3274 &:= (-9 - (F((F(8) - 7)) - (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3275 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) - F(((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3276 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) \times (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3277 &:= ((-9 - 8 \times F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3278 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) + F(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
3279 &:= (9 - ((F(8) - (F(F(7)) + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3280 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times F(7)) + F((F(6) + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3281 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
3282 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7)) \times F(F(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3283 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (((7 \times F(6)) + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3284 &:= ((9 \times (F((F(8) - 7)) - (6 + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3285 &:= ((9 \times 8 + (7 \times F(F(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3286 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + (F(6) \times 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3287 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7 + 6))) - F(((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3288 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7) + (F(6) + 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3289 &:= ((9 \times (F((F(8) - 7)) - 6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3290 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (F((6 + 5)) + (F(F(4)) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3291 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3292 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7)) \times F(F(6))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
3293 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) + F(F(7))) \times (F(6) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
3294 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (F((F(7) + (6 - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3295 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(7) + (F(6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3296 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) - ((7 + 6) \times F(5 + 4))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3297 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7)) \times (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3298 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) \times (6 + (5 + 4))) - F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3299 &:= ((9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3300 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5))) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3301 &:= (9 + (((F(8) + F(F(7))) \times (F(6) + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
3302 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (-7 + (6 \times 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3303 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) - F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3304 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3305 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times (F(6) \times 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3306 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + (F(7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

3307 := $(-1 + (2 \times (3 + ((F(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9))))$
3308 := $((-1 - 2 + ((F(3)^{F(4)+5}) \times (6 + 7))) - (8 + 9))$
3309 := $(-1 - 2 + ((F(3 + 4 + 5) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
3310 := $(-1 \times 2 + ((F(3 + 4 + 5) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
3311 := $(-1 + (((2 + F(3 + 4 + 5)) - F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
3312 := $((1 + 2) \times ((F(3) + 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
3313 := $(-1 + 2 + ((F(3 + 4 + 5) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
3314 := $(-1 - 2 + (((3 + F(F(4)))^5) + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
3315 := $((1 - (2^{F(3+F(4))})) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))$
3316 := $(-1 + (((F(F(2 + 3))^4) \times 5) + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
3317 := $(-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4 + 5) - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
3318 := $(-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4 + 5) - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
3319 := $(-1 - ((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 - (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3320 := $((-1 \times 2 - (3^4)) \times (5 - (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3321 := $((1 + 2) \times ((3 \times F((F(4) + (5 + 6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9))$
3322 := $((F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times (4^5)) + (F((6 + 7) + 8 + 9))$
3323 := $(1 - 2 + (3 \times (F(4) + (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))))))$
3324 := $(F(F((-1 - (2 - 3 - 4)))) \times ((5 \times (6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9)))$
3325 := $(-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times (4 + (5 + 6 + 7))) + F(8 + 9))))$
3326 := $(((-1 + (2^{3+4})) \times (5 + F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)$
3327 := $(-1 - ((2^{F(3+F(4))}) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))$
3328 := $(-1 \times ((2^{F(3+F(4))}) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))$
3329 := $(-1 + (2 \times ((3 + F(4 + 5)) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3330 := $((-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times F((F(4) \times 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
3331 := $(-1 - (2 \times ((3 - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7))) - F(8 + 9))))$
3332 := $(-1 \times 2 \times ((3 - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7))) - F(8 + 9)))$
3333 := $((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (F((F(4) \times 5)) + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
3334 := $(-1 \times 2 + ((F(3 \times F(4)) + (5 \times F(F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
3335 := $(1 - 2 + ((F(3 \times F(4)) + (5 \times F(F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
3336 := $((-1 + (2 \times ((3^4) - (5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$
3337 := $(-1 + (2 \times ((F(F(3 + 4)) \times 5) + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
3338 := $(-1 - 2 + (F(3 + 4) \times (F((5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3339 := $(-1 \times 2 + (F(3 + 4) \times (F((5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3340 := $(1 - 2 + (F(3 + 4) \times (F((5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3341 := $((-1 - (2^{F(3+F(4))})) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))$
3342 := $(-1 + 2 + (F(3 + 4) \times (F((5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3343 := $(-1 + 2 + (3 \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
3344 := $(((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times 4) \times (F((5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))$
3345 := $(-1 + 2 + ((F(3)^4) \times (F((5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)))$

3307 := $((-9 \times F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) + (6 \times F(5 + 4))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)))$
3308 := $(-9 \times 8 + (F(7) \times ((F(F(6)) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3309 := $(-9 - (F(8) \times (7 - ((F(6) - 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3310 := $(((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
3311 := $((-9 + ((8 + 7)^{F(6)-5})) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
3312 := $(F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3313 := $((-9 \times ((8 + F(F(7))) - F((6 + (5 + 4)))) - F(3 + 2 + 1))$
3314 := $((9 \times F((F(8) - 7))) - (F(6 + 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))$
3315 := $(9 + 8) \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
3316 := $((9 \times (F((F(8) - 7)) - F(6))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))$
3317 := $((-9 + (((8 \times F(7)) - 6) \times F(5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1))$
3318 := $((-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (F(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3319 := $(-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) - (6 - ((5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))))$
3320 := $((9 \times F(8)) + (F(7) \times (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
3321 := $(-9 \times ((8 + F(7 + 6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3322 := $((F(-9 + F(8)) \times ((7 + F(F(6))) - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$
3323 := $((9 + 8) \times (F(7) \times (6 + (5 + 4)))) + F(3 + 2 + 1)$
3324 := $((9 \times (F((F(8) - 7)) - 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
3325 := $(-9 - (F(8) - ((7 \times F(6)) + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3326 := $((9 \times (F((F(8) - 7)) - F(6))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))$
3327 := $((9 \times F((F(8) - 7))) - ((6 + 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3328 := $(-9 - (((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) - 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3329 := $((-9 \times ((8 + F(F(7))) - F((6 + (5 + 4)))) + F(3 + 2 + 1))$
3330 := $((-9 - 8 + (F(F(7)) + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
3331 := $(((-9 + F(8 + 7)) \times 6) - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3332 := $((-9 - (F(8) - F(7))) \times (F(6) - (F(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))$
3333 := $(-9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3334 := $(((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - 6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
3335 := $((9 \times F((F(8) - 7))) - (F(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3336 := $(-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (F((F(6) + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))$
3337 := $((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (F(F(6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3338 := $((9 \times F(((F(8)/7) + 6 + 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
3339 := $(-9 \times (F(8) - (7 \times ((6 - 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3340 := $((-9 + (F(8) + (F(F(7)) + F(6 + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
3341 := $(-9 - ((8 - (7^{F(6)-5})) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3342 := $((-9 \times ((8 + F(F(7))) - F((6 + (5 + 4)))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))$
3343 := $(-9 - 8 + (7 \times (F(6) \times (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3344 := $((9 \times (F((F(8) - 7)) - 6)) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))$
3345 := $(-9 - (F(8) - ((F(F(7)) - F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$

$$\begin{aligned} 3346 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((F(3) + (F(4 + 5) - F((6 + 7)))) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 3347 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((F(3) + (F(4 + 5) - F((6 + 7)))) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 3348 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((3 - F((F(4) \times 5))) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\ 3349 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F(3)^4)) \times (5 + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 3350 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times F(3 \times F(4)))) \times (5 + (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 3351 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3+4}) \times (5 + F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 3352 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3))^4 \times (5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 3353 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3 + 4) \times ((5 \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 3354 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) \times ((5 \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 3355 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3) \times F(4 + 5)) + ((6 + 7) + F(8 + 9)))) \\ 3356 &:= (((-1 + (F((2 \times (3 + 4)) + 5)) \times (6 + 7)) - F(8 + 9)) \\ 3357 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\ 3358 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4))) \times (5 \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 3359 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (F(3) \times F((F(4) \times 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 3360 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (F(3 + 4) \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 3361 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4))) \times (5 \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 3362 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) + ((F(4 + 5) - F((6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 3363 &:= (1 + 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4))) \times (5 \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 3364 &:= (-1 + (((2 + F(3)) \times (F(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7))) + F(8 + 9))) \\ 3365 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (F(4) \times (5 - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\ 3366 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) \times (F(4) \times (5 - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 3367 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) + (F((5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 3368 &:= ((-1 + ((F((2 \times (3 + 4)) + 5) \times (6 + 7)) - F(8 + 9)) \\ 3369 &:= (((F((-1 + 2 + F(3 + 4))) + 5) \times (6 + 7)) - F(8 + 9)) \\ 3370 &:= (((-1 + (F(F(2 + 3))^4) \times 5) + (F((6 + 7)) + 8 + 9)) \\ 3371 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times F((F(4) \times 5))) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 3372 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3 + 4 + 5) - (F((6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9)))) \\ 3373 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F((3 + F(F(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9))) \\ 3374 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(3 + 4)) \times (5 \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 3375 &:= (-1 \times ((F(F(2 + 3))^{F(4)} \times (5 - (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 3376 &:= (((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 \times 5))) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 3377 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) - ((F(4 + 5) - F((6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 3378 &:= (((-1 - 2 + (3 \times F((F(4) \times 5)))) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 3379 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) + ((F(4 + 5) - F((6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 3380 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (4 \times (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\ 3381 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 - F(((4 \times 5) - F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 3382 &:= ((-1 + F((F(2 + 3) \times 4)))/(5 + F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 3383 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (F(3 + 4) \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 3384 &:= (((-1 - 2 + F(F(3 + 4))) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 3385 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 - F(((4 \times 5) - F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3346 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) + 6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3347 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) \times (7 + 6 + 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3348 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) + (7 - (F(6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\ 3349 &:= (-9 - 8) \times ((F(7) \times 6) - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3350 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (F(7) + (6 \times 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3351 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) + 7) \times (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 3352 &:= (((9 \times F(8)) + (F(F(7)) + (6 - 5 - 4))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3353 &:= ((9 \times F((F(8) - 7))) + (F(6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\ 3354 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) + F(7))) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3355 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (F(F(7)) - (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 3356 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7)^{F(6)-5}) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\ 3357 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) + F(7)) \times (F(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3358 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) - F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3359 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (F(6) \times (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\ 3360 &:= ((-9 + F(F((8 + 7) - F(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3361 &:= (9 \times F(8) + F(F(7))) \times F(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\ 3362 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) + (((6 + 5)^{F(4)} + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3363 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F(7) \times ((F(F(6)) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 3364 &:= (9 - ((F(8) + (7 - F(6 + 5))) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3365 &:= (((9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\ 3366 &:= (-9 - ((8 - F(7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3367 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 \times F(F(6)) + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 3368 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + F(7))) + F((6 + (5 + 4)))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3369 &:= (9 + ((F(8) + 7) \times (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 3370 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(7) \times (F(F(6)) + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3371 &:= (((9 \times F(8)) + F(F(7))) \times F(6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\ 3372 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (7 \times (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\ 3373 &:= ((9 \times F((F(8) - 7))) - ((6 \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\ 3374 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) - F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3375 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + F(F(7))) - (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 3376 &:= ((-9 + (F(8 + 7) \times 6)) - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3377 &:= ((9 \times F((F(8) - 7))) - (F(F(6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\ 3378 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) \times F(7)) - (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 3379 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F(7) \times ((F(F(6)) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 3380 &:= (((-9 + F((F(8) - 7))) - (6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 3381 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) \times (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3382 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + (F((F(7) + 6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 3383 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8 + 7) - F((F(F(6)) - 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\ 3384 &:= (-9 - (F((F(8) - 7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 3385 &:= ((9 \times F((F(8) - 7))) - F((F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \end{aligned}$$

- 3386 := $(F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) - ((F(4 + 5) - F((6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9)))$
- 3387 := $((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - ((F((F(4) \times 5)) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)))$
- 3388 := $((-1 - 2 \times 3) \times ((4 \times 5) - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
- 3389 := $(-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
- 3390 := $((-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + F((F(4) \times 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
- 3391 := $(-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) - F(F((F(4) + 5)))) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))$
- 3392 := $((-1 + 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4))) \times 5)) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))$
- 3393 := $(F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times ((F((F(4) \times 5)) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))$
- 3394 := $(-1 + 2 + (3 \times ((F((F(4) \times 5)) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)))$
- 3395 := $((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) - (((F(4))^5 - F((6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9)))$
- 3396 := $(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) - ((F(4 + 5) - F((6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9)))$
- 3397 := $(-1 + (2 \times (F((F(3) + 4 + 5)) + ((6 + 7) + F(8 + 9))))$
- 3398 := $(-1 - (((2 - (3 \times F((F(4) \times 5)))) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))$
- 3399 := $(-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times (F(F((F(4) + 5)))) + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
- 3400 := $((-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times 4)) \times (5 - (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
- 3401 := $(-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))))$
- 3402 := $(-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))))$
- 3403 := $((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) - ((F(4 + 5) - F((6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9)))$
- 3404 := $((F(((F(-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times F(4))) - 5) \times (6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9))$
- 3405 := $(-1 - 2 - ((F(3) - F(((4 \times 5) - F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
- 3406 := $(-1 \times 2 - ((F(3) - F(((4 \times 5) - F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
- 3407 := $(-1 - ((2 - (F(F(3 + 4)) - F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
- 3408 := $(((-1 \times 2 + F(F(3 + 4))) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$
- 3409 := $(-1 + 2 - ((F(3) - F(((4 \times 5) - F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
- 3410 := $((-1 \times 2 \times F(F(3 + 4))) - ((5 - F((6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9)))$
- 3411 := $((-1 - 2) \times (((F(3) - F((F(4) \times 5))) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))$
- 3412 := $((F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times (4^5)) - (F((6 + 7)) - F(8 + 9)))$
- 3413 := $(-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3)^4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))))))$
- 3414 := $(-1 - 2 + ((F(3) - (F(4 + 5) - F((6 + 7)))) \times (8 + 9)))$
- 3415 := $(-1 \times 2 + ((F(3) - (F(4 + 5) - F((6 + 7)))) \times (8 + 9)))$
- 3416 := $(-1 + ((F(F(2 + F(3))) - (F(4 + 5) - F((6 + 7)))) \times (8 + 9)))$
- 3417 := $(-1 - 2 + (((3^4) - 5) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
- 3418 := $(-1 \times 2 + (((3^4) - 5) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
- 3419 := $(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F((F(4) + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$
- 3420 := $((-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) + F(F(4))) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
- 3421 := $(-1 + 2 + (((3^4) - 5) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
- 3422 := $(-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4) + (5 \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
- 3423 := $((-1 - 2 \times 3) \times ((F(4) \times 5) - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
- 3424 := $((-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times F((F(4) \times 5)))) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))$
- 3425 := $(-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times (((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9))))$
- 3386 := $((-9 \times F(8)) + (((7 + 6) \times 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
- 3387 := $(-9 + (F(8) + ((F(F(7)) - F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
- 3388 := $(-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
- 3389 := $(-9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times F(6)) + F(((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1))))$
- 3390 := $(((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
- 3391 := $((((-9 \times F(8)) + F(F(7))) \times F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
- 3392 := $(-9 + (F(8) + (F(7) \times ((F(F(6)) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
- 3393 := $(-9 \times (F(F((8 + 7) - F(6)))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
- 3394 := $((9 \times F((F(8) - 7))) + ((6 + 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))$
- 3395 := $((-9 \times F(8)) + (7 \times (F(6)^{5+4-3-2-1})))$
- 3396 := $(((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
- 3397 := $(-9 - (F(8) + (F(F(7)) - (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
- 3398 := $(((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) - (F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
- 3399 := $(-9 \times 8 - (F(7) \times (F(6) - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
- 3400 := $(((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) - (6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
- 3401 := $(((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + ((6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
- 3402 := $(-9 \times (F(8) \times ((7 + (6 \times 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
- 3403 := $((-9 \times (F(8 + 7) - F((F(6) - 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$
- 3404 := $(-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
- 3405 := $((-9 \times (8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5 + 4))))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))$
- 3406 := $(((-9 + F(8)) \times F(7 + 6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
- 3407 := $(-9 + (8 \times 7 \times (6 + (F(5 + 4) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))))$
- 3408 := $((-9 \times (F(8) + 7)) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
- 3409 := $(((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + (F(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))$
- 3410 := $(-9 - 8 - (F(F(7)) - (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
- 3411 := $(-9 \times (8 - (F((F(7) + (6 - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
- 3412 := $(((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
- 3413 := $(-9 - 8 + ((7^{F(6)-5}) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
- 3414 := $((9 \times F((F(8) - 7))) + (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
- 3415 := $(((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times (F(6) \times 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
- 3416 := $((F(-9 + F(8)) - F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$
- 3417 := $(9 + 8) \times ((F(7) \times (6 + (5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1)$
- 3418 := $((-9 + (F(8 + 7) \times 6)) - F((F(5 + 4) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))))$
- 3419 := $((9 + (F(8) + F(F(7)))) \times (F(6) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))$
- 3420 := $((-9 + (8 \times F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
- 3421 := $(-9 + ((F(8) + (F(F(7)) + F(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
- 3422 := $((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(F(6)))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
- 3423 := $(-9 \times 8 + (F(7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
- 3424 := $(((-9 \times F(8)) + (7 + F((6 + (5 + 4))))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1))$
- 3425 := $(-9 \times 8 - (F(7) \times (6 - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$

$$\begin{aligned}
3426 &:= (((-1-2+(3 \times F((F(4)) \times 5)))) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) & 3426 &:= (-9+8-(F(F(7))-(6 \times F(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3427 &:= (1 \times ((F(F(2 \times 3)) + F(F(4))) \times (5+(6 \times (7+8+9)))) & 3427 &:= ((-9+8) \times (F(F(7))-(6 \times F(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3428 &:= (F(F((-1+F(2+3)))) \times (((4+5) \times (6+7)) + F(8+9))) & 3428 &:= ((-9 \times (8-(F(7) \times (6 \times 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3429 &:= (-1-2+(F(3+4) \times ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) & 3429 &:= (-9+8+((7^{F(6)-5}) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
3430 &:= (-1 \times 2+(F(3+4) \times ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) & 3430 &:= ((9-8) \times ((7^{F(6)-5}) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
3431 &:= (-1+(F((F(F(2+3)) + F(F(4)))) \times ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) & 3431 &:= (F(9-F(8)) + (((7+6) \times 5) \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\
3432 &:= (F((-1+2) \times (3+4)) \times ((5+6) \times (7+8+9))) & 3432 &:= ((-9+(F(8) \times F(7))) \times (F(6)-(5-4-3-2-1))) \\
3433 &:= (-1+2+(F(3+4) \times ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) & 3433 &:= ((9 \times F((F(8)-7))) - (F(6) \times (5-4-3-2-1))) \\
3434 &:= (-1-(F(F(2 \times 3)) - (F(((4 \times 5) - F(6))) \times (7+8+9)))) & 3434 &:= (-9-8) \times ((7 \times (6-F(5+4))) - (3+2+1)) \\
3435 &:= (((-1-2) \times (F(3)-(F((F(4)) \times 5)) \times F(F(6)))) - 7-8-9) & 3435 &:= ((9+8+(F(F(7))-F(F(6)))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3436 &:= (-1 \times (F((2+F(3+4))) - ((5+F((6+7))) \times (8+9)))) & 3436 &:= (((-9+F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + (6 \times (5+4)))) - F(3+2+1)) \\
3437 &:= ((-1-2 \times 3) \times (F((F(F(4)) + 5)) - (F(F(6)) \times (7+8+9)))) & 3437 &:= ((9 \times F((F(8)-7))) - ((6+5) - F(4+3+2+1))) \\
3438 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) \times (F(F(4)) + ((5-F(F(6))) \times (7+8+9)))) & 3438 &:= (-9 \times (8+(F(7) \times (6 \times (5-4-3-2-1)))) \\
3439 &:= ((-1 \times 2+(3 \times (F((F(4)) \times 5)) \times F(F(6)))) - 7-8-9) & 3439 &:= ((-9-8) \times F(7)) + (6 \times F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3440 &:= ((-1-(F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F(F(4)))) \times (5 \times (F(6)-7-8-9))) & 3440 &:= (((-9+(8 \times 7 \times F(6))) - 5-4) \times F(3+2+1)) \\
3441 &:= (((-1+F((2+(3+4)))) \times (5 \times F(F(6)))) - 7-8-9) & 3441 &:= (F(9-F(8)) + ((F(F(7))+6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3442 &:= ((-1+2+(3 \times (F((F(4)) \times 5)) \times F(F(6)))) - 7-8-9) & 3442 &:= (((-9+(F(8) \times F(7))) \times (F(6)+5)) + 4+3+2+1) \\
3443 &:= (-1+(F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 \times 5+(6 \times (7+8+9)))) & 3443 &:= ((-9 \times 8+(F(7) \times (F(6) \times F(5+4)))) - F(F(3+2+1))) \\
3444 &:= (-1+(((2-F(F(3+4))) \times (5-(6+7))) + F(8+9))) & 3444 &:= ((-9+F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - ((6-5) - F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3445 &:= ((-1+(2 \times (3^{F(4)}))) \times (F(5+6)-7-8-9)) & 3445 &:= (((9 \times (8+7)) \times F(F(6))) + F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3446 &:= (-1-(((2-(3 \times F((F(4)) \times 5)))) \times F(F(6))) - 7-8-9) & 3446 &:= ((F(-9+F(8)) \times (F(7)+6+5)) - 4-3-2-1) \\
3447 &:= ((-1-2) \times (F(F(3)^4) - (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) & 3447 &:= (-9+(8 \times (F((F(7)+(6-5))) + F(4+3+2+1))) \\
3448 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) - (F(((4 \times 5) - F(6))) \times (7+8+9)))) & 3448 &:= ((9 \times F(((F(8)/7) + 6+5))) + F(4+3+2+1)) \\
3449 &:= (-1+((F(F(2 \times 3)) + F(F(4))) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 3449 &:= (-9+(F(8+7) + (F((6+5)) \times (4 \times F(3+2+1)))) \\
3450 &:= (1 \times ((F(F(2 \times 3)) + F(F(4))) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 3450 &:= (((-9-F(8)) \times 7) + (6 \times F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3451 &:= (-1-(2 \times (F(3) - ((4+5) \times (F(6) \times (7+8+9))))) & 3451 &:= ((-9-8) \times 7) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
3452 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - ((4+5) \times (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))) & 3452 &:= (-9+((8 \times F(7+6)) + F(((5+4) + F(3+2+1)))) \\
3453 &:= (-1-2+((F(F(3+4)) - F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) & 3453 &:= (((-9+8+F(F(7))) \times F(6)) + F(((5+4) + F(3+2+1)))) \\
3454 &:= (-1 \times 2+((F(F(3+4)) - F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) & 3454 &:= (-9-8-(F(7) \times (F(6) - (5 \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3455 &:= (-1+(F((F(F(2+3)) - (4-(5+6))) \times (7+8+9))) & 3455 &:= ((-9 \times (8-F(F(7)))) + ((F(F(6))+5) \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\
3456 &:= (F((-1 \times (F(2+F(3)) - (4+5+6)))) \times (7+8+9)) & 3456 &:= ((-9+F(8)) \times ((F(7) \times F(F(6))) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3457 &:= (-1+2+((F(F(3+4)) - F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) & 3457 &:= ((-9-8+(F(F(7)) \times (6+(5+4)))) - F(F(3+2+1))) \\
3458 &:= (F((-1+F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) & 3458 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) - (F(7) - (6 \times F(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3459 &:= (-1+(2 \times (F(3) + ((4+5) \times (F(6) \times (7+8+9))))) & 3459 &:= (((-9+8+F(F(7))) \times (6+(5+4))) - F(F(3+2+1))) \\
3460 &:= ((-1+F(2+3)) + (F(((4 \times 5) - F(6))) \times (7+8+9))) & 3460 &:= ((9 \times (F((F(8)-7)) + F(6))) + (5-4-3-2-1)) \\
3461 &:= (-1+(2 \times (3+((4+5) \times (F(6) \times (7+8+9))))) & 3461 &:= (-9+((F((F(8)-7)) - (6 \times 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
3462 &:= (((-1+2+(3 \times F((F(4)) \times 5))) \times F(F(6))) - 7-8-9) & 3462 &:= ((-9+(F(8+7) \times 6)) - ((5+4) \times F(F(3+2+1)))) \\
3463 &:= (-1+(F(2 \times 3) + (F(((4 \times 5) - F(6))) \times (7+8+9)))) & 3463 &:= (-9+(8 \times (((7+6) \times F(5+4)) - F(3+2+1))) \\
3464 &:= (-1+(F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (((4+5) \times F(F(6))) - 7-8-9))) & 3464 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) - (7 - (6 \times F(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3465 &:= ((F(F((-1+F(2 \times 3)))) \times (F(4) \times 5)) - (6+7+8+9)) & 3465 &:= (-9-(F(8) - (F(7+6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3466 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3+4+5) \times (6+7)) + F(8+9))) \\
3467 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3468 &:= ((-1 + ((2 - F(F(3+4))) \times 5)) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3469 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + (F(((4 \times 5) - F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3470 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + F(3+4)) \times F((5 + F(6))))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3471 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) \times (4 + 5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3472 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) \times (F(4) + (5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3473 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (F(3+4) - (5 \times F((6+7)))))) + 8 + 9) \\
3474 &:= (-1 - ((F(F(2+3))^{F(F(4))}) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3475 &:= (-1 \times ((F(F(2+3))^{F(F(4))}) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3476 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4+5) - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3477 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) \times (F(4) \times 5)) + (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3478 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F((3 \times 4)) - 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3479 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3480 &:= (((-1 + 2 + F(F(3+4))) - F(5+6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3481 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F((3 \times 4)) - 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3482 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 + F(3))^{F(4)}) \times ((5 \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3483 &:= ((-1 - (2³⁺⁴)) \times (5 - (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3484 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (4 + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3485 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
3486 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 \times (F((F(F(4) \times 5)) \times F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3487 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times (F((F(F(4) \times 5)) \times F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3488 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (F(F(3+4)) \times 5)) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
3489 &:= (((-1 + F((2 + (3+4)))) \times (5 \times F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3490 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3+4) \times (5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3491 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3+4) \times (5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3492 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (F(F(3+4)) \times 5)) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3493 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(F(3+4)) \times (5 \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
3494 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3+4) \times (5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3495 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) - ((5+6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
3496 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F(F(3+4)) \times (5 \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
3497 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F((3 \times 4)) - ((5 - (6+7)) - F(8+9)))) \\
3498 &:= ((1 - 2 - (F(F(3+4)) \times 5)) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3499 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) \times 4) + (F(5+6+7) - (8+9))) \\
3500 &:= (-1 - ((2 + (F(F(3+4)) \times 5)) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3501 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - (F(F(3+4)) \times 5)) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3502 &:= (1 - ((2 + (F(F(3+4)) \times 5)) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
3503 &:= (-1 + (((2 + F(F(3+4))) - F(5+6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3504 &:= ((-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 - (5+6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3466 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) + 6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3467 &:= (-9 - (F(8) + (F(7) \times (6 - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3468 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + ((6 - 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3469 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + F(((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3470 &:= (-9 + 8 - (F(7) \times (F(6) - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3471 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + F(7))) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3472 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times (6 + (5 + 4))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3473 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + 7) \times (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3474 &:= ((-9 - F((F(8) - 7))) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3475 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) + (6 + F(((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3476 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7) \times ((6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3477 &:= (9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3478 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F(7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3479 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 + 6) \times F(5 + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3480 &:= ((-9 + 8 + F(7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3481 &:= (((-9 + 8 + (F(7) \times F(6))) \times F(5 + 4)) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3482 &:= ((9 \times (F((F(8) - 7)) + 6 + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3483 &:= (9 - F(8) + (F(7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3484 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + (F(7) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3485 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7) \times (F(6) + 5)))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3486 &:= (-9 + (F(F(((8 + 7) - F(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3487 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) - 7) \times F(F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3488 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times (6 + (5 + 4))) + F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3489 &:= (((9 - 8 + F(F(7))) \times (6 + (5 + 4))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3490 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + (F(7) \times (F(6) + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3491 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (F(7) \times 6)) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3492 &:= (9 \times ((F(8) \times (7 + 6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3493 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(7) \times (6 \times 5)))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3494 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F(7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3495 &:= (F((F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) - F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3496 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times F((F(6) + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3497 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (F(7) \times (6 - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3498 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) - ((6 + 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3499 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + F((F(7) + 6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3500 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) + (F(7) \times (F(F(6) + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3501 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (7^{F(6)-5})) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3502 &:= ((9 \times (F((F(8) - 7)) + 6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3503 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (((7 + 6) \times 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3504 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) \times 7) - (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3545 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(F(2+3))) \times (F(4+5) \times F(F(6)))))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3546 &:= ((F(F(F(F(F((-1+2 \times 3)))))) \times (F(4+5) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3547 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F(3 \times F(4)) \times (5 \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3548 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) + ((F(F(4)) + 5) \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3549 &:= (-1 + ((2 - F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3550 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) - ((F(F(4)) \times F(5 + 6 + 7)) - F(8 + 9))) \\
3551 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (F(3 + 4 + 5) + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3552 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + (4 - F((5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3552 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + (4 - F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3553 &:= (-1 + ((F((2 + F(3 + 4))) \times 5) + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3555 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times (4 \times 5))) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3556 &:= ((-1 + F((F(F(2 \times 3)) - F(F(4)))) - ((5 + F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3557 &:= (F((-1 + (F(2 + 3) \times 4)) - ((5 + F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3558 &:= (-1 \times (((F(F(2 \times 3)) - F((F(4) \times 5))) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3559 &:= (-1 - (F((F(2 \times 3) + F(4)) \times (5 - (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3559 &:= (-1 - (F((F(2 \times 3) + F(4)) \times (5 - (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3560 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4 + 5) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3561 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3563 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) \times (5 + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3564 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
3565 &:= (((-1 - F(2 + 3)) + (F(F(4)) \times F(5 + 6 + 7))) - F(8 + 9)) \\
3566 &:= (((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) + (F(F(4)) \times F(5 + 6 + 7))) - F(8 + 9)) \\
3567 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (F(3 \times F(4)) \times 5)) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3568 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) - (F(4)^5)) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3569 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times F((F(4) \times 5))) - (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3570 &:= (((-1 + (F(2 + 3)^{F(4)}) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3571 &:= (F((-1 - 2 + F(F(3 + F(4)))) + F(((5 \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
3572 &:= (((-1 + 2)^{F(3)}) + ((F(F(4)) \times F(5 + 6 + 7)) - F(8 + 9))) \\
3573 &:= (((-1 + (F(F(2 + 3)) \times F(4 + 5))) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3574 &:= (-1 + (F((F(F(F(2 + 3))) \times F(F(4)))) \times (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
3575 &:= ((-1 + 2 - F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3576 &:= ((((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times F(4)) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3577 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times 4^5) + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3578 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times (F(4) + F(5 + 6 + 7)))) - F(8 + 9)) \\
3579 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 + 3)) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3580 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 + 3)) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3581 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3582 &:= (((((-1 - 2) \times 3) + F((F(4) \times 5))) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3583 &:= (-1 + ((F((F(2 \times 3) + F(4))) \times (5 \times F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3584 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) \times F(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3545 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (((7 + 6) \times 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3546 &:= (((-9 + F(8 + 7)) \times 6) - (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3547 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times F(7)) - (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3548 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7 + 6)) \times F(5 + 4)) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3549 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3550 &:= ((9 \times 8 - (7 - 6)) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3551 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) - F((F(7) + (6 - 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3552 &:= ((-9 + 8 + F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3553 &:= ((9 \times F((F(8) - 7))) + ((F(F(6)) \times 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3554 &:= ((-9 - 8 + F((F(7) + 6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3555 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3556 &:= (((-9 + F(8 + 7)) \times 6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3557 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) \times 7)) + (F(6) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3558 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((7 + 6) \times 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3559 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + 6))) + F(((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3560 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - F(F(7))) \times (F(6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
3561 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) + F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
3562 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - 7) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
3563 &:= (F((-9 + (F(8) + 7))) - (F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3564 &:= ((9 \times F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) - F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3565 &:= (F((-9 + (F(8) + 7))) - (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3566 &:= (9 + (((8 \times (7 + 6)) \times F(5 + 4)) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3567 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) - (7 + F((6 + (5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3568 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3569 &:= (9 - ((F(8) - F((F(7) + (6 - 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3570 &:= ((-9 + 8 + F((F(7) + 6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3571 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) - (F(F(7)) - (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3572 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) \times 7)) + (F(6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3573 &:= (-9 \times ((F(8)/7) - (F(6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3574 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((7 + 6) \times 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3575 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (F(7) - (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3576 &:= (F((-9 + (F(8) + 7))) - ((6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3577 &:= (F((-9 + (F(8) + 7))) + (6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3578 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times (F(F(6)) + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3579 &:= (F((-9 + (F(8) + 7))) + (F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3580 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3581 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3582 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (F(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3583 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + (F((F(7) + 6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3584 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3625 &:= ((-1 - F((2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3626 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((3 + F(F(4)))^5 + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3627 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (F((F(4) \times 5)) \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 3628 &:= (-1 + (((F(2 + 3)^4 \times 5) + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3629 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times F((F(4) \times 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3630 &:= ((-1 + (F((2 + F(3 + 4))/5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3631 &:= (((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) + (F((F(4) \times 5)) \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 3632 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (F(F(3 + 4)) - 5)) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 3633 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (F((F(3) + F((F(F(4) + 5)))) \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 3634 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) + (F((F(4) \times 5)) \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 3635 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times F((4 + 5 + 6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 3636 &:= ((F((-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times (4 + 5)))) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 3637 &:= (((-1 + 2)^{F(3)} + (F((F(4) \times 5)) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 3638 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + (F((F(4) \times 5)) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 3639 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) + (F((F(4) \times 5)) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 3640 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + (F((F(4) \times 5)) \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 3641 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) \times F((F(4) \times 5))) + (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
 3642 &:= (((((-1 + 2)^{F(3)} + F((F(4) \times 5))) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 3643 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) \times F((F(4) \times 5))) + (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
 3644 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 + 3)) \times (F(4)^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9})) \\
 3645 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3 + 4 + 5) + F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3646 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3 + 4 + 5) + F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3647 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((F(3 + 4) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3648 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((F(3 + 4) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3649 &:= (-1 - ((2 + F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3650 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3651 &:= (((-1 + 2 + F(3 \times F(4))) \times (5 \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 3652 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + ((3 + F((F(4) \times 5))) \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 3653 &:= (-1 + (((F((2 + F(3 + 4))) - 5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3654 &:= ((-1 + F((2 + F(3 + 4)))) \times (5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 3655 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((3 + F((F(4) \times 5))) \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 3656 &:= ((((-1 + (2 \times F(F(3 + 4)))) - 5) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 3657 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (F(3) \times F((F(4) \times 5)))) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 3658 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
 3659 &:= (-1 + ((F((2 + F(3 + 4))/5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3660 &:= ((1 \times F((2 + F(3 + 4))/5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3661 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F(3) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
 3662 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times F((F(4) \times 5)))) - (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 3663 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times F(F(3 + 4))) - 5) \times F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 3664 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3 + 4)) - 5)) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3625 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 3626 &:= ((9 \times F((F(8) - 7))) + F((F(6) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
 3627 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + ((F(F(7)) + F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3628 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) + (6 + F(((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3629 &:= (-9 + ((8 - (F(F(7)) - (6 + 5))) \times (4 - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3630 &:= (-9 - 8 - (F(7) - (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3631 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) + 7) \times ((F(6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3632 &:= ((-9 - ((F(8) \times 7) - F((6 + (5 + 4)))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3633 &:= (((-9 \times F(8))/7) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3634 &:= ((9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3635 &:= (9 - (F(8) + (F(7) - (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3636 &:= ((-9 - 8 - 7) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3637 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (7 + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3638 &:= ((-9 + (F(8 + 7) \times 6)) - (F(5 + 4) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3639 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3640 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - (F(7) - F((F(6) + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3641 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) - (F(7) \times (6 - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3642 &:= ((-9 \times F(F(8)/7)) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3643 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (F(7) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3644 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) + (F(7) \times (6 \times 5)))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3645 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) - (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3646 &:= (-9 + 8 - (F(7) - (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3647 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (F(7) - (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3648 &:= (-9 - ((F(8)/7) - (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3649 &:= (-9 - (F(F(8)/7) - (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3650 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3651 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) - F(F(6))) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3652 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3653 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3654 &:= (-9 + ((F(8)/7) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3655 &:= (9 - F(8) + (7 + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3656 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F(7) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3657 &:= ((-9 / (F(8)/7)) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3658 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6)))) + ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3659 &:= (-9 + F(8) - (F(7) - (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3660 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(7)) - 6) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3661 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) - ((7 - F(F(6))) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3662 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F(7) \times (F(6) + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3663 &:= (-9 + ((F((F(8)/7)) + F((6 + (5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3664 &:= 9 + 8 - F(7) + 6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3665 &:= ((-1 + ((F((2 + F(3 + 4))) + 5) \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) & 3665 &:= (-9 + F(8) - (7 - (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3666 &:= (((-1 - 2 + F((F(3) + F((F(4) + 5)))))) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 & 3666 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3667 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((3 - F((F(4) \times 5))) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 3667 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) + F(F(7)))) \times (6 + (5 + 4))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3668 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 \times 5 + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3668 &:= (F(-9 + 8 + 7) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3669 &:= ((-1 - 2 - (F(3) \times F((F(4) \times 5)))) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 3669 &:= (-9 + (((F(8)/7) + F((6 + (5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3670 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (((F(3) - F((F(4) \times 5))) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 3670 &:= (((-9 + F((F(8) - 7))) - (6 - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3671 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (F((3 \times 4)) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 3671 &:= 9 + F(F(8)/7) + 6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3672 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (F(3 + 4) - F(5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) & 3672 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F(7) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3673 &:= (((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F(F(4)))) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) & 3673 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (F(7) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3674 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - ((F(F((F(4) + 5))) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) & 3674 &:= (9 - 8 + (F(7) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3675 &:= ((-1 - 2 - F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3675 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) + F(7 + 6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3676 &:= ((-1 + F(((2 \times (3 + 4)) + 5))) - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 3676 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7 + 6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3677 &:= (F((-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times (4 + 5)))) - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 3677 &:= (-9 + ((F(8 + 7) \times 6) + (F(5 + 4) - F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3678 &:= (((-1 + F(((2 \times 3) + 4 + 5))) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) & 3678 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8)/7)) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3679 &:= (-1 - (((2 + F(F(3 + 4))) - 5) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) & 3679 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + (7 + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3680 &:= ((-1 - 2 + F(F(3 + 4))) \times ((5 \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 3680 &:= ((-9 + F(((F(8)/7) + 6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3681 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 - F(F((F(4) + 5)))) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) & 3681 &:= (F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3682 &:= (F((-1 + (F(2 + 3) \times 4))) + (5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3682 &:= ((9 \times 8 \times ((7 \times F(6)) - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3683 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) \times F((4 + 5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3683 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) + F(F(7)))) \times (6 + (5 + 4))) + F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3684 &:= ((F((-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times (4 + 5)))) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) & 3684 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3685 &:= (((-1 + 2)^{F(3)}) + ((F((F(4) \times 5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3685 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + (F(7) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3686 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + ((F((F(4) \times 5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3686 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + (F(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3687 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) + ((F((F(4) \times 5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3687 &:= (-9 + (8 \times 7 \times ((6 + 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3688 &:= (((-1 + 2 - F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 - F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) & 3688 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (7 \times F(F(6)))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3689 &:= (1 \times F(2 + 3) + ((F((F(4) \times 5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3689 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3690 &:= ((F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))))/F((F(4) \times 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3690 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (7 + 6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3691 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) \times F((F(4) \times 5))) + (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3691 &:= (((9 \times F(8)) - F(7)) \times F(F(6))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
3692 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (((4 + 5) \times F((6 + 7))) + F(8 + 9))) & 3692 &:= ((9 + 8) \times F(F(7))) + (6 - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3693 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times F((F(3) + 4 + 5)))) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) & 3693 &:= (-9 + ((F(8 + 7) \times 6) + (F(5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3694 &:= (((-1 + F(((2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) \times (5 + F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) & 3694 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (F(F(7)) \times F(6))) \times F(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
3695 &:= (1 - 2 + ((F(3) - F(F((F(4) + 5)))) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) & 3695 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 \times F(F(6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3696 &:= ((-1 + 2 + F(3 + 4)) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 3696 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3697 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3) - F(F((F(4) + 5)))) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) & 3697 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F((7 + F(6))) + (5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3698 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (F(F((F(4) + 5))) \times F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) & 3698 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
3699 &:= (((-1 + 2 + F(3 \times F(4))) \times (5 \times F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) & 3699 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (F((F(7) + (6 - 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3700 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - (F(F((F(4) + 5))) \times F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) & 3700 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times F(7))) - F(F(6))) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3701 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((F(F(3 + 4)) \times (5 - F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3701 &:= (-9 + ((F(8 + 7) \times 6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3702 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((F(F(3 + 4)) \times (5 - F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3702 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) - 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3703 &:= (-1 - ((F(F((F(F(F(2 + 3)))) + F(F(4)))) \times (5 - F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) & 3703 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3704 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times F(F(3 + 4)))) - 5) \times F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9) & 3704 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + (F(F(7)) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3705 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((F(F(3+4)) \times (5 - F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3706 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) + (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
 3707 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times F((4+5+6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3708 &:= (((-1 + (F((2 + F(3+4))) + 5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 3709 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) \times F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 3710 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (F(3) \times (4+5))) \times F((6+7))) + 8 + 9)) \\
 3711 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times F(F(3+4))) - 5) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 3712 &:= ((-1 + F(F((F(F(F(F(2+3)))) + F(F(4)))))) \times ((5 \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 3713 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) \times F(5+6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 3714 &:= (((F(F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3)))) + F((F(4) \times 5))) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 3715 &:= (-1 - (((2 - F(3 \times 4))) \times (5 + F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 3716 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 + F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 3717 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F((3 \times 4)) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3718 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F((3 \times 4)) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3719 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times F((F(4) \times 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3720 &:= ((-1 + ((F(F(2+3))^{F(F(4))} \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3721 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F((3 \times 4)) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3722 &:= ((-1 - F(2+3)) - (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 3723 &:= ((-1 \times F(2+3)) - (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 3724 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2+3))^{F(F(4))} \times (5 + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3725 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(F(3+4)) \times ((5 \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 3726 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(F(3+4)) \times ((5 \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 3727 &:= (-1 - (F((2 + (F(3) + 4 + 5))) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 3728 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) \times (F(4) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 3729 &:= ((-1 + F((2 + (3 + 4)))) \times (F(5+6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3730 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2+3))) - (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 3731 &:= (F((-1 + F(2+3)) - (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 3732 &:= (-1 + (F((F(F(2 \times 3)) - 4)) + (F(5+6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3733 &:= (F((-1 + 2 + (F(3)⁴))) + (F(5+6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3734 &:= (-1 + (F(F(F(F(2+3)))) \times ((F(4)⁵ + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3735 &:= (-1 - (((2 + F(F(3+4))) \times (5 - F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 3736 &:= (((-1 + 2 - F(F(3+4))) \times (5 - F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 3737 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4+5) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3738 &:= (1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4+5) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3739 &:= (-1 - ((F(2+3) \times 4) \times (5 - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3740 &:= ((-1 \times (F(2+3) \times 4)) \times (5 - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3741 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times F((F(3) + 4 + 5))) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 3742 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(F(3 + F(4))) + 5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3743 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F((3 \times 4)) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
 3744 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F((3 \times 4)) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3705 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(7))) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3706 &:= (-9 + ((F(8+7) \times 6) + (F(5+4) + F(F(3+2+1)))) \\
 3707 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3708 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3709 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) + F((F(6) + 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 3710 &:= ((9 + ((F(8) \times F(7)) + F(6+5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3711 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) + (F(F(7)) - 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3712 &:= ((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
 3713 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (F(6+5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
 3714 &:= ((9 + F(8+7)) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3715 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + (F((F(7) + 6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3716 &:= (9 - F(8) + (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
 3717 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) - 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 3718 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - (7 - 6)) \times (F(5 + 4) - F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3719 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + (((7 + 6) \times 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3720 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(7) \times F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3721 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3722 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 3723 &:= (-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times F(6)) - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3724 &:= ((-9 + 8 - F(7)) \times (6 - (F(5 + 4) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3725 &:= ((9 + 8 \times 7) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3726 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (F(F(7)) + F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3727 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
 3728 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
 3729 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3730 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (F(7) \times (6 \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3731 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) + F(7)) \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3732 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(7) + F((6 + (5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3733 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((7 \times F((6 + 5))) + F(F(4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3734 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 3735 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(7) \times (F(F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3736 &:= (((9 + (8 \times F(F(7)))) \times F((F(6) - 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 3737 &:= (9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) \times F((F(6) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))))) \\
 3738 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3739 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times F(7)) + 6) \times F(5 + 4)) + F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3740 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 + 5))) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 3741 &:= (-9 + ((F(F(8) - 7)) - F((F(6) - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3742 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) - (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3743 &:= ((9 \times (F((F(8) - 7)) + (F(6) \times 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 3744 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times 7) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3745 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(F(3 + F(4))) + 5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3746 &:= (((-1 + 2 + F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 + F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3747 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + (F((F(F(4)) + 5)) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3748 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) - (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
3749 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 + 3))^{F(F(4))}) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3750 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times F(3 + 4))) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3751 &:= (-1 - ((F(F((F(F(F(2 + 3)))) + F(F(4)))) \times (5 - F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3752 &:= (((-1 - 2 - F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 - F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3753 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((F(F(3 + 4)) \times (5 - F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3754 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3^{F(4)}) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
3755 &:= ((1 + 2 - (F(F(3 + 4)) \times (5 - F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3756 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times ((4 + 5) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3757 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times F((3 \times 4)))) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3758 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F((F(F(4)) + 5)) - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3759 &:= (-1 - (F(2 \times 3) \times (F(4 + 5) - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3760 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) \times (F(4 + 5) - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3761 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) \times F(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3762 &:= ((-1 - 2 + F(F(3 + F(4)))) \times (F((5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3763 &:= (((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (4 + 5)) + (F((6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9))) \\
3764 &:= (1 \times 2 + (((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times F((6 + 7))) - F(8 + 9)) \\
3765 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 - ((4 \times 5) \times F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3766 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4 + 5) + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3767 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (F((3 \times 4)) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3768 &:= (-1 \times ((F(F(2 \times 3)) - (F(F(4)) \times F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3769 &:= (1 + ((2 + (F((3 \times 4)) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3770 &:= ((1 \times F(F(2 + 3))) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3771 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 + F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3772 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - ((F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3773 &:= (-1 + (((F(F(2 + 3))^{F(4)}) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3774 &:= (((F((-1 + 2 \times 3))^{F(4)}) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3775 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (F(F(3 + 4)) + 5)) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
3776 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3 + 4)) + 5))) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3777 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 + F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
3778 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times ((F(4)^5) + 6 + 7))) - F(8 + 9)) \\
3779 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (F((F(4) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3780 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (F(3))^{F(F(4)+5)}) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3781 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + ((F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3782 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times F((F(3) + 4 + 5))) - (F((6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
3783 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times ((F(4) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3784 &:= (((-1 \times 2 - F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 - F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3745 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times F(7))) \times (F(6) \times 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3746 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) - (F(7) + F(F(6)))) \times F(5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3747 &:= (9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) - F(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3748 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times F(7)) + (F(F(6)) \times ((5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3749 &:= (F((-9 + (F(8) + 7))) - (F(6) \times ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3750 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + ((6 - 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3751 &:= (-9 + ((F((F(8) - 7)) - (6 - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3752 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times F(F(7))) + F(F(6)))) \times F(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
3753 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F((F(7) + (6 - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3754 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3755 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times F(7)) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3756 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) + (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3757 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) - 7) \times (6 - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3758 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (7 \times (F(F(6)) + 5)))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3759 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) + F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3760 &:= ((-9 + 8 + F((F(7) + (6 - 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3761 &:= (-9 + (F(((F(8)/7) + 6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3762 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) - ((7 - F((6 + (5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3763 &:= ((9 \times (F((F(8) - 7)) + (F(6) \times 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3764 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (F(F(7)) - (6 + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3765 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) + (F(F(7)) + 6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3766 &:= ((-9 + 8 - F(7)) \times (6 - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3767 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) - 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3768 &:= (9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + ((6 - 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3769 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F((F(7) + (6 - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3770 &:= (F((-9 + (F(8) + (F(7) - (6 + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3771 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) - (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3772 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + (F(7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3773 &:= (9 + ((8 \times F(7)) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3774 &:= ((9 \times F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3775 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (F(6) \times (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3776 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (F(7) \times (F(F(6)) + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3777 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (F(7) + F((6 + (5 + 4))))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3778 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((7 - F(F(6))) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3779 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times F(7))) \times (6 + F(5 + 4))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3780 &:= ((-9 + 8 + F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3781 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + 7) \times F(F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3782 &:= (((9 + 8) \times 7) - F(6)) \times F(5 + 4)) + F(3 + 2 + 1) \\
3783 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + F((F(F(6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
3784 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 \times F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4)) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3825 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F(3)^4)) \times (5 \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3826 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(F(3 + 4)) + (5 - (6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 3827 &:= (-1 - ((2 + F(3)) \times (F(4) - (5 \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
 3828 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - F(3)) \times (F(4) - (5 \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3829 &:= (((-1 + (F(F(2 + 3))^{F(4)})) \times (5 + 6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9)) \\
 3830 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (F(3 + 4) \times 5)) - (F((6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 3831 &:= ((1 + F(2 + 3)) - ((F(4) + (5 - F((6 + 7)))) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 3832 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) - ((4 \times 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3833 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) + ((4 \times 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3834 &:= ((-F(F(-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + 4 \times 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 3835 &:= ((-1 \times F(F(2 + 3))) + ((4 \times 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3836 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) - ((4 \times 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3837 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3)^{F(F(4))+5}) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3838 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3)^{F(F(4))+5}) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3839 &:= (1 - 2 + ((F(3)^{F(F(4))+5}) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3840 &:= ((F(F(-1 + F(2 + 3)))^{F(F(4))+5}) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3841 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3)^{F(F(4))+5}) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3842 &:= (F((F(-1 + F(2 + 3))^{F(F(4))})) \times (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3843 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3 \times F(4)) \times (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3844 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + ((4 \times 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3845 &:= (F(F(F(F(-1 + 2 \times 3)))) + ((4 \times 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3846 &:= (-1 + (((F(F(2 + 3))^{F(4)})) \times (5 + 6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9)) \\
 3847 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) + ((4 \times 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3848 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times ((F(4 + 5) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3849 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times F(3 + 4)) + ((5 - F((6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 3850 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 + F(4 + 5))) + (F((6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 3851 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) + (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3852 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (F((F(4) + (5 + F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 3853 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3) - (F(4)^5)) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
 3854 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(3 + 4)) \times (F((5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3855 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(F(3 + 4)) + 5) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3856 &:= ((-1 - 2 - (F(F(3 + 4)) + 5)) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 3857 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3) - (F(4)^5)) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
 3858 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((F(3) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) + F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3859 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (F(3) - ((F(4)^5) \times F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3860 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) + ((4 \times 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3861 &:= ((-1 + 2 - F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 - (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3862 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (F(3) \times ((F(4)^5) \times F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 3863 &:= (1 - 2 + ((F(3) \times ((F(4)^5) \times F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3825 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times F(F(7))) + ((6^5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 3826 &:= ((9 \times 8 \times (F(7) + (F(6) \times 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 3827 &:= (9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3828 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (F(7) \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3829 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - ((F(F(7)) - 6) \times ((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3830 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7^{F(F(6)-5)}))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3831 &:= (-9 + ((F((F(8)/7))^{F(6)}) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3832 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - F((F(6) + 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 3833 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6)))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3834 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7 + 6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3835 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7 + 6)^{F(5+4-3-2-1)})) \\
 3836 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - (F(7) - 6)) \times (F(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3837 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) - 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 3838 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + (F((F(F(6)) - 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3839 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (F(7 + 6) - (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 3840 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3841 &:= (-9 + ((8 + F((F(7) + (6 - 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3842 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - F((F(6) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
 3843 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (((7 + 6) \times F(5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3844 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (F(F(7)) - (6 + 5))) \times F(F(4)))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3845 &:= (F((-9 + (F(8) + 7))) - (F(6) \times (F(5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3846 &:= ((9 + 8) \times F(F(7))) - ((F(F(6)) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 3847 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (F(F(7)) - 6)) + ((5 + 4) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3848 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times ((F(F(7)) - (F(F(6)) \times F(5 + 4))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3849 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 - F(F(6))) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3850 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) + F(6)) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3851 &:= (F((-9 + (F(8) + 7))) - (6 \times (F(5 + 4) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3852 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - F((F(6) + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 3853 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + (6 \times F(5 + 4)))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3854 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + F(6 + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 3855 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times F(7))) \times (F(6) \times 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3856 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times F(7)) - (F(F(6)) \times ((5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 3857 &:= (-9 + (((8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3858 &:= ((-9 + (F(8 + 7) + (F(6) + F(5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3859 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (F(7) - (F(6) \times ((5 + 4) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3860 &:= ((9 + F(((F(8)/7) + 6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3861 &:= (9 \times (((F(8) + F(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3862 &:= ((9 \times F(8)) + (F(7) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3863 &:= (((9 + (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times F(5 + 4)) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3903 &:= ((-1 + (2^{3+4+5})) - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3904 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3+4})) - 5) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3905 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times ((F(F(4)) \times (5 \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
3906 &:= ((-1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) + 5)) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3907 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (F(3) - ((F(4)^5) \times F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3908 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3909 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + ((4 \times 5) \times F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3910 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + ((4 \times 5) \times F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3911 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (F(3 + 4 + 5) + F(F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3912 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times ((3 + 4) - F(5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3913 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + ((4 \times 5) \times F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3914 &:= (-1 - ((2 - F((F(3) + 4 + 5))) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3915 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + F((F(3) + 4 + 5))) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3916 &:= ((-1 + F((F(F(2 \times 3)) - F(F(4)))) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3917 &:= (F((-1 + (F(F(2 + 3)) \times 4)) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3918 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((F(3) + (F(4)^5)) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
3919 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times ((F(F(4)) \times F((5 + F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3920 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) - (F(4)^5)) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3921 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((F(3) + (F(4)^5)) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
3922 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) - (F(4 + 5) - (F((6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
3923 &:= ((-1 + F((F(F(2 \times 3)) - F(F(4)))) - (F((5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3924 &:= (((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 + 5))) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3925 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(F(3 + F(4))) \times (5 - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3926 &:= (1 - 2 - (F(F(3 + F(4))) \times (5 - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3927 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4)) \times (5 - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3928 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F(F(3 + F(4))) \times (5 - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3929 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) + (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3930 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (((F(4)^5) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3931 &:= (-1 - ((2 + F(3)) \times (4 - F(((5 \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
3932 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - F(3)) \times (4 - F(((5 \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
3933 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 + (F(4)^5)) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
3934 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3 + (F(4)^5)) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
3935 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (((3 + 4) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3936 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (((3 + 4) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3937 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) \times (4 + 5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3938 &:= (1 + (((F(F(2 \times 3)) - 4) \times F((5 + F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3939 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 + 3) \times 4) \times (5 + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3940 &:= (1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times F(F(4)) \times F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3941 &:= (-1 - ((2 + F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 - (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3903 &:= (-9 + ((F(8 + 7) + (F(6) + F(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3904 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (F(F(7)) + (F(6) \times F(5 + 4)))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3905 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + (F(F(7)) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3906 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + (F(7) \times (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3907 &:= (9 - 8 + (F((F(7) + 6)) - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3908 &:= ((-9 + 8 + F((F(7) + 6))) - (F(5 + 4) \times F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3909 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times F(6))) \times (5 + 4))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3910 &:= (9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3911 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7^{F(F(6)-5)}) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3912 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + (F(7) \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3913 &:= ((9 + 8) \times F(F(7))) + (6 - ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3914 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + (F((F(7) + (6 - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3915 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - F(7)) \times F(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3916 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (F(F(7)) + (6 - 5 - 4))) + (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3917 &:= ((9 + 8) \times F(F(7))) + ((6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3918 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + (F((F(7) + 6)) - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3919 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + F(6 + 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3920 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) + F(F(7)))) \times (F(F(6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
3921 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3922 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) - F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + (5 + 4))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3923 &:= (-9 + ((F(8 + 7) \times 6) + (F(5 + 4) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3924 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(7)) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3925 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) - 7) \times (6 + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3926 &:= (((-9 - 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3927 &:= ((9 + 8) \times F(F(7))) - (F(6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3928 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + F((6 + (5 + 4)))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1) \\
3929 &:= (9 + (8 \times ((7^{F(F(6)-5)}) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3930 &:= ((-9 - F(8)) \times (F(7) - (F(6 + 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3931 &:= (-9 + (((F(8) \times (F(7) + 6)) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3932 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + (F((F(7) + 6)) - (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3933 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((F(7) \times (6 \times 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3934 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) - (7 \times (F(F(6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3935 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(7) + (F(6) \times (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3936 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3937 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (F(F(7)) - F((F(6) - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3938 &:= (F((-9 + (F(8) + 7))) - (F((F(6) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3939 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times (6 + (5 + 4))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3940 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) - F(7)) \times (6 \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3941 &:= (F((-9 + (F(8) + 7))) - (F(6) \times ((5 + 4) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4731 &:= ((-1 - F(2+3)) - (F(4) \times ((5+6+7) - F(8+9)))) \\
4732 &:= (-1 - (((2 - F(F(3)^4)) \times 5) + (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
4733 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + F(F(3)^4)) \times 5) - (F(6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
4734 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3/F(4) + ((5+6+7) - F(8+9)))) \\
4735 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 + (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4736 &:= ((-1 + (F(((2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) + 5)) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4737 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3+4)) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
4738 &:= (((-1 + F((F(2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))))) \times 5) - (F(6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
4739 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2+3)))) - (F(4) \times ((5+6+7) - F(8+9)))) \\
4740 &:= ((-1-2 + (F(F(3)^4) \times 5)) - (F(6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
4741 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - ((F(F(4))^{5+6}) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4742 &:= ((-1 + (F((F(2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) \times 5)) - (F(6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
4743 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2+3)) \times 4) \times 5) - (F(6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
4744 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F(F(3)^4) \times 5)) - (F(6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
4745 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) \times (F(5+6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4746 &:= (F((-1 + F(2+3))) \times (F(4) - ((5+6+7) - F(8+9)))) \\
4747 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (F(4) - ((5+6+7) - F(8+9)))) \\
4748 &:= (((-1 + 2 + F(F(3)^4)) \times 5) - (F(6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
4749 &:= ((((-1 - 2 + F(F(3+4))) - 5) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4750 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times ((4-5-6-7) + F(8+9)))) \\
4751 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (F(4) \times ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
4752 &:= ((-1 - 2 + F(F(3+F(4)))) \times ((5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
4753 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F((3 - (4-5))) \times ((6+7) - F(8+9)))) \\
4754 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2+3)))) + ((F(F(4)) - 5) \times ((6+7) - F(8+9)))) \\
4755 &:= (F((-1 + F(2+3))) + ((F(F(4)) - 5) \times ((6+7) - F(8+9)))) \\
4756 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F((F(4)) + 5))) + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4757 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3^{F(4)}) \times F(5+6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
4758 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - F((4+5 + F(6)))))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4759 &:= (-1 + (((2 + F(F(3+4)))/5) + F((6+7)) \times (8+9))) \\
4760 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (F(3)^{4+5}) - F((6+7))) \times (8+9)) \\
4761 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - F((4+5 + F(6)))))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4762 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + ((F(F(3+4)) - 5) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4763 &:= (1 - 2 + (((F(F(3+4)) - 5) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4764 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (3 \times F((4+5 + F(6)))))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4765 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times F((4+5 + F(6)))))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4766 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 + F(3)) \times F((4+5 + F(6)))))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4767 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2+3))) \times F((4+5 + F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4768 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3 \times F((4+5 + F(6)))))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4769 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + ((4+5) \times (F(F(6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
4770 &:= ((-1 + (F(2+3) \times (F(F(4))^5))) \times (6+7+8+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4811 &:= (1 - 2 + (((F(F(3 + 4)) - 5) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4812 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 \times F((4 + 5 + F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4813 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times F((4 + 5 + F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4814 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 + F(3)) \times F((4 + 5 + F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4815 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times F((4 + 5 + F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4816 &:= (((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)))^{F(F(4))}) \times (5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4817 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) - (F(4) \times ((5 - (6 + 7)) - F(8 + 9)))) \\
4818 &:= (((-1 - F((F(F(2 \times 3)) - 4))) \times (5 - F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4819 &:= (1 \times (((F(2 \times (3 + 4))) - 5) \times (6 + 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\
4820 &:= ((1 \times F(2 + 3)) \times (4 + (5 \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4821 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 - (F(4 + 5) \times 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4822 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3 - (F(4 + 5) \times 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4823 &:= (-1 - ((F(2 + F(3)) - (F(4 + 5) \times 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4824 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4 + F(5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4825 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 - (F(4 + 5) \times 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4826 &:= (1 \times 2 - ((3 - (F(4 + 5) \times 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4827 &:= (1 \times (((F(F(2 \times 3)))^{F(F(4))}) \times (5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4828 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((F(3) - F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4829 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((3^{F(4)}) \times F(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4830 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4)^5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4831 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (F((3 \times 4) + 5)) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4832 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times 3) + F((F(4) \times 5))) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4833 &:= ((((-1 + 2 + F(F(3 + 4))) - 5) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4834 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times F((F(4) \times 5)))) - (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4835 &:= (1 + 2 - (((3 - F((F(4) \times 5))) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4836 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (F(4) \times ((5 + 6 + 7) + F(8 + 9)))) \\
4837 &:= (-1 - 2 - (((F(3) - F((F(4) \times 5))) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4838 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (((F(3) - F((F(4) \times 5))) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4839 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 \times 3) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4840 &:= ((((-1 + 2 - 3) + F((F(4) \times 5))) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4841 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((F(3) - F((F(4) \times 5))) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4842 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4)^5)) + (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4843 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F(3) + ((4 - (5 \times F(F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4844 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4)^5)) + (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4845 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((F(3) - (F(4 + 5) \times 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4846 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((F(3) - (F(4 + 5) \times 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4847 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times 4 + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4848 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) + (F(4 + 5) \times 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4849 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times F((F(4) \times 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4850 &:= (-1 - ((2 - F(F(3 + 4))) \times F((5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4811 &:= ((-9 + (F(8 + 7) \times F(6))) - (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4812 &:= (F((-9 + (F(8) + 7))) + (F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4813 &:= (((-9 + F(8 + 7)) \times F(6)) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
4814 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7) + (F(F(6)) \times F((F(5 + 4) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4815 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (F(6) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4816 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7) \times (F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4817 &:= ((-9 + (F(8 + 7) \times F(6))) - ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4818 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times F(F(7)))) - ((6 + 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4819 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (F(F(7)) \times F(F(6)))) - F(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
4820 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) \times (6 \times 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4821 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (F(F(7)) \times (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4822 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4823 &:= (((-9 + F(8 + 7)) \times F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4824 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7 + 6))) - (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4825 &:= (((-9 + F(8 + 7)) \times F(6)) + ((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4826 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (F(F(7)) \times F(F(6)))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
4827 &:= (9 - ((8 \times (7 - F((6 + (5 + 4))))) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4828 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times F(F(7)))) - ((6 - 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4829 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times F(F(7)))) - F(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4830 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (F(6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4831 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (F(7) - (F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4832 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4833 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (F(F(7)) \times F(F(6)))) - ((5 + 4) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4834 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7 + 6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4835 &:= ((9 \times (8 - F(7))) + (F(6) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4836 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4837 &:= (-9 - (F(8) + (F(7) - (F(6) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4838 &:= ((F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) \times F((F(6) + 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4839 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times F(7)) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4840 &:= (F(-9 + 8 + 7) \times ((6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4841 &:= (9 - ((F(8) - F(7)) \times (6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4842 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) \times F(F(6)))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4843 &:= (-9 - (F(8) + (7 - (F(6) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4844 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + (F(6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
4845 &:= (9 + 8) \times ((F(7) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4846 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) + F(F(6)))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4847 &:= (-9 - (((F(8)/7) - F((6 + (5 + 4)))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4848 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times F(F(7)))) - (F(F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4849 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) + (F(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4850 &:= (-9 - 8 - (F(7) - (F(6) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4851 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + F(F(3+4))) \times F(F((5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
4852 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) \times (4 \times 5)) + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4853 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3^{F(4)}) \times F(5+6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4854 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (F((4+5 + F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4855 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times F((4+5+6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4856 &:= ((F((-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times (4+5)))) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4857 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - (F((4+5 + F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4858 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2+3)))) + ((F((F(4) \times 5)) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4859 &:= (F((-1 + F(2+3))) + ((F((F(4) \times 5)) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4860 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (3 \times F((F(F(4)) \times 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4861 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (F((4+5 + F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4862 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4863 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) \times F((F(4) + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4864 &:= (((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3))^{F(F(4))}) \times (5+6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4865 &:= ((-1 - F((2 + (3+4)))) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4866 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (F(F(3 \times 4 - 5)) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4867 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) + (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4868 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4869 &:= ((F((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4 + 5)))) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4870 &:= ((-1 + (F((F(F(2+3)) \times F(F(4)))) \times F(5+6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4871 &:= ((F((-1 - 2 + F(3+4))) \times F(5+6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4872 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (F(3+4) + F(5+6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4873 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(F(3+4)) - (5 \times 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4874 &:= (-1 + (((F(F(2 \times 3))^{F(F(4))}) \times (5+6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4875 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) - (F(4+5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4876 &:= ((-1 + (F((2 \times (3+4)) \times (5 + F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4877 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times F((F(4) + 5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4878 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4)^5)) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4879 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times F((F(F(4)) - ((5+6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
4880 &:= (((F((-1 + F(2+3))) + F((F(4) \times 5))) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4881 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((3 + F((F(4) \times 5))) \times F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4882 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) - F(F(4))) \times (F((5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4883 &:= ((-1 + (F(2+3) \times 4)) \times (F((5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4884 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4) - (5 \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4885 &:= (-1 - 2 - (((F(3) - F((F(4) \times 5))) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4886 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (((F(3) - F((F(4) \times 5))) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4887 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (F(4+5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4888 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) - (F(4+5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4889 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 \times F((F(F(4)) \times 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4890 &:= (((-1 - 2 + F(F(3)^4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4851 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (F((7 + F(6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4852 &:= (-9 - (F(8) + (F(7) - (F(6+5) \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4853 &:= (((-9 \times F(8))/7) + (F(6) \times F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4854 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + (6 \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
4855 &:= (9 - (F(8) + (F(7) - (F(6) \times F(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4856 &:= ((-9 - 8 - 7) + (F(6) \times F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4857 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4858 &:= (-9 - (F(8) + (7 - (F(6+5) \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4859 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + ((6 \times 5) - F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4860 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) + (F(F(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4861 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (F(F(7)) \times F(F(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4862 &:= ((-9 \times F(F(8)/7) + (F(6) \times F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4863 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (F(F(7)) \times (6 + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4864 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times F(F(7)))) - ((6 \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
4865 &:= (-9 - 8 - (F(7) - (F(6+5) \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4866 &:= (-9 + 8 - (F(7) - (F(6) \times F(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4867 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (F(7) - (F(6) \times F(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4868 &:= (-9 - ((F(8)/7) - (F(6) \times F(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4869 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7+6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4870 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7) + (F(6) \times F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4871 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) - (7+6)) \times F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4872 &:= ((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times (6 + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4873 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (F(6) \times F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4874 &:= (-9 + ((F(8)/7) + (F(6) \times F(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4875 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4876 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F(F(7)) \times (6 + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4877 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) \times F(F(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4878 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times F(F(7)))) - (F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4879 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((F(7) - F(F(6))) \times F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4880 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times ((F(7) - F(F(6))) \times F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4881 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) + F(F(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4882 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (F(7) - (F(6+5) \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4883 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times F(F(7)))) - ((6+5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
4884 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times F(((7 + F(F(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4885 &:= (-9 + F(8) - (7 - (F(6) \times F(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4886 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + (F(6) \times F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4887 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4888 &:= (F(-9 + 8 + 7) + (F(6) \times F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4889 &:= (-9 + ((F(8)/7) + (F(6+5) \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4890 &:= ((9 + 8 - 7) + (F(6) \times F(5+4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4891 &:= ((-1 \times F(F(2+3))) + (F(4+5) \times (6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
4892 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) - (F(4+5) \times (6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
4893 &:= (-1 \times (F(2+F(3)) - (F(4+5) \times (6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
4894 &:= (-1 - (((2 - F(F(3)^4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4895 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + F(F(3)^4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4896 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((F(F(3+F(4))) - F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
4897 &:= (((-1+2)^{F(3)}) + (F(4+5) \times (6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
4898 &:= (F(F((-1+F(2+3)))) + (F(4+5) \times (6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
4899 &:= (F((-1+F(2+3))) + (F(4+5) \times (6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
4900 &:= (((-1+F((F(2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) \times 5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
4901 &:= (-1 \times (F((2 \times (3+4))) \times ((5+6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
4902 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (F(F(3)^4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4903 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (F(F(3)^4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4904 &:= ((-1 + (F((F(2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4905 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2+3)) \times 4) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4906 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F(F(3)^4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4907 &:= (F((-1 + F(2+3))) + ((F((F(4) \times 5)) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4908 &:= ((-1 + F(2+3)) + ((F((F(4) \times 5)) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4909 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 \times 3) \times F((F(4) \times 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4910 &:= (((-1 + 2 + F(F(3)^4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4911 &:= (((-1 - 2 + (F(F(3+4)) + 5)) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4912 &:= (((-1 + F((2 \times (3+4)))) \times (5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4913 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
4914 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + F(F(3)^4)) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4915 &:= ((-1 \times F(2+3)) \times (4 - F(((5 \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
4916 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F((F(4) \times 5) + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4917 &:= ((F((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4 + 5)))) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4918 &:= (-1 + ((F((F(2+3)) \times F(F(4))) \times F(5+6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4919 &:= ((F((-1 - 2 + F(3+4))) \times F(5+6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4920 &:= (((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))^{F(F(4))}) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4921 &:= ((-1 + F(2+3)) + ((F(F((F(4) \times 5))) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4922 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F(F((F(4) \times 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4923 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) \times F((F(4) \times 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4924 &:= (-1 + ((F((2 \times (3+4))) \times (5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4925 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times F((F(4) \times 5) + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4926 &:= (-1 + (((2 + F(F(3)^4)) \times 5) + (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
4927 &:= ((-1 + (F(2+3) \times (4^5))) - (F(6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
4928 &:= (((F((-1 + F(2+3))) + F((F(4) \times 5))) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4929 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((3 + F((F(4) \times 5))) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4930 &:= (1 \times 2 + (((3 + F((F(4) \times 5))) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4891 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4892 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) \times (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4893 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times F(F(7)))) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4894 &:= (-9 + F(8) - (F(7) - (F(6+5) \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4895 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) + (7 \times (6+5)))) \times F(4+3+2+1)) \\
4896 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) + (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4897 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) \times F(F(6)))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
4898 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + (F(5+4) - F(3+2+1))) \\
4899 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(7+6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4900 &:= (-9 + F(8) - (7 - (F(6+5) \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4901 &:= (F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) + (F(6) \times F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4902 &:= (-9 + ((F((F(8) - 7)) \times (F(6) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4903 &:= (F(-9 + 8 + 7) + (F(6+5) \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\
4904 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + ((6 \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
4905 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + (F(F(7)) \times (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4906 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F((7 + F((F(6) - 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4907 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4908 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + (F(6) \times ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4909 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times F(F(7)))) - ((6 \times 5) - F(4+3+2+1))) \\
4910 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + (F(F(6)) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
4911 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(7) - (F(6) - F(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4912 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(7) + F((6 + (5 + 4)))) \times F(3+2+1))) \\
4913 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (F(F(6)) + (5 \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4914 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times 7 + F(6)) - F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4915 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + (6 - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4916 &:= (F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) + (F(6+5) \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\
4917 &:= ((F((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6)))) \times F(5+4)) + F(F(3+2+1))) \\
4918 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + (F(6+5) - F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4919 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) - F(7)) \times (6 + F(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4920 &:= ((9 - (F(8) \times (7 - (6 \times 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4921 &:= (-9 + ((F(8+7) \times F(6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4922 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4923 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) + ((7 \times 6) - F(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4924 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + (F(F(7)) + (F(6) \times F(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4925 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(7))) + (F(6) \times F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4926 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + F((F(6) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))))) \\
4927 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (F(6) \times F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4928 &:= (F(-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4929 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (F(7) \times F(6))) - 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4930 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) + ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4931 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (F(F(3+4)) + 5)) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4932 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + (F(F(3+4)) + 5)) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4933 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(F(3)^4) \times 5) + (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
4934 &:= (-1 + (F(F(F(2+3))) \times F((F(4) - ((5+6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
4935 &:= ((-1 - 2 + F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4936 &:= (((-1 + (F((2 + F(3+4))) + 5)) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4937 &:= (((-1 + 2 + F(F(3)^4)) \times 5) + (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4938 &:= ((F(((-1 + F(2+3)) \times 4)) \times 5) - (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4939 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F(F(3)^4) \times 5)) - (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4940 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times ((4 \times F(5+6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4941 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4942 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3) + (F(4+5) \times 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4943 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 + F(3))) + (F(4+5) \times 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4944 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4945 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3) + (F(4+5) \times 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4946 &:= (((-1 + F((F(2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) \times 5) - (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4947 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4948 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4949 &:= (-1 + (F(2 + F(3)) \times (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4950 &:= ((-1 + F((2 + (3 + 4)))) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4951 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4952 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F(F(3)^4) \times 5)) - (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4953 &:= ((F(((-1 + F(2+3)) \times 4)) \times 5) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4954 &:= (-1 - (((2 - F(F(3)^4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4955 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + F(F(3)^4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4956 &:= (((-1 + 2 + F(F(3)^4)) \times 5) - (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4957 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + F(F(3)^4)) \times 5) + (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4958 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(F(F(2+3)))) \times F((F(4) + (5 + F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4959 &:= (((-1 - 2 + (F(F(3+4)) + 5)) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4960 &:= (((-1 + F((F(2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4961 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3) \times (F(4+5) \times (6+7))) + F(8+9)))) \\
4962 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(F(3)^4) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4963 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(F(3)^4) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4964 &:= (-1 + ((F((F(2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4965 &:= ((F(((-1 + F(2+3)) \times 4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4966 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(F(3)^4) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4967 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 + F(3)) + (F(4+5) \times 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4968 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2+3))) + (F(4+5) \times 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4969 &:= (-1 - ((2 - F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4970 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4931 &:= (-9 + ((F(8+7) \times F(6)) + (5 + F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4932 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times 7 + 6) - F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4933 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times ((F(6) + 5) \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4934 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times F(F(6))) - F(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4935 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) - F(7)) \times (F(6) + F(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4936 &:= (9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + (F(6+5) - F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4937 &:= (((9 + F(8+7)) \times F(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4938 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times F(F(7)))) - ((6-5) - F(4+3+2+1))) \\
4939 &:= ((9 \times 8 - F(7)) + (F(6) \times F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4940 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(7))) + (F(6+5) \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\
4941 &:= (-9 + (((8-7) + F(6+5)) \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\
4942 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (F(6+5) \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\
4943 &:= (-9 + ((F(8+7) \times F(6)) + ((5+4) \times F(3+2+1)))) \\
4944 &:= (F(-9+8+7) \times (F(6) + F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4945 &:= ((F((F(-9+8+7) + F(6))) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4946 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) + F(F(6)))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4947 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + (F(6) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
4948 &:= ((9 + 8) \times F(F(7))) + F((F(F(6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
4949 &:= (9 + ((F(8+7) \times F(6)) + (5 + F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4950 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6 + 5))) \times F(4+3+2+1)) \\
4951 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F((7 + F((F(6) - 5)))) + F(4+3+2+1)) \\
4952 &:= ((-9 - F(8+7)) \times (F((F(6) - 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
4953 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (F(F(7)) - (6 - 5 - 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4954 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (F(7) + F((6 + (5 + 4)))))) - F(F(3+2+1))) \\
4955 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + (F(F(6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4956 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) + (F(6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4957 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + (F(6) - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4958 &:= (((-9 + 8 + (7 \times F(F(6)))) \times F(5+4)) - (3+2+1)) \\
4959 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) + (F(7) \times ((6+5) - F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4960 &:= (((-9 + F(8+7)) - (F(F(6)) \times 5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
4961 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + (F(F(7)) \times (6+5))) \times F(F(4))) - F(F(3+2+1))) \\
4962 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + (6 + ((5+4) \times F(3+2+1)))) \\
4963 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + (F(6+5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
4964 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times 7) + (F(6) \times F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4965 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7 \times F(6+5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4966 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (7 + F((6 + (5 + 4)))) + F(F(3+2+1)))) \\
4967 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(7) + F((6 + (5 + 4)))) \times F(3+2+1))) \\
4968 &:= ((-9 - 8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4969 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + ((6 \times 5) + F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4970 &:= (9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4971 &:= ((-1 - 2 + ((F(F(3+4)) + 5) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4972 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + ((F(F(3+4)) + 5) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4973 &:= (1 - 2 + (((F(F(3+4)) + 5) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4974 &:= (-1 + (((2 + F(F(3)^4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4975 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times F((F(3) \times (4+5)))) - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4976 &:= (((-1 + (F(2+3)^4)) - 5) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4977 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(F(3)^4) \times 5) + (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4978 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(F(3)^4) \times 5) + (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4979 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (F(F(3+4)) + 5)) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4980 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3 \times F((F(F(4)) \times 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4981 &:= (-1 - (F((2 + F(3+4))) - (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4982 &:= (-1 \times (F((2 + F(3+4))) - (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4983 &:= (-1 + (((F(2+3)^4) - 5) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4984 &:= (((-1 + (F(2+3)^{F(4)})) \times (5 \times F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4985 &:= (((-1 + 2 + F(F(3)^4)) \times 5) + (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4986 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (F((F(F(4)) + 5)) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4987 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F(3) - (F((F(F(4)) + 5)) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4988 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - (F((F(F(4)) + 5)) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4989 &:= (-1 - 2 - (F(3+4) \times ((5 - F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4990 &:= ((-1 - (2 + (3+4))) \times (5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4991 &:= (-1 - ((F(2 \times 3) - F(4+5)) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4992 &:= ((-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) - F(F(4))) \times (5+6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4993 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F(3+4) \times ((5 - F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4994 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times 3) + F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4995 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (F(F(3+4)) + 5)) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4996 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times ((F(4)^5) + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4997 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (F((F(F(4)) + 5)) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4998 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(F(3 + F(4))) - (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4999 &:= (-1 + ((F(2+3)^4) \times F((5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5000 &:= (1 \times ((F(2+3)^4) \times F((5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5001 &:= (((1 - 2 + (F(F(3+4)) + 5)) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5002 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3))^4) + (F(5+6+7) + 8 + 9)) \\
5003 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((F((3 \times 4)) - 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5004 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((F((3 \times 4)) - 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5005 &:= ((-1 + F(((2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5006 &:= (-1 + (F(2 + F(3)) \times ((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9)))) \\
5007 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) - (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
5008 &:= (((-1 + ((F(2+3)^4) + 5)) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4971 &:= (9 + ((F(8) \times (F(F(7)) - (6 - 5 - 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4972 &:= ((-9 - 8 \times F(7)) \times ((6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4973 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + F((6 - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
4974 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4975 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4976 &:= ((9 + ((F(8)/7) + F((6 + (5 + 4)))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4977 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (F(7) - F(6 + 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4978 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7 - F((6 + (5 + 4)))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4979 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times 7) + (F(6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4980 &:= ((-9 - F((8 - (F(7) - F(F(6)))))) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
4981 &:= (9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + (F((6 + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
4982 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (F(6) + (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4983 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4984 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + 6))) - (F(5 + 4) - F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4985 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7 \times F(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4986 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (F(7) - 6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4987 &:= (9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + ((6 \times 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4988 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times ((F(6) + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4989 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (7 \times (F(6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4990 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times F(7)) + (F(6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4991 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + (F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4992 &:= (9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4993 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + 6))) - ((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4994 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4995 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) + (F(7) + (F(F(6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4996 &:= (-9 + ((F((F(8)/7) + F(6 + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4997 &:= (((-9 + F(8 + 7)) \times F(6)) + ((5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4998 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times (F(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4999 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (F(7 + 6) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5000 &:= (((-F(-9 + F(8)) \times 7) + F(6)) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5001 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (F(F(7)) + F((6 + (5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5002 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6)))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5003 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 \times (F(F(6)) \times F(5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5004 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5005 &:= ((-9 + 8 - (F(7) - (F(F(6)) \times 5))) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5006 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(7) \times ((6 + 5) \times F((F(4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5007 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7 - F((6 + (5 + 4)))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5008 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + 6))) - F(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5049 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times F(3+4))) \times (5 - (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
5050 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3^{F(4)}) \times (5 - (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
5051 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + (4 + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
5052 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4)^5)) + (F(6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
5053 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3+4) + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
5054 &:= (1 \times 2 \times ((3+4) + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
5055 &:= ((-1 + (F(2+3) \times ((4^5) - F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5056 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3+4})) \times (5 \times F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5057 &:= ((-1 + (((2-3) + (F(4)^5)) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5058 &:= (((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + 4 + 5) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5059 &:= (((F(F((-1 + F(2+3))))^{4+5}) \times (6+7)) - F(8+9)) \\
5060 &:= ((1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (4 - (F((5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5061 &:= (-1 - 2 - (((3 - (F(4)^5)) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5062 &:= (((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (4 - F((5 + F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5063 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (F(F(3+4)) + 5)) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5064 &:= ((-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) - F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5065 &:= (-1 + (F((2 + (3+4))) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5066 &:= (F((F((-1 + F(2+3)))^{F(F(4))})) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5067 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3 \times F(4)) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5068 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5069 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + F(F(3)^4)) \times 5) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5070 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2+3)) \times F(4+5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5071 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times (F((4+5+6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5072 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4)^5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5073 &:= (((-1 - F(2+3)) + ((F(4)^5) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5074 &:= (((-1 \times F(2+3)) + ((F(4)^5) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5075 &:= ((-1 + 2 + F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5076 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(F(3)^4) \times 5) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5077 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(F(3+4)) \times (5+6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5078 &:= (1 \times 2 \times ((F(F(3+4)) \times (5+6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5079 &:= (((F((-1 - (2-3-4)))^5) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5080 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(F(3)^4) \times 5) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5081 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2+3)))) + ((F(4)^5) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5082 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2+3))) + ((F(4)^5) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5083 &:= (((-1 + F(2+3)) + ((F(4)^5) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5084 &:= (((-1 + 2 + F(F(3)^4)) \times 5) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5085 &:= ((((-1 + 2 - 3) + (F(4)^5)) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5086 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + ((F(F(F(4)) + 5)) - F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5087 &:= (-1 - ((F(F(2 \times 3)) - F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5049 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) + ((7 + F(F(6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5050 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times F(7)) + 6)) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5051 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) + (F(6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5052 &:= (-9 + ((8 + F(F(7))) \times (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5053 &:= (((9 - 8 + (7 \times F(F(6)))) \times F(5 + 4)) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5054 &:= (-9 + (((8 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + F(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
5055 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times F(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5056 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (F(F(7)) + (F(6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5057 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6)))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
5058 &:= (-9 \times (8 \times 7 - (F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5059 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((F(7) - (F(F(6)) \times 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5060 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + 6 + 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5061 &:= (9 - 8 - ((F(7) - (F(F(6)) \times 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5062 &:= ((9 \times F(8)) - (7 - (F(6) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5063 &:= (F((-9 + (F(8) + 7))) + ((F(6) + F(5 + 4)) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5064 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times F(F(6)) + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5065 &:= (9 + (((8 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
5066 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + (7 \times (F(6) + (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5067 &:= (-9 + (((8 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5068 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F((7 + F(6)))) - F((F(5 + 4) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5069 &:= (-9 + (((8 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + ((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5070 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + 6)) + (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5071 &:= (F((-9 + (F(8) + 7))) + (F(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5072 &:= (-9 + F(8) - ((F(7) - (F(F(6)) \times 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5073 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5074 &:= ((9 \times 8 - F(7)) \times (F((6 + 5)) + (F(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5075 &:= (-9 + ((F(8 + 7) \times F(6)) + (F(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5076 &:= (-9 \times (8 + (F(7) \times ((6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5077 &:= ((9 \times F(8)) - (7 - (F(6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5078 &:= (-9 + (((8 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + (F(5 + 4) - F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5079 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (F(7 + 6) + (5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5080 &:= (((-F(-9 + F(8)) \times 7) - F(6)) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
5081 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(7 + 6) + (5 + 4)) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5082 &:= ((F((F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) - F(6))) + (5 + 4)) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5083 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + (F(6) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5084 &:= (((-9 - 8 + (F(F(7)) \times (6 + 5))) \times F(F(4))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5085 &:= (9 + (((8 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5086 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (7 + F((F(6) + 5)))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5087 &:= ((9 \times F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5088 &:= (-1 \times ((F(F(2 \times 3)) - F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 5089 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 + 3) \times (4^5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 5090 &:= ((F((-1 + 2 \times 3)) \times (4^5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 5091 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times F(F(3 + 4)))) \times (5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 5092 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + ((F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) - F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 5093 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times F((3 \times 4))) - 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
 5094 &:= (((-1 \times 2 \times F((3 \times 4))) + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 5095 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 \times F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 5096 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times ((F(F(4))^5) \times F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 5097 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3 \times F(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 5098 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(3 \times F(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 5099 &:= (-1 + (F(2 + 3) \times (F(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 5100 &:= (F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3)))) \times (F(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 5101 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3 \times F(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 5102 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times ((F(4) \times F(5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
 5103 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F((F(3) \times (4 + 5))) - (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 5104 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3+4})) \times (5 \times F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5105 &:= (-1 + (((2 - 3) + (F(4)^5)) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5106 &:= (((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + 4 + 5) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5107 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F((F(3) \times (4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 5108 &:= (1 \times 2 \times (F((F(3) \times (4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 5109 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 5110 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + (F(F(4)) \times (5 \times F(F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 5111 &:= (-1 - (((F(2 + 3) \times 4) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 5112 &:= ((-1 + ((F(F(2 + 3))^{F(4)} + F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 5113 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 + 3)) \times ((4^5) - 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 5114 &:= ((F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3))) \times ((4^5) - 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5115 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F((F(F(4)) \times 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 5116 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 + 3)) \times (4^5)) + (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
 5117 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times (F((F(F(4)) - (5 - F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
 5118 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (((F(4)^5) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 5119 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times (F((F(4) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 5120 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 - (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 5121 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3 + 4) \times (5 + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
 5122 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times F((F(3) \times (4 + 5)))) - (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 5123 &:= ((F(F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3)))) \times (4^5)) - (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 5124 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(F(3)^4) \times 5) + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 5125 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F(F(3 + 4)) \times ((5 + F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
 5126 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(F(3 + 4)) \times ((5 + F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
 5088 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(7 + 6)) + (F(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 5089 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) - (6 + 5)) \times (F(F(4)) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 5090 &:= ((((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 5091 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + ((7 + F(6 + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 5092 &:= (((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) + 6) \times F(5 + 4)) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 5093 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) \times (F(7) - (F(6) \times 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 5094 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + ((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 5095 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + (F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 5096 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F(F(7)) + (F(6) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 5097 &:= ((9 \times F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 5098 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + (F(6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 5099 &:= (9 + 8 + ((F(7 + 6) + (5 + 4)) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 5100 &:= ((-9 - F(8)) \times ((F(7) + F(F(6))) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
 5101 &:= (-9 + ((8 - (F(F(7)) \times (6 + 5))) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 5102 &:= (-9 + (((8 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 5103 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) \times (7 - (F(6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 5104 &:= (((-9 \times F(8)) + F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 5105 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + 6 + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 5106 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times F(7)) - (6 + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 5107 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + (F((F(6) + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
 5108 &:= (((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) + 6) \times F(5 + 4)) + F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 5109 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + ((5 + 4) - F(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 5110 &:= (((9 \times F(8)) + (F(F(7)) + F((6 + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 5111 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F(F(7)) + (F(6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 5112 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) + (F(6) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 5113 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (F(F(7)) + (F(6) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 5114 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 5115 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + (6 - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))))) \\
 5116 &:= (((-9 - (F(8) - F((7 + 6 + 5))) \times F(F(4))) + F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 5117 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + F((F(6) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))))) \\
 5118 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F((7 + F(6))) - F(5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 5119 &:= ((9 \times F(8 + 7)) - (F(((6 + 5) + F(4))) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 5120 &:= (((-9 + F(8 + 7)) - F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 5121 &:= (-9 \times ((F(8) \times (7 - F(F(6)))) - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 5122 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times F(7))) \times (6 \times (5 + 4))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 5123 &:= (9 + ((F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + 6 + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
 5124 &:= (9 + (((8 \times F(7)) - (6 + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 5125 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + (F(F(7)) + (F(6) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 5126 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + (F((F(6) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5127 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (F((F(3) \times (4 + 5))) - F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5128 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(F(3)^4) \times 5) + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5129 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + (F(4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5130 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F(3 \times F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5131 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F((F(3) \times (4 + 5))) + (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
5132 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4)^5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5133 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times ((F(F(4)) + (5 \times F(F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5134 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5135 &:= (-1 + (((F(F(2 + 3))^{F(4)} + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5136 &:= (((F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3))^{F(4)} + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5137 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times F((F(3) \times (4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5138 &:= ((F((-1 + 2 \times 3)) \times (4^5)) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5139 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times F(F(3 + 4)))) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5140 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5141 &:= (F((-1 + (F(2 + 3) \times 4)) + (5 \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5142 &:= (((F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) + (F(4)^5)) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5143 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times F((3 + (4 + 5 + 6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5144 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F((4 + 5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5145 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times F((F(F(4)) - (5 - F(F(6))))))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5146 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - ((4 + (5 + 6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9))) \\
5147 &:= (-1 - (((2 - 3) - (F(4)^5)) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5148 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (F((F(3) + F(4)))^5)) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5149 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 + 3) \times (4^5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5150 &:= ((F((-1 + 2 \times 3)) \times (4^5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5151 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times F((F(3) \times (4 + 5)))) + (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5152 &:= ((F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3)))) \times (4^5)) + (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5153 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + ((F(F(4)) \times F(5 + 6 + 7)) - (8 + 9))) \\
5154 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) + ((F(F(4)) \times F(5 + 6 + 7)) - (8 + 9))) \\
5155 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (F((F(3) \times (4 + 5))) + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5156 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times (F(F(4)) + F(5 + 6 + 7)))) - (8 + 9)) \\
5157 &:= (1 + ((2 \times (F((F(3) \times (4 + 5))) + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5158 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((3 + F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) - F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5159 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (F(3 \times F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5160 &:= ((1 \times 2 + (F(3 \times F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5161 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - F((F(4 + 5) + (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))))) \\
5162 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - F((F(4 + 5) + (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))))) \\
5163 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F(3) - F((F(4 + 5) + (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))))) \\
5164 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - F((F(4 + 5) + (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))))) \\
5165 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3) \times F((F(4 + 5) + (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))))) \\
5127 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) + (F(6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5128 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (F(7) \times (F(6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5129 &:= (9 - 8 + (F(F(7)) + (F(6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5130 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) + (F(7) + (6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5131 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times ((6 + 5) \times F(F(4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5132 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) + 7)) + (F(6) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5133 &:= (9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + (6 - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
5134 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (F(7) - (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5135 &:= ((9 + 8 \times 7) \times (F(6 + 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
5136 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + (F((F(6) - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5137 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (F((7 + F(6))) + F(5 + 4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5138 &:= ((9 \times (F(8 + 7) - (6 + F(5 + 4)))) + F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5139 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) + (F(7) - ((6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5140 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + (F(F(7)) + (F(6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5141 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (F(F(7)) \times (6 + 5))) \times F(F(4))) + F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5142 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) + F(F(7)))) \times F(F(6))) - ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5143 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(7) + (F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5144 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(7)) + (F(6) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5145 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) + F(F(7)))) \times (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5146 &:= (((-9 - 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5147 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) + 7)) + (F(6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5148 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + (6 \times (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5149 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + (7 \times ((F(6) + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5150 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(7) \times F(6))) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5151 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 + (F(F(6)) + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5152 &:= ((F((F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) - 6)) + F(5 + 4)) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5153 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(7) + 6) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5154 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(7) \times (F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5155 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) \times 7) + F(F(6))) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5156 &:= (-9 - (F(8 + 7) - (F(F(6)) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5157 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7) + F((F(6) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))))) \\
5158 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) \times (F(7) - (F(6) \times 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5159 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(7)) + (F(6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5160 &:= ((9 + (F(8) + F(7))) \times (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5161 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (F(7) + F(6 + 5))) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5162 &:= (((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) + F(6)) \times F(5 + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5163 &:= (((-9 \times (F(8) + (F(7) - F((6 + (5 + 4)))))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5164 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) + (F(5 + 4) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5165 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + (6 + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5166 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times ((F(4+5) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5167 &:= (-1 + (2 \times F((3 - ((F(4) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5168 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - F((4 - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
5169 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times F((F(4+5) + (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
5170 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times F((F(3) \times (4+5)))) - (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5171 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3) + F((F(4+5) + (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))))) \\
5172 &:= (((-1 + F(2+3)) + F((F(F(4)) + (5+6+7)))) - F(8+9)) \\
5173 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(F(3+4)) \times (5+6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5174 &:= ((F(F((-1+2 \times 3))) \times ((4^5) + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5175 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - ((4+5) \times (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
5176 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))^{F(F(4))}) \times (5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5177 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - ((F(4) + (5 \times F(F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5178 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - ((4+5) \times (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
5179 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (F((F(3) \times (4+5))) - 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5180 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) + (F((5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5181 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3) + F(4+5)) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5182 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3) + F(4+5)) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5183 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F(3+4+5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
5184 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3+4}) + F(5+6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5185 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3) + F(4+5)) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5186 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5187 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((3 + (F(4)^5)) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5188 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - F((F(F(4)) - (5 - F(F(6)))))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5189 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3) \times F((F(F(4)) - (5 - F(F(6)))))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5190 &:= (((F((-1 + F(2+3))) + (F(4)^5)) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5191 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times F((3 + (4+5+6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5192 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F((4+5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5193 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3) \times F((F(F(4)) - (5 - F(F(6)))))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5194 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - (F(5+6+7) + 8 + 9))) \\
5195 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (F(3) + F((F(F(4)) - (5 - F(F(6)))))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5196 &:= ((-1 - F(2+3)) + (F(F(4)) \times (F(5+6+7) + 8 + 9))) \\
5197 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times F((F(3) \times (4+5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5198 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((3+4) + F(5+6+7))) + 8 + 9)) \\
5199 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times F((F(3) \times (4+5)))) + (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5200 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (4 \times (F(5+6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5201 &:= ((F(F(F(F((-1+2 \times 3)))))) \times ((4^5) + F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5202 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times F(3+4+5))) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5203 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F((F(3) \times (4+5))) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
5204 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times 3) + (F(4)^5)) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5205 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(F(3+4)) + (5 - F(F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5166 &:= (-9 \times (((8+7) + F(F(6))) - F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5167 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) + (5 \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5168 &:= (F((-9 + (F(8) + 7))) + F((F(F(6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
5169 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + F((7+6+5))) \times F(F(4)))) - (3+2+1)) \\
5170 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + (F(F(7)) \times (F(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5171 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) + F(F(6)))) + (5 \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\
5172 &:= (((9 \times (F(8) + 7)) + F((6 + (5+4)))) \times (3+2+1)) \\
5173 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) + F(F(7)))) \times F(F(6))) + (F(5+4) - (3+2+1))) \\
5174 &:= (((F((-9+8+F(7))) + F(6)) \times F(5+4)) + 3+2+1) \\
5175 &:= (-9 \times (8 \times 7 - (F(F(6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5176 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) + (F(7) - F((6 + (5+4)))))) - F(3+2+1)) \\
5177 &:= (9 + ((F(8) \times F(7)) + (F(6+5) \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5178 &:= (((9+8+F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) - ((5+4) \times F(3+2+1))) \\
5179 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times ((6+5) + (F(4)^{3+2+1})))) \\
5180 &:= (9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + (6 + (F(5+4) \times F(3+2+1)))) \\
5181 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7)) \times ((6 \times (5+4) - F(F(3+2+1)))) \\
5182 &:= (((-9 - (8 - 7)) + (6^5)) - F((F(4) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
5183 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F(7) \times (F(6) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
5184 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) + (7+6 - F(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5185 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) - F(7)) \times (F(6) \times 5)) - F(4+3+2+1)) \\
5186 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + ((F((7+6+5)) \times F(F(4))) + 3+2+1))) \\
5187 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) + (6 + (5+4)))) \times F(F(3+2+1))) \\
5188 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F((7+6+5)) \times F(F(4))) + F(F(3+2+1)))) \\
5189 &:= (((F((-9+8+F(7))) + F(6)) \times F(5+4)) + F(F(3+2+1))) \\
5190 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(7) \times (F(6) \times 5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
5191 &:= ((9+8) \times (F(F(7)) + (F(6) \times (5+4)))) + 3+2+1 \\
5192 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) + (F(7) - F((6 + (5+4)))))) + F(3+2+1)) \\
5193 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) + (7 - ((6+5) \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5194 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) - F(6)) \times F(5+4) - F(3+2+1)) \\
5195 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) + F(F(7)))) \times F(F(6))) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
5196 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) - F(6)) \times F(5+4) - (3+2+1)) \\
5197 &:= (((9 \times F(8)) + F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + 5)) - F(4+3+2+1) \\
5198 &:= ((-9 - 8 \times F(7)) \times (F(6) - ((5+4) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
5199 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7+6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5200 &:= ((-9+8) \times (F(7) \times (F(6) \times (5 - F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5201 &:= (-9 + ((F(8+7) - F(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
5202 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) + F((6 + (5+4)))) \times (3+2+1))) \\
5203 &:= (((-9 + F(8+7)) \times 6) + F(((5+4) + F(3+2+1)))) \\
5204 &:= (9 + (F(8) + ((F((7+6+5)) \times F(F(4))) + 3+2+1))) \\
5205 &:= (((-9 + F((F(8) - 7))) - F(F(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5246 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4)^5)) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5247 &:= (((((-1 + F(2 + 3))^4) - 5) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5248 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 + 3)) \times ((4^5) + F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5249 &:= ((F(F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3)))))) \times ((4^5) + F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5250 &:= ((-1 + 2 + F(3 \times F(4))) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5251 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F((F(3 + 4) - 5)) \times (F((6 + 7) + 8 + 9)))) \\
5252 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) + (F(4)^5)) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5253 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 - ((F(4)^5) - F(F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5254 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 + (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5255 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times (3 + 4)) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5256 &:= (((-1 - 2 + F(F(3 + 4))) - (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5257 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F((F(3) \times (4 + 5))) + (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5258 &:= ((-1 - F((F(F(F(F(2 + 3)))) + F(4)))) \times ((5 + 6) - (F(F(7)) + 8 + 9))) \\
5259 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((3 - (F(4) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7)) - F(8 + 9))) \\
5260 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5261 &:= (F((-1 + (F(2 + 3) \times 4))) + (5 \times (F((6 + 7) - (8 + 9)))) \\
5262 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3^4) \times (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5263 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3^4) \times (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5264 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 + F(3))^4) \times (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5265 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3))^4) \times (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5266 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3^4) \times (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5267 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) - 4) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5268 &:= (1 + 2 + ((3^4) \times (F((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5269 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 + 3)) \times ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5270 &:= (F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3))) \times ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5271 &:= (1 + (F(F(2 + 3)) \times ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5272 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + (((F(4) + 5) \times (6 + 7)) - F(8 + 9))) \\
5273 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times F((3 \times 4))) + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5274 &:= (((-1 \times 2 \times F((3 \times 4))) - 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5275 &:= (1 - (((2 \times F((3 \times 4))) + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5276 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((F(3) + F(4 + 5)) \times (F(F(6)) \times 7))) - (8 + 9)) \\
5277 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((F(3 + 4) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5278 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((F(3 + 4) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5279 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (F(F(3 + 4)) - (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5280 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + F(F(3 + 4))) - (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5281 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((F(3 + 4) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5282 &:= (((F((-1 + F(2 + 3))^4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7))) + 8 + 9) \\
5283 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (((F(4)^5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5284 &:= (-1 + (((F(F(2 + 3))^4) \times (5 + 6)) + (7 - F(8 + 9)))) \\
5246 &:= ((9 \times (F(8 + 7) - (F(F(6)) + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5247 &:= (-9 \times (8 + (F(7) + (6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5248 &:= (-9 + (F((F(8) - 7)) + (F(6) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5249 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) + (F(6) + (5 + 4))) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5250 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - ((7 + F(6 + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5251 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F((7 + F(6)))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5252 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + (6 \times F(5 + 4)))) + F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5253 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) - ((5 + 4) \times F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5254 &:= ((9 - 8 + (F(7) \times F((6 + 5)))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
5255 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times 7 - (F(F(6)) \times F(5 + 4))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5256 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) + (F(7) - (F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5257 &:= ((9 \times F(8 + 7)) - F((F(6) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
5258 &:= ((((-9 \times F(8)) - F(7)) \times (F(6) - F(5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5259 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) + (7 - F((6 + (5 + 4)))))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5260 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) + F(F(7)))) \times (6 - (F(5 + 4) - F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5261 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) - F(7)) \times (6 + F(5 + 4))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5262 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + (6 \times ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5263 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 + F(6 + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5264 &:= (((-9 \times (F(8) \times F(7))) + (6^5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5265 &:= (((9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5266 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F((7 + F(6))) - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5267 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (7 \times F(F(6)))) \times F(5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5268 &:= (((-9 - (F(8) - F(F(7)))) \times (F(F(6)) + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5269 &:= ((9 \times (F(8 + 7) + 6)) - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5270 &:= (((9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) + (F(6) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5271 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((F(7) - (6 - 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5272 &:= (9 \times 8 + (F(7) \times (F(6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5273 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + (6 \times 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5274 &:= (-9 \times ((F(8)/7) + (F(F(6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5275 &:= ((9 \times (F(8 + 7) - (6 \times 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5276 &:= ((((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) - 6) \times F(5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5277 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times ((7 + F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5278 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) - F(F(7)))) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
5279 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 + F(6 + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5280 &:= (((-9 \times F(8)) + F(F(7))) \times (F(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5281 &:= (9 - 8 + ((7 + F(6 + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5282 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (7 \times F(F(6)))) \times F(5 + 4)) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5283 &:= (-9 \times (((8 + 7) + F(6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5284 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + (F(6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5285 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + (((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7)) - F(8 + 9))) \\
5286 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((F(3) \times F(4 + 5)) - (F((6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9)))) \\
5287 &:= (-F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) - ((F(4) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5288 &:= (1 + (((2 \times (F((3 \times 4)) + 5)) + (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9))) \\
5289 &:= (((-1 - 2 + (F(3)^{F(4)+5})) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5290 &:= ((-1 - 2 + F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5291 &:= ((-1 + F(((2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) \times (5 + (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5292 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times F((3 \times 4)) + 5)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5293 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times F(3 \times F(4)))) \times (F((5 + 6)) + (7 - (8 + 9)))) \\
5294 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4)^5)) + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5295 &:= (((((-1 + F(2 + 3))^4) - 5) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5296 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times F((F(F(4)) \times 5)))) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5297 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3)^4) + ((5 \times (6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9)))) \\
5298 &:= (((1 + 2) \times 3) \times F((F(4) \times 5))) - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5299 &:= (1 + (2 \times (F(F(3)^4) + ((5 \times (6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9)))) \\
5300 &:= (1 \times 2 + (3 \times ((F((F(F(4)) + 5)) \times (6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9))) \\
5301 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 \times 4 - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5302 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3 \times 4 - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5303 &:= (-1 + (((2 - 3) + (F(4)^5)) - F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5304 &:= (((-1 + F(F((F(2 + 3) + F(F(4)))))) - (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5305 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 \times 4 - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5306 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) + (((F(4)^5) - F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5307 &:= ((-1 \times F(F(2 \times 3))) + (((F(4)^5) - F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5308 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(4) - ((5 + 6) \times F(7)) - F(8 + 9))) \\
5309 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(F(4)) + 5))) + F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5310 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times F((F(3) + 4 + 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5311 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times F((F(3) \times (4 + 5)))) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5312 &:= (-1 - ((2 - F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
5313 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5314 &:= (1 - ((2 - F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
5315 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (4 + (F((5 + 6)) \times (7 - (8 + 9)))))) \\
5316 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4) \times F(5 + 6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5317 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3^{F(4)}) \times (5 + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5318 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 + F(3))^{F(4)}) \times (5 + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5319 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))^{F(4)}) \times (5 + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5320 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5321 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) + (((F(4)^5) - F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5322 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) + (((F(4)^5) - F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5323 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) + (((F(4)^5) - F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5285 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + 6)) + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5286 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F((7 + F(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5287 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (F(F(7)) \times (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5288 &:= (((-9 - (F(8) - F(F(7)))) \times (F(F(6)) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5289 &:= (-9 + (((F(8) \times F(7)) + F((6 + (5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5290 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5291 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times ((6 \times 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5292 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) + ((7 - 6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5293 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + F(7)) - F((6 + (5 + 4)))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5294 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F((7 + F(6)))) - (5 - (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5295 &:= ((9 \times F(8 + 7)) - (6 + ((5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5296 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F((7 + F(6)))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
5297 &:= (9 + 8 + ((7 + F(6 + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5298 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times ((7 + 6) \times F(5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5299 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F((7 + F(6)))) - F(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
5300 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - (F(7) + F(F(6)))) \times (5 - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5301 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + (7 + 6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5302 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F((7 + F(6)))) + ((5 + 4) - F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5303 &:= (-9 + ((F(8 + 7) + (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5304 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) \times (F(6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5305 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) \times ((6 + 5) \times F(4))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5306 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F((7 + F(6)))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
5307 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + F(7)) - F((6 + (5 + 4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5308 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) - ((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5309 &:= (((-9 \times (F(8) \times F(7))) + (6^5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5310 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - ((7 - 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5311 &:= (-9 + (8 \times 7 \times ((F(6) \times 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5312 &:= (((9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times F(F(6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5313 &:= (((-9 \times F(8)) + ((7 + 6) \times F(5 + 4))) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5314 &:= 9 \times (F(8 + 7) - F(F(6))) + F(5 + 4) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5315 &:= (F((-9 + (F(8) + 7))) + (F(F(6)) \times ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5316 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F((7 + F(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5317 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + (7 + 6)) \times F(5 + 4)) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5318 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + (6 \times 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5319 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5320 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
5321 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (F(F(7)) + ((F(6) - F(5 + 4)) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5322 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + F(7)) - F((6 + (5 + 4)))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5323 &:= (((9 \times F(8 + 7)) + F((6 + 5))) - (F(F(4))^{F(3+2+1)}))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5363 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((F((3 \times 4)) + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
5364 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4) \times F(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5365 &:= ((-1 + 2 + F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 + (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5366 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times ((4^5) + F((6 + 7)))) + F(8 + 9))) \\
5367 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + (F(F(4)) \times (F(5 + 6 + 7) - (8 + 9)))) \\
5368 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times ((4^5) + F((6 + 7)))) + F(8 + 9)) \\
5369 &:= (((-1 - F(2 + 3)) \times (4 - (5 \times F((6 + 7)))) - F(8 + 9)) \\
5370 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times 3)^{F(F(4))}) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5371 &:= (-1 - ((2 + F(3)) \times (F((F(4) + 5)) + (F((6 + 7)) - F(8 + 9)))) \\
5372 &:= ((-1 - 2 + ((3^4) + (5 + F((6 + 7)))) \times (8 + 9)) \\
5373 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (F(3)^{F(4)+5})) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5374 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (((3 \times F(4)) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5375 &:= (-1 + (((2 + F(F(3 + 4))) - (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5376 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times 3) + F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5377 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((3 \times F(4)) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5378 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) - ((F(F(F(F(4)) + 5))) - F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5379 &:= (((-1 + (2^{F(3+4)-5}) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5380 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) \times (4 - (5 \times (F((6 + 7)) - (8 + 9)))) \\
5381 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3^{F(F(4)+5}) + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5382 &:= ((-1 + 2 + F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5383 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times F((5 + F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5384 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + ((F(F(4)) \times F(5 + 6 + 7)) - (8 + 9))) \\
5385 &:= (-1 - 2 - (3 \times (F(4 + 5) - (F((6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9)))) \\
5386 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (3 \times (F(4 + 5) - (F((6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9)))) \\
5387 &:= (-1 - (F(2 + F(3)) \times (F(4 + 5) - (F((6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9)))) \\
5388 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times F((F(3) \times (4 + 5)))) + ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\
5389 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (F(4 + 5) - (F((6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9)))) \\
5390 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) \times (F(F(4)) - (5 \times (F((6 + 7)) - (8 + 9)))) \\
5391 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + ((F(F(F(F(4)) + 5))) - F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5392 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) - ((F(F(F(F(4)) + 5))) - F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5393 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) + ((F(F(F(F(4)) + 5))) - F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5394 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5395 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times 4)) \times (F(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5396 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5397 &:= (F((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4)))) \times (F((5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5398 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + ((F(F(F(F(4)) + 5))) - F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5399 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3)^{F(4)}) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5400 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5401 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(F(3 \times 4 - 5)) - F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5402 &:= ((1 - 2 + 3) + ((F(F(F(F(4)) + 5))) - F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5363 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (7 \times F(6 + 5)))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5364 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7) - (6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5365 &:= ((9 \times (F(8 + 7) + (F(F(6)) - F(5 + 4)))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5366 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) - (7 - F(F(6)))) \times F(5 + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5367 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5368 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (F(F(7)) - 6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5369 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + ((F(7) + 6) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5370 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7) + (F(6) + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5371 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + (F(F(7)) \times (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5372 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (7 + F((6 + (5 + 4)))))) + F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5373 &:= (-9 \times (F((8 + 7) - F(6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5374 &:= ((9 \times (F(8 + 7) - (F(F(6)) - 5 - 4))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5375 &:= ((9 \times F(8 + 7)) - ((F(F(6)) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5376 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - F((6 + (5 + 4)))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5377 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) + 7)) \times (F(6) + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5378 &:= (9 - (F(8) + ((7 - (F(F(6)) \times 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5379 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) + ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5380 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + F((F(7) + F((F(6) - 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5381 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) + (7 \times (6 + 5))) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5382 &:= (-9 \times ((F((F(8)/7)) \times 6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5383 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + (6 \times 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5384 &:= ((-9 + (F(8 + 7) + (F(6) \times (5 + 4)))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5385 &:= (9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5386 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times F(7)) + (F((6 + 5)) \times (F(4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5387 &:= ((-9 - 8 - (F(7) \times F((6 + 5)))) + (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)}) \\
5388 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) - (F(6) \times F(5 + 4))) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5389 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 - (F(F(6)) \times 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5390 &:= ((9 + F(((8 - 7) \times (6 + 5)))) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5391 &:= (-9 \times ((F(8)/7) + (F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5392 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F((7 + F(6)))) - (F(5 + 4) - F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5393 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) - (7 - F(F(6)))) \times F(5 + 4)) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5394 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) + (F(6) + (5 + 4))) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5395 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (7 \times F((6 + 5)))) - (F(F(4)) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5396 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times F(F(7)))) + (F(6)^{5+4-3-2-1})) \\
5397 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7) + F((6 + (5 + 4)))))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5398 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + (7 + F(6))) \times F(5 + 4)) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5399 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (F(7) \times (F(6) - (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5400 &:= ((9 \times F(8 + 7)) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5401 &:= ((9 \times (F(8 + 7) - (6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5402 &:= 9 \times (F(8 + 7) - 6 - 5) + F(4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5403 &:= (1 + 2 + ((F(F(3 \times 4 - 5)) - F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5404 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
5405 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + F(F(4))) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5406 &:= (1 + ((2 + F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
5407 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) + ((F(F(F(F(4)) + 5))) - F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5408 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 + 3)) \times F(4 + 5))) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5409 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 \times (4 + 5)) - (F((6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9)))) \\
5410 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + ((4 + 5 + F((6 + 7))) - F(8 + 9))) \\
5411 &:= (-1 - ((F(F(F(2 + 3)) \times 4))/5) \times ((6 + 7) - (8 + 9))) \\
5412 &:= (((-1 \times F((F(F(2 + 3)) \times 4))/5) \times ((6 + 7) - (8 + 9))) \\
5413 &:= (1 - ((F(F(F(2 + 3)) \times 4))/5) \times ((6 + 7) - (8 + 9))) \\
5414 &:= (((1 + 2) \times ((3 + F(F(4)))^5) - (F((6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9))) \\
5415 &:= ((((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4))/5) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5416 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4 + 5) \times F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5417 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) \times ((5 \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5418 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + ((F(F(4)) \times F(5 + 6 + 7)) + 8 + 9)) \\
5419 &:= (-1 - ((2 + F(3)) \times ((4 + 5 + F((6 + 7))) - F(8 + 9)))) \\
5420 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) + ((F(F(F(F(4)) + 5))) - F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5421 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3 + 4) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5422 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (((3 + 4) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5423 &:= ((1 - 2) - (((3 + 4) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5424 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + (4 - (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5425 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times 3)^{F(4)})) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5426 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) - ((F(F(F(F(4)) + 5))) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5427 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) - ((F(F(F(F(4)) + 5))) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5428 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + F(4)) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5429 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + F(F(3)^4)) \times 5) + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5430 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3^4)) + (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5431 &:= (F((-1 + (F(2 + 3) \times 4))) + (5 \times (F((6 + 7)) + 8 + 9))) \\
5432 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) + (4 \times ((5 + F((6 + 7))) - F(8 + 9))))) \\
5433 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(3 + 4) \times (F((5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5434 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) \times (F((5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5435 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + (F(F(4)) \times (F(5 + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9))) \\
5436 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(F(3)^4) \times 5) + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5437 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(3 \times F(4)) \times (5 \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5438 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) + (F((5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5439 &:= (-1 + (F(F(F(2 + 3))) \times (F(4 + 5) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5440 &:= (F(F(F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3))))) \times (F(4 + 5) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5441 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3 \times F(4)) \times (5 \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5442 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) + ((F(F(F(F(4)) + 5))) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5403 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F((7 + F(6))))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5404 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (F(7) \times F((6 + 5)))) + (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)})) \\
5405 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times ((F(F(6)) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5406 &:= ((-9 + ((F(8 + 7) - 6) \times (5 + 4))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5407 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (F(F(7)) - (F(6) \times (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5408 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (7 \times F(6 + 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5409 &:= (-9 \times (((8 + 7) - 6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5410 &:= ((-9 + (((8 \times F(7)) + 6) \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5411 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) - (7 - (F((6 + 5)) \times (F(4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5412 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7) + F((6 + (5 + 4))))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5413 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F((7 + F(6))))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
5414 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + (7 + F(6))) \times F(5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5415 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times F(6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5416 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F((7 + F(6))))) - F(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
5417 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (F(7) - F(6 + 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5418 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - ((7 + 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5419 &:= ((-9 + ((F(8 + 7) - 6) \times (5 + 4))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5420 &:= (9 + (F(8) - ((7 - (F(F(6)) \times 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5421 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + ((F(7) + F(6 + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5422 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) - (F(6) - F(5 + 4))) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5423 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F((7 + F(6))))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
5424 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + ((7 + F(6 + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5425 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) - 7) \times (F(6) \times 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5426 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7) + F((6 + (5 + 4))))) + F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5427 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5428 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (7 \times F(6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5429 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (7 \times F((6 + 5))))) + (F(4) + F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5430 &:= (((-9 + F((F(8) - 7))) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5431 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5432 &:= ((-9 + ((F(8) - F(7)) \times (F((6 + 5)) - F(4)))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5433 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F((7 + F(6))))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5434 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + 6))) \times (F(5 + 4) - F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5435 &:= ((9 \times F(((8 \times F(7)) - F(6 + 5)))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5436 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - 7) \times 6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5437 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (7 \times F((6 + 5))))) - (F(F(4)) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5438 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times 6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5439 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7) + F((6 + (5 + 4))))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5440 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + (F(F(6)) + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5441 &:= ((9 \times (F(8 + 7) - 6)) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
5442 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) \times 7)) + F(((6 \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5483 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (3 \times F((F(4) \times 5)))) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5484 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) + (F((F(4) \times 5)) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
5485 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F(3 + 4) \times (5 - (F((6 + 7)) - (8 + 9))))) \\
5486 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3 + 4) \times (5 - (F((6 + 7)) - (8 + 9)))) \\
5487 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (3 \times F((F(4) \times 5)))) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5488 &:= (-1 + ((2 - F(3 + 4)) \times (5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5489 &:= (-1 + ((F((2 + F(3 + 4)))/5) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5490 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3+4})) - 5) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5491 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) - ((4 - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5492 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) + ((4 - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5493 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((F(3) + (F(F(4)) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5494 &:= (((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F(4))) \times F(5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5495 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (F(F(3 + F(4)))) \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5496 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4))) \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5497 &:= (((-1 + 2)^{F(3)}) - ((4 - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5498 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) - ((4 - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5499 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) - ((4 - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5500 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) - ((4 - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5501 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5502 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5503 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) - ((4 - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5504 &:= (((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times 4) + (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5505 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F(F(3 + 4)) + (5 \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5506 &:= (((-1 + 2)^{F(3)}) + (F(4) \times (5 + (F((6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9)))) \\
5507 &:= (-1 - ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times 4) - (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5508 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (F(4 + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5509 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) - ((4 - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5510 &:= (-1 - ((F(2 + F(3))^4) - (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5511 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) - ((F(4) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5512 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3^4) - (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5513 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) - ((F(4) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5514 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) - ((F(4) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5515 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) - ((F(4) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5516 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3^{F(4)})) \times (5 + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5517 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 - F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5518 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3 - F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5519 &:= (-1 - ((F(2 + F(3)) - F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5520 &:= ((-1 + (F((F(F(2 + 3)) + F(4))) \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5521 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 - F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5483 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F((7 + F(6))) \times (5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5484 &:= ((9 \times F(8 + 7)) - (F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5485 &:= ((9 \times F(((8 + F(7)) - 6))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
5486 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5487 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - F((6 + (5 + 4))))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5488 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times F(F(7)))) - (6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5489 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + ((6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5490 &:= ((-9 \times 8 / (F(7) - F(F(6)))) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5491 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) - (7 - 6)) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5492 &:= ((9 \times F(8 + 7)) + F((F(6) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
5493 &:= (-9 - (F(8) \times (7 + 6 - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5494 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(7 + 6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5495 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((F(7) \times 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5496 &:= (-9 + (F(8 + 7) + (F(6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5497 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F((7 + F(6))) \times (5 + 4)) + F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5498 &:= ((F((F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) - 6)) \times (5 + 4)) + F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5499 &:= (-9 \times ((8 / (F(7) - F(F(6)))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5500 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5501 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) - 7) \times (6 + F(5 + 4))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5502 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5503 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(F(7)) \times (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5504 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + (6 \times 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5505 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F((7 + F(6))))) + (F(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5506 &:= (9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) - (6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5507 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) + 7) \times (F(6) + ((5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5508 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - ((7 \times F(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5509 &:= (((-9 \times F(8)) - 7) \times (6 - F(5 + 4))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5510 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times F(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5511 &:= ((F((F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) - 6)) \times (5 + 4)) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5512 &:= (9 + ((F(8) \times F(7 + 6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5513 &:= (-9 - (((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
5514 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) - (6 \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
5515 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times F(F(7))) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5516 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) - (7 - (F(6) \times (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5517 &:= (-9 \times ((F(8)/7) - (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5518 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F((7 + F(6))) + 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5519 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((F(F(7)) \times (6 - 5 - 4)) + F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5520 &:= ((-9 + F((F(8) - (F(7) - 6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5521 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(7) + 6)) \times F(5 + 4)) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5522 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5523 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) - ((F(4) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5524 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) - ((F(4) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5525 &:= ((1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times 4)) \times (F((5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5526 &:= (((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times F(4)) + (F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5527 &:= (-1 - ((F(2 \times 3))^{F(F(4))}) - (F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5528 &:= (-1 \times ((F(2 \times 3))^{F(F(4))}) - (F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5529 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times F(F(3 + F(4)))) + (F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5530 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times (F(4) + ((5 \times F((6 + 7))) + F(8 + 9)))) \\
5531 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(3) \times (F(4) + ((5 \times F((6 + 7))) + F(8 + 9)))) \\
5532 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) \times (4 + ((5 \times F((6 + 7))) + F(8 + 9)))) \\
5533 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) - ((F(4) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5534 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3+4}) - 5) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5535 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) - ((F(F(4)) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5536 &:= (1 + (((2^{3+4}) - 5) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5537 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3))^{F(F(4))}) \times (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5538 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) - ((F(F(4)) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5539 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) - ((F(F(4)) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5540 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) - ((F(4) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5541 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4))) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5542 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4))) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5543 &:= (-1 + (F((F(2 + 3) + F(4))) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5544 &:= (F((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4)))) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5545 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(F(3 + F(4))) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5546 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) - ((F(F(4)) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5547 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) - ((F(F(4)) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5548 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) - ((F(F(4)) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5549 &:= (1 \times F(2 + 3) - ((F(F(4)) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5550 &:= (-1 \times ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F(F(4))) - (F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5551 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F((F(3) \times (4 + 5))) + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5552 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5553 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times F(3 + 4)) + (F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5554 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (F((F(4) + 5)) + (F((6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9)))) \\
5555 &:= (-1 - 2 - (F(3 \times F(4)) - (F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5556 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 \times 4)) + (F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5557 &:= (-1 - (F((2 + (3 + 4))) - (F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5558 &:= (-1 \times (F((2 + (3 + 4))) - (F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5559 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F(3 \times F(4)) - (F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5560 &:= (-1 \times ((F(2 \times 3) \times 4) - (F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5561 &:= ((1 + 2 - F((3 \times F(4)))) + (F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5522 &:= (((-9 + F(8 + 7)) \times F(6)) + (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5523 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) + 7)) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5524 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + (6 \times 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5525 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times F(6 + 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5526 &:= (-9 \times (F(F(8)/7) - (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5527 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (F(7) - F(6 + 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5528 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) \times (F(6) - 5)))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5529 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times F(F(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5530 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times (F(6) \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5531 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + (F(7) \times (F(6) \times (F(5 + 4) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5532 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5533 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times F((6 + 5)))) + (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5534 &:= (-9 + ((8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5535 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - (7 + 6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5536 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((F(7) - (F(F(6)) \times F(5 + 4))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5537 &:= (((9 + 8 + 7) \times F((F(6) + 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5538 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(7) + F(6 + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5539 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
5540 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) + 6 + 5) \times (F(F(4)) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5541 &:= (-9 + 8 - (F(F(7)) - (F(F(6)) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5542 &:= ((9 \times F(8 + 7)) - (F(6) - (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5543 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(7) + F((6 + (5 + 4)))))) + F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5544 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5545 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times F(6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5546 &:= ((9 \times F(8 + 7)) + ((6 - 5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5547 &:= ((-9 + ((F(8 + 7) + F(6)) \times (5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5548 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((7 - (F(6) \times F(5 + 4))) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5549 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times F(F(6))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
5550 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times F(6))) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5551 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (F(7) + (6 - (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5552 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + F(F(7)))) + (6^5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5553 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 - (F(6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5554 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times F(7)) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5555 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(7) + F(6 + 5))) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5556 &:= (-9 + ((F((F(8) - 7)) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5557 &:= ((9 \times (F(8 + 7) + F(6))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
5558 &:= ((9 \times F(8 + 7)) + (F(6) + (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5559 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5560 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - F(F((F(7) - F(6)))) \times (F(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5561 &:= ((9 \times F(8 + 7)) + (F(F(6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5562 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3^{F(4)}) - (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5563 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3^{F(4)}) - (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5564 &:= (((-1 - 2 \times 3) \times 4) + (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5565 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(F(3 + 4)) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5566 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(F(3 + 4)) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5567 &:= (-1 + (((2 - 3) + F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5568 &:= ((-1 + F((F(2 + 3) - (F(4) - (5 + 6)))))) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5569 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(F(3 + 4)) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5570 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) - (F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5571 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) - (F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5572 &:= ((-1 \times (F(2 + 3) \times 4) + (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5573 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((F(3)^4) - (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5574 &:= (((-1 - F(2 + 3)) \times F(4) + (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5575 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) - (4 + (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5576 &:= (-1 - 2 - (F(3 + 4) - (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5577 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 + 4))) + (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5578 &:= ((-1 \times (2 \times (3 + 4))) + (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5579 &:= (-F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + (F((F(F(4)) + (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5580 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F(3 + 4) - (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5581 &:= ((1 \times 2 - F(3 + 4)) + (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5582 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4) \times F(5 + 6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5583 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5584 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) - (F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5585 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5586 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) + (F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5587 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) + (F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5588 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) - (F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5589 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F((3 \times 4)) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5590 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5591 &:= (-1 + (F((F(2 + 3) - (F(4) - (5 + 6)))))) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5592 &:= (F((-1 + 2 - (3 - (4 + 5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5593 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F((3 \times 4)) + F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5594 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + (F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5595 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) + (F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5596 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + (F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5597 &:= ((1 \times F(2 + 3)) + (F((F(F(4)) + (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5598 &:= (-1 - ((2 - F(3 + 4)) \times (5 + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5599 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) + (F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5600 &:= ((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4))) + (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5601 &:= (((1 + 2) \times 3) + (F((F(F(4)) + (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5562 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - F(6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5563 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(7) + 6)) \times F(5 + 4)) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5564 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times ((F(7) \times F(F(6))) - 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5565 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(F(7)) - 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5566 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) - (F(F(7)) + 6 + 5)) \times (4 + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5567 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) + 7)) \times ((F(6) \times F(5 + 4)) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5568 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5569 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + (6 \times 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5570 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + (F(5 + 4) - F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5571 &:= ((-9 - F(8 + 7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5572 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + (F(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5573 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) - (F(7) - (F(F(6)) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5574 &:= (-9 + (((F(8 + 7) + F(6)) \times (5 + 4)) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5575 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times (F(6) \times 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5576 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F((7 + F(6)))) + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5577 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - ((F(7 + 6) + F(5 + 4)) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5578 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (F(7) - (F(F(6)) \times F(5 + 4)))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5579 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) - (7 - (F(F(6)) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5580 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - ((F(7) + F(6 + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5581 &:= ((9 \times ((8 \times (F(7) \times 6)) - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5582 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + F((F(6) + 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5583 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) \times (F(6) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
5584 &:= ((-9 + 8 - (F(F(7)) \times (6 - 5 - 4))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5585 &:= (-9 + ((F(8 + 7) \times F(6)) + (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5586 &:= (((9 - 8 - 7) + (F(6) \times F(5 + 4))) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5587 &:= (9 + ((F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + (6 \times 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5588 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + F(7)) \times F((6 + 5)))) \times F(4)) + F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5589 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (F(7) + (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5590 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times F(6 + 5)))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5591 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) - 7) \times (F(6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5592 &:= (9 + 8 + 7) \times F(F(6) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
5593 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(7) + F(6 + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5594 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5595 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) - (F(6) - F(5 + 4)))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5596 &:= (-9 - (F(F(8)/7) - (F((6 + 5)) \times (F(4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5597 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + F(F(7)))) + (6^5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5598 &:= (9 \times ((F((F(8)/7)) \times 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5599 &:= ((9 \times (F(8 + 7) + 6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5600 &:= ((-9 + 8 - F(7)) \times (F(6) \times (5 - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5601 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) + F(7)) \times ((F(6) - 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5641 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3) + F((F(4)) + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5642 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + ((F(F(4)) + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5643 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))^{F(4)}) \times (F((5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5644 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + ((F(F(4)) + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5645 &:= (((-1 + (F(2 \times 3))^{F(4)}) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5646 &:= ((1 + F(2 + 3)) + ((F(F(4)) + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5647 &:= (F((-1 - 2 + F(3 + 4))) + (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5648 &:= (((-1 - ((2 - F((3 \times 4))) \times 5)) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5649 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 + 3)))^{F(4)}) \times (5 + ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
5650 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (F(F(3 + 4)) + F(5 + 6 + 7))) + 8 + 9)) \\
5651 &:= (-F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + ((F(4) + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5652 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times F(4)) + (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5653 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + ((F(F(4)) + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5654 &:= (-1 - (F((2 \times (3 + 4))) \times (5 \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
5655 &:= (-1 + (((F(2 \times 3))^{F(4)}) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5656 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3))^{F(4)}) + (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5657 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) + ((F(4) + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5658 &:= ((-1 - (F((2 \times (3 + 4))) \times 5)) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5659 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) + ((F(4) + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5660 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) + ((F(F(4)) + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5661 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5662 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5663 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 + F(3)) + F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5664 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) + F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5665 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5666 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + ((F(4) + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5667 &:= (((-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times F(4 + 5))) \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5668 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + ((F(4) + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5669 &:= (1 \times F(2 + 3) + ((F(4) + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5670 &:= ((-1 - F((2 \times (3 + 4)))) \times (5 \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5671 &:= ((-1 + ((F(2 \times 3))^{F(4)}) \times F(5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5672 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3))^{F(4)}) \times F(5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5673 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))^4) + (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5674 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3^4) + (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5675 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) \times 4) + (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5676 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) - (F((6 + 7)) - F(8 + 9)))) \\
5677 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(4 + 5) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5678 &:= ((-1 + ((F(2 + F(3)) \times F(4 + 5)) + F((6 + 7)))) \times (8 + 9)) \\
5679 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + ((4 + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5680 &:= (((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F(4 + 5))) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5641 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (F(F(6)) \times F(5 + 4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5642 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + ((F((7 + F(6))) \times (5 + 4)) + F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5643 &:= (-9 \times ((F(8)/7) - (F(F(6)) \times ((5 + 4) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5644 &:= (-9 - 8) \times ((F(7) \times (F(6) - F(5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5645 &:= ((9 \times F(8 + 7)) + ((6 + 5) + F((4 + F(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5646 &:= (-9 + (F((F(8) - (F(7) - 6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5647 &:= (((9 + 8 + 7) \times F((F(6) + 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5648 &:= (F(-9 + 8 + 7) \times ((F(F(6)) \times F(5 + 4)) - F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5649 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - 7)) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5650 &:= ((9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5651 &:= ((9 \times ((8 \times (F(7) \times 6)) + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5652 &:= (-9 \times ((F(8)/7) - (F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5653 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (F(7) + (F(6) \times (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5654 &:= (-9 + ((F((F(8) - 7)) \times (6 + (5 + 4))) + F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5655 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5656 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) - (7 - F(6 + 5))) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5657 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + (F(F(7)) + 6)) \times F(5 + 4)) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5658 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7 \times (F(6) + (5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5659 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) - (F(F(7)) + 6)) \times (F(5 + 4) - F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5660 &:= ((-9 \times ((F(8) - (7 \times F(F(6)))) \times 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5661 &:= (-9 \times (F(F(8)/7) - (F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5662 &:= (-9 + (((8 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5663 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((F(F(7)) \times (F(6) - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5664 &:= ((9 \times (F(8 + 7) + F(F(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5665 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (F(7) + (6 - 5)))) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5666 &:= ((-9 - 8 - F(7)) + (F((6 + 5)) \times (F(F(4))^{3+2+1}))) \\
5667 &:= (-9 + ((F((F(8) - 7)) \times (6 + (5 + 4))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5668 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (F(F(6)) \times F(5 + 4)))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5669 &:= ((9 \times (8 + (7 \times F(6 + 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5670 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 - (F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5671 &:= ((9 \times ((8 \times (F(7) \times 6)) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5672 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + (F(F(7)) + 6)) \times F(5 + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5673 &:= (9 - (8 \times (7 - ((F(6) + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5674 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7) \times F(F(6))))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5675 &:= (-9 - (F(8) + (7 - (F(6) \times (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5676 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(F(7))) \times (6 + (5 + 4))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5677 &:= (((-9 \times F(8)) - F(7)) \times (6 - F(5 + 4))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5678 &:= (-9 + (((F(8 + 7) + F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4)) + F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5679 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (7 \times 6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5680 &:= ((-9 \times ((F(8) - (7 \times F(F(6)))) \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5681 &:= (F((-1 \times 2 + F(3 + 4))) + (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5682 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) + ((4 + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5683 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) + ((4 + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5684 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) + ((F(4) + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5685 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3) + (F(F(4)) + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5686 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + ((4 + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5687 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (F(3) + F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5688 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5689 &:= (((-1 + 2)^{F(3)}) + ((4 + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5690 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + ((4 + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5691 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) + ((4 + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5692 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + ((4 + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5693 &:= ((1 \times F(2 + 3)) + ((4 + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5694 &:= ((1 + F(2 + 3)) + ((4 + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5695 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F((F(3) + 4 + 5)) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5696 &:= (F((-1 \times 2 + F(3 + 4))) \times ((5 \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5697 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times F(3 + 4))) \times (5 - (F((6 + 7)) - (8 + 9)))) \\
5698 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3^{F(4)}) \times (5 - (F((6 + 7)) - (8 + 9)))) \\
5699 &:= (-1 \times ((F(2 \times 3) \times (4 \times (5 - F((6 + 7)))) + F(8 + 9))) \\
5700 &:= ((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - ((5 - (6 + 7)) - F(8 + 9))) \\
5701 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + ((4 + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5702 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7)))) - (8 + 9)) \\
5703 &:= (-1 - (((2 - F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 \times F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5704 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 \times F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5705 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3+4+5}) + ((6 + 7) + F(8 + 9)))) \\
5706 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (4^5)) + ((6 + 7) + F(8 + 9))) \\
5707 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3))^{F(F(4)) \times 5}) + (F((6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9)))) \\
5708 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) + ((4 + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5709 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(F(3 + 4)) - (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5710 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3) + (F(4) + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5711 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5712 &:= ((F(F(F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3)))))) + F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5713 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3) + (F(4) + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5714 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) - ((F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5715 &:= (((-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times F(4 + 5))) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5716 &:= ((1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) + ((F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5717 &:= F(F(F(2 + 3))^{F(4)} + F(5 + F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5718 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((F(3) \times (4^5)) + 6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9))) \\
5719 &:= (-1 + (((F(2 \times 3))^{F(F(4))}) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5681 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) + (F(F(6)) \times F(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5682 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times ((F(7) \times F(F(6))) - F(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
5683 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times F(7)) + (F((6 + 5)) \times (F(F(4))^{3+2+1}))) \\
5684 &:= (((-9 \times F(8)) - 7) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5685 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) + (6 \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5686 &:= ((9 \times F(8 + 7)) + ((6 \times F(5 + 4)) - F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5687 &:= (-9 - ((F(F(8)/7) - (F(F(6)) \times F(5 + 4))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5688 &:= ((-9 - 8 - 7) + (F(6) \times (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5689 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (7 + (F(6) \times (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
5690 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (F(7) - (F(F(6)) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5691 &:= (-9 + ((F(8 + 7) - (F(6) \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5692 &:= ((-9 - 8 + F(7)) + (F((6 + 5)) \times (F(F(4))^{3+2+1}))) \\
5693 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F((7 + F(6)))) + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5694 &:= ((9 \times (F(8 + 7) + F(F(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5695 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) + (F(6) \times (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5696 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5697 &:= (-9 \times (((F(F(8)/7) - F(F(6))) \times F(5 + 4)) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5698 &:= (-9 + 8 - (F(7) - (F(6) \times (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5699 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (F(7) - (F(6) \times (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5700 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5701 &:= (-9 - (F(F(8)/7) - (F(6) \times (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5702 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) + (F(6) \times (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5703 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((F(7) \times F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5704 &:= ((F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) \times (F(6) \times F(5 + 4))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5705 &:= ((9 \times (F(8 + 7) + (6 \times 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5706 &:= ((F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) \times (F(6) \times F(5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5707 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7 \times F(6))) \times (F(5 + 4) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5708 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F(7) + (F(6) \times (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5709 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5710 &:= (((-9 + F(8 + 7)) - (6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5711 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) + F(6 + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5712 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times (F(6) + (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5713 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) - 6) \times (F(5 + 4) - F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5714 &:= ((-9 \times ((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times (F(6) - 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5715 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (F(7) + (F(F(6)) \times ((5 + 4) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5716 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (F(7) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5717 &:= (-9 + F(8) - (7 - (F(6) \times (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5718 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + (F(6) \times (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5719 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5720 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3))^{F(4)} \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5721 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F(3 + 4) \times ((F((5 + 6)) \times F(7)) - F(8 + 9)))) \\
5722 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((3 \times F((F(4) \times 5))) + F((6 + 7)))) + F(8 + 9))) \\
5723 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - ((4^5) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5724 &:= (1 + ((2 \times ((3 \times F((F(4) \times 5))) + F((6 + 7)))) + F(8 + 9))) \\
5725 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - ((4^5) - (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5726 &:= (((-1 + F((2 \times (3 + 4)))) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 - F(8 + 9))) \\
5727 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + ((F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5728 &:= (((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F(4 + 5))) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5729 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) + ((F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5730 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (F(F(4))^5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5731 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) + ((F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5732 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times ((F(4)^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5733 &:= (-1 \times ((F(F(2 \times 3))^{F(F(4))}) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5734 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + ((F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5735 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) + F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5736 &:= ((F((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4 + 5)))) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5737 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(F(3 \times 4 - 5))) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5738 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + ((F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5739 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) + ((F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5740 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + ((F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5741 &:= ((1 \times F(2 + 3)) + ((F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5742 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5743 &:= (-1 - (F(2 \times 3) \times (F(F(4)) - (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5744 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (F((3 \times 4) \times 5)) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5745 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5746 &:= ((-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3))^{F(F(4))}) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5747 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (F(F(4)) - (5 \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5748 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) \times (F(F(4)) - (5 \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5749 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + ((F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5750 &:= ((1 + 2 - F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5751 &:= ((F((-1 - 2 + F(3 + 4))) \times (5 \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5752 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) + (F(4) \times (F((5 + 6)) + (F(F(7)) + F(8 + 9)))) \\
5753 &:= (1 + (((2 + (F((3 \times 4) \times 5)) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5754 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - (F(F(4)) \times (5 \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5755 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F(3) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5756 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(3) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5757 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - ((F(4 + 5) + F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5758 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((3 + 4) + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5759 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times ((F(F(4))^5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5720 &:= (F(-9 + 8 + 7) \times ((F(6) + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5721 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) - ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5722 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) - F(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
5723 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F((7 + F(6)))) - F(((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5724 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7) \times (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5725 &:= ((9 \times ((8 + F(7)) \times (6 \times 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5726 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) + F(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
5727 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) + ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5728 &:= (((F(-9 + 8 + 7) \times F((6 + 5))) + 4) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5729 &:= (-9 - 8) \times ((F(7) \times F(F(6))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5730 &:= ((-9 - F(8)) \times (7 + 6 - (F(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5731 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + (7 + (F(6) \times (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5732 &:= (9 + ((F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + (F(6) \times 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
5733 &:= ((-9 + ((F(8) \times (7 + 6)) + (5 + 4))) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5734 &:= ((-9 \times ((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times (F(6) - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5735 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) - F(7)) \times ((6 + 5) - (F(4)^{3+2+1}))) \\
5736 &:= (-9 + ((F((F(8) - 7)) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5737 &:= (9 + ((F(8) \times (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
5738 &:= (-9 - (F(8) + (7 - (F(F(6)) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5739 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5740 &:= (9 + ((F(8) \times (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) - F(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
5741 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) + ((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5742 &:= (-9 \times ((F(8) \times (7 - (F(6) \times 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5743 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(7) - (F(6) - (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5744 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(7) + (F(F(6)) \times F(5 + 4))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5745 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(F(7)) + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5746 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) - 7) \times (F(6) + F(5 + 4))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5747 &:= (9 + ((F(8) \times (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
5748 &:= (((-9 \times F(8))/7) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5749 &:= (9 + (F(8) + (7 + (F(6) \times (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5750 &:= (((-9 + F(8 + 7)) - (F(F(6)) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5751 &:= ((-9 - 8 - 7) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5752 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (7 + (F(F(6)) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5753 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (F(F(7)) \times ((6 \times 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5754 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + ((F(7) + F(6 + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5755 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) + F(F(7)))) \times F(F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5756 &:= (9 + 8) \times (F(7) \times (F(F(6)) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5757 &:= ((-9 \times F(F(8)/7) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5758 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(7) + F(6)) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5759 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (F(6) \times (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5800 &:= ((-1 + 2 - F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5801 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times F(3 + 4))) \times F((5 + F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5802 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - ((F(4)^5) \times F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5803 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(F(4)) + (5 \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5804 &:= ((-1 + F((F(2 + 3) \times 4))) - (5 \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5805 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - ((F(F(4))^5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5806 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((3 \times F(4)) + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5807 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (F(F(3 + 4)) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5808 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (F(F(3 + 4)) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5809 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((3 \times F(4)) + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5810 &:= (-1 - (((F(2 \times 3) - F((4 + 5 + 6))) \times 7) - F(8 + 9))) \\
5811 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5812 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - F(3)) \times (F((4 - (5 - (6 + 7)))) - F(8 + 9))) \\
5813 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times ((F((3 \times 4)) - 5) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5814 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 + 3) \times 4)) \times ((5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\
5815 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 \times F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5816 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (3 \times (F(4)^5))) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5817 &:= (((1 + 2) \times (3 + ((F(4)^5) \times F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5818 &:= (((1 \times F(2 + 3)) \times (F(F(4)) + (5 \times F((6 + 7)))) - 8 - 9) \\
5819 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) - (4 \times (((5 + 6) \times F(7)) - F(8 + 9)))) \\
5820 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times ((F(4) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5821 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) - (4 - (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5822 &:= (-1 - 2 - (F(F(3 + 4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5823 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(F(3 + 4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5824 &:= ((1 - 2) - (F(F(3 + 4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5825 &:= (-F(F((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5826 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F(F(3 + 4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5827 &:= (1 \times 2 - (F(F(3 + 4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5828 &:= (1 + 2 - (F(F(3 + 4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5829 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3^{F(4-5+6)}) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5830 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3^{F(4-5+6)}) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5831 &:= 1 - 2 + 3^{F(4-5+6)} \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5832 &:= (1 - 2 + F(F(3 + 4)) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5833 &:= -1 + 2 + 3^{F(4-5+6)} \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5834 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F(F(3)^4) + (5 \times (F((6 + 7)) - F(8 + 9)))) \\
5835 &:= ((-1 - (F(2 \times 3) \times (F(4)^5))) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5836 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (F(4)^5))) \times ((6 + 7) - (8 + 9))) \\
5837 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5838 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5800 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - (7 + F(F(6)))) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5801 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (F(7) + (F(F(6)) \times F(5 + 4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5802 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times (F(6) + F(5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5803 &:= (((9 + 8 \times 7) \times F((6 + 5))) - (F(4) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5804 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) \times (F(6) + F(5 + 4))) + F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5805 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - ((7 \times F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5806 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) + (7 \times F(6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5807 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) + (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5808 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) - ((6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5809 &:= ((-9 - 8 + ((7 + 6 + 5)^{F(4)})) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5810 &:= (((-9 \times 8 \times (F(7) - F(F(6)))) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5811 &:= (((-9 \times 8 / (7 - (6 + 5)))^{F(4)} - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5812 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + (F(((6 + 5) + F(4))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5813 &:= (F((-9 + (F(8) + 7))) + (6 \times (F(5 + 4) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5814 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - F(6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5815 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times (F(6) \times 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5816 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7 \times (F(F(6)) \times 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5817 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times (F(6) + F(5 + 4)))) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5818 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(7 + 6) \times (5^{F(F(4))})) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5819 &:= ((9 \times (F(8 + 7) + 6)) + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5820 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - F(7))) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5821 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7) + (F(F(6)) \times 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5822 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5823 &:= (-9 \times (F((F(8) - 7)) - (F((F(6) - 5))^{4+3+2+1}))) \\
5824 &:= (-9 + 8 - (F(F(7)) \times ((6 \times 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5825 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (F(F(7)) \times ((6 \times 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5826 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) + (F(F(6)) \times F(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5827 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + (7 + F(F(6)))) \times F(5 + 4)) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5828 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (F(7) + (F(F(6)) \times F(5 + 4)))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5829 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times ((F(7) \times F(F(6))) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
5830 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times F(7)) + 6 + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5831 &:= (-9 + ((F(8 + 7) - (F(F(6)) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5832 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times 6)) \times (5 + 4)) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5833 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) + F(F(7))) \times (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5834 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) + (F((6 + 5) \times (F(F(4))^{3+2+1}))) \\
5835 &:= ((-9 + (F((F(8) - 7)) + F(F(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5836 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((7 + 6 + 5)^{F(4)} + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5837 &:= (-9 + F(8) - (F(F(7)) \times ((6 \times 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5838 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) + (F(6) \times F(5 + 4))) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5839 &:= (-1 + (F(2+3) \times ((4^5) + (6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
5840 &:= (F(F((-1+2 \times 3))) \times ((4^5) + (6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
5841 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (F((3 \times 4) - 5))) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5842 &:= (((((-1-2) \times 3) + F(4+5)) \times F((6+7))) + 8 + 9) \\
5843 &:= (F((-1 + (F(F(2+3)) \times 4))) + ((5 \times (6+7)) + F(8+9))) \\
5844 &:= ((-1 - F(2+3)) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) + ((6+7) - F(8+9)))) \\
5845 &:= (((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + F(4)) \times (5+6+7)) + F(8+9)) \\
5846 &:= ((F((-1+2 + F(3+4))) \times 5) + (F((6+7)) \times (8+9))) \\
5847 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3 - ((F(4)^5) \times F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5848 &:= (((-1 + F(2+3))^4) + (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5849 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times F(3+4))) \times F((5 + F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5850 &:= ((1 - 2 - F(F(3+4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5851 &:= (1 + (2 \times (F(3+4) \times (5 \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5852 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3^{F(4)})) \times (F((5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5853 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(F(3+4)) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5854 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(F(3+4)) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5855 &:= (1 - 2 + ((F(F(3+4)) + (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5856 &:= ((F(F((-1+2) \times (3+4))) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5857 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(F(3+4)) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5858 &:= (1 \times 2 + ((F(F(3+4)) + (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5859 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times 3)^{F(4)})) \times (5 - (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5860 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((F(3) - F(4+5)) \times F((6+7))) + F(8+9))) \\
5861 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((F((3 \times 4) - 5) \times F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5862 &:= ((((-1 + F((F(2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) - 5) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5863 &:= (-1 + (((2 + F((3 \times 4))) \times (5 \times F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5864 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))^{F(4)} - (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
5865 &:= ((-1 + (2^{F(3+F(4))})) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5866 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + ((F(F(3)^4) - 5) \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5867 &:= ((-1 + ((F((F(2 \times 3) \times F(F(4)))) - 5) \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5868 &:= (((F((-1 + F(2+3)) \times 4) - 5) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5869 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((F(F(3)^4) - 5) \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5870 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + ((4 \times (5 - F((6+7)))) + 8 + 9)) \\
5871 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (3 \times (F(4)^5))) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5872 &:= (((1 + ((2 + F((3 \times 4))) \times 5)) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5873 &:= (1 + (((2 + (3 \times (F(4)^5))) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5874 &:= (-1 - ((2 + F(F(3+4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5875 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - F(F(3+4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5876 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) \times (4 \times (F(5+6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5877 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 \times 4 + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5839 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times ((F(7) \times F(F(6))) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5840 &:= ((-9 + ((F(8) \times (7 + F(F(6)))) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5841 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + F(F(7))) - (F(6+5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5842 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) - 7)) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5843 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) - (F(7) - (F(6) \times (F(5+4) \times F(F(3+2+1)))))) \\
5844 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + (F(6) \times (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5845 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7 \times F(F(6)))) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5846 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) + F(7))) \times F(F(6+5-4))) + F(F(3+2+1))) \\
5847 &:= (-9 + (((8 - F(F(7))) \times (F(6) - F(5+4))) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5848 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times F(F(7)))) + (6^5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5849 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (7 - F(6+5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5850 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - F(7)) \times F(6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5851 &:= (-9 - (((8 - F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
5852 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + 6))) \times (F(5+4) - (3+2+1))) \\
5853 &:= ((-9 - (F(8+7) + F((6+5)))) + (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)})) \\
5854 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + (7 + F(F(6)))) \times F(5+4)) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5855 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(7) + (6 + (F(5+4) \times F(F(3+2+1)))))) \\
5856 &:= (F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) + (F(6) \times (F(5+4) \times F(F(3+2+1)))) \\
5857 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) + (F((6+5)) \times (F(F(4))^{3+2+1}))) \\
5858 &:= (((-9 \times F(8)) - F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5859 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) \times (F(7) + ((6+5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5860 &:= (((-9 - (F(8) - F(F(7)))) \times F(F(6))) + F(((5+4) + F(3+2+1)))) \\
5861 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7 \times (F(F(6)) \times 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5862 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (F((F(F(6)) - 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
5863 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times ((6 + F(5+4)) \times F(F(3+2+1)))) \\
5864 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) \times (F(5+4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
5865 &:= (-9 - ((8 - F((F(7) - (6 - 5 - 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5866 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - (7 \times F((6+5)))) + (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)})) \\
5867 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times F((F(F(6)) - 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5868 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((F(7) - (6 - 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5869 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
5870 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times F(7)) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5871 &:= (-9 - (8 \times 7 \times (F(F(6)) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
5872 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - ((F(F(7)) - 6) \times (F(5+4) - F(3+2+1)))) \\
5873 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (F(F(7)) + (F(6) \times (F(5+4) \times F(F(3+2+1)))))) \\
5874 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - F(F(7))) \times (6 - ((5+4) \times F(3+2+1)))) \\
5875 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) - ((F(F(7)) \times (F(6) - F(5+4))) - (3+2+1))) \\
5876 &:= ((-9 - 8 \times F(7)) \times (F(6) - (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5877 &:= (-9 \times ((F(8) - F(F(7))) - (F(F(6))^{F(5+4-3-2-1)})))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5878 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times 4 + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5879 &:= (-1 + (((2^{F(3+F(4))}) - (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5880 &:= ((-1 - ((2 - F(F(3)^4))/5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5881 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times 4 + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5882 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (((3 \times (4 \times 5)) - F((6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \\
5883 &:= (1 + 2 + ((3 \times 4 + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5884 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times (F((F(4) \times 5)) + F((6 + 7)))) - (8 + 9)) \\
5885 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - ((4^5) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5886 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + F((F(3) \times (F(4) + 5)))) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5887 &:= (-1 + ((2^{F(3+F(4))}) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
5888 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3))^4) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5889 &:= (-1 - (F(F(F(2 + 3))) \times (4 - ((5 \times F((6 + 7))) + 8 + 9)))) \\
5890 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) \times (4 - ((5 \times F((6 + 7))) + 8 + 9))) \\
5891 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((F(F(3)^4) - 5) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
5892 &:= (((-1 + F((2 \times (F(3 + 4) - 5)))) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5893 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((F(3 + 4) \times (5 - F((6 + 7)))) + 8 + 9))) \\
5894 &:= (1 \times 2 \times (((F(F(3 + 4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7)) - (8 + 9))) \\
5895 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (((F(4)^5) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5896 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (F((F(3) \times (F(4) + 5))) \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5897 &:= ((-1 + (F((2 \times (F(3 + 4) - 5))) \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5898 &:= ((F((-1 + (F(2 \times 3) + 4 + 5))) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5899 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F((F(3) \times (F(4) + 5))) \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5900 &:= ((-1 - 2 - F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5901 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(3 + 4) + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5902 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(3 + 4) + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5903 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (F(F(3 + 4)) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5904 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((3 + 4) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5905 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(3 + 4) + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5906 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times F(F(3)^4)) - 5) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5907 &:= (((-1 \times 2 \times F(F(3)^4)) + 5) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5908 &:= (((-1 - 2 \times 3) \times 4) \times (5 - (F((6 + 7)) - (8 + 9)))) \\
5909 &:= (-1 - (((2 - F(F(3)^4))/5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5910 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + F(F(3)^4))/5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5911 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times (F((5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5912 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times ((3^4) - F(5 + 6 + 7))) - F(8 + 9)) \\
5913 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (F(F(4)) \times F(((5 \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
5914 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((F(F(3)^4) - 5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5915 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))^{F(F(4))}) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5916 &:= (((F((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times 4) - 5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5878 &:= (((-9 + F((F(8) - 7))) \times (F(F(6)) - 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5879 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5880 &:= (((-9 + F(8 + 7)) - (F(6) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5881 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7 \times (F(F(6)) \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5882 &:= (-9 - 8) \times ((F(7) \times (F(6) - F(5 + 4))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5883 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) - (6 - F(5 + 4)))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5884 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times ((F(7) \times F(F(6))) + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5885 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - (7 + (6 \times 5))) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5886 &:= (9 \times (F(8 + 7) - ((6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5887 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (7 - F((6 + 5)))) + (4 - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5888 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times 7) + (F(6) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5889 &:= (((-9 - F(8)) \times (7 - (6 \times F(5 + 4)))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5890 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5891 &:= ((-9 - 8 + ((7 \times (6 + 5))^{F(F(4))}) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5892 &:= (-9 + ((8 + F(7)) \times (6 + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5893 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times F(F(7)))) + (6^5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5894 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (7 - F(6 + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5895 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) + (F(7) \times (F(6) - (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5896 &:= (-9 - (((8 - F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) + 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5897 &:= (9 \times 8 - (F(F(7)) \times ((6 \times 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5898 &:= (((-9 + F((F(8) - 7))) \times (F(F(6)) - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5899 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (F(7) - (6 \times (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5900 &:= (((-9 + F(8 + 7)) - (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5901 &:= (F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) \times (6 + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5902 &:= (((-9 - F(8)) \times (7 - (6 \times F(5 + 4)))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5903 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times 7) + (F(6 + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5904 &:= (-9 \times 8 \times (F(F(7)) - (F(F(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5905 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F((F(7) - (6 - 5 - 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5906 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) - (F(7) - (F(F(6)) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5907 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) - (F(7) - F(F(6)))) \times (F(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5908 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times F(F(7)))) + (F((F(6) - 5))^{4+3+2+1})) \\
5909 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times F(F(7))) + (F((F(F(6)) - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5910 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (F(6) \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5911 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F((7 + F(6)))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5912 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times F((F(F(6)) - 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5913 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - ((7 \times F(6 + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5914 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (7 - F(6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5915 &:= (((9 + (8 \times 7 \times F(F(6)))) \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5916 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) + (F(6) \times (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5917 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((F(F(3)^4) - 5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5918 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times F((3 \times 4)) - 5) \times F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5919 &:= (-1 - 2 + (F(F(3)^4) \times (5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5920 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times ((F(4 + 5) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5921 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times F((F(4) - ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
5922 &:= (1 - 2 + F(F(3)^4) + 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5923 &:= (-1 + 2 + (F(F(3)^4) \times (5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5924 &:= (1 \times 2 + (F(F(3)^4) \times (5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5925 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((F(3) - ((F(4)^5) + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5926 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((F(3) - ((F(4)^5) + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5927 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times (3 + 4)) + F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5928 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + (F(4) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5929 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((F(3) - ((F(4)^5) + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5930 &:= (((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) - 4) \times (5 + F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5931 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times F(F(3 + 4))) - (5 + 6)) \times F(7)) + 8 + 9) \\
5932 &:= (1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 + (F((6 + 7)) + F((8 + 9)))))) \\
5933 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(F(3)^4)) \times (5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5934 &:= (-1 + 2 + F(F(3)^4) + 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5935 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3))^{F(4)} + (F((5 + F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5936 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times F(F(3)^4)) + 5) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5937 &:= (((-1 \times 2 \times F(F(3)^4)) - 5) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5938 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(F(3)^4) + (5 - (F((6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
5939 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times F(3 \times F(4)))) \times F(5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5940 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3+4}) + 5)) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5941 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (F((F(4) + 5 + 6)) + (7 + F(8 + 9)))) \\
5942 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (F(F(3)^4) + F((5 + 6)))) \times 7) - F(8 + 9)) \\
5943 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F((F(3) \times (F(4) + 5))) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5944 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F((F(3) \times (F(4) + 5))) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5945 &:= (-1 + ((F((2 \times (F(3 + 4) - 5))) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5946 &:= ((F((-1 + (F(2 \times 3) + 4 + 5))) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5947 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F((F(3) \times (F(4) + 5))) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5948 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F((F(3) \times (F(4) + 5))) - (F((6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
5949 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 - F(4 + 5)) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5950 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3 - F(4 + 5)) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5951 &:= (-1 - ((F(2 + F(3)) - F(4 + 5)) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5952 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + (4 + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5953 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 - F(4 + 5)) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5954 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) + (((F(4)^5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5955 &:= ((-1 \times F(F(2 \times 3))) + (((F(4)^5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5917 &:= (((9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
5918 &:= (((-9 - F(8)) \times (7 - (6 \times F(5 + 4)))) + F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5919 &:= (F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5920 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7 + F(F(6)))^{F(5+4-3-2-1)})) \\
5921 &:= (-9 + (((F(8) \times (7 + F(F(6)))) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5922 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((7 \times F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5923 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (((F(7) \times F(6)) + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5924 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5925 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7 \times F(F(6)))) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
5926 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7 \times (F(F(6)) \times 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5927 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) - F(7 + 6)) \times (F(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5928 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - (F(7) - F((6 + (5 + 4)))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5929 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(7) \times 6))^{F(5+4-3-2-1)}) \\
5930 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) - (7 \times F(6 + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5931 &:= (-9 + ((F(8 + 7) - (F(F(6)) - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5932 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times F((F(F(6)) - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5933 &:= (-9 + (((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times (6 - F(5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5934 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7 + 6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5935 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5936 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (F(F(7)) + (F(F(6)) \times (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5937 &:= ((-9 + 8 - (7 \times F((6 + 5)))) + (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)})) \\
5938 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times F((6 + 5))) + (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)}) \\
5939 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (F((6 + 5)) \times 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5940 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times ((6 + 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5941 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (F((6 + 5)) \times 4))) + F(3 + 2 + 1) \\
5942 &:= ((-9 + ((F(8)/7)^{F(6)}) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5943 &:= (F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) \times (F(6) + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5944 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) + (F(6) \times (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5945 &:= (9 - ((F(8) - F(7 + 6)) \times (F(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5946 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times F((F(F(6)) - 5 - 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5947 &:= (-9 + F(8) + (((7 \times (6 + 5))^{F(F(4))}) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5948 &:= (-9 + (((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times (6 - F(5 + 4))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5949 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (F((7 + F(6))) + ((5 + 4) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5950 &:= (-9 - 8) \times ((F(7) - 6) \times (5 - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5951 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (F(F(6)) \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5952 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + F(6)) \times ((5 + 4) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5953 &:= ((-9 - (F(8 + 7) - (6 + 5))) + (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)})) \\
5954 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (F((6 + 5)) \times 4))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5955 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) + (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5956 &:= (((-1-2+F(F(3+4))) \times (5+F(F(6)))) - 7-8-9) \\
5957 &:= ((-1+(2 \times (3^4))) \times (5+(F(6)+7+8+9))) \\
5958 &:= ((-1-((2 \times 3) \times F((F(4) \times 5)))) \times (6-7-8-9)) \\
5959 &:= ((F((-1+F(F(2 \times 3)))) + (4^5)) - (F((6+7)+F(8+9)))) \\
5960 &:= ((-1+F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) \times (5+(6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
5961 &:= (-1+(2 \times (((3+F(F(4)))^5) - (6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
5962 &:= (1 \times 2 \times (((3+F(F(4)))^5) - (6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
5963 &:= (1+(2 \times (((3+F(F(4)))^5) - (6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
5964 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + (F(F(3)^4) + 5)) \times 6) + 7+8+9) \\
5965 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (3 \times ((4+5) \times ((6+7) \times (8+9)))))) \\
5966 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times F((3 \times 4))) - 5) \times F(F(6))) + 7+8+9) \\
5967 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) + (((F(4)^5) + 6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
5968 &:= (-1 + (F((2 \times (3+4))) + (F((5+F(6))) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
5969 &:= (F((-1+2+F(3+4))) + (F((5+F(6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
5970 &:= ((F(F((-1+F(2 \times 3)))) - F(4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
5971 &:= ((-1 \times F(2+3)) + (((F(4)^5) + 6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
5972 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - F(3)) + (((F(4)^5) + 6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
5973 &:= (F((-1+F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(4) \times ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
5974 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(F(3+4)) - (5 - F(F(6)))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
5975 &:= (1 - 2 + ((F(F(3+4)) - (5 - F(F(6)))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
5976 &:= ((-1-2) \times (F((3 \times 4)) - (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
5977 &:= (-1+2+((F(F(3+4)) - (5 - F(F(6)))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
5978 &:= (F(F((-1+F(2+3)))) + (((F(4)^5) + 6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
5979 &:= (F((-1+F(2+3))) + (((F(4)^5) + 6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
5980 &:= ((-1+F(2+3)) + (((F(4)^5) + 6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
5981 &:= (-1 - (((2 - F(F(3+4))) \times (5+F(F(6)))) + 7+8+9)) \\
5982 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + F(F(3+4))) \times (5+F(F(6)))) - 7-8-9) \\
5983 &:= (-1 - (F(2 \times 3) \times (4 \times (5 - (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
5984 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3+4}) + 5) \times (F(F(6)) + 7+8+9))) \\
5985 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 \times 4) \times (5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
5986 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3 \times 4) \times (5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
5987 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times F(3 \times F(4)))) \times F(5+6)) + 7+8+9) \\
5988 &:= ((-1+2-F(3+4)) \times (5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
5989 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3^{F(4)}))) \times (F(5+6) + 7+8+9)) \\
5990 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (((3 - (4+5)) \times F((6+7))) - F(8+9))) \\
5991 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3 - ((F(4)+5) \times (F((6+7))+8+9)))) \\
5992 &:= (((-1+F(F(2 \times 3)))^{F(F(4))} + (F((5+F(6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
5993 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times ((4^5) - F(F(6)))) - 7-8-9) \\
5994 &:= (F((-1+F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(4) \times (F((5+F(6))) + 7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5956 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + F(7)) \times F((6+5)))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
5957 &:= ((9 \times F(8)) - (7 - (F(F(6)) \times (5 \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5958 &:= (-9 \times (((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times 6) + F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5959 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (7 - F(6+5))) + F(4+3+2+1)) \\
5960 &:= (((-9 + F(((8 + F(7)) - 6))) - 5) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
5961 &:= (-9 + ((F((F(8) - 7)) + F(F(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5962 &:= (-9 + F(8) + (((7 \times (6+5))^{F(F(4))} + F(F(3+2+1)))) \\
5963 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - (7 \times (6+5))) \times F((F(4) + F(3+2+1)))) \\
5964 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times (F(F(6)) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
5965 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - ((F(7) \times F(6)) + 5) \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\
5966 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + ((5+4) + F(3+2+1)))) \\
5967 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (F(7) - F(6+5))) - F(4+3+2+1))) \\
5968 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (F(F(7)) - F((F(F(6)) - 5)))) + F(4+3+2+1))) \\
5969 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) - (F(F(7)) \times ((6 \times 5) - F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5970 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
5971 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + (7 \times ((F(F(6)) - 5) \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5972 &:= ((-9 + (F(8+7) \times (6+5))) - (F(4)^{3+2+1})) \\
5973 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - ((F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + 5)) - F(4+3+2+1))) \\
5974 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((F(F(7)) + 6) \times (5 \times (F(4) - F(3+2+1)))) \\
5975 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) + (7-6)) \times (F(5+4) \times F(3+2+1)))) \\
5976 &:= (9 \times (F(8+7) - ((6-5) - F(4+3+2+1))) \\
5977 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times F((F(F(6)) - 5))) + F(4+3+2+1)) \\
5978 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((F(7) \times F(6)) + 5) \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\
5979 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + (F((6+5) \times F(4)))) - F(F(3+2+1))) \\
5980 &:= (((-9 + F(8+7)) - (F(6) - 5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
5981 &:= (-9 + ((F(8+7) - (6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
5982 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (F((F(F(6)) - 5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
5983 &:= (-9 + (8 \times 7 \times (F((6+5)) - (F(4) - F(F(3+2+1)))))) \\
5984 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times 7 + F((6 + (5+4)))) \times F(3+2+1)) \\
5985 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) + 7)) \times (F(F(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5986 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7+6)) + 5) \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\
5987 &:= (F((-9 + (F(8) + 7))) + ((F((6+5)) - F(4)) \times F(F(3+2+1)))) \\
5988 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times 6)) - (5 + F(4+3+2+1))) \\
5989 &:= ((-9 - 8 \times F(7)) \times (F((F(6) - 5)) - F(4+3+2+1))) \\
5990 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (F(7) - F(6+5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
5991 &:= (-9 + ((8+7) \times (F(6) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
5992 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((F(F(7)) \times (F(6) - F(5+4))) - (3+2+1))) \\
5993 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times 6)) - (F(5+4) + F(F(3+2+1)))) \\
5994 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - F(6+5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6033 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (F(3+4) \times F((5+F(6)))))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6034 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) \times (F(4+5) - F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6035 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F(F(3+4) \times (5 + F(F(6)))))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6036 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(4))^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9}) \\
6037 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + (((F(4))^5 + F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6038 &:= ((-1 - 2 + ((F(F(3 + F(4))) + 5) \times F((6 + 7)))) - (8 + 9)) \\
6039 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((F(3) - F(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7)) - F(8 + 9))) \\
6040 &:= (-1 - (((F(2 \times 3) - F(4 + 5)) \times F((6 + 7))) + 8 + 9)) \\
6041 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6042 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6043 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(F(4)) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6044 &:= ((-1 + F((F(2 + 3) \times 4))) - (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6045 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + 4 + 5) \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6046 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + 4 + 5) \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6047 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - (4 + 5))) \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6048 &:= ((-1 - 2 - (3 \times (4 - F(5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6049 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + 4 + 5) \times (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6050 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) \times ((F(F(4) \times 5)) - F((6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \\
6051 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times F(3 + 4 + 5))) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6052 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (F((F(4) - (5 - (6 + 7)))) \times (8 + 9))) \\
6053 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (F((F(4) + 5)) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6054 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (3^{F(4)+5})) - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6055 &:= ((-1 + (2^{F(3+4)})) - (F(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6056 &:= (-1 \times ((F((2 \times (3 + 4))) \times (5 - F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6057 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (F(F(3 + 4)) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6058 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (F(F(3 + 4)) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6059 &:= (1 - (2 \times (F(F(3 + 4)) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6060 &:= (((-1 + 2 + F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 + F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6061 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(F(2 + 3))) \times ((4 + F((5 + 6))) \times F(7))) + 8 + 9)) \\
6062 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times F(F(3 \times 4 - 5)))) \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9) \\
6063 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - ((F(F(4))^{5+6}) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6064 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - F(((3 \times F(4)) + 5))) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6065 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (F((F(4) + (5 + F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6066 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - ((F(F(4))^{5+6}) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6067 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - ((F((F(F(4) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7)) - (8 + 9))) \\
6068 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - ((F(4) \times (5 + F((6 + 7)))) - (8 + 9))) \\
6069 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times ((F(F(4))^{5+6}) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6070 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times ((F(F(4))^{5+6}) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6071 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times F(F(3 + 4)))) \times ((5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6072 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times ((F(F(4))^{5+6}) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6033 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6034 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + 7) \times (6 + F(5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6035 &:= (((-9 - (F(8) - F(F(7)))) \times (6 \times 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6036 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((F(F(7)) \times (F(6) - F(5 + 4))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6037 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times ((F(F(7)) \times (F(6) - F(5 + 4))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6038 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - ((F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6039 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times ((F(7) \times F(F(6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6040 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times (6 - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6041 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (F(7) + F(6 + 5))) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6042 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6043 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times 6)) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
6044 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(7) + F(F(6)))) \times F(5 + 4)) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6045 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times 6)) - ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6046 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times 6)) - F(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
6047 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 \times F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6048 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times (F(F(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6049 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F((7 + F(6))) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6050 &:= ((F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) + F(6 + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6051 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6052 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (F(F(7)) + (F(F(6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6053 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times 6)) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
6054 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times (F(6) + F(5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6055 &:= ((((-9 \times F(8)) + (F(F(7)) \times 6)) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6056 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times (F(6) + F(5 + 4))) + F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6057 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
6058 &:= (F((F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) - F(6))) \times (F(5 + 4) - F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6059 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + 5))) - (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6060 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times F(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6061 &:= (-9 + ((F(8 + 7) - (F(6) - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6062 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + ((F((7 + F(6))) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6063 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times 6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6064 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times ((F(F(7)) \times (F(6) - F(5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6065 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - F(F(7))) \times (F(6) - 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6066 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (F(7) - F(F(6)))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6067 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6068 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + (F(6) \times F(5 + 4)))) + F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6069 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) \times (F(6) + F(5 + 4))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6070 &:= (((9 \times F(8)) + F(7)) \times (6 \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6071 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((F(7) - F(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6072 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6073 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times ((F(F(4))^{5+6}) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6074 &:= (1 \times 2 + (3 \times ((F(F(4))^{5+6}) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6075 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 \times ((F(F(4))^{5+6}) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6076 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3^{F(4)}) \times (5 \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6077 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times (4^5)) - F(F(6)))))) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6078 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((F(3) + (F(F(4))^{5+6})) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6079 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((F(F(3 + 4)) \times (5 + F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6080 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(F(3 + 4)) \times (5 + F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6081 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (F(3 + 4) \times F((5 + F(6)))))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6082 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) \times (F(4 + 5) - F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6083 &:= (1 + ((2 \times (F(3 + 4) \times F((5 + F(6)))))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6084 &:= (((-1 - F(2 + 3)) + (4^5)) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6085 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 + F(F(6)))))) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6086 &:= (((1 \times 2 + F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 + F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6087 &:= (1 + (((2 + F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 + F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6088 &:= (((1 + 2) \times ((F(3) \times (4^5)) - (6 + 7))) - 8 - 9) \\
6089 &:= (-1 - (((F(2 + 3) - (4^5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6090 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times F(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6091 &:= (1 - (((F(2 + 3) - (4^5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6092 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3) - ((F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + F(F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6093 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - ((F(4 + 5) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6094 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + ((F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + F(F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6095 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 \times 3)) + F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6096 &:= (((-1 + F(2 \times 3))^{F(4)} - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6097 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F(F(3 \times 4 - 5)) + F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6098 &:= (1 - 2 + 3 + ((F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + F(F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6099 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3 \times F(4)) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6100 &:= (1 \times 2 \times ((F((3 \times F(4))) \times F(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6101 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3^{F(4)} \times (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6102 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3^{F(4)} \times (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6103 &:= 1 + 2 \times (3^{F(4)} \times (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6104 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) - (F((4 + 5 + 6)) \times (7 - (8 + 9)))) \\
6105 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3 + 4) \times F((5 + F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6106 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times 4) \times (5 + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6107 &:= (1 + (2 \times ((F(3 + 4) \times F((5 + F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6108 &:= (((-1 + 2 + F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 + F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6109 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times 4) \times (5 + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6110 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times ((F(4) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6111 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 + ((4 - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6073 &:= (((9 + (F(8) - F(7))) \times (F((6 + 5) \times 4)) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6074 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times 6)) + (F(5 + 4) - F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6075 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - F(F(7))) \times (F(6) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
6076 &:= (((-9 + 8 - F(F(7))) \times (F(6) - F(5 + 4))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6077 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) + F(6)) \times (F(5 + 4) - F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6078 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F((7 + F(6))) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6079 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times ((F(F(7)) \times (F(6) - F(5 + 4))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6080 &:= (((-9 - (F(8) - F(F(7)))) \times (6 \times 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6081 &:= (-9 + ((F(8 + 7) - (6 - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6082 &:= (((-9 - (F(8) - F(F(7)))) \times (F(F(6)) + (5 + 4))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6083 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F((F(7) + F((F(6) - 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6084 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) \times 7)) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6085 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - F(F(7))) \times (F(6) - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6086 &:= (-9 - 8) \times ((F(7) \times (6 - F(5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6087 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6088 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times ((F(F(6)) - 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6089 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - F(F(7)))) + F((F(F(6)) - F(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
6090 &:= ((-9 + 8 + F((F(7) + F((F(6) - 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6091 &:= (-9 + ((F((F(8)/7)) + F(6)) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6092 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) \times (F(6) - 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6093 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) + 6) \times ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6094 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) + (F(F(7)) \times (6 - 5 - 4)))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6095 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + 7) \times (F(6) \times 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6096 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7 + 6) + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6097 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) - (7 \times (F((6 + 5)) - F((F(F(4)) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6098 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times 6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6099 &:= (-9 + 8 + (F((F(7) + F((F(6) - 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6100 &:= ((-9 - (F(F(8)/7) - F(F(6)))) \times F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6101 &:= (-9 + ((F(8 + 7) + (6 - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6102 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) \times (F(6) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
6103 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 + (((6 + 5) \times 4) \times F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6104 &:= (((-9 \times F(8)) + ((7 + F(F(6))) \times F(5 + 4))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6105 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) + (F(F(6)) \times 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6106 &:= ((9 \times F(8 + 7)) + (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6107 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - F(7)) \times F((6 + 5)))) + (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)})) \\
6108 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times 6)) + (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6109 &:= (((-9 + (F((F(8)/7))^{6+5})) \times F(4)) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6110 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times ((F(6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6111 &:= (-9 + ((F(8 + 7) + F((F(6) - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6112 &:= (-1 \times ((F((2 \times (3 + 4))) + 5) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6113 &:= (1 - ((F((2 \times (3 + 4))) + 5) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6114 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) + ((4 - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6115 &:= (((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) + ((4^5) \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6116 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6117 &:= (-1 - 2 - (3 \times ((4 - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6118 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (3 \times ((4 - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6119 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (F(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6120 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times (F(F(4))^{5+6})) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6121 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times ((4 - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6122 &:= ((F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + ((4^5) \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6123 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) + ((4^5) \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6124 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + ((4^5) \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6125 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F((F(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6126 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (F(3)^{F(F(4)) \times 5})) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6127 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) \times (4^5)) + (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6128 &:= ((-1 - (F((2 \times (3 + 4))) + 5)) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6129 &:= ((-1 - 2 + ((F(3) + (4^5)) \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6130 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + ((F(3) + (4^5)) \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6131 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F((4 + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6132 &:= (((F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + (4^5)) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6133 &:= (-1 + (((2 + F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 + F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6134 &:= (((1 \times 2 + F(F(3 + 4))) \times (5 + F(F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6135 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F((F(4) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6136 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 \times 3)) + ((F(F(4))^5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6137 &:= (-1 - (((F(2 + 3) - (4^5)) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6138 &:= (((F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) + (4^5)) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6139 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) + ((F(F(4))^5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6140 &:= ((-1 + F((F(2 + 3) \times 4))) - ((5 + F(F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6141 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((F(3) - F(4 + 5)) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6142 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((F(3) - F(4 + 5)) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6143 &:= (-1 - ((2 + (3 \times (F(4) - F(5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6144 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (3 \times (4 - F(5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6145 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((F(3) - F(4 + 5)) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6146 &:= (1 \times 2 - ((F(3) - F(4 + 5)) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6147 &:= ((-1 - (2^{F(3)+4+5})) \times (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6148 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + ((F(F(4))^5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6149 &:= ((-1 + ((F(2 + 3) + (4^5)) \times 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6150 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times F(F(4)))) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6112 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6113 &:= (F((-9 + (F(8) + 7))) + ((F((6 + 5)) + F(4)) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6114 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7 - F(F(6))) \times F(5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6115 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^{F(4)}) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6116 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) + 6 + 5) \times F(4)) + F(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6117 &:= (-9 + ((F((8 - (F(7) - F(F(6)))))) + F(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6118 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) + ((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6119 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7 + F((6 + 5)))) - F(F(4))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6120 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((F(7) \times 6) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6121 &:= (-9 + ((F(8 + 7) + (F(6) - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6122 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - F(F(7)))) + (6 - 5)) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
6123 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) + (F(F(7)) \times (6 - 5 - 4)))) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6124 &:= (9 \times 8 - ((F(F(7)) \times (F(6) - F(5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6125 &:= ((9 - (F(8) + F(F(7)))) \times ((6 \times 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6126 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + 7) + F(6))) + F(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6127 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(7) + 6 + 5) \times (F(F(4))^{F(3+2+1)}))) \\
6128 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times F(7)) + F((6 + (5 + 4)))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6129 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) + (F(7) \times ((6 - 5) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6130 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - F(F(7))) \times (F(6) - 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6131 &:= (((-9 + F((F(8) - 7))) \times F(F(6))) - F((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6132 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times F(F(6)))) \times (F(5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6133 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F((7 + F(6))) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6134 &:= (F((-9 + (F(8) + 7))) + ((F((6 + 5)) + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6135 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(7) \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6136 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(7) + F((6 + (5 + 4)))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6137 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) + (6 \times 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6138 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) \times 7) + (6 + (5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6139 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6140 &:= ((-9 + (F(8 + 7) + (F(6) + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6141 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times F(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6142 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) + 6) \times (F(5 + 4) - F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6143 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times ((F(F(6)) - 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6144 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7 + 6) + (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6145 &:= (((-9 - (F(8) - F(F(7)))) \times (6 \times 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6146 &:= ((-9 + F((F(8) - (7 - 6)))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6147 &:= (9 \times ((F(8) \times (7 + (F(F(6)) + 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
6148 &:= 9 - F(8) + 7 \times (F(F(6)) - 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6149 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F((7 + F(6))) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6150 &:= ((F((F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) - 6)) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6151 &:= (1 + (((F(2+3) + (4^5)) \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6152 &:= (1 \times F(2 \times 3) + ((F(F(4))^5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6153 &:= -1 - 2 - (F(3) - 4^5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6154 &:= -1 \times 2 - (F(3) - 4^5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6155 &:= 1 - 2 - (F(3) - 4^5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6156 &:= (((-F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + (4^5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6157 &:= -1 + 2 - (F(3) - 4^5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6158 &:= 1 \times 2 - (F(3) - 4^5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6159 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (F(F(4))^{5+6}))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6160 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) \times ((4^5) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6161 &:= (1 + (((2 \times 3) \times (4^5)) - (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6162 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - (F(F(4))^{5+6}))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6163 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) + (((4^5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6164 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (F((3 \times 4)) - 5)) \times (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6165 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6166 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times (F(F(4))^{5+6})) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6167 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (3 \times (4 - F(5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6168 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times (F(F(4))^{5+6})) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6169 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times (F(F(4))^{5+6})) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6170 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + (((4^5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6171 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) + (((4^5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6172 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + (((4^5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6173 &:= ((1 \times F(2 + 3)) + (((4^5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6174 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (F(3)^{F(F(4)) \times 5})) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6175 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (F((F(3) \times (4 + 5))) + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6176 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times F((3 \times 4)) + 5) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6177 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((F(3) + (4^5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6178 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((F(3) + (4^5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6179 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F((4 + 5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6180 &:= (((F(F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))) + (4^5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6181 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((F(3) + (4^5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6182 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times ((F(F(4))^{5+6} + 7)) + 8 + 9) \\
6183 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 + ((F(4) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6184 &:= ((1 \times 2 \times (((3 + F(F(4)))^5) - F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6185 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F((F(4) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6186 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) + ((F(4) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6187 &:= (1 + (2 \times (((3 + F(F(4)))^5) - (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6188 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) \times (4^5)) + (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6151 &:= (9 - 8 + ((F((7 + F(6))) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6152 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((F(7) \times F(6)) - 5 - 4))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6153 &:= (F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) \times ((F(6) \times F(5 + 4)) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6154 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6155 &:= (F((-9 + 8 + (F(7) + F(6)))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6156 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times (7 \times F(F(6)))) \times F(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
6157 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (F(F(7)) \times (F(6) - 5)))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6158 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (F(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6159 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times ((F(F(6)) - 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6160 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times 7)) - (F(F(6)) + 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6161 &:= (-9 - (F(8 + 7) + (6 - (F((5 \times 4)) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6162 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + ((F((7 + F(6))) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6163 &:= (9 - ((F(8) + F(7)) \times (F(6) - ((5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6164 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) \times (F(6) - 5)))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6165 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (F(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6166 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) + (7 - (F(F(6)) \times F(5 + 4)))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6167 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (F(7) \times (6 - F(5 + 4)))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6168 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (F(7) \times (F(6) \times (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6169 &:= (((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times (6 - (5^4))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6170 &:= ((-9 + (F(8 + 7) + (F(F(6)) - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6171 &:= (-9 + ((8 + F((F(7) + F((F(6) - 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6172 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + (7 \times ((F(F(6)) - 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6173 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times ((F(6) + F(5 + 4)) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6174 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) + ((F(F(7)) \times (6 - 5 - 4)) - F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6175 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times F(7))) \times (F((6 + 5) - (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6176 &:= (((-9 \times ((F(8)/7) - F((6 + 5)))) - F(F(4))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6177 &:= (9 + 8 + (7 \times ((F(F(6)) - 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6178 &:= ((-9 - ((F(8) + F(7)) \times (6 + 5))) + (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)})) \\
6179 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) + 7)) \times (F((6 + 5) - (F(F(4))^{F(3+2+1)}))) \\
6180 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(7) \times F(6))) \times (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6181 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (F(7) \times 6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6182 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) + (6 \times 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6183 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) + (7 - ((F(6) + 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6184 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + 7) + F(6)) \times F(5 + 4))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6185 &:= (((-9 + F(8)) \times (F(7) \times (F(6) \times 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6186 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (7 + (F((F(6) + 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6187 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) - 7)) \times (6 - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6188 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times (F(6) - (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6189 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + F(F(4)))^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6190 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (3 \times ((F(4) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6191 &:= (-1 - (F(2 + F(3)) \times ((F(4) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6192 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (F(4) \times F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6193 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times ((F(4) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6194 &:= (1 \times 2 - (3 \times ((F(4) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6195 &:= (1 + 2 - (3 \times ((F(4) - F(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6196 &:= (-1 - 2 - (((F(3) - (4 \times F(5 + 6))) \times F(7)) - F(8 + 9))) \\
6197 &:= (-1 + (((F(2 + 3) + (4^5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6198 &:= (((F((-1 + 2 \times 3) + (4^5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6199 &:= (-1 - ((2 + F(3)) \times (F(4 + 5) + ((6 + 7) - F(8 + 9)))) \\
6200 &:= ((1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) - ((5 + F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6201 &:= (-1 + (F((2 + F(3 + 4))) + (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6202 &:= (1 \times (F((2 + F(3 + 4))) + (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6203 &:= (1 + (F((2 + F(3 + 4))) + (F((5 + F(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6204 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + (F(4) \times (5 - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6205 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3))^4) \times (5 + 6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9) \\
6206 &:= (1 + ((2 \times ((3 + F(F(4)))^5) - (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6207 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - ((F(F(4))^{5+6}) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6208 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - F(3)) \times ((F(F(4))^5) + ((6 + 7) - F(8 + 9)))) \\
6209 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + (4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6210 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - ((F(F(4))^{5+6}) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6211 &:= ((F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))))/F(4)) - (5 - (F((6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
6212 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(F(F(2 + 3)))) \times (F(F(4)) \times (F((5 + 6)) \times 7)))) - (8 + 9) \\
6213 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times ((F(F(4))^{5+6}) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6214 &:= (-1 + (F((F(F(F(2 + 3))) \times F(F(4)))) \times (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6215 &:= (F((-1 - 2 + F(3 + 4))) \times (F(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6216 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) \times ((F(F(4))^{5+6}) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6217 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times ((F(F(4))^{5+6}) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6218 &:= (-1 + (F(2 + F(3)) \times ((F(4)^5) + (F((6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9)))) \\
6219 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times ((3 + F(F(4)))^5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6220 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times ((F(4)^5) + (F((6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9)))) \\
6221 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + (F(4 + 5) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6222 &:= ((-1 - F(2 + 3)) \times ((4 - (5 \times (6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \\
6223 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times ((3 - (F(4)^5)) \times (6 + 7))) - (8 + 9) \\
6224 &:= (-1 + (F(2 + 3) \times ((4^5) + ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
6225 &:= (F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3))) \times ((4^5) + ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
6226 &:= (((-1 + 2)^{F(3)}) + ((4 \times (F((5 + 6)) \times F(7))) + F(8 + 9))) \\
6227 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(4 + 5) + (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6189 &:= ((-9 \times F((F(8) - 7))) + (6 \times F(((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6190 &:= ((-9 - F(8 + 7)) \times ((6 + 5) - F((F(F(4)) + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6191 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (7 \times F(F(6)))) \times (F(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6192 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 + (F(F(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6193 &:= (-9 + (F(8 + 7) + (F((F(6) + 5)) \times (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6194 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + ((F((7 + F(6))) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6195 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
6196 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (F(7) \times (6 - F(5 + 4)))) + F(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6197 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) + 6) \times (F(5 + 4) - F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6198 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (F(F(7)) \times (6 - 5 - 4)))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6199 &:= (-9 + ((F((F(8) - 7)) + 6 + 5) \times (F(F(4)) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6200 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (7 \times (F(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6201 &:= (-9 + ((F(8 + 7) + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6202 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
6203 &:= (((-9 - F(8)) \times (F(7) + 6)) + (F((5 \times 4)) + F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6204 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) \times F(7))) \times (F(6) - ((5 + 4) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6205 &:= (((-9 - 8 + F(7)) \times F((6 + 5))) + (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)})) \\
6206 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) - (F(7) - (F(F(6)) \times 5))) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6207 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7) + (F(6) + (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6208 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) - ((F(F(7)) \times (F(6) - F(5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6209 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) \times (F(6) - 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6210 &:= (((9 \times F(8)) + (F(F(7)) - F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6211 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (F(F(7)) \times (6 - 5 - 4)))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6212 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6213 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (F(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6214 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) + (F(F(7)) - 6))) \times (F(5 + 4) - F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6215 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) - (F(7) \times (6 + 5)))) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6216 &:= ((9 \times 8 + (F(7 + 6) - 5 - 4)) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6217 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7^{F(6)-5}) - (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)})) \\
6218 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (F(7 + 6) + 5)) \times F(4))) + F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6219 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) \times (F(6) + (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
6220 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times F(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6221 &:= (-9 + ((F(8 + 7) + (F(6) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6222 &:= ((-9 - 8 - (F(F(7)) + F((6 + 5)))) + (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)})) \\
6223 &:= (-9 - 8 + (F(7) \times (F(6) \times (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6224 &:= (((-9 \times ((F(8)/7) - F((6 + 5)))) + 4) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6225 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7)) \times (F(6) \times 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6226 &:= (-9 + (F(8) + ((F(F(7)) + 6) \times (F(5 + 4) - F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6227 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) \times (7 - (F(6) \times 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6267 &:= (((F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))^{F(4)} \times F((5 + F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6268 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((3^{F(4)} \times F((5 + F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6269 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + (F(4) + (5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6270 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) \times 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6271 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + ((F(F(4)) \times 5) - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6272 &:= ((-1 - ((2 - F(F(3)^4))/5) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6273 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times F(4 + 5) + F((6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6274 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + (F((4 \times 5)) - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6275 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - ((F(F(4)) \times F((5 + F(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6276 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + ((F(4) \times 5) - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6277 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) + (((4 \times 5) \times F((6 + 7))) + F(8 + 9)))) \\
6278 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (((F(4)^5) \times (6 + 7)) - (8 + 9)))) \\
6279 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((3 + F(F(4)))^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6280 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(F(4)) + ((5 + F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6281 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + ((4 \times 5) - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6282 &:= (1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) + (F((4 \times 5)) - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6283 &:= (((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4) \times 5) - (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6284 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (((F(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9))) \\
6285 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3 + F(F(4)))^5) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
6286 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((F(3) - ((F(4)^5) + F(F(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6287 &:= (-1 - ((F(F(2 + 3)) - (F(4) \times F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6288 &:= (((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) + (F(4) \times F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6289 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(F(3 + 4)) \times (5 - (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6290 &:= ((1 - 2) - (F(F(3 + 4)) \times (5 - (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6291 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) \times (F(F(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6292 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (F((4 + 5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6293 &:= (1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times (F((4 + 5 + F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6294 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((3 + F(F(4)))^5) + (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6295 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + (F(4 + 5) - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6296 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((F(F(3)^4) \times (5 - (6 + 7))) + F(8 + 9)) \\
6297 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((F(F(3)^4) \times (5 - (6 + 7))) + F(8 + 9)) \\
6298 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (F(F(3 + 4)) - F(5 + 6 + 7))) - F(8 + 9)) \\
6299 &:= (-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6300 &:= (((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^{F(4)}) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6301 &:= (1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6302 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (F(3) - ((4 + 5) \times F((6 + 7)))) + 8 + 9) \\
6303 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) \times (4 \times (5 + (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6304 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + F(F(3)^4))/5) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6305 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((F((3 \times 4)) + 5) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6267 &:= (-9 + (((8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6268 &:= ((-9 - ((F(8) \times F(7)) + 6 + 5)) + (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)})) \\
6269 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - F(((6 + 5) + F(4)))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6270 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7) \times (F(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6271 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (F(F(7)) + ((F((6 + 5)) + F(4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6272 &:= ((-9 + F(F(((8 + 7) - F(6)))) \times (F(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6273 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (F(F(7)) + (F(6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6274 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (F(F(7)) \times (F(6) - 5)))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6275 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) + F(7))) \times ((F(6) \times F(5 + 4)) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6276 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (F(7) \times (F((6 + 5)) - F(4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6277 &:= ((-9 + ((F(8)/7)^{F(6)}) - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6278 &:= (-9 - (((8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(6) - F(5 + 4))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6279 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) + (F(F(7)) + (6 \times (5 + 4)))) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6280 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7)) \times ((6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6281 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (F(7) \times 6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6282 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + (6 \times F((F(5 + 4)) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6283 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (F(F(6)) \times F(5 + 4)))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6284 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((F(F(7)) - 6) \times (F(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6285 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (F(F(6)) \times F(5 + 4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6286 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7)) \times (6 + F(5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6287 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) + (F(F(7)) + 6 + 5))) + (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)})) \\
6288 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - F(7)) \times ((6 \times (5 + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6289 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 \times ((6 \times 5)^{F(F(4))}) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6290 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7)) \times (F(6) \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6291 &:= (-9 \times ((F(8) \times F(F(7)))/(F(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6292 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) \times (7 - (F(6) \times 5)))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6293 &:= ((9 \times (F(8 + 7) + F((6 + 5)))) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6294 &:= (((9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times (F(F(6)) + (5 + 4)))) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6295 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((F(F(7)) \times 6) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6296 &:= (-9 - (((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times (6 \times 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6297 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (F(F(6)) \times F(5 + 4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6298 &:= (-9 + ((F((F(8) - 7)) - 6) \times ((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6299 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (F(F(6)) \times F(5 + 4)))) + F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6300 &:= ((-9 - F(8)) \times ((7 - F(F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6301 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (7 \times F(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6302 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) - 7) \times ((6 \times (5 + 4)) - F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6303 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + (7 \times 6)) \times F(5 + 4)) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6304 &:= (F(-9 + F(8)) + (7 \times ((F(F(6)) - 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6305 &:= (((-9 - ((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times 6)) \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6306 &:= ((-1-2) \times (F(3 \times F(4)) - (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
6307 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) - (4 \times ((5+6+7) - F(8+9)))) \\
6308 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) + (4 \times ((5+6+7) - F(8+9)))) \\
6309 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3 + F(F(4)))^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6310 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F(F(3+4)) + (5 \times 6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6311 &:= (-1 - (((2 + F(3)) - (F(4) \times F(5+6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6312 &:= (((1 - F(2+3)) + (F(4) \times F(5+6))) \times (7+8+9)) \\
6313 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (4 \times (F(5+6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6314 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) + (((F(4)^5) + F(F(6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6315 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(4) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6316 &:= (-1 + (F((F(F(2 \times 3)) - F(F(4)))) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
6317 &:= (F((-1 + (F(2+3) \times 4))) + (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6318 &:= (1 + (F((F(F(2 \times 3)) - F(F(4)))) + (F((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
6319 &:= (-1 + ((2 - 3^4) \times (5 \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)))) \\
6320 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (4 + ((5 + F(6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
6321 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (((4 \times 5) \times F(F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6322 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 + F(3)) - ((F(4+5) \times F((6+7))) - F(8+9))) \\
6323 &:= (-F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + (((F(4)^5) + F(F(6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6324 &:= (((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (F(4) \times (5 \times F(F(6)))))) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6325 &:= ((F((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4 + 5)))) \times F((6+7))) - F(8+9)) \\
6326 &:= (((-1 + 2)^{F(3)}) + ((F(4+5) \times F((6+7))) - F(8+9))) \\
6327 &:= ((-1-2) \times ((3^{F(4)}) - (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
6328 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 \times 3)) + (((F(4)^5) + F(F(6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6329 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^{F(4)} - 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
6330 &:= ((-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) - F(F((F(F(4)) + 5)))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
6331 &:= ((-1 \times F(2+3)) + (((F(4)^5) + F(F(6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6332 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - F(3)) + (((F(4)^5) + F(F(6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6333 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 - (F(4) \times F(5+6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6334 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3 - (F(4) \times F(5+6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6335 &:= ((1 - 2) - ((3 - (F(4) \times F(5+6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6336 &:= ((-1 + (F(2+3)^{F(F(4))})) \times ((5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6337 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 - (F(4) \times F(5+6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6338 &:= (1 \times 2 - ((3 - (F(4) \times F((5+6)))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6339 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((F(3) \times F((4+5+F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6340 &:= ((-1 + F(2+3)) + (((F(4)^5) + F(F(6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6341 &:= (1 + (2 \times ((F(3) \times F((4+5+F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6342 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 - ((5+6+7) \times (8+9)))) \\
6343 &:= ((-1 + F(2 \times 3)) + (((F(4)^5) + F(F(6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6344 &:= (-1 - ((2 + F(F(3+4))) \times (5 - (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6306 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (7 + (F(F(6)) \times F(5+4)))))) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6307 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (F(F(7)) + (6 - F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
6308 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - (7 + (F(F(6)) \times F(5+4)))))) + F(3+2+1) \\
6309 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (7 + ((F(6) + 5) \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6310 &:= ((-9 + (F(8+7) + (6 \times 5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
6311 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (F(F(6)) \times 5)) + F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6312 &:= (9 \times 8 + (F(7) \times (F(6) \times (5 + F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6313 &:= (-9 + (F(8+7) + (F(6) \times (F(5+4) \times F(F(3+2+1)))))) \\
6314 &:= (9 - (((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times (6 \times 5)) + F(4+3+2+1))) \\
6315 &:= (((-9 \times F(8)) + F((7 + F(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6316 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times F(7)) + 6 + 5) \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\
6317 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (F(F(7)) + 6 + 5)) + (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)})) \\
6318 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - ((F(F(7)) + F(6)) \times ((5+4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
6319 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (F(F(7)) - (F((F(6) - 5))^{4+3+2+1}))) \\
6320 &:= ((-9 + (F(8+7) + (F(F(6)) \times (5+4)))) \times F(3+2+1)) \\
6321 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + 7) \times (F(6) + F(5+4))) - F(F(3+2+1))) \\
6322 &:= ((-9 - 8 - (F(F(7)) - (6 + 5))) + (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)})) \\
6323 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times 6)) + (5 \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\
6324 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (F(F(7)) - ((6+5) \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\
6325 &:= (((9 \times (F(8) - 7)) - (6 + 5)) \times F(4+3+2+1)) \\
6326 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - ((F(F(7)) - 6) \times (F(5+4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
6327 &:= (-9 \times ((F(8) \times (7 - (F(6) \times 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
6328 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) - 6) \times (F(5+4) - (3+2+1))) \\
6329 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) - ((F(F(7)) \times (6 - F(5+4))) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6330 &:= (((-9 \times F(8)) - F(F(7))) \times ((F(6) \times 5) - F(4+3+2+1))) \\
6331 &:= (((-9 + F((F(8) + (7 - (6 + 5)))))) \times 4) - F(F(3+2+1)) \\
6332 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + (7 \times 6)) \times F(5+4)) + F(3+2+1)) \\
6333 &:= (-9 - (F(8) \times (F(7) - (F(F(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6334 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) + F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
6335 &:= (((F(-9 + F(8)) + F(7)) \times (F(6) \times 5)) + F(4+3+2+1)) \\
6336 &:= (((-9 \times F(8)) + F(F(7))) \times (F(6+5) + F(4+3+2+1))) \\
6337 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) \times (F(7) + F(F(6)))))) \times (5+4)) - F(3+2+1) \\
6338 &:= ((-9 + 8 - (F(F(7)) - (6 + 5))) + (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)})) \\
6339 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(F(7)) - 6) \times (F(5+4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
6340 &:= (((-9 - F(8)) \times 7) - (6 + 5)) + (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)}) \\
6341 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) + F(F(7))) \times ((6 \times 5) - F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6342 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + 7) \times (F(F(6)) \times F(5+4-3-2-1))) \\
6343 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) - (F(F(7)) - F(((6 \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
6344 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) \times ((F(7) \times 6) - F(5+4))) + F(3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6463 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) \times 5) + (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6464 &:= ((-1 + 2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6465 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(F(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6466 &:= ((-1 + (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4)^5))) - (F((6 + 7)) - F(8 + 9))) \\
6467 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(F(4)) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
6468 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (4 - ((5 + F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6469 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - ((F(4 + 5) \times F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6470 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((3 + F(F(4)))^5)) + ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
6471 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (F(4) \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
6472 &:= (((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4) \times 5) + (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6473 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + (4 \times ((5 + 6 + 7) + F(8 + 9)))) \\
6474 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - ((F(4) \times F(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6475 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times ((4 + (5 + 6 + 7)) + F(8 + 9)))) \\
6476 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) \times 5) + (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6477 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + (F(4) \times F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6478 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + (F(4) \times F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6479 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 + F(3)) + (F(4) \times F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6480 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3))) + (F(4) \times F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6481 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + (F(4) \times F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6482 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) \times 5) - (F(F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6483 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times (F((4 + 5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6484 &:= ((-1 + F(2 + 3)) \times (F((4 + 5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6485 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (F(3 + 4) \times (5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6486 &:= (1 - 2 - (F(3 + 4) \times (5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6487 &:= -F((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) \times (5 - F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6488 &:= (-1 + 2 - (F(3 + 4) \times (5 - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6489 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(4) - ((5 + F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6490 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - ((F(4)^5) + (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6491 &:= (((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4) \times 5) - (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6492 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - ((F(4)^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6493 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((F((F(3 + 4) - 5)) \times F((6 + 7))) + F((8 + 9)))) \\
6494 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + (F((4 \times 5)) - (F(F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6495 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6496 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times F(4 + 5))) \times (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6497 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (4 + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6498 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(4) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6499 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(F(4)) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6500 &:= ((-1 + F((F(F(2 + 3)) \times 4))) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6463 &:= ((9 \times ((F(8) - F(7)) \times F(6 + 5))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6464 &:= ((9 + 8) \times F((F(7) + (6 - 5)))) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6465 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (F(F(7)) + F(6))) \times (F(5 + 4) - F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6466 &:= (((-9 + (F(8)/7)) - F((6 + 5))) + (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)})) \\
6467 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + (F(7) \times (F(6)^{5+4-3-2-1}))) \\
6468 &:= (-9 + ((F(8 + 7) \times F(6)) + F(((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6469 &:= (((-9 + 8 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) + F(((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6470 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 - F(6 + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6471 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - (7 + 6)) - (F(5 + 4) \times F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6472 &:= (((-9 - 8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) + (5 + 4))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6473 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((F(7) + (F(F(6)) \times 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6474 &:= (((-9 - 8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) + (5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6475 &:= ((-9 + (F(8) \times F(F(7)))) - (6 - F(((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6476 &:= ((9 \times (F(8) \times (F(7) + F(F(6)))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6477 &:= ((-9 \times F((F(8) - 7))) + (F((F(F(6)) - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6478 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) - F((6 + 5))) + (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)})) \\
6479 &:= ((-9 - F(F(8)/7)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6480 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times F(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6481 &:= ((-9 + F((F(8) - (7 - 6)))) - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6482 &:= ((-9 + 8 - (F(7) \times 6)) + ((5 - F(F(4)))^{F(3+2+1)})) \\
6483 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) \times F(7)) - F(((6 \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
6484 &:= ((-9 + F((F(8) - (7 - 6)))) - (F(5 + 4) \times F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6485 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7 - (6 + 5))) + (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)})) \\
6486 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + F(F(7))) \times (6 - 5 - 4))) - F(F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6487 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + (6 + F(((5 + 4) + F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6488 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (F(F(6)) \times 5)))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6489 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(7) + (F(F(6)) \times 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6490 &:= (F((-9 + 8 + (F(7) + F(6)))) - (5 \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6491 &:= (-9 + ((F(8 + 7) + (F(6) \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6492 &:= ((-9 + ((F(8)/7)^{F(6)})) - (5 + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6493 &:= (F((-9 + 8 + (F(7) + F(6)))) - (F(5 + 4) \times F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6494 &:= (-9 - (F(8) - (7 \times (F((F(F(6)) - 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6495 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + F(F(7))) \times (F(6) \times 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6496 &:= ((-9 + 8 + F(7 + 6)) \times (F(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6497 &:= ((-9 + ((F(8)/7)^{F(6)})) - (F(5 + 4) + F(F(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6498 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - F(F(6)))) - F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6499 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + F(F(7))) \times (6 - 5 - 4))) - F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6500 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times F(F(6)))) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6501 &:= (F((-1 + F((F(2 + 3) + F(4)))))) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) & 6501 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + F(F(7))) \times (6 - 5 - 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6502 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6502 &:= ((-9 + ((F(8)/7)^{F(6)})) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6503 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + (F(F(4)) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6503 &:= (-9 + ((F(8 + 7) + (6 \times F(5 + 4))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6504 &:= (((-1 + F(2 + 3)) + (F(4) \times F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) & 6504 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) - (F(F(7)) + F((6 + (5 + 4)))))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6505 &:= (1 + ((2 + (F(3) + (F(4) \times F(5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 6505 &:= ((-9 + ((F(8) + 7) \times F((F(6) + 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6506 &:= (-1 - (F(F(2 \times 3)) - (F(4 + 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 6506 &:= (((-9 - 8 - F(F(7))) \times (F(6) - F(5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6507 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) - (F(4 + 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 6507 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (F((F(F(6)) - 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6508 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F((F(F(4)) + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6508 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) \times 7)) + ((6^5) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6509 &:= (1 + (F((F(2 + 3) \times 4)) - (F((5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6509 &:= ((-9 + ((F(8) + 7) \times F(F(6 + 5 - 4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6510 &:= (-1 \times (F(F(2 \times 3)) \times (F(F(4)) - ((5 + F(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 6510 &:= (((-9 \times (F(8) \times 7)) + F(F(6))) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
6511 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) \times 5) + (F(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6511 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (F(F(7)) - (6 + F(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6512 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + (4 - (F((5 + F(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6512 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (F(7) \times F(6)))) - 5 - 4) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6513 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (3^{F(4)+5})) - (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6513 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) + 7)) + F(((6 \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
6514 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(F((F(F(4)) + 5))) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) & 6514 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6 + 5)) + (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)})) \\
6515 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 + F(3))^{F(4)+5})) - (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6515 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) + 7) \times F((F(6) - (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))))) \\
6516 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))^{F(4)+5}) - (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6516 &:= (-9 + ((8 - F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6517 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - ((F(4 + 5) \times F(6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 6517 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((F(F(7)) \times (6 - F(5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6518 &:= (1 \times 2 + ((3^{F(4)+5}) - (F(F(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6518 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times ((F(F(7)) \times (6 - F(5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6519 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (F(4 + 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6519 &:= (-9 + ((F(8)/7) \times (F(6) \times (F(5 + 4) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6520 &:= (-1 \times (F(2 \times 3) - (F(4 + 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 6520 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + (F(7) + 6)) \times (F(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6521 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) + (F(4 + 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6521 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + (F((7 + (F(6) + 5))) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6522 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - ((F(4) \times F(5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 6522 &:= (-9 - (F(8) \times (F(7) - (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6523 &:= ((-1 \times F(2 + 3)) + (F(4 + 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6523 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (F((F(F(6)) - 5)) - F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6524 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) \times (F(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6524 &:= (F((F(F(-9 + 8 + 7)) - F(6))) \times (F(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6525 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - ((F(4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6525 &:= (-9 + (((F(8) + 7) \times F((F(6) + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6526 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (F(4 + 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6526 &:= ((-9 + ((F(8)/7)^{F(6)})) - (F(5 + 4) - F(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6527 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(2 + 3)) + (F(4) \times F(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 6527 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (F(F(7)) - (F(F(6)) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6528 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (3^{F(4)+5})) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6528 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (F(F(6)) + F(5 + 4)))) \times F(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6529 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (3^{F(4)+5})) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6529 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((F(F(7)) \times (6 - F(5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6530 &:= ((-1 + (F(2 + F(3))^{F(4)+5})) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6530 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times ((F(F(7)) \times (6 - F(5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6531 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2 + 3)))^{F(4)+5}) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6531 &:= (-9 + 8 - (F(F(7)) - F(((6 \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
6532 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3^{F(4)+5})) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6532 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (F(F(7)) - F(((6 \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
6533 &:= (F(F(F(F(F((-1 + 2 \times 3)))))) + (F(4 + 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6533 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (F(F(6)) \times 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6534 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (F((3 - (4 - 5)))^{F(6)})) - 7 - 8 - 9) & 6534 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + ((6 \times 5) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6535 &:= (-1 + (F(2 \times 3) + (F(4 + 5) \times (F(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 6535 &:= (((-9 - 8 + F(F(7))) \times (6 \times 5)) + F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6536 &:= ((-1 + (F(((2 + (3 + 4)) - 5))^{F(6)})) - 7 - 8 - 9) & 6536 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) - ((7 + F(F(6))) \times 5)) \times F(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6537 &:= (((-1 - (F(2 + 3) - (4 + 5)))^{F(6)} - 7 - 8 - 9) & 6537 &:= ((-9 + ((F(8)/7)^{F(6)})) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6538 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (F((3 - (4 - 5)))^{F(6)})) - 7 - 8 - 9) & 6538 &:= ((-9 - ((F(8)/7) + 6 + 5)) + (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)}))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6578 &:= (1 \times 2 + ((F(3) + (F(4+5) \times F(6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6579 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2+3)))^{F(4)+5}) - (6-7-8-9)) \\
6580 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3^{F(4)+5})) - (6-7-8-9)) \\
6581 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) + (F(4)^{F(5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)})) \\
6582 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + (4+5 - (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
6583 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((F((3 - (4-5)))^{F(6)}) + 7+8+9)) \\
6584 &:= (-1 + ((F(((2 + (3+4)) - 5))^{F(6)}) + 7+8+9)) \\
6585 &:= (((-1 - (F(2+3) - (4+5)))^{F(6)}) + 7+8+9) \\
6586 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((F((3 - (4-5)))^{F(6)}) + 7+8+9)) \\
6587 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(4+5) + (6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
6588 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3^{F(4)+5}) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
6589 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3^{F(4)+5}) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
6590 &:= (-1 + ((F(2 + F(3)))^{F(4)+5}) + 6+7+8+9) \\
6591 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2+3)))^{F(4)+5}) + 6+7+8+9) \\
6592 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3^{F(4)+5}) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
6593 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2+3)))^{F(4)+5}) + (F(6) + 7+8+9)) \\
6594 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3^{F(4)+5}) + (F(6) + 7+8+9))) \\
6595 &:= ((F((-1 - (F(2+3) - (4+5))))^{6+7}) - F(8+9)) \\
6596 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (((3+4) - 5)^{6+7})) - F(8+9)) \\
6597 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + ((4 - (5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6598 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + (F(4+5) \times F(6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6599 &:= (-1 + ((2 + F(3)) \times (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6600 &:= ((-1 + F(2+3)) \times (F((F(F(4)) \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
6601 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + (F(4+5) \times F(6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6602 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(4) + (5 \times (F(6) + 7+8+9)))) \\
6603 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + ((4+5) \times (6-7-8-9))) \\
6604 &:= ((-1 + F((F(2+3) \times 4))) - (5 \times (F(6) + 7+8+9))) \\
6605 &:= (1 \times (F((F(2+3) \times 4)) - (5 \times (F(6) + 7+8+9)))) \\
6606 &:= ((F((-1 + F(2+3)))^{F(4)+5}) + (F(F(6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
6607 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + (F(4+5) - (F(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
6608 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F((F(F(4)) + 5)) + (6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
6609 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + (4 - (5 \times (F(6) + 7+8+9)))) \\
6610 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(4) + (F(5+6+7)/(8+9)))) \\
6611 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (4 + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6612 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(4) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6613 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(F(4)) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6614 &:= ((-1 + F((F(F(2+3)) \times 4))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
6615 &:= (F((-1 + F((F(2+3) + F(4)))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6578 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) \times (F(5+4) - F(3+2+1))) \\
6579 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (F(7) - (F(6) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6580 &:= (-9 + (((F(8)/7)^{F(6)}) + (F(5+4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
6581 &:= ((-9 + 8 + F((7+6-5))) + (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)})) \\
6582 &:= (-9 + (((F(8)/7)^{F(6)}) + ((5+4) + F(F(3+2+1)))) \\
6583 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + (7 + F(((6 \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
6584 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (F(7) \times (F(6)^{5+4-3-2-1}))) \\
6585 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7 \times F(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
6586 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + (F((7 + (F(6) + 5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
6587 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) + (F(F(7)) - F((F(F(6)) - 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6588 &:= (-9 \times ((F(8+7) \times 6)/(5-4-3-2-1))) \\
6589 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + (F(7) + F(((6 \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
6590 &:= (((-9 - F(8)) \times (F(7) - F((F(6) + 5)))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6591 &:= (-9 + (((8+7) + (F(F(6)) \times 5)) \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\
6592 &:= (-9 + (((F(8)/7)^{F(6)}) + (F(5+4) + 3+2+1))) \\
6593 &:= ((F(F(-9+8+7)) + 6+5) + (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)})) \\
6594 &:= ((F(-9 + F(8)) + (7+6)) \times (F(5+4) + F(3+2+1))) \\
6595 &:= (-9 + ((F(8) + F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) - (5-4-3-2-1)))) \\
6596 &:= ((-9 - (F(8) - ((7+6) \times 5))) + (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)})) \\
6597 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) + (F(F(7)) - F((F(F(6)) + (5-4-3-2-1)))))) \\
6598 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (F(F(6)) \times 5)))) + F(4+3+2+1)) \\
6599 &:= (((-9 + F(8+7)) \times (6+5)) - (4 + F(3+2+1))) \\
6600 &:= ((-9 - F(8)) \times ((7 - (6+5)) \times F(4+3+2+1))) \\
6601 &:= (((-9 + F(8+7)) \times (6+5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6602 &:= (-9 + (((F(8)/7)^{F(6)}) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6603 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) \times (F(5+4) - F(3+2+1)))) \\
6604 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) \times 7)) + ((F((6+5))^{F(F(4))}) + 3+2+1)) \\
6605 &:= (-9 + (((F(8) + F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) + 5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
6606 &:= (-9 + ((8 + F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6607 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) + (F(F(7)) - F((F(F(6)) - 5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
6608 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (F(F(7)) + F((6 + (5+4)))) \times F(3+2+1)) \\
6609 &:= (-9 - ((F(8) \times 7) - F(((6 \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)))) \\
6610 &:= (((-9 - F(8)) \times (F(7) - F((F(6) + 5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
6611 &:= ((-9 + F(8+7)) \times (6 - (5-4-3-2-1))) \\
6612 &:= (-9 + (((F(8)/7)^{F(6)}) + (5 + F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6613 &:= ((-9 + (F((F(8) - 7)) + F(F(6)))) \times ((5+4) + F(3+2+1))) \\
6614 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (F(7) - (F(F(6)) \times 5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6615 &:= (F(F(-9+8+7)) \times (F(F(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6616 &:= (1 + (F((F(2+3)) \times 4)) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
6617 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + (F(F(4)) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6618 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + (F(4) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6619 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + (4 - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6620 &:= ((-1 + F((2 + (F(3) \times (4+5)))) - (6 \times (7+8+9))) \\
6621 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times ((F(4) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
6622 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times ((F(4) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
6623 &:= (-1 + (F(2 + F(3)) \times ((F(4) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
6624 &:= (F((-1 + F(2+3))) \times ((F(4) + F(5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6625 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6626 &:= (1 \times 2 + (3 \times ((F(4) + F((5+6))) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
6627 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(F(4)) - ((5 - (6+7)) \times (8+9)))) \\
6628 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + (F(F(4)) + (5 - (6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
6629 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^{F(4)} + 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
6630 &:= (((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) + (F(4)^5)) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
6631 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + ((F(F(4)) \times 5) - (6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
6632 &:= (((-1 + F(2+3))^4 \times (5 + F(F(6)))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6633 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(4) + ((5 \times F(F(6))) + 7+8+9))) \\
6634 &:= (F((-1 + F(2 \times 3))) + (F((4 \times 5)) - (6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
6635 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(F(4)) \times (F(5+6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6636 &:= (1 \times (F((F(2+3) \times 4)) - ((5 \times F(F(6))) + 7+8+9))) \\
6637 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + ((F(4) + 5) \times (F(6) - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6638 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + (F(F(4)) - ((5 \times F(F(6))) + 7+8+9))) \\
6639 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + ((F(F(4)) + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6640 &:= ((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3))) \times ((4 \times F(5+6)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6641 &:= (F(F((-1 + F(2 \times 3)))) + (F(4) \times (F(5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
6642 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3^4)) \times ((5 \times F(F(6))) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6643 &:= ((1 - (F(2 \times 3)^{F(4)})) \times ((5+6) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6644 &:= ((-1 - F(F(2 \times 3))) \times (4 - ((5+6+7) \times (8+9)))) \\
6645 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(4 - 5 + 6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6646 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((F(3)^{F(4)+5}) + F(F(6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6647 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times F((3 \times 4))) - (5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6648 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3 \times (F(4) + F(5+6)))) \times (7+8+9)) \\
6649 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(4) + (F(5+6) + 7+8+9))) \\
6650 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) - (F(F(4)) + (F(5+6) + 7+8+9))) \\
6651 &:= ((-1 + F((F(2+3) \times 4))) - (F(5+6) + 7+8+9)) \\
6652 &:= (F((-1 + F((F(F(2+3)) + F(4)))) - (F(5+6) + 7+8+9)) \\
6653 &:= ((F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + (F(F(4))^5)) - (6 \times (7+8+9))) \\
6654 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(2 \times 3)))) + (F(F(4)) - (F(5+6) + 7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6616 &:= 9 \times ((F(8)/7)^6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6617 &:= ((-9 + (F(8+7) \times (6+5))) - (4 \times F(F(3+2+1)))) \\
6618 &:= (((-9 \times F(8)) + (F((7+6+5))/F(F(4)))) \times (3+2+1)) \\
6619 &:= (((-9 + F(8+7)) \times (6+5)) + (F(F(4)) + 3+2+1)) \\
6620 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + (F(F(7)) \times 6)) \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6621 &:= (((-9 + F(8+7)) \times (6+5)) + 4+3+2+1) \\
6622 &:= ((-9 - F(F(8)/7)) \times (F(6) - F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
6623 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) \times (7 - (F(6) + F(5+4)))) + F(3+2+1)) \\
6624 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) - (7 \times F(F(6)) + F(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6625 &:= (-9 - (((8 - F(7)) \times ((6+5)^{F(4)})) + F(F(3+2+1)))) \\
6626 &:= ((-9 - F(8)) + (F(7) \times (F(6)^{5+4-3-2-1}))) \\
6627 &:= (-9 - ((8 - ((7+6+5)^{F(F(4))})) \times F(F(3+2+1)))) \\
6628 &:= (((-9 + F(8+7)) \times (6+5)) - (4 - F(F(3+2+1)))) \\
6629 &:= (((-9 + F(8+7)) \times (6+5)) - (F(4) - F(F(3+2+1)))) \\
6630 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) + F(((6 \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
6631 &:= ((-9 \times F(8)) + (F((7 + (F(6) + 5))) + F(4+3+2+1))) \\
6632 &:= (((-9 + F(8+7)) \times (6+5)) + F((F(F(4)) + 3+2+1))) \\
6633 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((7 \times (F(F(6)) \times 5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
6634 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (F(7) - (F(F(6)) \times 5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
6635 &:= (((-9 + F(8+7)) \times (6+5)) + (4 \times (3+2+1))) \\
6636 &:= ((-9 + F(8)) \times (7 \times (F(6+5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
6637 &:= ((-9 + (F(8+7) \times (6+5))) - (F(F(4))^{3+2+1})) \\
6638 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + F((7 + (F(6) + 5)))) - F(4+3+2+1)) \\
6639 &:= ((-9 \times (F(8) - 7)) + F(((6 \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
6640 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + (F(F(7)) \times 6)) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6641 &:= ((-9 + F(((8 - 7) \times (6+5)))) + (F(4)^{F(3+2+1)})) \\
6642 &:= ((F((-9 + 8 + F(7))) - F(F(6))) \times ((5+4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
6643 &:= (((-9 + F(8+7)) \times (6+5)) + (4 \times F(3+2+1))) \\
6644 &:= ((-9 - F(F(8)/7)) \times (6 - F(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
6645 &:= (((-9 \times (F(8) \times 7)) - 6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
6646 &:= ((-9 + (F(8+7) \times (6+5))) - F(4+3+2+1)) \\
6647 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times F(7)) \times (F(6)^{F(5+4-3-2-1)}))) \\
6648 &:= (-9 + (F(8) \times (7 \times 6 + (5 \times F(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6649 &:= (9 + (8 \times (((F(7) \times 6) + 5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6650 &:= (((-9 \times F(8)) + (7 \times F(6))) \times (5 - F(4+3+2+1))) \\
6651 &:= (-9 \times (F(8) + ((F(7) - F(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6652 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times F(7)) - F(((6 \times 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))) \\
6653 &:= (((-9 + F(8+7)) \times (6+5)) + (F(F(4)) \times F(F(3+2+1)))) \\
6654 &:= (((-9 + (F(8) + F(7))) \times (F((6+5)) \times F(4))) - F(F(3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

